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Numerical Modeling of Geological Carbon Sequestration: Enhanced Dissolution in Randomly Heterogeneous Media

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Abstract

Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS) plays a major role in mitigating the global warming due to the increasing concentration of CO_2 in atmosphere. Injecting gaseous CO_2 into subsurface formation can change the geo-chemical system and the potential leakage of CO_2 can have impact on the quality of water resources in shallow aquifer. It is thus important to understand the GCS process to analyze and predict its influence on the CO_2 reservoir site. This work firstly offers three finite difference programs for simulating the GCS process, secondly applies the program to perform quantitative analysis of the GCS, and finally gives several remarks related to the GCS.

Firstly, we describe the three finite difference programs, which, to different extents, take into account the role of chemical reaction in the GCS process.

The first program is a reactive two-phase flow model that only considers the interplay between brine and gas phases, which can be solved with explicit method. The second program is a simplified reactive three-phase flow model that also considers the heterogeneous reaction between mineral rock and the aqueous species, but all the chemical reactions are treated as equilibrium reactions and expressed with empirical formulas, to avoid performing grid-by-grid calculation of chemical reaction at each time step. In this second program, the chemical state only depends on gas pressure; that is, mass fractions of the species, which have been calculated with mass action law (MAL), are only empirical functions of the gas pressure. This simplification has negligible effect on the estimation if the time scale of transport is quite larger than the time scale of interested chemical reaction. The third program is a full reactive three-phase flow model that accounts for partial equilibrium reaction system (i.e., both equilibrium and kinetic reactions are included) as well as the pure equilibrium reaction system. In this third program, the partial equilibrium chemical system is solved with MAL, and chemical reactions and mass transport are alternately solved with Newton-Raphson method. All these programs have been approved through non-ideal benchmark test that only considers the transport issue.

Secondly, the first program is employed to perform two qualitative analysis on the dissolution trapping.

The first quantitative analysis focuses on the enhanced dissolution efficiency of gaseous CO_2 into brine owing to gravity-driven convection (GDC) in the brine phase. On the one

hand, the injected CO_2 will override the denser brine and reduce the security of GCS. On the other, at the interface of the gaseous CO_2 and brine, the dissolution of CO_2 into brine will increase the security of the GCS. Studies have shown that the dissolution is not only driven by molecular diffusion that fades away as the concentration profile reaches Gaussian distribution, but also enhanced by the GDC in the brine, because the dissolution of CO_2 can increase the density of the brine in the upper portion. As a result, the dissolution rate reaches a non-zero constant value that significantly enhances the security of GCS. In literature, the GDC in homogeneous media has been well studied and researchers are attempting to investigate the GDC in realistic heterogeneous media. It is yet to find an efficient formula to predict the dissolution rate in heterogeneous media with anisotropic permeability distribution. This work conducts a large number of numerical simulations in various heterogeneous fields, analyzes the simulation results, and proposes two formulas that efficiently predict the dissolution rate based on geological and fluid parameters.

The second quantitative analysis focuses on the enhanced dissolution trapping due to the layered permeability structure during the injection period. Numerical simulations are conducted on layered fields with detailed heterogeneity information in the vertical direction, as well as on simplified anisotropically homogeneous fields, of which the horizontal and vertical permeabilities, respectively, equal to the effective horizontal and vertical permeabilities in the corresponding heterogeneous reservoir structure. Besides, different injection rates are employed to analyze if the effect of permeability heterogeneity on dissolution efficiency is affected by the gravity factor. Results show that when buoyant forces are important, vertical segregation controls the overall behavior of CO_2 , diminishing the influence of small-scale heterogeneity on dissolution. However, when buoyant forces are relatively small compared to the degree of heterogeneity, CO_2 migrates preferentially through high permeability layers and dissolution efficiency increases with heterogeneity due to the stretching of the CO_2 plume that enhances mixing. As a result, in this situation, the upscaling of permeability leads to an underestimation of the dissolution efficiency. A review of field sites shows that dissolution is heterogeneity-controlled in most real systems. Knowing that most numerical models cannot afford to represent heterogeneity at an adequate scale, results indicate that dissolution efficiency can be typically underestimated by a factor close to 1.5.

Finally, we point out that the developed programs can be employed to study the wormhole during the GCS and to test the water-alternating-gas technique. Moreover, the programs can also be modified to simulate enhanced oil recovery, nuclear waste storage, environmental assessment and soil remediation (e.g., NAPL removal). Additionally, we give in the appendix a parallel study on how to enhance NAPL removal and mixing with engineering chaotic advection.

Resumen

El secuestro geológico de carbono (GCS) juega un papel importante en la mitigación del calentamiento global debido a la creciente concentración de CO₂ en la atmósfera. La inyección de CO₂ gaseoso en la formación del subsuelo puede cambiar el sistema geoquímico y la posible fuga de CO₂ puede tener un impacto en la calidad de los recursos hídricos en los acuíferos poco profundos. Por lo tanto, es importante entender el proceso de GCS para analizar y predecir su influencia en el sitio del depósito de CO₂. Este trabajo, en primer lugar, ofrece tres programas de diferencias finitas para simular el proceso GCS, en segundo lugar, aplica uno de los programas para realizar análisis cuantitativos del GCS y, finalmente, ofrece varios comentarios relacionados con el GCS.

Primero, describimos los tres programas de diferencias finitas, que, en diferentes grados, tienen en cuenta el papel de la reacción química en el proceso de GCS.

El primer programa es un modelo de flujo reactivo de dos fases que solo considera la interacción entre las fases de salmuera y gas, que se puede resolver con un método explícito. El segundo programa es un modelo de flujo reactivo trifásico simplificado que también considera la reacción heterogénea entre la roca mineral y la especie acuosa, pero todas las reacciones químicas se tratan como reacciones de equilibrio y se expresan con fórmulas empíricas, para evitar realizar cuadrícula por cuadrícula el cálculo de la reacción química en cada paso de tiempo. En este segundo programa, el estado químico solo depende de la presión del gas; es decir, las fracciones de masa de la especie, que se han calculado con la ley de acción de masas (MAL), son solo funciones empíricas de la presión del gas. Esta simplificación tiene un efecto insignificante en la estimación si la escala de tiempo de transporte es bastante mayor que la escala de tiempo de la reacción química interesada. El tercer programa es un modelo de flujo reactivo de tres fases completo que tiene en cuenta el sistema de reacción de equilibrio parcial (es decir, se incluyen las reacciones de equilibrio y cinéticas), así como el sistema de reacción de equilibrio puro. En este tercer programa, el sistema químico de equilibrio parcial se resuelve con MAL, y las reacciones químicas y el transporte de masa se resuelven alternativamente con el método de Newton-Raphson. Todos estos programas han sido aprobados a través de una prueba de referencia no ideal que solo considera el tema del transporte.

En segundo lugar, el primer programa se emplea para realizar dos análisis cualitativos

sobre el trapeo por disolución.

El primer análisis cuantitativo se centra en la eficiencia de disolución mejorada del CO_2 gaseoso superpuesto en la salmuera subyacente debido a la convección impulsada por gravedad (GDC) en la fase de salmuera. Por un lado, el CO_2 inyectado anulará la salmuera más densa y reducirá la seguridad del GCS. Por otro lado, en la interfaz del CO_2 gaseoso y la salmuera, la disolución del CO_2 en la salmuera aumentará la seguridad del GCS. Los estudios han demostrado que la disolución no solo es impulsada por la difusión molecular, sino también mejorada por el GDC en la salmuera, porque la disolución de CO_2 puede aumentar la densidad de la salmuera en la parte superior. Como resultado, la tasa de disolución alcanza un valor constante distinto de cero que mejora significativamente la seguridad de GCS. En la literatura, la GDC en medios homogéneos ha sido bien estudiada y los investigadores están intentando investigar la GDC en medios heterogéneos realistas. Aún está por encontrar una fórmula eficiente para predecir la tasa de disolución en medios heterogéneos con distribución de permeabilidad anisotrópica. Este trabajo realiza una gran cantidad de simulaciones numéricas en varios campos heterogéneos, analiza los resultados de la simulación y propone dos fórmulas que predicen de manera eficiente la velocidad de disolución en función de parámetros geológicos y de fluidos.

El segundo análisis cuantitativo se centra en la captura de disolución mejorada debido a la estructura de permeabilidad en capas durante el período de inyección. Las simulaciones numéricas se realizan en campos estratificados con información detallada de heterogeneidad en la dirección vertical, así como en campos anisotrópicamente homogéneos simplificados, de los cuales el horizontal y permeabilidades verticales, respectivamente, iguales a las permeabilidades horizontales y verticales efectivas en la estructura heterogénea del yacimiento correspondiente. Además, se emplean diferentes velocidades de inyección para analizar si el efecto de la heterogeneidad de la permeabilidad sobre la eficiencia de disolución se ve afectado por el factor de gravedad. Los resultados muestran que cuando las fuerzas de flotación son importantes, la segregación vertical controla el comportamiento general de CO_2 , lo que disminuye la influencia de la heterogeneidad a pequeña escala en la disolución. Sin embargo, cuando las fuerzas de flotación son relativamente pequeñas en comparación con el grado de heterogeneidad, el CO_2 migra preferentemente a través de capas de alta permeabilidad y la eficiencia de disolución aumenta con la heterogeneidad debido al estiramiento de la pluma de CO_2 que mejora la mezcla. Como resultado, en esta situación, la ampliación de la permeabilidad conduce a una subestimación de la eficiencia de disolución. Una revisión de los sitios de campo muestra que la disolución está controlada por heterogeneidad en la mayoría de los sistemas reales. Sabiendo que la mayoría de los modelos numéricos no pueden darse el lujo de representar la heterogeneidad a una escala adecuada, los resultados indican que la eficiencia de disolución puede subestimarse normalmente en un factor cercano a 1,5.

Finalmente, señalamos que los programas desarrollados se pueden emplear para estudiar el agujero de gusano durante el GCS y para probar la técnica de agua-alternancia-gas. Además, los programas también se pueden modificar para simular la recuperación mejorada de petróleo, el almacenamiento de desechos nucleares, la evaluación ambiental y la remediación del suelo (por ejemplo, eliminación de NAPL). Además, proporcionamos en el apéndice un estudio paralelo sobre cómo mejorar la eliminación y mezcla de NAPL con advección caótica de ingeniería.

Declaration

This dissertation is the result of my own work and includes nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration except as declared in the Preface and specified in the text. It is not substantially the same as any that I have submitted, or am concurrently submitting, for a degree or diploma or other qualification at the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya or any other University or similar institution except as declared in the Preface and specified in the text. I further state that no substantial part of my dissertation has already been submitted, or is being concurrently submitted, for any such degree, diploma or other qualification at the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya or any other University or similar institution except as declared in the Preface and specified in the text.

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: ‘In his later life, Yufei Wang found the PhD life in UPC composes a very important part of his memory.’

He experienced a challenging and interesting PhD life in Barcelona, where he worked with a group of (very) kind people, who had helped and enlightened him.

It is cliché but it is true: the most important person to his PhD was his supervisor Dani, without whom he would not have the chance to come to Barcelona, without whom he could not improve so fast. He was really happy that Dani let him study ‘Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS)’ as his PhD thesis, and he really enjoyed this topic. Dani was very nice in life, but very picky in work. What he had learned from Dani is not only the figures, formulas and the ideas in the thesis, but also the way to do it. Another important person was Maarti, who from the beginning to the end helped him with the whole composing of this thesis. Maarti took part in all the discussions on this thesis and gave his important comments and suggestions to improve the thesis. Five-year PhD study formed a solid backstone in his late-stage research career.

His first work was doing a project (High Efficiency Enhanced Oil Recovery, 2017 September - 2018 March) for the oil company, Repsol. In this project, he got help from Paula and Guillem. Since this was the first time for him to participate in team work, he triggered many unnecessary arguments. From this project, he learned how to do teamwork, as well as how to simulate oil recovery. Anyway, he felt a good sense of achievement when he finished his first project.

However, the satisfaction was soon substituted by new challenges. Following Dani’s advice, he embarked on the GCS, which was more complex than his first project on oil recovery. In the beginning, he built a model based on the traditional method in oil recovery, which was not the best choice for GCS. Because this was his first time to code, he also had difficulty in finding out the reason when he met warnings in testing the code.

Maarti came to help Yufei on December of 2019! Maarti’s coming was very important to his thesis. Maarti recommended his model to Yufei. With Maarti’s model, Yufei finally finished the reactive two-phase flow model for GCS. Then he adopted Maarti’s simplified reactive three-phase flow model, based on which he further extended to full reactive three-phase flow model.

When one lives and works in a foreign country, he/she has to deal with a lot of paper work with the tax agency, policy station, the company, etc. Yufei is not an exception. In most cases, the staff in Barcelona only spoke Catalan or Spanish, but Yufei only spoke English. Dani and Tere helped him do a lot of paperwork, but he always felt that Oriol was also a very helpful guy in dealing with paperwork.

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:If a bird wants to fly further, he needs first to fly higher - -[Zhuangzi]

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

1.1.1 Origin of Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS)

Increasingly high CO_2 level in atmosphere causes climate disasters associated with global temperature increase, urging the government to introduce policies to reduce CO_2 emissions (*European Commission*, 2012). The globally annual emission of CO_2 from consumption of energy, mainly coal and coke, has increased from 23,156 million tonnes in 1996 to 35,666 million tonnes in 2016; during this two decades' period, the annual emission of CO_2 in Asia & Oceania jumps from 7,138 to 17,667 million tonnes (cf. www.eia.gov). The goal of 2019 Paris agreement on climate change is limiting the global temperature increase to 2 Celsius by 2100, and to this end, the greenhouse gas emissions should be substantially reduced by 80-95% (at least 50%) compared to 1990 level and finally reach zero by 2050 (*European Commission*, 2014; *Helveston and Nahm*, 2019). According to the Paris agreement on climate change, both developing and developed countries are responsible to track and report their CO_2 emissions (*Matacic*, 2018). Policies have been introduced in some countries to reduce CO_2 emissions. Canada, for instance, has already implemented a tax on CO_2 emissions in some provinces and the tax rate is expected to increase (*Brainard*, 2018). The 2020 climate and energy targets of European Commission is 'EU binding legislation to cut greenhouse gas emissions by 20%, increase the share of renewable energy to 20% and increase energy efficiency by 20%' (*European Commission*, 2014). EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) is proposed to cut greenhouse gas emissions from the power, industry and aviation sectors.

According to *IPCC* (2005, 2008) and *European Commission* (2007), Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS)- which stores carbon by injecting CO_2 , removed from natural air, into subsurface geologic formation- may be the most promising way to reduce carbon emissions (*Baklid and Korb*, 1996; *Torp and Gale*, 2003; *Zweigel et al.*, 2004). Pilot CO_2

storage projects (cf. www.co2captureandstorage.info; www.cslf.gov), including enhanced oil recovery with CO_2 injection, prove that CO_2 can be safely stored in subsurface over a long period up to hundreds of years (*Law and Bachu*, 1996; *White et al.*, 2003). Among the candidate formations, such as depleted oil/gas reservoirs (*Holloway*, 2001; *Hill et al.*, 2013) and unminable coal seams (*White et al.*, 2005; *Bromhal et al.*, 2005), saline aquifer deeper than 800 m has the largest capacity for CO_2 storage (*Weir et al.*, 1996; *Lindeberg and Wessel-Berg*, 1997; *Stevens et al.*, 2001; *Pruess et al.*, 2003; *Kumar et al.*, 2005; *Lu and Lichtner*, 2007; *Qi et al.*, 2009; *Firoozabadi and Cheng*, 2010; *Vilarrasa et al.*, 2010; *Krevor et al.*, 2012; *Celia et al.*, 2015). Moreover, saline aquifer has better storage security because of its large depth (*van der Meer*, 1992; *Bachu et al.*, 1994; *Szulczewski et al.*, 2012a). Examples of large-scale GCS projects are Sleipner in the North Sea (*Lindeberg and Bergmo*, 2003; *Arts et al.*, 2004, 2008a; *Chadwick et al.*, 2010), Kalundborg in Denmark (*Chadwick et al.*, 2008), Mid Norway in Norway (*Chadwick et al.*, 2008), Schwarze Pumpe and CO2SINK in Germany (*Forster et al.*, 2006; *Chadwick et al.*, 2008), Valleys in UK, Weyburn in Canada (*Whittaker et al.*, 2011), In Salah in Algeria (*Mathieson et al.*, 2011a), Tongliao in China (*Lei et al.*, 2016) and Changhua Coastal Industrial Park in China (Taiwan) (*Sung et al.*, 2014). More information on the GCS site can be found in *EU GeoCapacity* (2009) and *U.S. Department of Energy* (2012).

1.1.2 Trapping Mechanisms of GCS

In order to analyze security of GCS, we should understand the trapping mechanisms in CO_2 reservoir. It is important to know that the injected CO_2 are sequestered in four ways: (1) being sealed by low permeable cap-rock (hydrodynamic trapping), (2) being trapped by capillarity (residual trapping), (3) dissolving in brine (dissolution trapping) and (4) reacting with formation rock (mineral trapping) (*Vargaftik*, 1975; *Gunter et al.*, 1993; *Hendriks and Blok*, 1993; *Gunter et al.*, 1997; *Lindeberg and Wessel-Berg*, 1997; *Celia et al.*, 2005; *Ennis-King and Paterson*, 2005a; *Riaz et al.*, 2006a; *Ennis-King and Paterson*, 2007; *Gaus et al.*, 2008; *Saadatpoor et al.*, 2010; *Celia et al.*, 2006; *Iglauer et al.*, 2011; *Pentland et al.*, 2011; *El-Maghraby and Blunt*, 2013). Hydrodynamic trapping is provided by the low permeable cap-rock (e.g., mudstone) that stops the injected low-density CO_2 migrating upward to the shallow aquifer under buoyancy force. Hydrodynamic trapping is the main trapping mechanism in the initial stage of the carbon sequestration process, because most CO_2 is in mobile gaseous (or super critical) phase with less density at the early stages. Hydrodynamic trapping diminishes as all gaseous CO_2 is immobilized by other trapping mechanisms. Residual trapping is the trapping mechanism that immobilizes gaseous CO_2 by capillarity. The nonwetting gaseous CO_2 becomes immobile and is trapped in the pore in the form of bubbles due to capillary pressure. Residual trapping, which can immobilize a considerable amount of CO_2 , starts to take effect when a region changes from

drainage process to imbibition process. Residual trapping diminishes as all the gaseous CO_2 dissolves into the brine. Dissolution trapping results from dissolution of gaseous CO_2 into brine phase, as the injected CO_2 plume spreads in the formation. Dissolution trapping depends on temperature, pressure and brine salinity. Mineral trapping arises from the reaction between the CO_2 -dissolved brine and formation rock. This trapping mechanism can take effect early if the formation rock contains active species such as calcite, and it lasts for a very long time until all potential reactions are in chemical equilibrium state.

Here, we classify the hydrodynamic trapping by the caprock as the unstable trapping while the capillary, dissolution and mineral trappings are stable (or permanent) trappings, because only hydrodynamic trapping is sensitive to unpredictable factors such as fractures in caprock and improperly sealed well (*Rutqvist and Tsang, 2002; Jimenez and Chalaturnyk, 2002; Flett et al., 2004; Moreno et al., 2005; Hesse and Woods, 2010; Saadatpoor et al., 2010; Krause et al., 2011; Perrin and Benson, 2010; Kuo and Benson, 2015*). Usually, only dissolution trapping and mineral trapping are deemed as permanent trapping mechanisms; however, from the knowledge of Water-Alternating-Gas (WAG) technique in enhanced oil recovery, researchers notice that capillary trapping has a vital impact on sequestration and can be treated as permanent trapping (*Flett et al., 2004*). The numerical results from *Flett et al. (2004)* show that capillarity and dissolution can, respectively, trap 36% and 33% of the total injected CO_2 . Apart from the four mechanisms, *Saadatpoor et al. (2010)* argue that heterogeneity of sedimentary rocks leads to a fifth trapping mechanism, called local capillary trapping, which occurs during buoyancy-driven migration of CO_2 plume (*Perrin and Benson, 2010; Kuo and Benson, 2015*). Because of local capillary trapping, the residual saturation in heterogeneous media can be much larger than that in homogeneous media, where the residual gas is in the form of isolated ganglia (*Hesse and Woods, 2010; Krause et al., 2011*). However, we prefer to classify this local capillary trapping as general hydrodynamic trapping, which traps the buoyant CO_2 by low-permeable region. The underground CO_2 reservoir should sequester CO_2 for a long enough period in the magnitude of a few thousand years or more (*Lindeberg and Bergmo, 2003*), which means that annual leakage rate from the CO_2 reservoir should be smaller than $\sim 0.01\%$ of the injected CO_2 (*Benson et al., 2002*).

1.1.3 Impacts of GCS

CO_2 injection leads to chemical and biological changes in the CO_2 reservoir. When the concentration of aqueous CO_2 in brine increases, the pH value of the brine decreases. The reduced pH of the brine due to CO_2 injection can significantly change the chemical and biological reactions, for instance, dissolution of mineral, oxidation of organic matter, adsorption, cation exchange and biomass growth (*Dillard Nogaret and Blunt, 2000; Zhou et al., 2000; Held and Celia, 2001; Dupin et al., 2001a,b; Wang and Jaffe, 2004; Acharya*

et al., 2005; *Li et al.*, 2015, 2018b).

The injected super critical CO_2 may have the potential to escape from the deep reservoir formation to the shallow aquifer and finally atmosphere (*Lindeberg and Bergmo*, 2003; *Juanes et al.*, 2006; *Krevor et al.*, 2011; *Liang and Clarens*, 2018). We thus need to evaluate the impact of leakage on the local environment close to reservoir site. The major impacts are: decrease in pH due to increased CO_2 concentration and increase in mineral concentration due to the reaction between acidified groundwater and formation rock (or soil). The enhanced dissolution of rock (or soil) could release heavy metals and thus reduce water quality (*Chadwick et al.*, 2008). If leaking CO_2 locally accumulates at the reservoir site, high CO_2 concentration would affect humans and even the biodiversity of ecosystems.

Other impacts of GCS are related to seismicity due to the build up of liquid pressure. The build up of gas and liquid pressures can induce strain of the rock matrix, open fractures, and cause seismic events (*Riano-Vilarrasa*, 2012).

1.1.4 Technical Support for GCS

Numerical Simulations

Numerical simulations, having the merit of high efficiency and precision, are widely employed to analyze the GCS process. Many commercial or non-commercial multiphase flow programs have been developed to simulate the GCS process (*Van der Meer*, 1996; *Law et al.*, 2002). The often-used simulators are TOUGH developed at Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (*Pruess et al.*, 1999a; *Xu et al.*, 2006a; *Zhang et al.*, 2008; *Xu et al.*, 2011), GPRS developed at Stanford University (*Cao*, 2002; *Jiang*, 2008), CODEBRIGHT developed at Technical University of Catalonia (*Olivella et al.*, 1996), RETRASO developed at Technical University of Catalonia (*Saaltink et al.*, 2004, 2013), NUFT developed at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (*Johnson et al.*, 2005; *Morris et al.*, 2011; *Hao et al.*, 2012), FEHM developed at the Los Alamos National Laboratory (*Robinson et al.*, 2000), IPARS developed at the University of Texas (*Wheeler et al.*, 2007), ECLIPSE (*Schlumberger; Graupner et al.*, 2011; *Li-ping et al.*, 2015), GEM (*Computer Modelling Group*), DUMUX (*The Dumux website*), SIMED II (*Connell and Detournay*, 2009; *Pan and Connell*, 2009), OpenGeoSys (*The OpenGeoSys project*), d^3f (*Elenius et al.*, 2014a), and COORES (*Le Gallo et al.*, 2006; *Trenty et al.*, 2006). Other more simulators for GCS and similar problems, such as nuclear waste sequestration, can be found in *Law et al.* (2002), *Class et al.* (2009) and *Bourgeat et al.* (2013).

These simulators have different degrees of complexity. For instance, COORES and GPRS, only consider the interplay between gas and liquid phases, and use simplified flash model or empirical tabulated relationship between CO_2 solubility and state variables (*Young et al.*, 1983; *Cao*, 2002; *Oldenburg et al.*, 2003; *Pruess et al.*, 2004). If the

dissolution/precipitation of solid minerals needs to be considered, sophisticated numerical models, such as TOUGHREACT and RETRASO, are needed (*Saaltink et al.*, 2004; *Obi and Blunt*, 2006; *Xu et al.*, 2011).

The challenge of modeling GCS is that the fluid properties and compositions are not only affected by the compressibility, convection and dispersion, but also changed by the mass exchange between/within different phases owing to the chemical reactions. The mass exchange between phases can cause phase appearance and disappearance, which can incur numerical challenges. Traditionally, the numerical model is solved by IMplicit Pressure Explicit Saturation and Concentration (IMPESC) method, where the pressure, saturation and concentration are solved alternately (*Cao*, 2002; *Jiang*, 2008). IMPESC is developed on the basis of well-known IMplicit Pressure Explicit Saturation (IMPES) method, which is widely used in petroleum engineering without considering the mass exchange between the two phases. However, IMPESC cannot be obtained by simply adding the concentration variable to IMPES. IMPESC becomes complex in dealing with phase appearance/disappearance and variable substitution has to be used (e.g., *Pruess et al.* (1999b) and *Flemisch et al.* (2011)). For instance, if a grid has only one phase then the independent variable for this grid should be concentration and (gas or liquid) pressure; if this grid changes into two-phase state then the independent variables should be substituted with liquid saturation and (gas or liquid) pressure. Besides, Boussinesq approximation-density variations are neglected except for the gravity term- is sometimes needed when solving the transport equation (*Cheng et al.*, 2012). Advanced models overcome these issues by simply using the most efficient independent variables (*Saaltink et al.*, 2004; *Bourgeat et al.*, 2013).

Some professional chemical reaction programs, based on Mass Action Law (MAL) or Gibbs Energy Minimization (GEM), are powerful in solving chemical reactions involved in GCS, though these professional chemical programs can only deal with simple single-phase flow process. Some often-used professional chemical reaction programs are: PHREEQC (*Parkhurst et al.*, 1999; *Parkhurst and Appelo*, 2013a), CHESS (*Van der Lee*, 1998; *Van Der Lee et al.*, 2003), CHEPROO (*Bea et al.*, 2009), etc. More professional chemical reaction programs can be found in *Leal et al.* (2013)

Analytic and Semi-Analytic Models

Analytic and semi-analytic models are also popular in analyzing the GCS, because they take only several seconds to get the result (*Nicot*, 2008; *Pruess*, 2009; *MacMinn et al.*, 2010, 2011; *Mijic et al.*, 2014). Analytic and semi-analytic models can offer qualitative analysis to assist the design of engineering project. Dr. Nordbotten and his colleagues have done a large quantity of researches on analytic and semi-analytic models for GCS (e.g., *Nordbotten et al.* (2005a) and *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006)). Semi-analytic models, such as Estimating Leakage Semi-Analytically (ELSA) (*Nordbotten et al.*, 2005b, 2009)

and vertical equilibrium (VE) models (*Gasda et al.*, 2009, 2011; *Court et al.*, 2012; *Kang et al.*, 2014; *Guo et al.*, 2016) , can offer good prediction of the GCS process.

Laboratory Experiments and Field Observations

Laboratory experiments serve to provide necessary information on the chemical reactions, fluid properties and the pore-scale behavior of the fluids, all of which can affect the fate of injected CO_2 . First, detailed information on chemical reaction, such as equilibrium constant, activity, heat capacity and entropy, needs to be determined based on laboratory experiments (*Spycher and Pruess*, 2005; *Cooper and Dooley*, 2007; *Leal et al.*, 2013). Data bases, such as PHREEQC and SUPCRT92, provide abundant experimental data on the chemical reaction. Second, the fluid properties, such as density and viscosity, are also obtained with laboratory experiments. These experimental data are then used to obtain empirical formulas for predicting the density and viscosity (*Phillips et al.*, 1982; *Garcia*, 2003). Third, the pore-scale behavior, which is mainly related to the capillarity and relative permeability, is also obtained in the laboratory. Recent experimental studies extend the famous Brook-Corey and van Genuchten models by investigating the effect of hysteresis of the drainage and imbibition paths (*Land*, 1968; *Agarwal*, 1967; *Spiteri et al.*, 2008; *Krevor et al.*, 2012; *Liang and Clarens*, 2018). More experimental studies are related to the dissolution process due to gravity-driven convection and the intrusion process of CO_2 (*Li et al.*, 2017b; *Ramanathan et al.*, 2010; *Zhang et al.*, 2011a; *Trevisan et al.*, 2017; *Wang et al.*, 2021).

Field observations of GCS at reservoir sites help calibrate the parameters used in the numerical model and provides more precise long-term prediction of the security. Field observations are preformed through 3D seismic surveys (*Zhou et al.*, 2020; *Boait et al.*, 2011, 2012). Dr. Chadwick and coworkers contribute a quantity of works on field observations (*Chadwick et al.*, 2004, 2005, 2008, 2010; *Chadwick and Noy*, 2010).

1.2 Objectives

This work studies the GCS via numerical approach. We first construct three numerical programs for GCS, and then apply the first developed program to analyze two specific problems in GCS. The three numerical programs are, respectively, reactive two-phase flow model, simplified equilibrium reactive three-phase flow model and full reactive three-phase flow model. All these programs are constructed based on finite difference method. Advanced selection of independent variables is used to avoid variable substitution when dealing with phase appearance/disappearance (*Bourgeat et al.*, 2010; *Angelini et al.*, 2011; *Ern and Mozolevski*, 2012; *Neumann et al.*, 2013; *Saaltink et al.*, 2013). The two applications focus on the dissolution efficiency of CO_2 in brine, because dissolution trapping, which is safe and relatively efficient, plays an important role in increasing the security of GCS (*Strandli*

and Benson, 2013).

Construction of Three Numerical Programs

The reactive two-phase flow model only considers the mutual solubility between the gas and brine. This can offer well estimation of the fate of CO_2 if the interplay between formation rock and brine is slow and negligible. In this model, the simple mutual solubility module can be explicitly solved, significantly reducing the computational cost.

The simplified reactive three-phase flow model considers the reaction between the acidified brine and the formation rock as well as the mutual solubility between brine and CO_2 . Regarding the solid phase, this simplified model only considers the most active solid species, calcite; furthermore, the reaction between calcite and brine is assumed to be in equilibrium. This simplification is on the basis of the assumption that the transport time scale is much greater than the half time of the calcite dissolution/precipitation, while the transport time scale is much less than the half time of the precipitation/dissolution of other rock species such as silicate minerals. This program does not calculate the reaction at every time step, and instead it calculates the chemical reaction only once, and gets empirical relations between species compositions at equilibrium equilibrium state and the gas pressure. The empirical relations are then used to complete the transport equations.

The third program is full reactive three-phase flow model that accounts for kinetic reactions as well as equilibrium reactions. Compared to the aforementioned two simplified programs, this program is slow, because the chemical reaction needs to be solved grid-by-grid at each time step.

Applications

The first application studies how Gravity-Driven Convection (GDC) enhances dissolution efficiency in the late-stage of GCS, when all the gaseous (or super critical) CO_2 is floating in the top of the reservoir due to gravitational segregation. In the post-injection stage, the dissolution rate is controlled by the GDC arising from the density increase of brine due to dissolved CO_2 , because downward transport of CO_2 by GDC can generate a constant dissolution rate while the downward transport by molecular dispersion diminishes (Weir *et al.*, 1996; Lindeberg and Bergmo, 2003; Pruess and Zhang, 2008; Emami-Meybodi and Hassanzadeh, 2015). In literature, the GDC-induced dissolution rate of CO_2 in brine is usually studied in homogeneous media, and only a few researches study the effect of permeability heterogeneity on the dissolution process. An efficient predictor for the dissolution rate remains lacking. In this work we systematically study the effect of permeability heterogeneity on the dissolution rate, and obtain two efficient predictors for the dissolution rate.

The second application studies the effect of permeability stratification on the dissolution efficiency during the injection period of GCS. In the injection period, the dissolution rate is controlled by the area of the interface between the CO_2 and brine phases. Natural CO_2

reservoir, such as deep saline formation, usually has layered structure that affects the contact area between gas and brine phases, thus impacting the dissolution efficiency of CO_2 in brine. However, in large-scale simulation with coarse gridding system, detailed information of the layered reservoir may not be considered, which could lead to bias in estimating the dissolution efficiency. Here, numerical simulations are conducted on layered fields with detailed permeability information in the vertical direction, as well as on simplified anisotropically homogeneous fields, of which the horizontal and vertical permeabilities, respectively, equal to the effective horizontal and vertical permeabilities in the corresponding heterogeneous reservoir structures. Moreover, different injection rates are employed to analyze if the effect of permeability heterogeneity on the dissolution efficiency is affected by the gravity factor.

1.3 Layout

Overall, this work contains seven parts: Chapter 1 (i.e., this Chapter) gives the introduction, Chapters 2 to 4 give the three numerical models, Chapters 5 and 6 give specific applications based on the first model, and Chapter 7 gives conclusions and future work. Additionally, we give in Appendix J a parallel study on enhanced NAPL removal through engineered injection and extraction. Detailed layout is given as follows:

- (1) Chapter 1 gives the background and objectives of this work.
- (2) Chapter 2 gives the reactive two-phase flow model that accounts for the mutual solubility of CO_2 and brine.
- (3) Chapter 3 gives the simplified reactive three-phase flow model that takes into account only the equilibrium reaction among gas, liquid and rock phases.
- (4) Chapter 4 gives the full reactive three-phase flow model that takes into account both kinetic and equilibrium reactions among gas, liquid and rock phases.
- (5) Chapter 5 analyzes how GDC enhances CO_2 dissolution rate in heterogeneous fields.
- (6) Chapter 6 analyzes the effect of permeability stratification on CO_2 dissolution efficiency during the injection period in the GCS process.
- (7) Chapter 7 gives several concluding remarks and potential work.
- (8) Appendix J, which is parallel to the main body of this dissertation, studies how engineered injection and extraction can enhance NAPL removal.

Chapter 2

Reactive Two-Phase Flow Model for Geological CO_2 Sequestration

2.1 Introduction

High nonlinearity gives rise to challenges in numerical study of reactive two-phase flow in Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS). Numerical models designed for unsaturated/saturated reactive two-phase flows have been frequently deployed in enhanced oil recovery, NAPL removal, nuclear waste storage and GCS. In these models, IMplicit Pressure EXplicit Saturation Composition (IMPESC) algorithm is often employed to sequentially update the pressure, saturation, and then composition. However, the traditional IMPESC model appears to be handicapped by the issues of density change, mass exchange between phases, phase appearance and disappearance, etc., when it is used to simulate the gas (e.g. carbon dioxide and hydrogen) storage in deep geological formations. If the density is affected by the composition, Boussinesq approximation is often used (*Yeh and Tripathi, 1991; Engesgaard and Kipp, 1992; Walter et al., 1994; Šimůnek and Suarez, 1994*). Moreover, variable substitution has to be used when the saturation state of a grid is changed (*Pandy et al., 1995; Forsyth et al., 1998; Wu and Forsyth, 2001; Class et al., 2002; Cao, 2002*). For instance, the gas pressure and liquid saturation are used as the independent variables in the unsaturated grid, but gas pressure and mass composition in liquid phase are used as the independent variables in liquid-saturated grid.

In this chapter, a reactive two-phase flow model, without sequential iteration and variable substitution, is developed for the purpose of simulating GCS process. This model considers the partition between the gaseous and liquid phases, where four species- gaseous and aqueous CO_2 and gaseous and liquid H_2O - are in chemical equilibrium state. The model developed in this chapter can be modified to other subsurface reactive transport processes, such as enhanced oil recovery, soil remediation and nuclear waste storage (*Bourgeat et al., 2009, 2013*).

In the rest of this Chapter, Sections 2.2 and 2.3, respectively, give the numerical method and the benchmark test of the model; Section 2.4 lists the conclusions of this chapter.

2.2 Methods

The proposed model is comprised of two major modules: the mass transport module and the chemical reaction module. The mass transport module forms the main body of the numerical program while the chemical reaction module is in charge of the mass fractions of different species. To build seamless connection between the transport module and the chemical reaction module, we should try to use the same independent variables. Therefore, the first step is selection of independent variables. If liquid phase only contains saline water and gas phase only contains CO_2 (i.e., there is no mass change between two phases), then we need two independent variables to solve the transport module of the two-phase flow system. Usually, the two variables can be any combination of four variables: gas pressure, liquid pressure, and gas saturation (or liquid saturation). If mutual solubility between water and CO_2 is considered and the solubility is controlled by the gas and liquid pressures, then the best combination should be gas pressure and liquid pressure (or capillary pressure) (*Angelini et al.*, 2011; *Neumann et al.*, 2013).

Here, we use the gas pressure and liquid pressure as the two independent variables for transport module. Because these two variables are capable of determining the chemical reaction state, we do not need more variables to fix the reactive transport system. In virtue of mutual solubility law and Van Genuchten retention curve, combination of gas pressure and liquid pressure has strong advantage in solving the reactive two-phase flow process, especially in dealing with phase appearance/disappearance. We note that although the retention curve can relate the gas pressure, liquid pressure and gas saturation, the combination of gas pressure and liquid pressure is different from the combination of liquid pressure and gas saturation, because the relation is not reversible. For instance, when Van Genuchten curve is used for the retention curve, if the gas pressure ≤ 100 bar and liquid pressure is 100 bar, we can obtain the liquid saturation is 1.0; however, if we know the liquid pressure is 100 bar and the saturation is 1.0, we can only obtain that the gas pressure ≤ 100 bar. Therefore, combination of gas pressure and liquid pressure is superior to other combinations, such as combination of gas pressure and liquid saturation. Finally, gas pressure and liquid pressure are used to simulate the reactive two-phase GCS process, and the chemical reaction is inserted into the transport module without introducing new independent variables. We note that, when only the solubility of gas in water is considered and Henry's law is used to describe this solubility, then we can select concentration and liquid pressure as independent variables, because one can get the gas pressure and thus the saturation by using the gas concentration in water (*Bourgeat et al.*, 2009, 2013).

The transport equations and the reaction equations are solved in a fully coupled way. The independent variables-gas and liquid pressures- are updated by solving the governing flow equation based on the mass balance of the given conservative component, in which the chemical reaction is explicitly expressed by the independent variables through the chemical reaction module. Because all the rest variables can be directly or indirectly expressed as these two independent variables through the constitution equation and chain rule, the two employed independent variables contain all information for mass transport and chemical reaction, that is, the feedback of chemical reaction on mass composition is coupled to the mass transport. For instance, the brine density is a function of liquid pressure and CO_2 mass fraction, while CO_2 mass fraction is a function of gas pressure and liquid pressure, then the brine density can be indirectly expressed as a function of gas pressure and liquid pressure.

The mass transport module and chemical reaction module are, respectively, given in Sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2. The initial condition and injection well designing are, respectively, given in Sections 2.2.3 and 2.2.4. The model is solved with Newton-Raphson algorithm given in Section 2.2.5. The constraint for time step control is given in Section 2.2.6. Finally, Section 2.2.7 summarizes the algorithms implemented in the program.

2.2.1 Transport Module

When a transport process involves chemical reaction, the governing equations for multi-species two-phase flow are constructed based on the mass balance of conservative component. Using component instead of species can eliminate the source term due to chemical reaction. If we built the governing equations based on the mass balances of the reactive species, the equation contains not only advection and dispersion terms but also the source/sink term due to chemical reaction, because the local chemical interaction will contribute to the mass change of species. In contrast, no source terms due to chemical reactions exist if we use conservative component, which is independent from the chemical reactions. Because we have two independent variables, we need two governing equations, which means we need to select two components.

Component, a linear combination of species, can be defined in two ways. We can obtain the kernel matrix for the component based on the chemical element (e.g., H , Na , O , etc.), because the total mass of chemical element is independent from the chemical reaction (Leal *et al.*, 2013; Leal, 2014; Leal *et al.*, 2014, 2016). We can also obtain the kernel matrix for the component based on the stoichiometric matrix and the kernel matrix obtained with this approach is not unique (Saaltink *et al.*, 1998, 2013). Here, we use the first approach to obtain the component matrix while the second approach is going to be used in the next chapter.

In this chapter we only consider four major reactive species- liquid water ($H_2O(l)$),

water vapor ($H_2O(g)$), gaseous CO_2 ($CO_2(g)$) and aqueous CO_2 ($CO_2(aq)$)- that are involved in only two reactions (c.f. Equations (2.13) and (2.14)), despite that the CO_2 -brine system has many species (e.g., H^+ , OH^- , H_2CO_3 , etc.) that are involved in many reactions (e.g., water ionization). We also consider Na^+ and Cl^- species, but we assume their molality is constant. Na^+ and Cl^- species are introduced to adjust the brine density, viscosity and chemical reaction. We select two elements H and C as the components. The component matrix based on these two elements are

$$\mathbf{E} = \begin{array}{c} \\ \\ \end{array} \begin{array}{cccc} & H_2O(g) & H_2O(l) & CO_2(g) & CO_2(aq) \\ H & 2 & 2 & 0 & 0 \\ C & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{array}, \quad (2.1)$$

i.e., the component vector (\mathbf{e}) is given as

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{E}\boldsymbol{\xi}, \quad (2.2)$$

where, $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ is a vector that stores the masses of the four species. The H component is a combination of liquid water and water vapor (i.e., $[H_2O(l)]_m + [H_2O(g)]_m$), and the C component is a combination of aqueous CO_2 and gaseous CO_2 (i.e., $[CO_2(aq)]_m + [CO_2(g)]_m$); here, $[\cdot]_m$ means the mass of corresponding species. Clearly, components H and C are independent from reactions (2.13) and (2.14).

Based on the mass balances of H and C components, two transport equations are constructed as

$$0 = \mathcal{F}_1 = \sum_{\alpha=l,g} \left[\frac{\partial(\phi S_{\alpha\rho_{\alpha}} X_{\alpha}^H)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_{\alpha} X_{\alpha}^H \mathbf{q}_{\alpha}) - \nabla \cdot (\phi S_{\alpha} \mathbf{D}_{\alpha\rho_{\alpha}} \nabla X_{\alpha}^H) \right] - \sum_{j=1}^{NW} [Q_{\alpha W}^H]^j, \quad (2.3)$$

$$0 = \mathcal{F}_2 = \sum_{\alpha=l,g} \left[\frac{\partial(\phi S_{\alpha\rho_{\alpha}} X_{\alpha}^C)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_{\alpha} X_{\alpha}^C \mathbf{q}_{\alpha}) - \nabla \cdot (\phi S_{\alpha} \mathbf{D}_{\alpha\rho_{\alpha}} \nabla X_{\alpha}^C) \right] - \sum_{j=1}^{NW} [Q_{\alpha W}^C]^j, \quad (2.4)$$

where, subscripts $\alpha = l$ and $\alpha = g$ denote liquid brine and gaseous CO_2 -rich phases, respectively; superscripts H and C denote the two components, which are $H_2O(l, g)$ and $CO_2(aq, g)$, respectively; ϕ [-] is the porosity of the deep saline aquifer; S [-] represents the saturation; ρ [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$] represents the density; X_{α}^{β} [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$] represents the mass fraction of species β in phase α ; t [s] is time; \mathbf{D} [$\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] is the dispersion tensor; $Q_{\alpha W}$ [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] is the source term due to injection well; $\alpha W = l$ and $\alpha W = g$ denote injecting liquid brine and gaseous CO_2 phases, respectively; NW [-] is the number of wells; and the discharge

rate (\mathbf{q}_α) is given as extended Darcy's law

$$\mathbf{q}_\alpha = -\frac{\kappa_{r\alpha}}{\mu_\alpha} \kappa (\nabla p_\alpha - \rho_\alpha g \nabla z), \quad (2.5)$$

where, κ_r [-] denotes the relative permeability; μ [pa·s] the viscosity; κ [m²] the intrinsic permeability; p [pa] the pressure; z [m] the depth; and g [m·s⁻²] the gravitational acceleration. Besides, we have the following constitution equations:

$$X_l^S = 0.05844 X_l^H m_l^S, \quad (2.6)$$

$$X_l^H + X_l^C + X_l^S = 1, \quad (2.7)$$

$$X_g^H + X_g^C = 1, \quad (2.8)$$

$$S_l + S_g = 1, \quad (2.9)$$

$$S_l = S_l(p_c) \quad (2.10)$$

and

$$p_c = p_g - p_l, \quad (2.11)$$

where, superscript S denotes *NaCl* and p_c denotes the capillary pressure. The capillary pressure is related to saturation through retention curve. Here, we assume that the salt comprises only *NaCl*, and the molality of *NaCl* (m_l^S) is fixed. Define $\omega = (1 + 0.05844 m_l^S)$ and then Equations (2.6) and (2.7) merge to

$$\omega X_l^H + X_l^C = 1. \quad (2.12)$$

The empirical models for ρ_α , μ_α , \mathbf{D}_α , $\kappa_{r\alpha}$ and retention curve can be found in the Appendices A, B and C. Next section gives the chemical reaction module for calculating $X_\alpha^\beta(p_l, p_g)$, $\partial X_\alpha^\beta(p_l, p_g) / \partial p_l$ and $\partial X_\alpha^\beta(p_l, p_g) / \partial p_g$. We note that all the variables in the governing equations can be expressed with independent variables p_l and p_g , through the constitution equations and chain rule.

2.2.2 Chemical Reaction Module

The explicit model by *Spycher and Pruess* (2005) is used because it can give efficient and accurate prediction of the CO_2 dissolution efficiency in GCS. Compared to traditional

Table 2.1: Subroutine SP: Chemical reaction module.

Input: \mathbf{p}_l and \mathbf{p}_g ; \mathbf{m}_l^S is a given fixed vector
1: calculate fugacity coefficients $\mathbf{F}^\beta = \mathbf{F}^\beta(\mathbf{p}_g)$, ($\beta = H, C$) (c.f. Equation (D.2));
2: calculate the equilibrium constants $\mathbf{K}^\beta = \mathbf{K}^\beta(\mathbf{p}_l)$ (c.f. Equation (D.18));
3: calculate $\mathbf{A} = \frac{\mathbf{K}^H}{\mathbf{F}^H \mathbf{p}_g}$ and $\mathbf{B} = \frac{\mathbf{K}^C \mathbf{p}_g}{55.508 \gamma'_{CO_2} \mathbf{K}^C}$ (c.f. Equations (2.21) and (2.22));
4: calculate mole fractions in CO_2 and pure water phase $\mathbf{x}_g^{H_0}$ and $\mathbf{x}_l^{C_0} = \mathbf{B}(1 - \mathbf{x}_g^{H_0})$; here, \mathbf{B} is calculated with $\gamma'_{CO_2} = 1$;
5: calculate CO_2 molality in pure water $\mathbf{m}_l^{C_0} = \frac{55.508 \mathbf{x}_l^{C_0}}{1 - \mathbf{x}_l^{C_0}}$;
6: calculate activity coefficient of $CO_2(aq)$ $\gamma'_{CO_2} = \gamma'_{CO_2}(\mathbf{p}_l)$ (c.f. Equation (D.11));
7: calculate CO_2 molality in brine $\mathbf{m}_l^C = \mathbf{m}_l^{C_0} / \gamma'_{CO_2}$;
8: calculate mole fraction of $CO_2(aq)$ in liquid brine phase and mole fraction of $H_2O(g)$ in gaseous CO_2 -rich phase: $\mathbf{x}_l^C = \frac{\mathbf{m}_l^C}{\mathbf{m}_l^C + 55.508 + \nu \mathbf{m}_l^S}$; $\mathbf{x}_g^H = \mathbf{A}(1 - \mathbf{x}_l^C - \mathbf{x}_l^S)$, where, $\mathbf{x}_l^S = \frac{\nu \mathbf{m}_l^S}{\mathbf{m}_l^C + 55.508 + \nu \mathbf{m}_l^S}$;
9: change the mole fractions into mass fractions with $\mathbf{X}_g^H = \frac{18.015 \mathbf{x}_g^H}{18.015 \mathbf{x}_g^H + 44.01(1 - \mathbf{x}_g^H)}$ and $\mathbf{X}_l^C = \frac{44.01 \mathbf{x}_l^C}{18.015(1 - \mathbf{x}_l^C) + 44.01 \mathbf{x}_l^C}$ (c.f. Equations (2.26) and (2.27)); obtain $\mathbf{X}_l^H = 1 - \mathbf{X}_l^C$ and $\mathbf{X}_g^C = \mathbf{X}_g^H$;
10: calculate $\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{-\mathbf{K}^H \frac{\partial(\mathbf{F}^H \mathbf{p}_g)}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}}{(\mathbf{F}^H \mathbf{p}_g)^2}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{\mathbf{K}^C \frac{\partial(\mathbf{F}^C \mathbf{p}_g)}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}}{55.508 \cdot (\mathbf{K}^C)^2}$; $\frac{\partial(\mathbf{AB})}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} \mathbf{K}^H \mathbf{F}^H \mathbf{K}^C - \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} \mathbf{K}^C \mathbf{F}^C \mathbf{K}^H}{55.508 \cdot (\mathbf{F}^H \mathbf{K}^C)^2}$;
11: calculate $\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_g^{H_0}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} - \frac{\partial(\mathbf{AB})}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}\right)(1 - \mathbf{AB}) + \frac{\partial(\mathbf{AB})}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}(\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{AB})}{(1 - \mathbf{AB})^2}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^{C_0}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}(1 - \mathbf{x}_g^{H_0}) - \mathbf{B} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_g^{H_0}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}$;
12: calculate $\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}_l^{C_0}}{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^{C_0}} = \frac{55.508}{(1 - \mathbf{x}_l^{C_0})^2}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}_l^{C_0}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}_l^{C_0}}{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^{C_0}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^{C_0}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}_l^{C_0}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} \frac{1}{\gamma'_{CO_2}}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{55.508 + \nu \mathbf{m}_l^S}{(\mathbf{m}_l^C + 55.508 + \nu \mathbf{m}_l^S)^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^S}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{-\nu \mathbf{m}_l^S}{(\mathbf{m}_l^C + 55.508 + \nu \mathbf{m}_l^S)^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_g^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}(1 - \mathbf{x}_l^C - \mathbf{x}_l^S) - \mathbf{A} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^S}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} \right)$;
13: calculate $\frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_g^H}{\partial \mathbf{x}_g^H} = \frac{18.015 \cdot 44.01}{(44.01 - 25.995 \mathbf{x}_g^H)^2}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^C} = \frac{18.015 \cdot 44.01 (1 + 0.0584 \mathbf{m}_l^S)}{[18.015(1 - \mathbf{x}_l^C) + 44.01 \mathbf{x}_l^C]^2}$;
14: obtain $\frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_g^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_g^H}{\partial \mathbf{x}_g^H} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_g^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^C} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}$;
15: calculate $\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} = \frac{\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}}{\mathbf{F}^H \mathbf{p}_g}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} = \frac{1}{55.508} \frac{-\mathbf{F}^C \mathbf{p}_g \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}}{(\mathbf{K}^C)^2}$; $\frac{\partial(\mathbf{AB})}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} = \frac{1}{55.508} \frac{\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} \mathbf{F}^C \mathbf{F}^H \mathbf{K}^C - \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} \mathbf{F}^H \mathbf{F}^C \mathbf{K}^H}{(\mathbf{F}^H \mathbf{K}^C)^2}$;
16: calculate $\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_g^{H_0}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} = \frac{\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} - \frac{\partial(\mathbf{AB})}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}\right)(1 - \mathbf{AB}) + \frac{\partial(\mathbf{AB})}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}(\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{AB})}{(1 - \mathbf{AB})^2}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^{C_0}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}(1 - \mathbf{x}_g^{H_0}) - \mathbf{B} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_g^{H_0}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}$;
17: calculate $\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}_l^{C_0}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}_l^{C_0}}{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^{C_0}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^{C_0}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} = \frac{\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}_l^{C_0}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} \gamma'_{CO_2} - \frac{\partial \gamma'_{CO_2}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} \mathbf{m}_l^{C_0}}{(\gamma'_{CO_2})^2}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} = \frac{55.508 + \nu \mathbf{m}_l^S}{(\mathbf{m}_l^C + 55.508 + \nu \mathbf{m}_l^S)^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^S}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} = \frac{-\nu \mathbf{m}_l^S}{(\mathbf{m}_l^C + 55.508 + \nu \mathbf{m}_l^S)^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_g^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}(1 - \mathbf{x}_l^C - \mathbf{x}_l^S) - \mathbf{A} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^S}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} \right)$;
18: obtain $\frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_g^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_g^H}{\partial \mathbf{x}_g^H} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_g^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}$; $\frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^C} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}$;
Output: \mathbf{X}_l^H , \mathbf{X}_l^C , \mathbf{X}_g^H , \mathbf{X}_g^C , $\frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_g^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}$, $\frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}$, $\frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_g^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}$ and $\frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_l^C}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l}$.

methods- Mass Action Law (MAL; stoichiometric method) and Gibbs Energy Minimization (GEM; nonstoichiometric method)- which require the grid-by-grid calculation of Jacobian matrix of reaction equations, *Spycher and Pruess* (2005) method explicitly calculates the chemical reaction and significantly reduces the CPU time.

Spycher and Pruess (2005) model only considers two reactions among $H_2O(l)$, $H_2O(g)$, $CO_2(g)$ and $CO_2(aq)$:

where, K^H and K^C are the equilibrium constants for H_2O and CO_2 evaporations, and f and a denote the fugacity and activity, respectively.

The fugacity is calculated as

$$f_g^\beta = F^\beta x_g^\beta \frac{p_g}{p^0}, \quad (2.15)$$

where, $\beta = (H, C)$ denote ($H_2O(g)$, $CO_2(g)$), respectively; the fugacity coefficients are given in Appendix D; x_α^β is the mole fraction of β species in α phase; and, the reference pressure $p^0 = 1$ bar. The activity of liquid water is simply calculated as

$$a_l^H = x_l^H = (1 - x_l^S - x_l^C), \quad (2.16)$$

where, x_l^S is defined as

$$x_l^S = \frac{\nu m_l^S}{55.508 + \nu m_l^S + m_l^C}, \quad (2.17)$$

where, m_l^C represents molality of aqueous CO_2 in liquid brine phase; ν is the stoichiometric number of ions in the salt (e.g., 2 for $NaCl$ and 3 for $MgCl_2$). The sophisticated Helgeson-Kirkham-Flowers (HKF) model is also used to calculate the liquid water activity, and we find that the concise formula (2.16) yields very similar results as HKF model, given in Appendix D. The activity of aqueous CO_2 is calculated as

$$a_l^C = \gamma'_{CO_2} m_l^C, \quad (2.18)$$

where, γ'_{CO_2} is the activity coefficient of aqueous CO_2 , and *Duan and Sun* (2003) model, given in the Appendix D, is used to calculate γ'_{CO_2} . For pure water $\gamma'_{CO_2} = 1$.

When reaction is at equilibrium we have

$$x_g^H = \frac{K^H a_l^H}{F^H p_g} \quad (2.19)$$

and

$$x_l^C = \frac{F^C (1 - x_g^H) p_g}{55.508 \gamma'_{CO_2} K^C}. \quad (2.20)$$

Setting

$$A = \frac{K^H}{F^H p_g} \quad (2.21)$$

and

$$B = \frac{K^C p_g}{55.508 \gamma'_{CO_2} K^C}, \quad (2.22)$$

the mutual solubilities are then explicitly given as

$$x_g^H = \frac{1 - B - x_l^S}{\frac{1}{A} - B} \quad (2.23)$$

and

$$x_l^C = B (1 - x_g^H). \quad (2.24)$$

It is better to use salt molality instead of mole fraction because salt molality is independent of CO_2 solubility; therefore, we change Equation (2.23) into

$$x_g^H = \frac{55.508 (1 - B)}{\left(\frac{1}{A} - B\right) (\nu m_l^S + 55.508) + B \nu m_l^S}. \quad (2.25)$$

The detailed derivation of Equation (2.25) can be found in *Spycher and Pruess (2005)*. With Equations (2.25) and (2.24) we can explicitly update the mole fractions in both liquid brine and gaseous CO_2 -rich phases. Note that in transport equations the concentrations are given as mass fractions, while mole fractions are used to solve the mutual solubility. We can change the mole fractions into mass fractions with

$$X_g^H = \frac{18.015 x_g^H}{18.015 x_g^H + 44.01 (1 - x_g^H)} \quad (2.26)$$

and

$$X_l^C = \frac{44.01 x_l^C}{18.015 (1 - x_l^C) (1 + 0.05844 m_l^S) + 44.01 x_l^C}. \quad (2.27)$$

Herein, we use the model proposed in *Duan and Sun (2003)* to calculate the activity coefficient of $CO_2(aq)$. Because the activity coefficient of $CO_2(aq)$ given by *Duan and Sun (2003)* is not ‘true’ activity coefficient, we need to slightly change the aforementioned steps. The activity coefficient given by *Duan and Sun (2003)* actually describes the relation between the solubility of $CO_2(aq)$ in pure water and brine:

$$\gamma'_{CO_2} = m_l^{C_0} / m_l^C, \quad (2.28)$$

Table 2.2: Subroutine I2: Initialization.

Input: $[\mathbf{p}_l]^{top,0}$, $[\mathbf{p}_g]^{top,0}$ and \mathbf{G} (e.g., the number of layers n_L , the (x, y, z) location of each cell, etc.);
1: $\mathbf{p}_l^{i=1} = \mathbf{p}_l^{top,0}$, $\mathbf{p}_g^{i=1} = \mathbf{p}_g^{top,0}$;
2: for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n_L - 1$, do 3 to 9 ; % n_L denotes number of layers;
3: $\mathbf{p}_l^{i+1,j=0} = \mathbf{p}_l^i$, $\mathbf{p}_g^{i+1,j=0} = \mathbf{p}_g^i$;
4: calculate $\mathbf{p}_l^{i+1,j+1}$, $\mathbf{p}_g^{i+1,j+1}$ with Equations (2.29) and (2.30); calculate $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^\beta]^{i+1,j+1}$ with Algorithm SP given in Table 2.1; calculate the density $\rho_l^{i+1,j+1}$ and $\rho_g^{i+1,j+1}$ with Equations (A.5) and (A.12);
5: while $\max(\mathbf{p}_l^{i+1,j+1} - \mathbf{p}_l^{i+1,j}, \mathbf{p}_g^{i+1,j+1} - \mathbf{p}_g^{i+1,j}) > \epsilon_p$, do 6 to 7;
6: $j=j+1$;
7: repeat Step 4;
8: endwhile ⁵ ;
9: $\mathbf{p}_l^{i+1} = \mathbf{p}_l^{i+1,j+1}$, $\mathbf{p}_g^{i+1} = \mathbf{p}_g^{i+1,j+1}$, $\rho_l^{i+1} = \rho_l^{i+1,j+1}$, $\rho_g^{i+1} = \rho_g^{i+1,j+1}$, $\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{\beta,i+1} = \mathbf{X}_\alpha^{\beta,i+1,j+1}$;
10: endfor ² ;
11: $[\mathbf{p}_l]^0 = [\mathbf{p}_l^1, \mathbf{p}_l^2, \dots, \mathbf{p}_l^{n_L}]$, $[\mathbf{p}_g]^0 = [\mathbf{p}_g^1, \mathbf{p}_g^2, \dots, \mathbf{p}_g^{n_L}]$, $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^\beta]^0 = [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{\beta,1}, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^{\beta,2}, \dots, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^{\beta,n_L}]$, $[\rho_l]^0 = [\rho_l^1, \rho_l^2, \dots, \rho_l^{n_L}]$, $[\rho_g]^0 = [\rho_g^1, \rho_g^2, \dots, \rho_g^{n_L}]$;
Output: $[\mathbf{p}_l]^0$, $[\mathbf{p}_g]^0$, $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^\beta]^0$, $[\rho_l]^0$ and $[\rho_g]^0$.

where, $m_l^{C_0}$ and m_l^C represent the molality of aqueous CO_2 in pure water and brine at same temperature and pressure, respectively.

Table 2.1 summarizes the algorithm for solving the chemical reaction on the basis of the aforementioned steps. The accuracy of this chemical module is checked in Appendix E.

2.2.3 Initialization

Initially, the system is assumed to be at stable state under gravity and capillary pressure. This means the horizontal pressure gradient, caused by capillarity, is zero and the vertical pressure gradient, caused by gravity and capillarity, is equal to ρg . If both gas phase and liquid phase exist, the saturation distribution at steady state could be nonuniform, with the saturation of wetting phase (brine) in the low permeable region being larger than that in high permeable region, because we use Leverett's scaling factor, which is a function of intrinsic permeability and porosity, to calibrate the relation between the saturation and capillary pressure. If there are multiple layers in the vertical direction, we give the gas and liquid pressures on the first layer (top layer). From these two pressures we can get the saturation distribution in the first layer. We can also get the densities of gas phase (if exists) and liquid phase of the first layer. The pressures of the rest layers (beneath the first layer) are estimated by

$$p_l^{i+1,j+1} = p_l^i + \frac{1}{2} (\rho_l^i + \rho_l^{i+1,j}) g \Delta z \quad (2.29)$$

and

$$p_g^{i+1,j+1} = p_g^i + \frac{1}{2} (\rho_g^i + \rho_g^{i+1,j}) g \Delta z. \quad (2.30)$$

where the superscript i represent the i th layer and j represents the j th estimation. Initially, we assume $\rho_l^{i+1,0} = \rho_l^i$. Once we have the $(j+1)$ th estimation of the pressures of the $i+1$ layer, we can update the densities ($\rho_l^{i+1,j+1}$, $\rho_g^{i+1,j+1}$) of the $(i+1)$ th layer. Having updated the densities we can re-predict the pressures of $(i+1)$ th layer with Equations (2.29) and (2.30). This process is repeated until the pressure change is smaller than the tolerance and we move to the next layer. Once we have the pressures, we can calculate the saturation with the retention curve. Table 2.2 summarizes the aforementioned procedure. In Table 2.2, grid system (\mathbf{G}) is generated as input of the main routine. \mathbf{G} contains the information of the relation between cells and interfaces, center positions of cells and faces, cell volumes and face areas. For instance, for each face, we can read from \mathbf{G} the sequence number of its two neighbor cells, its area and the position of its center. Details of generation of the grid system are not given here. We neither give the details of different types of boundary conditions.

The system generated by aforementioned procedure can be further improved. Before starting the target simulation, we can first run the simulation without any external forces or sources until the velocity is lower than tolerance. Actually, this step is not really necessary because the result from the aforementioned procedure is already quite satisfactory.

2.2.4 Injection Well

Gaseous CO_2 or water is injected to the domain through injection well. If a grid is pierced by injection well, we add a source term to this grid. We can inject pure CO_2 , pure water, CO_2 -saturated water, or wet CO_2 . If we inject α -phase, the governing equation for the j th well is

$$\mathcal{F}_W^j = -[Q_{\alpha W}]^j + \sum_{m=1}^M \left[\rho_{\alpha W} W I^{j,m} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}}{\mu_\alpha} \left(p_{bh}^j - \rho_{\alpha W} g (z_{bh}^j - z^{j,m}) - p_\alpha^{j,m} \right) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{j,m}) \right], \quad (2.31)$$

and the source term for m -th grid pierced by j -th injection well can be given as

$$[Q_{\alpha W}^\beta]^{j,m} = X_{\alpha W}^\beta \rho_{\alpha W} W I^{j,m} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}}{\mu_\alpha} \left(p_{bh}^j - \rho_{\alpha W} g (z_{bh}^j - z^{j,m}) - p_\alpha^{j,m} \right) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{j,m}), \quad (2.32)$$

where, superscript (j, m) means the m -th grid pierced by the j -th well, $Q_{\alpha W}$ is the given injection mass rate of α phase; M is the total number of the pierced grids by j th well, $X_{\alpha W}^\beta$ is the mass fraction of β -species in α -phase in the well, $\rho_{\alpha, W}$ is the density of α -phase in the well (here, we assume the density in the well is only a function of bottom hole pressure), $\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}$ is the maximum relative permeability of the injected α -phase, p_{bh}^j is

the bottom hole pressure at reference depth z_{bh}^j for the j -th well, $p_\alpha^{j,m}$ is the pressure of α -phase in the m -th grid pierced by the j th injection well and the well index $WI^{j,m}$ is defined in Appendix B.

2.2.5 Newton-Raphson Iteration

The nonlinearities in the governing equations are solved with the Newton-Raphson method. The system of three equations given by Equations (2.3), (2.4) and (2.31) is rewritten in compact form

$$\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (2.33)$$

where

$$[\mathcal{F}] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{F}_1 \\ \mathcal{F}_2 \\ \mathcal{F}_W \end{bmatrix}, \quad [\mathbf{x}] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_l \\ \mathbf{p}_g \\ \mathbf{p}_{bh} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.34)$$

The control equations for the injection wells and those for the field grids have been written separately, because one injection well may pierce more than one cell. Equation (2.33) is solved for \mathbf{x} by using a Taylor series expansion omitting higher-order terms:

$$\mathcal{F}^{n+1,k+1} \approx \mathcal{F}^{n+1,k} + \frac{\partial[\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} [\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k}, \quad (2.35)$$

where, n and k denote the time step and iteration step, respectively.

As $\mathcal{F}^{n+1,k+1}$ should be zero, Equation (2.35) is rewritten in the well known Newton-Raphson form, through which the three groups of independent variables are solved. The Newton-Raphson form is given as

$$\frac{\partial[\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} [\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k} = -[\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k}, \quad (2.36)$$

with the Jacobian matrix

$$\left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right]^{n+1,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_1}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_1}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_1}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_2}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_2}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_2}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{11} & \mathbf{M}_{12} & \mathbf{M}_{1W} \\ \mathbf{M}_{21} & \mathbf{M}_{22} & \mathbf{M}_{2W} \\ \mathbf{M}_{W1} & \mathbf{M}_{W2} & \mathbf{M}_{WW} \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k} = \mathbf{M}^{n+1,k}. \quad (2.37)$$

Here, \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{F}_2 , respectively, store the \mathcal{F}_1 (c.f. Equation (2.3)) and \mathcal{F}_2 (c.f. Equation (2.4)) for all the grids; similarly, \mathbf{p}_l and \mathbf{p}_g , respectively, store the liquid pressures and gas pressures for all the grids; \mathbf{p}_{bh} and \mathcal{F}_W , respectively, store p_{bh} and \mathcal{F}_W (c.f. Equation (2.31)) for all the wells. Detailed information on numerical discretization of \mathcal{F} and \mathbf{M} can

Table 2.3: Subroutine NR2: Netown-Raphson iteration.

Input: $[\mathbf{p}_l]^n$, $[\mathbf{p}_g]^n$, $[\mathbf{p}_{bh}]^n$ and Δt^{n+1} ; and also the grid discretization (\mathbf{G});
0: set $k = 0$; $[\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,0} = \text{inf}$;
$[\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,0} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_l \\ \mathbf{p}_g \\ \mathbf{p}_{bh} \end{bmatrix}^n$; $[\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,0} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{F}_1 \\ \mathcal{F}_2 \\ \mathcal{F}_W \end{bmatrix}^n$;
1: while $\max[\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k} > \epsilon_p$ and $k < N_{kmax} = 15$, do steps 2 to 3
2: using Δt^{n+1} , the density (ρ_α) calculated with the models given in Appendix A, the viscosity (μ_α) calculated with the models given in Appendix A, the saturation (\mathbf{S}_α) calculated with the models given in Appendix C, the relative permeability ($\kappa_{r\alpha}$) calculated with the models given in Appendix C, the flux (\mathbf{q}_α) of each face calculated with Darcy's law (i.e., Equation (2.5)), the dispersion tensor (\mathbf{D}) calculated with the model given in Appendix B, and the mass fraction (\mathbf{X}_α^β) calculated with Subroutine SP given in Table 2.1, sequentially calculate
$[\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{F}_1 \\ \mathcal{F}_2 \\ \mathcal{F}_W \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k}$; $[\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \mathbf{x}}]^{n+1,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_1}{\partial p_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_1}{\partial p_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_1}{\partial p_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_2}{\partial p_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_2}{\partial p_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_2}{\partial p_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial p_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial p_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial p_{bh}} \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k}$;
$[\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k} = - \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right]^{n+1,k}{}^{-1} [\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k}$; $[\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k+1} = [\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k} + [\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k}$;
3: $k = k + 1$;
4: endwhile ¹ ;
5: if $k = N_{kmax}$ % the algorithm does not converge after N_{kmax} NR iterations;
6: then $\Delta t^{n+1} = t_s = 0.1$ second; and go to step 0; % reduce Δt^{n+1} and restart from t^{n+1} with a very small new Δt^{n+1} ;
7: endif ⁵ ;
8: calculate $\Delta \mathbf{p}^n = [\mathbf{p}]^{n+1,k+1} - [\mathbf{p}]^n$; $\Delta \mathbf{S}_\alpha^n = [\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^{n+1,k+1} - [\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^n$;
Output: $(\mathbf{p}_l^{n+1}, \mathbf{p}_g^{n+1}, \mathbf{p}_{bh}^{n+1}) = [\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k+1}$; $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^\beta]^{n+1}$; $[\rho_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $[\mu_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $[\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $[\mathbf{q}_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $\Delta \mathbf{p}^n$; $\Delta \mathbf{S}_\alpha^n$; and Δt^{n+1} .

be found in Appendix B.

Having obtained $[\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k}$ with Equation (2.36), we can update $[\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k}$ according to

$$[\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k+1} = [\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k} + [\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k}. \quad (2.38)$$

The Newton-Raphson iteration is terminated if the maximum change of the gas and liquid pressures is smaller than the tolerance value ϵ_p (e.g., 10^{-5} pa), or if the maximum error is smaller than the tolerance value ϵ_{err} (e.g., 10^{-12}). The Netown-Raphson algorithm is summarized in Table 2.3, where the time step is reduced to a very small value (t_s) if the Newton-Raphson iteration does not converge at maximum allowed number of iteration N_{kmax} . The reason will be explained in the following section.

2.2.6 Time Step Control

Time step control is critical in improving the efficiency as well as the accuracy of the numerical simulation (*Chen et al.*, 2006). One should not overlook the role of time step control in the simulation, although it only composes a very small portion of the program. As we know, a too large time step will sacrifice the accuracy while a too small time step will compromise the efficiency.

Normally, the time step is only limited by the convection strength, and we only need the classic CFL constraint that requires

$$\max_{\substack{1 \leq j \leq N \\ i=x,y,z}} \frac{l_{conv,i}^{j,n+1}}{\Delta l_i^j} = \max_{\substack{1 \leq j \leq N \\ i=x,y,z}} \frac{q_i^{j,n} \Delta t_c^{n+1}}{\phi^j \Delta l_i^j} = \max_{\substack{1 \leq j \leq N \\ i=x,y,z}} \frac{q_i^{j,n} A_i^j \Delta t_c^{n+1}}{\phi^j V_c^j} < c_{conv}, \quad (2.39)$$

where, N denotes the total number of the grids, superscript j denotes the j th grid, subscript $i = (x, y, z)$ denotes the i th direction of the face of the grid, n denotes the time step, l_{conv} is the characteristic length scale of the convection, V_c is the volume of the grid, Δl_i is the grid length in i th direction, A_i is the grid area in i th direction, $q = \max(q_l, q_g)$, q/ϕ is the interstitial velocity, and c_{conv} , smaller than unit (e.g., 0.2), is a constant controlling the maximum allowed time step, Δt_c^{n+1} .

However, it is worthy of noting that in some cases the time step may be controlled by either the diffusion strength or the convection strength at different stages. For instance, in the case of Gravity-Driven-Convection (GDC) simulation, the convection strength is very small when the GDC is not fully developed and the diffusion strength controls the time step length; however, when the GDC is fully developed, the time step is limited by the convection strength. As such, we should consider both the convection and diffusion when selecting the time step. Neglecting one or the other could cause low efficiency or low accuracy. In literature, few researchers offer information on the time step control when Fickian diffusion is at similar magnitude as Darcian convection. When studying GDC, *Elenius and Johannsen* (2012a) tried different time steps and selected a reasonable one based on sensitivity analysis. This way of determining the time step is cumbersome and not automatic. Here, we extend the CFL condition for flow dominated by convection strength to flow controlled by either convection or diffusion strength. For the system dominated by diffusion, we similarly propose that the time step is governed by

$$\max_{\substack{1 \leq j \leq N \\ i=x,y,z}} \frac{l_{diff,i}^{j,n+1}}{\Delta l_i^j} = \max_{\substack{1 \leq j \leq N \\ i=x,y,z}} \frac{\sqrt{2\phi^j D_i^j \Delta t_c^{n+1}}}{\Delta l_i^j} = \max_{\substack{1 \leq j \leq N \\ i=x,y,z}} \frac{A_i^j \sqrt{2\phi^j D_i^j \Delta t_c^{n+1}}}{V_g^j} < c_{diff}. \quad (2.40)$$

where l_{diff} is the characteristic length scale of diffusion and c_{diff} , smaller than unit (e.g., 0.2), is a constant controlling the maximum allowed time step, Δt_c^{n+1} . Equations (2.39) and (2.40) are together used for automatically updating the time steps. We call Equations

Table 2.4: Subroutine UT: Update time step Δt and time t .

Input: $[\mathbf{q}_\alpha]^n$; $\Delta \mathbf{p}^n$; $\Delta \mathbf{S}_\alpha^n$; t^n ; Δt^n ; and \mathbf{G} ;
1: in virtue of the flux at each face $[\mathbf{q}_\alpha]^n$ and the grid information \mathbf{G} , calculate the characteristic time (Δt_c^n) with Equations (2.39) and (2.40);
2: using the characteristic time (Δt_c^n), the current time (t^n), the pressure change ($\Delta \mathbf{p}^n$) and the saturation change ($\Delta \mathbf{S}_\alpha^n$), update the time step Δt^{n+1} with Equations (2.41) and (2.42);
% note that t^n is updated in the main loop;
Output: Δt^{n+1} .

(2.39) and (2.40) extended CFL condition. For high permeable region, l_{diff} is smaller than l_{conv} , and the time step is controlled by convection strength. For low permeable region, l_{diff} is larger than l_{conv} , and the time step is controlled by the diffusion strength.

Moreover, the time step is very sensitive to the phase appearance/disappearance. When the simulation experiences phase appearance and disappearance at a time point, the extended CFL condition for time step control does not work anymore, and it is important to redefine the constraint for time step. If using the new time step (Δt^{n+1}) makes the iteration number $k > N_{kmax}$ (e.g. $N_{kmax} = 15$) to converge, we should reduce the time step to a very small value, t_s (e.g., 0.1 second), and calculate the $n + 1$ step again. If the time step drops to t_s , the time step then increases gradually from t_s according to

$$\Delta t^{n+1} = \min \left(\Delta t_c^{n+1}, \Delta t_m^{n+1} \right), \quad (2.41)$$

where

$$\Delta t_m^{n+1} = \min \left[\Delta t_{max}, t_{tot} - t^n, \Delta t^n \cdot \min \left(5, \frac{\Delta p_{gmax}}{\max[\Delta p_g]^n}, \frac{\Delta p_{lmax}}{\max[\Delta p_l]^n}, \frac{\Delta S_{lmax}}{\max[\Delta S_l]^n} \right) \right], \quad (2.42)$$

where, Δt_{max} is maximum allowed time step, Δp_{gmax} is maximum allowed change of gas pressure, Δp_{lmax} is maximum allowed change of liquid pressure, ΔS_{lmax} is maximum allowed change of brine saturation, and t_{tot} is the total simulation time. Initial time step Δt^0 can be selected as 0.1 second. The time is updated by

$$t^{n+1} = t^n + \Delta t^{n+1}. \quad (2.43)$$

2.2.7 Main Routine

Having described the mechanisms of the program separately in Sections 2.2.1 to 2.2.6, we give in this section the main routine of the program, which is comprised of the aforementioned four subroutines, which have been, respectively, given in Tables 2.1 to 2.4.

Table 2.5: Main routine.

Require: $[\mathbf{p}_l]^{top,0}$, $[\mathbf{p}_g]^{top,0}$, \mathbf{p}_{bh}^0 , $\mathbf{Q}_{\alpha W}$, $t^0 = 0$ and Δt^0 ; the grid discretization (\mathbf{G}); the field property (i.e., permeability $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ and porosity ϕ);
0: initialization with Subroutine I2, given in Table: 2.2;
1: while $t^n < t_{tot}$, do 2 to 5;
2: update $[\mathbf{p}_l; \mathbf{p}_g; \mathbf{p}_{bh}]^n$ and probably Δt^{n+1} with Subroutine NR2, given in Table 2.3;
3: $t^{n+1} = t^n + \Delta t^{n+1}$;
4: update Δt^{n+1} with Subroutine UT given in Table 2.4;
5: $n=n+1$;
6: endwhile ¹ ;
Output: $(\mathbf{p}_l^{n+1}, \mathbf{p}_g^{n+1}, \mathbf{p}_{bh}^{n+1})$; $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^\beta]^{n+1}$; $[\boldsymbol{\rho}_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $[\boldsymbol{\mu}_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $[\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $[\mathbf{q}_\alpha]^{n+1}$.

The main routine is given in Table 2.5.

2.3 Benchmark Test and Sensitive Analysis

Benchmark test is conducted against the theoretical solution by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006), which predicts saturation distribution when injecting CO_2 into a formation initially filled with brine. In *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006), the mutual solubility between the two phases and the capillary pressure between the two phases are not considered (although an advanced model for mutual solubility is also offered, it does not apply to our case). In the numerical simulation we consider the dissolution of CO_2 into brine as well as the evaporation of water into gaseous CO_2 ; we also consider the capillary pressure between the two phases. Even though there exist discrepancies between the simplified theoretical model by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006) and the numerical model in this work, the major mechanisms (e.g., the competition between viscous force and gravity force) are the same. Therefore, we can use *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006) model to benchmark our numerical model. Actually, as we will see in the following of this section, the numerical result from this work agrees well with the theoretical solution by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006).

Moreover, we also conduct sensitive analysis over the effects of the retention curve and the dispersion coefficient.

2.3.1 Setup Description

We consider a confined saline formation with an isolated fully-penetrating well centered in the middle. The system is represented by an axisymmetric model defined by cylindrical coordinates (r, φ, z) . The z -axis coincides with the center of the fully-penetrating well. Figure 2.1 shows a sketch diagram of the model setup. By symmetry, the solution does not depend on the angular coordinate φ . The top and bottom boundaries are impermeable boundaries, and the outer boundary has constant liquid pressure and zero saturation

gradient. The system is initially saturated with brine, which is assumed to be at hydrostatic state, i.e., the liquid pressure increases downward with a vertical gradient given by the specific gravity of the liquid phase, $\rho_l g$. The injected $CO_2(g)$ is saturated with water vapor. This is mostly the case in real applications because dry CO_2 can trigger the dissolution of minerals, such as halite, and reduce well injectivity. The radius of the injection well is 0.1 [m]. The initial liquid pressure is $p_{li} = 150$ [bar] on the top layer, and the initial gas pressure is $p_{gi} = 10$ [bar] everywhere. CO_2 is injected at a constant mass injection rate Q_{well} . With these parameters, $Q_{well} \approx Q_g^C$ and Q_g^H is very small ($\sim 0.2\%$). The concentration of $NaCl$ (m_l^S) is fixed to 0.5 [molal] and the temperature (T_c) is 60 [°C]. The axisymmetric model grid discretization consists of N_z layers and N_r coaxial rings around the z -axis. The discretization is uniform in the vertical direction but increases linearly with r . In order to satisfy the analytical solution requirements, the permeability, fluid densities, and fluid viscosities are assumed constant, and the relative permeability is assumed to be linearly proportional to saturation. Table 2.6 provides a summary of the parameters adopted for the benchmark test. Based on these parameters, we can calculate the gravity factor $G = 2\pi\kappa B^2 \Delta\rho g \rho_g / (Q_{g,m} \mu_l) = 0.1636$ and the mobility ratio $\lambda = \mu_l / \mu_g = 8.377$. These two parameters- G and λ - are used to obtain the theoretical solution by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006) (c.f. Appendix F).

For comparison purposes, we estimated the location of the interface by balancing the area of the saturation distribution above and below the interface to preserve mass balance,

$$z(r) = b - \int_0^b S_g(r, z) dz. \quad (2.44)$$

Moreover, in order to test the effect of retention curve on the spread of $CO_2(g)$ plume, we also use combinations of ($m_p = 0.8, \alpha_p = 50$ [bar]) and ($m_p = 0.4, \alpha_p = 5$ [bar]). When we conduct simulations for sensitive analysis we use the real models for viscosities and densities (c.f. Appendix A). We also use different dispersivities to test the effect of dispersivity on the GCS. The parameters are listed in Table 2.7.

In total, one simulation, in which the densities and viscosities of the fluids are constant, is conducted to benchmark the numerical program and four more simulations, which use real density and viscosity models, are conducted to analyze the effect of retention curve and dispersion coefficient.

Table 2.6: Parameter settings adopted for the benchmark test.

Parameters	Symbol	Units	Values
Domain size	(R, b)	[m×m]	(2000,15)
Grid discretization	(N_r, N_z)	[-]	(100,20)
Intrinsic permeability	κ	[m ²]	2×10^{-14}
Porosity	ϕ	[-]	0.15
Parameter for Eq. (C.1)	α_p	[bar ⁻¹]	5
Parameter for Eq. (C.1)	m_p	[-]	0.8
Initial pressures	$(p_l^{top,i}, p_g^i)$	[bar]	(150,10)
Well radius	r_w	[m]	0.1
Injection rate	Q_{well}	[Mt/year]	0.028
Simulation time	T_s	[day]	5194
Viscosities	(μ_l, μ_g)	[mpa·s]	(0.511,0.061)
Densities	(ρ_l, ρ_g)	[kg·m ⁻³]	(1099,733)
Hydrodynamic dispersivities	(α_L, α_T)	[m]	(5,1)
Molecular diffusion coefficient	D_m	[m ² ·s ⁻¹]	10^{-9}
Salinity	m_l^S	[molal]	0.5
Temperature	T_c	[°C]	60

Table 2.7: Parameter settings for sensitive analysis.

Case 1:	$\alpha_p = 5$ [bar], $m_p = 0.8$, $\alpha_{Ll} = 5$ [m], $\alpha_{Tl} = 1$ [m]
Case 2:	$\alpha_p = 5$ [bar], $m_p = 0.4$, $\alpha_{Ll} = 5$ [m], $\alpha_{Tl} = 1$ [m]
Case 3:	$\alpha_p = 50$ [bar], $m_p = 0.8$, $\alpha_{Ll} = 5$ [m], $\alpha_{Tl} = 1$ [m]
Case 4:	$\alpha_p = 5$ [bar], $m_p = 0.8$, $\alpha_{Ll} = 50$ [m], $\alpha_{Tl} = 20$ [m]

Figure 2.1: Sketch of the benchmark system.

2.3.2 Results

Benchmark Test

The saturation distribution given by the numerical simulation is shown in Figure 2.2. In order to compare with the solution by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006), we need to get a clear interface between the gas and liquid phases. The interface between the gaseous CO_2 and brine is obtained by moving all the gaseous CO_2 to the upper side of the liquid brine;

Figure 2.2: Numerical results: saturation distribution of gas phase.

Figure 2.3: Comparison of the numerical result with the theoretical solution by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006).

that is, the depth of the interface is calculated by

$$z(r) = \int_0^B S_g(r, z) dz. \quad (2.45)$$

The comparison between the theoretical result by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006) and the numerical results from this work is shown in Figure 2.3, from which we can see that, when $m_p = 0.8$, the numerical results agree very well with the theoretical result. The size of the $CO_2(g)$ plume calculated with the numerical simulation in this work is slightly smaller than that calculated with the theoretical method; this is because the code considers the dissolution of CO_2 in the brine. Therefore, the numerical model is approved by the theoretical solution, provided that the capillary pressure distribution is uniform (i.e., $m_p = 0.8$).

Sensitive Analysis

The saturation distributions of the four cases are shown in Figures 2.4 and 2.5. If we compare Cases 1 and 2, we can see the parameter m_p significantly affects the saturation distribution, this is because when $m_p = 0.4$ the capillary pressure is not uniform, which favors the saturation dispersion (*Bolster et al.*, 2009). If we compare Cases 1 and 3, we can see that the high entry pressure makes the interface between the two phases sharper, while the average saturation distribution is negligibly affected. If we compare Cases 1 and 4, we can see that the dispersion of the $CO_2(aq)$ has negligibly effects on the saturation distribution. We can conclude that saturation dispersion is more important than concentration dispersion in the mass transport of two-phase flow.

If we compare the accumulative dissolution efficiency (E_a), shown in Figure 2.6, we can see that the dissolution efficiency reaches a constant value, around 30% of the injected CO_2 . This means dissolution trapping is important in GCS. We can also see that (a)

Figure 2.4: Numerical results: saturation distribution of gas phase.

Figure 2.5: Comparison of the vertical average saturation with different parameters; Table 2.7 lists the parameter settings of Cases 1, 2, 3 and 4.

Figure 2.6: Comparison of the accumulative dissolution efficiency with different parameters; Table 2.7 lists the parameter settings of Cases 1, 2, 3 and 4.

Figure 2.7: Numerical results: distributions of mass fraction of aqueous CO_2 in brine (X_t^C).

nonuniform retention curve could enhance the dissolution of the CO_2 because nonuniform retention curve enhances the mixing between the gas and brine phases, (b) high entry pressure could suppress the dissolution efficiency because high capillary pressure suppress the mixing between two phases, and (c) high dispersion coefficient can slightly enhance the gas dissolution efficiency.

The distributions of the mass fractions are show in Figure 2.7. From Figure 2.7 we can see that the region below the gas phase has been totally saturated with aqueous CO_2 . This is because of downward and outward movement of CO_2 -saturated brine, as can be seen in Figures 2.8 and 2.9. If we compare Cases 1 and 4, we can see the dispersion coefficient has negligible effect on in the two-phase flow cases.

The (outward) radial ($q_{l,r}$) and (downward) vertical ($q_{l,v}$) fluxes of liquid phase are shown in Figures 2.8 and 2.9, respectively. From Figure 2.8 we can see that the maximum horizontal flux is close to the tip of the $CO_2(g)$ plume. From Figure 2.9 we can see that the maximum vertical flux is also close to the tip of the $CO_2(g)$ plume, and that the vertical flux of the brine beneath the $CO_2(g)$ plume is larger than zero (i.e. the direction is downward). However, we could observe negative flux (i.e. the direction is upward) near the tip. From Figures 2.8 and 2.9, we can see that the retention curve can significantly affect the velocity of the liquid phase.

Figure 2.8: Numerical results: distributions of radial flux of saline water ($q_{l,r}$).

The log radial flux ($\log(q_{g,r})$) and vertical flux ($q_{g,v}$) of gas phase are shown in Figures 2.10 and 2.11, respectively. From Figure 2.10 we can see that the maximum horizontal flux of gas phase is close to the well, and the radial flux decreases exponentially in the radial direction. From Figure 2.11 we can see that the maximum vertical flux is close to the tail of the $CO_2(g)$ plume, and that the vertical flux of the $CO_2(g)$ plume is smaller than zero (i.e. the direction is upward).

2.4 Conclusions

The conclusions of this chapter are listed as follows.

This work first offers a fully-coupled reactive two-component two-phase flow program for the Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS) process, and then applies this program to qualitatively analyze the effect of capillarity and dispersivity on the GCS process.

The program has three major characters, given as follows:

(a). The proposed model considers that one component can exist in two phases due to chemical reaction, i.e., the water may evaporate into gas and the gas may dissolve into the brine. Including the mutual solubility between brine and gas is important for GCS, because the dissolution trapping plays an important role in the trapping CO_2 . The effect of the salinity on the mutual solubility performance is also considered, because the salinity

Figure 2.9: Numerical results: distributions of vertical flux of saline water ($q_{l,v}$).

Figure 2.10: Numerical results: distributions of log radial flux of gaseous CO_2 ($\log(q_{g,r})$).

Figure 2.11: Numerical results: distributions of vertical flux of gaseous CO_2 ($q_{g,v}$).

can significantly reduce the dissolution efficiency.

(b). In this highly nonlinear model with many variables, gas pressure and liquid pressure are chosen as the persistent independent variables, and all the other variables can be explicitly expressed with these two independent variables through constitution equations. Compared to the traditional variable substitution approach, this selection of independent variables has advantage in coping with phase appearance/disappearance.

(c). The independent variables are solved simultaneously and implicitly by Newton-Raphson iteration.

Then, this program is tested against the theoretical solution given by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006). Furthermore, we conduct qualitative analysis on the effect of capillary pressure and dispersion coefficient on the GCS process. The conclusion and discussion are given as follows.

(a). The gas saturation distribution obtained by the numerical model is slightly lower than that given by the theoretical solution. This is because the dissolution of CO_2 can reduce the mass of CO_2 -rich phase, but theoretical solution does not consider the dissolution.

(b). The theoretical model, which neglects the capillary pressure, only works when the parameter (m_p) for the retention curve is large (e.g., $m_p = 0.8$). This is because when m_p is large the capillary pressure-saturation curve is quite uniform and the saturation

dispersion due to capillary pressure is quite small.

(c). Nonuniform retention curve could enhance the saturation dispersion (mixing of gas and brine) and the dissolution of the CO_2 .

(d). High entry pressure could suppress the mixing between two phases and thus the dissolution efficiency.

(e). High dispersion coefficient has little effect on the saturation dispersion but can slightly enhance the gas dissolution efficiency.

This numerical model for GCS can be modified to simulate other classic reactive multi-component multi-phase flow processes, such as black oil recovery, NAPL removal and nuclear waste disposal.

Chapter 3

Simplified Reactive Three-Phase Flow Model for Geological CO_2 Sequestration

3.1 Introduction

During the Geological CO_2 Sequestration (GCS) process, CO_2 dissolves into the brine phase, altering the chemical composition of the brine and thus influencing the chemical equilibrium between brine and solid phases (*Babaei and Islam, 2018*). As a result, dissolution/precipitation would appear and the geological formation would experience change of porosity structure. Because the dissolution/precipitation can feed back upon the flow field, partial dissolution/precipitation may occur. For instance, the partial dissolution, called wormholing, can substantially undermine the mechanic performance of the formation. Therefore, in order to get a more sophisticated analysis of the GCS, it is necessary to consider the partition between rock-forming minerals and the CO_2 -laid brine.

This chapter incorporates the chemical reaction among aqueous species and rock-forming minerals, as well as the partition between gaseous CO_2 phase and liquid brine phase. It is possible but not necessary to incorporate all the chemical reactions in the subsurface system during CO_2 injection. The rock formation can involve up to 40 kinds of minerals, of which the half time, the time for consuming half of the initial amount of a reactant, ranges from several seconds to thousands of years. For the injection period of several decades, it is not necessary to incorporate the reaction of minerals of long half time. For instance, reactions associated with silicate mineral is usually neglected if the simulation period is small, because these reactions have very slow rates and equilibrium state is not reached at the time-scale of laboratory experiments, which is usually less than two years (*Chadwick et al., 2008*). Increasing the number of reactions can significantly impact the efficiency of the simulation, because it can lead to a large Jacobian matrix,

which has to be solved for each grid, although the calculation of transport of the species is not time consuming. During the injection process, the high flow rate requires a very short time step as low as several minutes, which means we need thousands of time step to finish the simulation of decades injection. It will cost a huge amount of CPU time if we calculate the chemical reaction grid by grid at every time step. During to post injection process, it is however necessary and numerically efficient to consider the reaction of species that have long half time, because the time step is weakly controlled by the flow conditions.

Simplification is introduced to increase the calculation efficiency without significantly loosing the accuracy. Here, we neglect the slow reactions and assume that those fast reactions are in equilibrium state. Regarding to the rock phase, we assume the only active rock species is calcite, which will experience dissolution and precipitation during the procedure. The partition between calcite and brine is assumed to be at equilibrium state, considering the time scale for chemical reaction is small compared to that for fluid transport. The equilibrium assumption, which simplifies the calculation, is widely applied in subsurface flow systems (*Ott and Oedai, 2015; Leal et al., 2016; Molins et al., 2017*). Regarding to the brine phase, we only consider the major reactions and their related species, while neglect the secondary reactions and their related species (*Duan and Sun, 2003; Duan and Li, 2008*). For instance, the aqueous calcite and its related reactions are not considered. Furthermore, to avoid calculating the chemical reaction at every time step, we give an empirical formula for the chemical compositions in aqueous phase for different gas pressures.

In the rest of this Chapter, Sections 3.2 and 3.3, respectively, give the numerical method and the benchmark test of the method.

3.2 Methods

In this chapter, we only consider 11 species (H_2O , $CO_2(g)$, $CaCO_3(s)$, H^+ , Ca^{2+} , HCO_3^- , $CO_2(aq)$, CO_3^{2-} , OH^- , Na^+ , Cl^-). Among these 11 species we further assume that the molalities of the Na^+ and Cl^- are constant and not halite precipitates or dissolves. The evaporation of water into CO_2 -rich phase is not considered. Hence, the number of unknown equilibrium species is $n_e = 9$. The partition of these 9 species is controlled by $n_E = 5$

equilibrium reactions given as

The goal of this chapter is to solve the three-phase flow system accompanied by the five reactions. Such chemical system is selected because most of the reactions associated with CO_2 injection are precipitation/dissolution of carbonate minerals, and new equilibrium state is roughly reached within around several minutes under reservoir pressure and temperature (Leal, 2014).

The numerical solution is comprised of three steps: first, select conservative components, determine the independent variables and build governing transport equations; second, obtain an empirical relation between the conservative components and independent variables; and three, solve the governing transport equations given in first step, in virtue of the empirical relations obtained in the second step. These three steps are, respectively, given in Sections 3.2.1, 3.2.2 and 3.2.3.

3.2.1 Flow Equations

Components

Conservative components should be selected before we construct governing equations. The advantage of component over species has been given in Chapter 2, where we also gave how to get the component matrix based on the mass of the element. The component defined in Chapter 2 is called *element component*, the value of which is always positive. Here, we describe how to obtain the components based on the stoichiometric matrix, which is widely used in mass transport (Saaltink et al., 1998; Molins et al., 2004; De Simoni et al., 2007). Traditionally, for a chemical system, the component is obtained such that the molar abundance of the component is independent on the reaction. This component is called *molar component*. For instance if we define $(CO_2(g) - Ca^{2+} + HCO_3^- + CO_2(aq) + CO_3^{2-})$ as a molar component, then the molar abundance of the molar component is $[CO_2(g)] - [Ca^{2+}] + [HCO_3^-] + [CO_2(aq)] + [CO_3^{2-}]$, here $[\cdot]$ means the molar abundance of the species. However, in the flow system, governing equations are usually constructed based on the conservation of mass rather than molar abundance. Therefore, we should obtain the component in such a way that the mass of the component is independent on the reaction. This component is called *mass component*. For instance, the CO_2 component is

comprised of $(CO_2(g) - 1.09811Ca^{2+} + 0.7212HCO_3^- + CO_2(aq) + 0.73339CO_3^{2-})$, then the mass of CO_2 component is $[CO_2(g)]_m - 1.09811[Ca^{2+}]_m + 0.7212[HCO_3^-]_m + [CO_2(aq)]_m + 0.73339[CO_3^{2-}]_m$, here $[\cdot]_m$ means the mass of the species. The value of the molar component and mass component could be negative values. The sum of the mass fractions of all the species is equal to unit, but the sum of the mass fractions of all the components is not necessarily equal to unit. In this chapter, \mathbf{u}_e and \mathbf{U}_e are used to represent the mass component and the kernel matrix of mass component, respectively; $\boldsymbol{\omega}_e$ and $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_e$ are used to represent the molar component and the kernel matrix of molar component, respectively. The subscript e denotes that these variables are related to equilibrium reactions (This is introduced to avoid confusion in Chapter 4, where the reactions, species and components are all split into kinetic and equilibrium groups).

In this section we need the mass component vector and its corresponding kernel matrix, which are given in the following. The stoichiometric matrix for the 5 equilibrium reactions (3.1) is

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}_e = \begin{array}{c} E1 \\ E2 \\ E3 \\ E4 \\ E5 \end{array} \begin{array}{cccccccccc} H_2O & CO_2(g) & CaCO_3(s) & H^+ & Ca^{2+} & HCO_3^- & CO_2(aq) & CO_3^{2-} & OH^- \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & -1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{array} \quad (3.2)$$

Because the mass of the mass component is independent on the reaction, the kernel matrix (\mathbf{U}_e) for the mass component should satisfy

$$\mathbf{0} = \mathbf{U}_e \mathbf{M}_{me} \boldsymbol{\nu}_e^t \mathbf{r}_e \Rightarrow \mathbf{0} = \mathbf{U}_e \mathbf{M}_{me} \boldsymbol{\nu}_e^t, \quad (3.3)$$

where, \mathbf{r}_e [$\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] stores the reaction rates of the five equilibrium reactions, and the molar mass matrix \mathbf{M}_{me} [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$] is a $(n_e \times n_e)$ diagonal matrix, of which the (β, β) entry stores the molar mass of equilibrium species β :

$$\mathbf{M}_{me} = 10^{-3} \text{diag}(18.015, 44.01, 100.0869, 1.0078, 40.078, 61.017, 44.01, 60.009, 17.008). \quad (3.4)$$

The solution to Equation (3.3) is given as follows. Let $\boldsymbol{\nu}_E = \boldsymbol{\nu}_e \mathbf{M}_{me}^t$, and Equation (3.3) is changed to

$$\mathbf{0} = \mathbf{U}_e \boldsymbol{\nu}_E^t. \quad (3.5)$$

The solution to Equation (3.5) is not unique. A convenient way to construct \mathbf{U}_e is (Saaltink *et al.*, 1998, 2013)

$$\mathbf{U}_e = [\mathbf{I} - \boldsymbol{\nu}_{E1}^t (\boldsymbol{\nu}_{E2}^t)^{-1}], \quad (3.6)$$

where, we have split the stoichiometric matrix into $n_E \times (n_e - n_E)$ $\boldsymbol{\nu}_{E1}$ and $n_E \times n_E$ $\boldsymbol{\nu}_{E2}$,

i.e., $\boldsymbol{\nu}_E = [\boldsymbol{\nu}_{E1} | \boldsymbol{\nu}_{E2}]$. The solution is calculated as

$$\begin{array}{rcccccccccc}
 & H_2O & CO_2(g) & CaCO_3(s) & H^+ & Ca^{2+} & HCO_3^- & CO_2(aq) & CO_3^{2-} & OH^- \\
 \mathbf{U}_e = & w & c & m & \text{pH} & & & & & \\
 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.44950 & 0.29525 & 0 & 0.30020 & 1.05921 \\
 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1.09811 & 0.7212 & 1 & 0.73339 & 0 \\
 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 2.49730 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0.05029 & -0.01652 & 0 & -0.03359 & -0.05925
 \end{array} \quad (3.7)$$

The rank of \mathbf{U}_e is $n_e - n_E$. In our case, the rank is 4 (i.e., $9 - 5$). The 4 conservative components are water (w), CO_2 (c), calcite (m) and pH.

Independent Variables

In the transport process accompanied with equilibrium reactions, the independent variables are classified into two groups: independent transport variables and independent reaction variables. The number of the independent transport variables equals to the number of the phases, while the number of the independent reaction variables equals to the number of the equilibrium components (i.e., $(n_e - n_E)$). For instance, if there is only one pure liquid phase, we only need the liquid pressure to solve the transport system; if there are pure liquid and pure gas phases, we need another variable (gas pressure, gas saturation or liquid saturation) to close the system; if there is only liquid phase and the liquid phase is comprised of two components, we need three independent variables, i.e., liquid pressure, masses of two components. Because the model considers the reactive transport of three phases (gas, liquid and solid), three independent transport variables are needed. Here, we use as independent transport variables liquid pressure (p_l), gas pressure (p_g) and porosity (ϕ). From porosity, we can know the volumes of the solid and fluid phases. From the gas and liquid pressures, with the aid of retention curve, we can know the liquid and gas volume fractions. We note that other selection of independent transport variables would cause complex code structure. Traditionally, if there exist equilibrium chemical reactions, $(n_e - n_E)$ more independent reaction variables are needed to solve the equilibrium chemical reactions. To avoid introducing more independent variables due to the equilibrium chemical reactions, we assume that the compositions of the interested species and component are functions of the gas pressure, which is one of the independent transport variables (c.f. Section 3.2.2). Therefore, we only need three independent transport variables to solve the transport process accompanied by equilibrium chemical reactions.

Governing Equations

Three governing transport equations are needed to solve the three independent transport variables. The three governing transport equations are constructed based on the mass balances of three mass components. Because the transport equations concern the volumes of water, CO_2 -rich and mineral phases, we construct the transport equations based on the

mass balance of water component (w), CO_2 component (c) and calcite component (m):

$$0 = \mathcal{F}_C = \sum_{\alpha=l,g,s} \left[\frac{\partial(\phi_\alpha \rho_\alpha X_\alpha^C)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^C \mathbf{q}_\alpha) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_\alpha \mathbf{D}_\alpha \rho_\alpha \nabla X_\alpha^C) \right] - \sum_{\beta=1}^{n_e} \left(U_{C\beta} \sum_{j=1}^{NW} [Q_{\alpha W}^\beta]^j \right), \quad (3.8)$$

where, subscripts $\alpha = (l, g, s)$, respectively, represent liquid, gas and solid phases; $\mathcal{C} = (w, c, m)$ denote the components; $\phi_l = \phi S_l$ and $\phi_g = \phi S_g$ [-] are the volumetric fractions of liquid and gaseous phases, respectively; S [-] represents the saturation; $\phi_s = 1 - \phi$ [-] is the volumetric fraction of solid phase; ρ [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$] represents the density; X_α^C [-] represents the mass fraction of component \mathcal{C} in phase α ; t [s] is time; \mathbf{q} [$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] is the Darcy discharge; \mathbf{D} [$\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] is the dispersion tensor; Q [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] is the source term; and NW [-] is the number of wells. The mass fraction of component is defined as

$$X_\alpha^C = \sum_{\beta \in \alpha} U_{C\beta} X_\alpha^\beta, \quad (3.9)$$

where, $U_{C\beta}$ denotes the \mathcal{C} - row and β - column of \mathbf{U}_e .

Constitutional Equations

Flow equations (3.8) are complemented by the following constitutional equations. The velocity of the solid phase is assumed to be zero. For the fluid phases, the discharge rate (\mathbf{q}_α , $\alpha = l, g$) is given as extended Darcy's law

$$\mathbf{q}_\alpha = -\frac{\kappa_{r\alpha}}{\mu_\alpha} \kappa (\nabla p_\alpha - \rho_\alpha g \nabla z), \quad (3.10)$$

where, κ_r [-] denotes the relative permeability; μ [$\text{pa} \cdot \text{s}$] is the viscosity; κ [m^2] is the intrinsic permeability; p [pa] denotes the pressure; z [m] is the depth; and g [$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$] is the gravitational acceleration.

The flow process should satisfy the following constraints:

$$S_l + S_g = 1, \quad (3.11)$$

$$S_l = S_l(p_c), \quad (3.12)$$

$$p_c = p_g - p_l, \quad (3.13)$$

where, p_c is capillary pressure given by the retention curve given in Appendix C. The intrinsic permeability κ changes with porosity according Közeny-Carman model (Közeny, 1927; Carman, 1997; Hommel et al., 2018). The traditional Közeny-Carman model is

$$\kappa = \kappa_0 \left(\frac{\phi}{\phi_0} \right)^{\gamma_c} \left(\frac{1 - \phi_0}{1 - \phi} \right)^2, \quad (3.14)$$

where, κ_0 is the initial intrinsic permeability and ϕ_0 is the initial porosity. Normally, γ_c is 3.0.

We assume that the rock consists of only calcite and the gas consists of only $CO_2(g)$, and then we have

$$\begin{aligned} X_s^w &= 0, X_s^c = 0, X_s^m = 1; \\ X_g^w &= 0, X_g^c = 1, X_g^m = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.15)$$

We assume that

$$X_l^c = X_l^c(p_g), \quad \mathcal{C} = w, c, m, \quad (3.16)$$

which means the mass fractions of chemical components are only functions of gas pressure. In this way, we avoid calculating the chemical reaction at every time step.

The rock density ρ_s is assumed to be constant value, $2700 \text{ [kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}]$. The empirical models for ρ_l , ρ_g , μ_α , \mathbf{D}_α , $\kappa_{r\alpha}$ and retention curve can be found in the Appendices A, B and C. Section 3.2.2 gives the empirical formulas for $X_l^c(p_g)$ and $\partial X_l^c(p_g)/\partial p_g$, from which we can explicitly express the mass composition of brine based on the independent variable p_g . Because the density and viscosity of liquid phase are affected by the mass fraction of $CO_2(aq)$ (X_l^c), Section 3.2.2 also gives the empirical formulas for $X_l^c(p_g)$ and $\partial X_l^c(p_g)/\partial p_g$. We note that all the variables in the governing equations can be expressed with independent variables p_l , p_g and ϕ , through the constitutional equations.

3.2.2 Equilibrium Reactions

Mass Action Law (MAL), the classic stoichiometric method, is used to calculate the equilibrium reactions (Leal *et al.*, 2013). The basic mechanism of MAL is that at equilibrium state the activities and fugacities, stored in n_e -dimensional vector \mathbf{a} , should satisfy

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}_e \ln \mathbf{a}_e = \ln \mathbf{K}_e, \quad (3.17)$$

where, n_E -dimensional vector \mathbf{K}_e stores equilibrium constants of n_E reaction equations. The stoichiometric matrix ($\boldsymbol{\nu}_e$) is given as (3.2). The equilibrium constants (\mathbf{K}_e) are only affected by the pressures and temperature. The activities and fugacities (\mathbf{a}_e) are dependent on molar abundances of the species as well as the pressures and temperature. The calculation of activity, fugacity and equilibrium constant is given in the Appendix D. To solve Equation (3.17) is to obtain the molar abundances of all the species so that their activities or fugacities satisfy Equation (3.17).

Usually the number of linearly independent equilibrium reactions is smaller than the number of equilibrium species, i.e. $n_E < n_e$, and $(n_e - n_E)$ more constraints are needed. The additional constraints should be independent from the reactions. The additional

Table 3.1: Algorithm MAL-E: Mass action law for solving equilibrium reactions.

Input: independent variable ω_e ; state variables: p_l, p_g, T_k ; constant parameters: Ω_e and ν_e ; initial guess of the molar abundance ζ_e^0 ; % theoretically, this initial value can be arbitrary since the solution converges fast with the Newton-Raphson iteration;
0: set $l = 0$ and $\delta_\zeta^0 = \text{inf}$; 1: while $\max \frac{\delta_\zeta^l}{\zeta_e^{l+1}} > \epsilon_\zeta$, do 2 to 4; 2: in virtue of the activities (\mathbf{a}_e) calculated by using the models given in Appendix D and the equilibrium constants given in Appendix D, calculate the residual vector (\mathcal{F}_e^l) and its corresponding Jacobian matrix (\mathbf{J}_e^l), respectively, using Equations (3.21) and (3.22); 3: calculate $\delta_\zeta^{l+1} = -[\mathbf{J}_e^l]^{-1} \cdot \mathcal{F}_e^l$; and then $\zeta_e^{l+1} = \zeta_e^l + \eta_d \delta_\zeta^{l+1}$; 4: $l = l + 1$; 5: endwhile ¹ 6: $\zeta_e = \zeta_e^{l+1}$; $\mathbf{J}_e = \mathbf{J}_e^{l+1}$.
Output: ζ_e and \mathbf{J}_e . % \mathbf{J}_e would be used in calculating the partial equilibrium system in Chapter 4.

constraints can be (1) number of moles of an element (e.g. H), (2) charge balance in the aqueous solution, (3) activity of an aqueous species (e.g., the activity of species H^+ is obtained from $10^{-\text{pH}}$ if the pH is known) and (4) partial pressure (or fugacity) of a gaseous species. Here, we use the molar abundances of the molar components as the constraints, though the results are expressed in the form of mass component. Similar to the calculation of the kernel matrix for the mass component, the kernel matrix for molar component is defined as

$$\mathbf{0} = \Omega_e \nu_e^t \mathbf{r}_e \Rightarrow \mathbf{0} = \Omega_e \nu_e^t, \quad (3.18)$$

where, the $(n_e - n_E) \times n_e$ kernel matrix Ω_e is given as

$$\Omega_e = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} H_2O & CO_2(g) & CaCO_3(s) & H^+ & Ca^{2+} & HCO_3^- & CO_2(aq) & CO_3^{2-} & OH^- \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} w \\ c \\ m \\ \text{pH} \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 & -1 & 0 & -2 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix} . \quad (3.19)$$

Then the additional constraints can also be expressed in a matrix form

$$\Omega_e \zeta_e = \omega_e, \quad (3.20)$$

where, the molar mass of all the species are stored in n_e -dimensional vector ζ_e and the $(n_e - n_E)$ -dimensional vector ω_e characterize the additional constraints. We note that we can also use the mass component as the constraints but we use molar component only because molar abundance is usually used in chemical reaction.

Equations (3.17) and (3.20) are solved simultaneously using the Newton-Raphson method. The n_e linear equations can be written in compact form as

$$\mathbf{0} = \mathcal{F}_e = \begin{bmatrix} \nu_e \ln \mathbf{a}_e - \ln \mathbf{K}_e \\ \Omega_e \zeta_e - \omega_e \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.21)$$

The Jacobian matrix of linear system (3.21) is

$$\mathbf{J}_e = \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_e}{\partial \zeta_e} = \begin{bmatrix} \nu_e \frac{\partial \ln \mathbf{a}_e}{\partial \zeta_e} \\ \Omega_e \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.22)$$

Molar abundance vector is updated by

$$\zeta_e^{l+1} = \zeta_e^l + \eta_d \delta_\zeta^{l+1}, \quad (3.23)$$

where δ_ζ^{l+1} is obtained by solving

$$\mathbf{J}_e^l \delta_\zeta^{l+1} = -\mathcal{F}_e^l. \quad (3.24)$$

Here $\eta_d \in (0, 1)$ is used to scale the increase of ζ if it is ill conditioned, defined as

$$\max \left| \frac{\mathbf{J}_e \zeta - \mathcal{F}_e}{|\mathcal{F}_e| + 1} \right| > \epsilon_{ill}, \quad (3.25)$$

where ϵ_{ill} (e.g. 10^{-8}) is the tolerance for the ill condition. The value of η_d reduces to 0.1 if the matrix is ill conditioned; otherwise, the $\eta_d = 1$ (Leal, 2014). We note that the equilibrium problem has to satisfy equality and inequality constraints. The equality constraints include the mass balance of the components (i.e. $\Omega_e \zeta_e = \omega_e$) and the mass action law (i.e. $\nu_e \ln \mathbf{a}_e = \ln \mathbf{K}_e$). The inequality constraints, $\zeta_e \geq \mathbf{0}$, ensure that the non-negative molar amounts of any species. We impose nonnegativity constraints to formula (3.23). There are two ways to cope with the unwelcome negative values. One method sets the molar abundance in $(l + 1)$ th iteration to zero if we get a negative value in the $(l + 1)$ th iteration (Carrera *et al.*, 2004), and the other multiplies the value in l th iteration by a factor of η_s ($\eta_s < 1$) if we get negative values for the $(l + 1)$ th iteration (Leal *et al.*, 2013). The convergence criterion is based on the relative change of the species, given as

$$\max \frac{\delta_\zeta^{l+1}}{\zeta_e + 1} < \epsilon_\zeta, \quad (3.26)$$

where ϵ_ζ is the tolerance value for the convergence.

The aforementioned solution for equilibrium reactions is given as Algorithm MAL-E in Table 3.1. Algorithm MAL-E is not inserted into the flow equations directly, because it needs to calculate the reaction for each grid at every time step. The equilibrium calculation

Figure 3.1: Molality of all the aqueous species, when the liquid pressure is 100 bar, the temperature is 60 °C and the molality of $NaCl$ is 0.5.

is proportional to the number of grids in numerical simulations and can cost more than 2/3 of the total simulation time (Leal *et al.*, 2016). In order to save time, we use the method proposed by Saaltink *et al.* (2013), where the chemical partition is expressed as empirical functions of gas pressure. In order to close Equations (3.8), we only need the empirical functions for X_l^w , X_l^c , and X_l^m . Because the density and viscosity of liquid phase are affected by the mass fraction of aqueous CO_2 , we also need the empirical function for the aqueous CO_2 . Here, we use X_l^C to denote the mass fraction of aqueous CO_2 in liquid phase.

We assume that the liquid pressure is 150 bar, the temperature is 60 °C and the molality of $NaCl$ is 0.5. When gas pressure changes from 1×10^{-2} to 4×10^2 bar, the molalities of all the aqueous species can be calculated with the aforementioned method. The results are given in Figure 3.1. The mass fractions of components in the liquid phase are given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 X_l^w &= \frac{1 + (\mathbf{m}_l)^t \times \mathbf{M}_{me}(4 : 9, 4 : 9) \times \mathbf{U}_e(1, 4 : 9)^t}{1 + 58.44 \cdot [NaCl]_{mo} + \sum[(\mathbf{m}_l)^t \times \mathbf{M}_{me}(4 : 9, 4 : 9)]}; \\
 X_l^c &= \frac{(\mathbf{m}_l)^t \times \mathbf{M}_{me}(4 : 9, 4 : 9) \times \mathbf{U}_e(2, 4 : 9)^t}{1 + 58.44 \cdot [NaCl]_{mo} + \sum[(\mathbf{m}_l)^t \times \mathbf{M}_{me}(4 : 9, 4 : 9)]}; \\
 X_l^m &= \frac{(\mathbf{m}_l)^t \times \mathbf{M}_{me}(4 : 9, 4 : 9) \times \mathbf{U}_e(3, 4 : 9)^t}{1 + 58.44 \cdot [NaCl]_{mo} + \sum[(\mathbf{m}_l)^t \times \mathbf{M}_{me}(4 : 9, 4 : 9)]};
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3.2: Mass fractions of all the three components (X_l^w , X_l^c , X_l^m) and mass fraction of the aqueous CO_2 (X_l^C) in the liquid phase, when the liquid pressure is 150 bar, the temperature is 60 °C and the molality of $NaCl$ is 0.5.

where, \mathbf{m}_l [molal] stores the molalities of the 6 reactive aqueous species, i.e., $\mathbf{m}_l = ([H^+]_{mo}, [Ca^{2+}]_{mo}, [HCO_3^-]_{mo}, [CO_2(aq)]_{mo}, [CO_3^{2-}]_{mo}, [OH^-]_{mo})^t$, in which $[\cdot]_{mo}$ denotes the molality of the aqueous species; on the basis of the results in Figure 3.1, we can obtain the mass fractions of the three mass components and aqueous CO_2 in liquid phase at different gas pressure, given in Figure 3.2. Then we use least square regression method to obtain polynomial curves that fit the calculated data by MAL methods, also shown in Figure 3.2. The empirical polynomial functions for the mass fractions of the three mass components and aqueous CO_2 are given as

$$X_l^w = -3.691 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot p_g^3 + 2.605 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot p_g^2 - 6.274 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot p_g + 0.9703; \quad (3.27)$$

$$X_l^g = 3.618 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot p_g^3 - 2.554 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot p_g^2 + 6.182 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot p_g + 8.841 \cdot 10^{-4}; \quad (3.28)$$

$$X_l^m = 1.077 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot \log^2 p_g + 4.656 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot \log p_g + 6.151 \cdot 10^{-4}; \quad (3.29)$$

$$X_l^C = 3.58 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot p_g^3 - 2.53 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot p_g^2 + 6.135 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot p_g + 2.2288 \cdot 10^{-4}. \quad (3.30)$$

The obtained X_l^C mass fraction of $CO_2(aq)$ is employed in formulas (A.5) and (A.16). The algebra calculation of derivatives of formulas (3.27) to (3.30), (A.5) and (A.16) are straightforward and are not given.

We note that in this case, the equilibrium constants and activity coefficients are

Table 3.2: Subroutine NR3E: Netown-Raphson iteration for simplified reactive three-phase flow model.

Input: $[\mathbf{p}_l]^n, [\mathbf{p}_g]^n, \phi^n, \mathbf{Q}_{\alpha W}, \mathbf{p}_{bh}^n$ and $\Delta t^n; \mathbf{G}; \boldsymbol{\kappa}^0, \phi^0$;
0: set $k = 0; N_{kmax} = 15; [\delta \mathbf{p}_g]^{n+1,0} = [\delta \mathbf{p}_l]^{n+1,0} = [\delta \mathbf{p}_{bh}]^{n+1,0} = \text{inf}$;
$[\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,0} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_l \\ \mathbf{p}_g \\ \phi \\ \mathbf{p}_{bh} \end{bmatrix}^n; [\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,0} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{F}_w \\ \mathcal{F}_c \\ \mathcal{F}_m \\ \mathcal{F}_W \end{bmatrix}^n;$
1: while $\max([\delta \mathbf{p}_l]^{n+1,k}, [\delta \mathbf{p}_g]^{n+1,k}, [\delta \mathbf{p}_{bh}]^{n+1,k}) > \epsilon_p$ & $k < N_{kmax}$ do steps 2 to 3 2: in virtue of Δt^n , the fluid density (ρ_α), fluid viscosity (μ_α), saturation (\mathbf{S}_α), relative permeability ($\boldsymbol{\kappa}_{r\alpha}$) calculated with the models given in Appendices A and C, the flux (\mathbf{q}_α) of each face calculated with Darcy's law, the dispersion tensor calculated with the model given in Appendix B, the mass fraction of components in liquid phase (\mathbf{X}_l^C) calculated with formulas (3.30), and the intrinsic permeability ($\boldsymbol{\kappa}$) calculated with Közeny-Carman model given by formula (3.14), we sequentially
$\text{calculate } [\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{F}_w \\ \mathcal{F}_c \\ \mathcal{F}_m \\ \mathcal{F}_W \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k}; \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right]^{n+1,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k};$
$[\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k} = - \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right]^{n+1,k}{}^{-1} [\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k}; [\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k+1} = [\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k} + [\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k};$
3: $k = k + 1$; 4: endwhile ¹ ; 5: if $k = N_{kmax} = 15$ % the algorithm does not converge after N_{kmax} NR iterations; 6: then $\Delta t^n = t_s = 0.1$ second; and go to step 0; % reduce Δt^n and restart from t^n with a very small new Δt^n ; 7: endif ⁵ ; 8: $[\mathbf{p}_l; \mathbf{p}_g; \phi; \mathbf{p}_{bh}]^{n+1} = [\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k+1}$; 9: calculate $\Delta \mathbf{p}^n = [\mathbf{p}_l; \mathbf{p}_g; \mathbf{p}_{bh}]^{n+1} - [\mathbf{p}_l; \mathbf{p}_g; \mathbf{p}_{bh}]^n$; $\Delta \mathbf{S}_\alpha^n = [\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^{n+1} - [\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^n$;
Output: $[\mathbf{p}_l; \mathbf{p}_g; \phi; \mathbf{p}_{bh}]^{n+1}; [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^C]^{n+1}; [\rho_\alpha]^{n+1}; [\mu_\alpha]^{n+1}; [\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^{n+1}; [\mathbf{q}_\alpha]^{n+1}; \Delta \mathbf{p}^n; \Delta \mathbf{S}_\alpha^n$; and Δt^n ;

insensitive to liquid pressure, and the temperature is assumed to be constant. Thus, the chemical system is only affected by the gas pressure, which determines the dissolution of CO_2 , the pH and salinity of the brine, and thus the dissolution of calcite. We also note that this chemical reaction system can also be solved with Gibbs Energy Minimization method, which is equivalent to the MAL method.

3.2.3 Numerical Solution to Flow Equations

Newton-Raphson method is used to solve the reactive flow equations. Injection well is also considered in the model. Because the injection well may pierce more than one grid, it is convenient to separate the governing equation for the field grid from the governing

equation for the injection well (c.f. Chapter 2). Therefore, the system, which consists three governing equations for the mass balances of three components in the field grid (i.e., Equation (3.8)) and one governing equation for the mass balance of injected species in the injection well (i.e., Equation (2.31) in Chapter 2), is rewritten as

$$\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (3.31)$$

where

$$[\mathbf{x}] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_l \\ \mathbf{p}_g \\ \phi \\ \mathbf{p}_{bh} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.32)$$

$$[\mathcal{F}] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{F}_w \\ \mathcal{F}_c \\ \mathcal{F}_m \\ \mathcal{F}_W \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.33)$$

The Newton-Raphson form of Equation (3.31) is given as

$$\frac{\partial[\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} [\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k} = -[\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k}, \quad (3.34)$$

and the Jacobian matrix

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right]^{n+1,k} &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{11} & \mathbf{M}_{12} & \mathbf{M}_{13} & \mathbf{M}_{1W} \\ \mathbf{M}_{21} & \mathbf{M}_{22} & \mathbf{M}_{23} & \mathbf{M}_{2W} \\ \mathbf{M}_{31} & \mathbf{M}_{32} & \mathbf{M}_{33} & \mathbf{M}_{3W} \\ \mathbf{M}_{W1} & \mathbf{M}_{W2} & \mathbf{M}_{W3} & \mathbf{M}_{WW} \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k} = \mathbf{M}^{n+1,k}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.35)$$

Here, \mathcal{F}_w , \mathcal{F}_c and \mathcal{F}_m , respectively, store the \mathcal{F}_w , \mathcal{F}_c and \mathcal{F}_m (c.f. Equation (3.8)) for all the grids; similarly, \mathbf{p}_l , \mathbf{p}_g and ϕ , respectively, store the liquid pressure, gas pressure and porosity for all the grids; \mathbf{p}_{bh} and \mathbf{f}_W , respectively, store the bottom hole pressure and \mathcal{F}_W (c.f. Equation (2.31) for all the wells. Here, for three-phase flow model, we do not give detailed information on numerical discretization of \mathcal{F} and \mathbf{M} , because discretization of \mathcal{F} and \mathbf{M} is quite similar to that for two-phase flow which can be found in the Appendix B.

Table 3.3: Main routine for simplified three-phase flow model.

Require: $[\mathbf{p}_l]^{top,0}$, $[\mathbf{p}_g]^{top,0}$, \mathbf{p}_{bh}^0 , $\mathbf{Q}_{\alpha W}$, $t^0 = 0$ and Δt^0 ; the grid discretization (\mathbf{G}); the field property (i.e., initial permeability κ^0 and initial porosity ϕ^0);
0: initialize the system with Subroutine I2, given in Table: 2.2; % the composition of brine is calculated with Equations (3.27) to (3.30); the brine density is calculated with Equation (A.5) with the aid of the empirical formula (3.30);
1: while $t^n < t_{tot}$, do 2 to 5;
2: update $[\mathbf{p}_l; \mathbf{p}_g; \phi; \mathbf{p}_{bh}]^n$ and probably Δt^n with Subroutine NR3E in Table 3.2;
3: $t^{n+1} = t^n + \Delta t^n$;
4: update Δt^n with Subroutine UT given in Table 2.4;
5: $n=n+1$;
6: endwhile ¹ .
Output: $(\mathbf{p}_l^{n+1}, \mathbf{p}_g^{n+1}, \phi^{n+1}, \mathbf{p}_{bh}^{n+1})$; $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^C]^{n+1}$; $[\rho_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $[\mu_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $[\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $[\mathbf{q}_\alpha]^{n+1}$.

Having obtained $[\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k}$ with Equation (3.34), we can update $[\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k}$ according to

$$[\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k+1} = [\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k} + [\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k}. \quad (3.36)$$

The Newton-Raphson iteration is terminated if the maximum change of the gas and liquid pressures is smaller than the tolerance value ϵ_p , or if the maximum error is smaller than the tolerance value ϵ_{err} .

Once we have updated these three independent variables through three control equations based on three components, we can obtain the mass fractions of the all the species and components based on the updated pressure (c.f. Figures 3.1 and 3.2).

The structure of the numerical program for simplified reactive three-phase flow model is quite similar to that for reactive two-phase flow model. Here we give, in Table 3.3, the main routine of the numerical program for simplified reactive three-phase flow model. Table 3.2 gives the subroutine for solving the transport equations with the Newton-Raphson method. The subroutine for updating the time step has been already given in Table 2.4 of Chapter 2. The subroutine for initializing the system for reactive three-phase flow can be obtained by slightly revising that for reactive two-phase flow given in Table 2.2 of Chapter 2; the only difference is that different formulas for the brine density and mass fraction are used. In Table 3.3 we add comments when the algorithms for two-phase and three-phase cases are different.

3.3 Benchmark Test and Partial Erosion Analysis

Similar to Chapter 2, the theoretical solution by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006) is used as a non-ideal benchmark. The results from Chapter 2 have shown that despite the fact that the theoretical model and the numerical model are not exactly the same, the numerical

Table 3.4: Parameter setting for the benchmark test.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
$R \times H$ [m×m]	2000×15	(μ_l, μ_g) [mpa·s]	(0.511, 0.061)
$N_x \times N_z$ [-]	100×20	(ρ_l, ρ_g) [kg·m ⁻³]	(1099, 733)
κ_0 [m ²]	2×10^{-14}	α_p [bar ⁻¹]	5
ϕ_0 [-]	0.15	m_p [-]	0.8
m_l^S [molal]	0.5	$Q_{g,m}$ [kg·s ⁻¹]	0.8889
T_c [°C]	60	T_s [day]	5194
$(p_l^{top,i}, p_g^i)$ [bar]	(150, 10)	r_w [m]	0.1
$(\alpha_{Ll}, \alpha_{Tl})$ [m]	(5, 1)	D_m [m ² s ⁻¹]	10^{-9}

Figure 3.3: Setup design of the benchmark system.

result agrees well with the theoretical result, because the effect of chemical reaction on the flow process is relatively small compared to the effect of mobility ratio and gravity segregation. Partial erosion analysis is conducted after the benchmark test.

3.3.1 Setup Description

The setup design of the simulation domain is quite similar to that used in Chapter 2, except that the outer boundary conditions should consider the porosity change (see Figure 3.3). We assume the gradient of porosity on the boundary is zero, that is, the porosity on the boundary is the same as the porosity of the cell next to the boundary. We also consider injecting dry gaseous CO_2 at the center of a cylindrical saline formation, with radius R and thickness H . Initially, the intrinsic permeability and porosity are, respectively, κ_0 and ϕ_0 . In the numerical simulation, we consider the dissolution of CO_2 and the porosity

Figure 3.4: Numerical results: saturation distribution of gas phase; the solid blue line is the analytic result of *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006), and the green dash lines are the contour lines of saturation.

Figure 3.5: Comparison of the numerical result with the theoretical solution by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006).

change. The evaporation of water in gas phase is not considered. The relative permeability curve is linearly proportional to the saturation, and the retention curve is described by Van Genuchten model, of which the shape parameters are m_p and α_p . The molality of the *NaCl* is constant m_l^S . The initial brine pressure at the top of the formation is $p_l^{top,i}$, increasing downward under gravity force, and the initial gas pressure is p_g^i everywhere. The densities of liquid and gas phases are, respectively, ρ_l and ρ_g . The viscosities of liquid and gas phases are, respectively, μ_l and μ_g . In the benchmark test the densities and viscosities of the fluids are set to be constant values (c.f. Table 3.4), while in the following partial erosion analysis we employ the real density and viscosity models (c.f. Appendix A). The temperature is constant T_c throughout the formation. The longitudinal and transverse dispersivities of the brine are α_{Ll} and α_{Tl} , respectively, while the molecular diffusion coefficient of brine is D_l^* . The vertical injection well is located at the center of the cylindrical domain and the effective length of the well equals to H . The radius of the injection well is r_w . The mass injection rate of dry CO_2 is $Q_{g,m}$ and the total injection time is T_s . All the parameter settings can be found in Table 3.4.

3.3.2 Results

Benchmark Test

The numerical result for saturation distribution of gaseous CO_2 is given in Figure 3.4. If we separate the gaseous CO_2 phase and liquid brine phase by moving upward the gaseous CO_2 and moving downward the liquid brine, we will get a boundary line between gaseous CO_2 and liquid brine phases. Figure 3.5 compares this boundary line with the theoretical solution by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006), showing that the numerical result agrees well with the theoretical solution. The gas saturation of the numerical solution is slightly smaller than that of the theoretical solution. This is due to the slight dissolution of CO_2 in brine.

Partial Erosion Analysis

The temporal changes of the saturation distribution and the porosity are given in Figures 3.6 and 3.7. From Figure 3.6 we can see obvious gravity segregation of the gas and liquid phases. Comparing Figures 3.6 and 3.7, we can see that the shape of the erosion

region mimics the shape of the $CO_2(g)$ plume. If we observe Figure 3.7, we can see that injecting dry CO_2 does not significantly affect the porosity. This is because the dissolution process is limited by the high Ca^{2+} concentration. The brine loses its ability to dissolve the calcite once it is saturated with Ca^{2+} . It is interesting to notice that the maximum dissolution does not appear around the injection well but on the top of the formation. This phenomenon indicates that the integrity of the caprock may be changed due to the CO_2 injection. This phenomenon agrees with the results given in *Chadwick et al. (2008)* and *Yu et al. (2015)*. To explain this partial erosion, we show in Figure 3.8 the porosity change rate. From Figure 3.8, we can clearly see that the highest dissolution rate exists at the tip of $CO_2(g)$ plume.

We can divide the dissolution into four regimes, as shown in Figure 3.8. In regime I, the porosity increases due to increasing gas pressure. In regime II, ahead of the frontier of the $CO_2(g)$ plume, we observe slight precipitation of calcite; this is because the local brine with low Ca^{2+} and HCO_3^- concentrations mixes with the flux of brine of high Ca^{2+} and HCO_3^- concentrations from the upstream direction, where the calcite dissolves due to CO_2 dissolution. Figure 1(a) in *De Simoni et al. (2005)* illustrates the fact that mixing of two equilibrium solutions can cause precipitation of the solid species, given that the two solutions have different concentrations. In regime III, close to the frontier of the $CO_2(g)$ plume, we can observe dissolution of calcite, because at this region the brine absorbs CO_2 , becomes acid, and dissolves the calcite. The reason why we observe fast dissolution at the tip of $CO_2(g)$ plume is that the saturation change at the tip is very active, as can be seen in Figure 3.9. In regime IV, behind the frontier of the $CO_2(g)$ plume, there is very slight precipitation of calcite; this is because the gas pressure decreases as the injectivity increases as a result of the increasing fraction of highly mobile $CO_2(g)$ in the field. We note that although both regimes I and II experience the mixing of high concentration fluid with low concentration fluid, regime I experiences dissolution while regime II experiences precipitation; this may be because the chemical system Equation (3.1) is a combination of more than one reaction.

In order to analyze the detailed process of the four dissolution regimes, we give, in Figures 3.10 and 3.11, the temporal developments of $(\Delta X_l^m/\Delta t)^*$, $(\Delta P_g/\Delta t)^*$, $(\Delta\phi/\Delta t)^*$ and $(\Delta S_g/\Delta t)^*$ of observation points P1 and P2 shown in Figure 3.8. $(\chi)^*$ is defined as

$$(\chi(t))^* = \frac{\chi(t)}{\max \chi(t)}. \quad (3.37)$$

From the curve for $(\Delta\phi/\Delta t)^*$ in Figure 3.10, we can see that P1 skips regime II. From Figures 3.10 and 3.11 we can see that (1) the dissolution rate $(\Delta\phi/\Delta t)^*$ for both P1 and P2 start to increase earlier than $(\Delta S_g/\Delta t)^*$, and (2) the $(\Delta S_g/\Delta t)^*$ for both P1 and P2 start to increase when the dissolution rates $(\Delta\phi/\Delta t)^*$ drop to zero. This is because the

injected gas phase will first dissolve into the brine and then the acidified brine reacts with the calcite, and the gas phase starts to appear when the brine is saturated with aqueous gas and calcium.

From Figure 3.10, we can see that $(\Delta X_l^m/\Delta t)^*$, $(\Delta P_g/\Delta t)^*$ and $(\Delta\phi/\Delta t)^*$ are closely related in P1. This correlation however is not always true in P2. In P2, we could observe calcite precipitation even if the gas pressure increases. This precipitation is due to the mixing of two brines with different concentrations. Only considering regimes I and II of P2 in Figure 3.11, it is interesting to note that the calcite dissolves if $(\Delta X_l^m/\Delta t)^*$ is high, and calcite precipitates if $(\Delta X_l^m/\Delta t)^*$ is low; this explains why calcite dissolves in regime I and precipitates in regime II. The precipitation due to pressure decrease is negligible in regime IV.

Figures 3.15 and 3.16 give the distributions of the mass fractions of CO_2 and mineral components. From these two figures we can see that the vertical mixing of the solution in the brine phase is very fast. This is due to the outward and downward brine fluxes, as shown in Figures 3.17 and 3.18. Comparing Figures 3.15 and 3.16 with 3.7, we can see that the CO_2 saturated brine has influenced a very large region, but formation rock is only affected in a small region. This is because the CO_2 -saturated brine is also saturated with aqueous mineral species that prohibit the dissolution of solid mineral species. In the case of injecting gaseous CO_2 , the dissolution of solid mineral species is restricted by the amount of brine. ‘Fresh’ brine, with less aqueous Ca^{2+} , is needed to increase the dissolution of calcite. The distributions of H^+ , Ca^{2+} and $CO_2(aq)$ (not shown) are similar to that for the CO_2 component given in Figure 3.15; all of these four variables increase with gas pressure, as shown in Figures 3.1 and 3.2. Comparing Figures 3.15 and 3.16 with 3.14, we can see that the mass fractions of the components are closely related to the gas pressure; this follows the definition of Equations (3.27) to (3.30).

3.4 Conclusions

This chapter first provides an equilibrium reactive three-phase flow program for simulating Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS), then benchmarks the numerical solution against the theoretical solution, and finally qualitatively analyzes the partial erosion in GCS.

Firstly, this program considers a simplified system: the rock formation is only comprised of calcite, the reaction between the acidified brine and calcite is at equilibrium, and the system is isothermal. The program uses persistent independent variables without variable substitution. These independent variables are solved simultaneously with implicit approach. In solving the reactive transport equations, the mass changes due to chemical reaction have been expressed as empirical functions of gas pressure. These empirical functions are based on solving the equilibrium reaction using mass action law.

Figure 3.6: Numerical results: saturation distribution of gas phase.

Figure 3.7: Numerical results: porosity change, $(\phi - \phi_0)/\phi_0$ [-].

Figure 3.8: Numerical results: porosity change rate, $\Delta\phi/\Delta t$ [s^{-1}]; the white dash line denotes the place experiencing the appearance of gas phase; the roman number denotes the dissolution regimes; P1 and P2 are the two observation points.

Figure 3.9: Numerical results: saturation change rate, $\Delta S_g/\Delta t$ [s^{-1}]; the white dash line denotes the place experiencing the appearance of gas phase.

Figure 3.10: Numerical results: developments of $(\Delta X_l^m/\Delta t)^*$, $(\Delta p_g/\Delta t)^*$, $(\Delta\phi/\Delta t)^*$ and $(\Delta S_g/\Delta t)^*$ for P1 in Figure 3.8.

Figure 3.11: Numerical results: developments of $(\Delta X_l^m/\Delta t)^*$, $(\Delta p_g/\Delta t)^*$, $(\Delta\phi/\Delta t)^*$ and $(\Delta S_g/\Delta t)^*$ for P2 in Figure 3.8.

Figure 3.12: Numerical results: distribution of log radial flux of gaseous CO_2 ($\log q_{g,r}$).

Figure 3.13: Numerical results: distribution of vertical flux of gaseous CO_2 ($\log(q_{g,v})$).

Figure 3.14: Numerical results: gas pressure, p_g [pa]; the magenta dash line denotes the place experiencing the appearance of gas phase..

Figure 3.15: Numerical results: mass fraction of CO_2 component, X_i^c [-].

Figure 3.16: Numerical results: mass fraction of mineral component, X_l^m [-].

Figure 3.17: Numerical results: distribution of radial flux of saline water ($q_{l,r}$).

Figure 3.18: Numerical results: distribution of vertical flux of saline water ($q_{l,v}$).

Secondly, the numerical program is tested against the theoretical solution by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006). The numerical result agrees well with the theoretical solution. The average gas saturation estimated by the numerical solution is but slightly smaller than that given by the theoretical solution, because the theoretical solution does not consider the dissolution of CO_2 and calcite.

Finally, we qualitatively analyze the partial dissolution/precipitation of calcite due to gas injection. We find that the caprock on the top of the formation experiences more significant erosion, due to the gravity segregation of the gas and brine. The maximum fractional porosity increase is only around 10^{-3} , because we only inject dry gas. We note that we need also inject water or brine with low salinity if we want to get greater erosion. In order to get a detailed figure of the erosion process, we also analyze the development of erosion rate. We find that the formation rock may experiences four erosion regimes: dissolution (I), precipitation (II), dissolution (III) and negligible precipitation (IV). Among these regimes, regime III denotes the most significant dissolution at the interface between gas and brine phases, while regime IV, denotes the negligible precipitation behind the frontier due to very small decrease in gas pressure (i.e., increase in injectivity).

Chapter 4

Reactive Multi-Component Three-Phase Flow Model for Geological CO_2 Sequestration

Description: This chapter is based on a manuscript- Wang Y., Fernandez-Garcia D. & Saaltink M. (2022), *MRST-CO2: Reactive Multi-Component Three-Phase Flow Program for Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS)*- to be submitted to *Computers & Geosciences*.

4.1 Introduction

This chapter extends the simplified equilibrium reactive three-phase flow model in Chapter 3 to full reactive three-phase flow model. In Chapter 3, we assumed that the heterogeneous reaction between calcite and brine is at equilibrium state, and that the mass compositions at equilibrium state are expressed as functions of gas pressure. That is an acceptable simplification when the reaction between calcite and the brine has a time scale smaller than the transport time scale. However, there are many geological chemical reactions that have low reaction rates and it is therefore necessary to introduce kinetic reactions to the transport model (*Aradóttir et al., 2012*). In this chapter, in addition to equilibrium reactions, we also incorporate kinetic reactions to the three-phase flow model. This reactive transport process gives rise to the following concerns.

In the open system that involves both reaction and transport, we need to take into account the feedback between reaction and transport. The chemical reaction will generate source term in the transport equation, and the transport will change the chemical state. Improper coping with the interplay between reaction and transport could lead to low accuracy, slow convergence rate and even unreal results. This is especially true when mass exchanges among phases cause phase appearance/disappearance, which leads to coexistence of saturated and unsaturated regions and complicates the program if the

governing equations and independent variables are not properly selected. For instance, when a gas phase (e.g., hydrogen, methane and CO_2) is injected to a system initially filled with liquid phase, the gas phase will not immediately appear because the gas will first dissolve into the liquid phase, and then the gas phase appears at bubbling point; traditional algorithm may employ ‘variable substitution’ method that uses different independent variables in the saturated and unsaturated regions.

When both kinetic and equilibrium reactions exist in a chemical system, they should be solved in a coupled manner. In chemical engineering, it is common to simultaneously solve the kinetic and equilibrium reactions in a closed system (i.e., a well-mixed batch reactor that does not consider the convection-dispersion transport) (Leal, 2014). Partial equilibrium system is used to term a system comprised of both kinetic and equilibrium reactions (Helgeson *et al.*, 1969, 1970). The kinetic reaction evolves according to the kinetic reaction rate while the equilibrium reaction is controlled by mass action law. The kinetic reaction and the equilibrium reaction influence each other and they should be solved simultaneously. However, in the current reactive flow models, the kinetic reactions are usually decoupled from the equilibrium reactions (Saaltink *et al.*, 2004). In these models, the kinetic reactions are included in the transport equations, and then the transport equations and the equilibrium reactions are solved sequentially and alternately. In this work, we totally separate all the reactions from the transport equations, and the transport equations are arranged such that they are free of source term due to chemical reactions. The kinetic and equilibrium chemical reactions are solved in a coupled manner. The chemical reactions and the transport equations are solved sequentially and alternately.

Moreover, the computational efficiency should be considered in solving the partial equilibrium chemical system. The reactions are classified into kinetic and equilibrium reactions to increase the efficiency. The time scales of different reactions can differ from each other by several orders of magnitude, from microseconds to millennium (Lasaga, 2014; Langmuir, 1996; Chadwick *et al.*, 2008). For example, the halftime of homogeneous chemical reaction in liquid phase is usually less than one second, while the heterogeneous reaction between calcite and acid water can be several weeks in low temperature (Leal, 2014). The huge contrast of reaction rate can incur numerical problems when a partial equilibrium system is not well defined, because the time step should be very small if the fast reaction is treated as kinetic reaction. The very small time step of the order of microseconds makes it formidable to simulate the long-term geochemical process. Thus, it is necessary to assume that the fast reaction is in equilibrium state while the slow reaction evolves kinetically with a slow reaction rate during the process (Helgeson, 1968; Helgeson *et al.*, 1969). This assumption has been widely used in geological chemical systems (Lichtner, 1985; Steefel and Lasaga, 1994). We note that the kinetic reaction assumption only applies to the reaction of a timescale similar to the time step for solving transport

equations. On the one hand, if the time scale of a reaction is very small compared to the time step for solving transport equation, it is not necessary to treat the reaction as kinetic reaction and instead the reaction should be treated as equilibrium reaction. On the other hand, if the time scale of a reaction is very large compare to the total simulation time, it is reasonable to neglect this reaction. We also note that a reaction treated as kinetic reaction in one system could be treated as equilibrium reaction in another system and that even in the same system a reaction could be treated as kinetic reaction or equilibrium reaction at different stages. For instance, assuming the half time of reaction between a mineral species and CO_2 -saturated brine is one hour, then this reaction should be treated as kinetic reaction during the CO_2 injection stage and be treated as equilibrium reaction during the post-injection stage, because the time step of transport in the injection stage (around one hour) is smaller than (or similar to) the time scale of the reaction, while the time step of the transport in the post injection stage (around several weeks) is quite larger than the time scale of reaction. Therefore, it is important to properly separate the reactions into kinetic and equilibrium reactions in simulating the geochemical system where chemical reaction and transport are taking place in a coupled manner.

Overall, there are three challenges for the reactive three-phase flow model. First, in reactive transport system, we need to take into account the feedback between reaction and transport. Second, if a chemical system has both kinetic and equilibrium reactions, the kinetic and equilibrium reactions should be solved in a coupled way. Third, the kinetic and equilibrium reactions should be well classified for a given process to improve the computational efficiency.

In this chapter, we offer a full reactive three-phase flow model that accounts for all the aforementioned concerns. This model structure is used to construct a specific program for the case of GCS, though it also applies to other reactive multiphase transport systems. The rest of this chapter is organized as follows. The numerical method for reactive three-phase flow is given in Section 4.2, which is comprised of the general reactive three-phase flow model and a specific reactive three-phase flow program for GCS process. In Section 4.3, we first conduct benchmark test for the specific three-phase flow program for GCS and then perform simple sensitive analysis on how kinetic reaction rate affects the reactive transport process. The specific three-phase flow program is then applied to perform a simple analysis on partial dissolution in Section 4.4. Conclusions are listed in Section 4.5

4.2 Methods

In this section, we first describe the general reactive three-phase flow model in Section 4.2.1, and then give the specific reactive three-phase flow program for GCS in Section 4.2.2.

4.2.1 General Reactive Three-Phase Flow Model

This reactive three-phase flow model is comprised of two modules: the chemical reaction module and the transport module. All the related chemical reactions are solved by the chemical reaction module, which is then embedded into the transport module to solve the reactive transport process.

4.2.1.1 Chemical Reaction Module

Partial Equilibrium System

To simulate the geochemical system where many reactions are taking place in a coupled manner, the first step is to separate the reactions into equilibrium and kinetic reactions. If the half time of a reaction is much smaller than the interested time scale, this reaction is treated as equilibrium reaction. If the half time of a reaction is close to the interested time scale, this reaction is treated as kinetic reaction. We do not consider the reaction having a time scale much larger than the interested time scale. The partial equilibrium system, which involves both equilibrium and kinetic reactions, is limited (or controlled) by the kinetic reaction rate. We note that treating fast reaction as kinetic reaction will require a very small time step to calculate the reaction, which is time-consuming and unnecessary.

Once we have separated the reactions into kinetic and equilibrium reactions, we need to separate the species (β) into kinetic species (β_k) and equilibrium species (β_e). The former only participates in kinetic reactions, while the latter can participate in both kinetic and equilibrium reactions (Leal, 2014).

$$\beta = \beta_e \cup \beta_k, \emptyset = \beta_e \cap \beta_k. \quad (4.1)$$

We use vector ζ_k and ζ_e to store the molar abundances of kinetic and equilibrium species, respectively. Vector ξ_k and ξ_e are used to store the masses of kinetic and equilibrium species, respectively. The numbers of kinetic and equilibrium reactions are denoted by n_K and n_E , respectively. The numbers of kinetic and equilibrium species are denoted by n_k and n_e , respectively. The total number of the species is n_s . The stoichiometric matrices for kinetic and equilibrium reactions are $(n_K \times n_s) \nu_k$ and $(n_E \times n_s) \nu_e$, respectively. The reactions can be written in matrix form as

$$\mathbf{0} \rightleftharpoons \nu_k \beta \quad (4.2)$$

and

$$\mathbf{0} \rightleftharpoons \nu_e \beta, \quad (4.3)$$

with

$$\boldsymbol{\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\nu}_k \\ \boldsymbol{\nu}_e \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.4)$$

The reaction rate vector is

$$\boldsymbol{r} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{r}_k \\ \boldsymbol{r}_e \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.5)$$

The chemical system is calculated by simultaneously solving reactions (4.2) and (4.3). The kinetic reaction is governed by the empirical expression for the reaction rate, while the equilibrium reaction is governed by Mass Action Law (MAL). New equilibrium state among the equilibrium species is reached as soon as the old equilibrium state is perturbed by the kinetic reaction; therefore the chemical system is governed by the slow kinetic reactions. As a new temporal equilibrium state is reached, the rate of kinetic reaction is also changed. For a closed partial equilibrium system (i.e., without convection or dispersion), the kinetic reaction rate decreases with time, and finally all the (equilibrium and kinetic) species are at equilibrium state. We can understand the partial equilibrium system in such a way that the kinetic reaction evolves slowly, which perturbs the equilibrium reactions away from the equilibrium state, and the equilibrium reaction instantaneously adjusts the disequilibrium state to a new equilibrium state for the equilibrium species.

To solve a system including both kinetic and equilibrium reactions, it is important to define the constraint (i.e., independent variables) of this system. Solving the partial equilibrium reaction only needs the mass (or molar abundance) of the kinetic species and equilibrium components. For instance, considering the equilibrium water evaporation, the mass of certain species (e.g., $H_2O(g)$ and $H_2O(l)$) will change with time during the reaction, but the mass of any chemical component (e.g., $H_2O(g) + H_2O(l)$) keeps constant; therefore, we could use the mass of chemical component as the constraint for a given equilibrium system. If a system only contains n_e species involved in (n_E) equilibrium reactions, then we need another ($n_e - n_E$) constraints to solve the equilibrium system. If a partial equilibrium system includes n_k kinetic species and n_e equilibrium species involved in (n_K) kinetic and (n_E) equilibrium reactions, then we need ($n_k + n_e - n_E = n_s - n_E$) constraints to solve the chemical system. For this partial equilibrium system, the mass of all the equilibrium species can be calculated with the ($n_e - n_E$) constraints on masses of pure equilibrium components. The obtained masses of the equilibrium species are then used to calculate the kinetic reaction rate and thus the masses of the kinetic species. Therefore, we use the masses of the n_k kinetic species and the $n_e - n_E$ pure equilibrium components as the independent variables for updating the masses of all the species. We note that the pure equilibrium components, which only include equilibrium species, are not changed by equilibrium reactions but can be changed by the kinetic reactions. The

pure equilibrium components are obtained by extracting the equilibrium species from the equilibrium components. Of course, the state variables (pressure and temperature) are also independent variables. In Chapter 3, we use the molar abundance as the unit when solving the chemical reaction system, but we can also use mass as the unit. Here, we use the masses rather than the molar abundances of the components and the kinetic species as the independent variables, because the transport equation is usually written based on the mass balance of the component.

In a partial equilibrium system, the kinetic and equilibrium reactions should be solved simultaneously in a coupled manner. The pure equilibrium system has been described in Chapter 3, and in this section we describe how to solve the partial equilibrium system based on the algorithm for equilibrium reactions.

To solve the partial equilibrium system, we need masses of kinetic species (ξ_k) and pure equilibrium components (u_{ee}). However, from the transport equation, we first read the masses of kinetic species (ξ_k) and full conservative components (u_c). In the following we first describe how to extract the pure equilibrium components from the full components, and then solve the partial equilibrium reaction. The masses of kinetic species and full components are stored in vector

$$\mathbf{u}^* = \begin{bmatrix} \xi_k \\ u_c \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4.6)$$

where, u_c is $(n_s - n_K - n_E)$ -dimensional vector, defined as

$$u_c = U\xi. \quad (4.7)$$

u_c is comprised of kinetic (u_k) and equilibrium components (u_e), which are, respectively, calculated with

$$u_k = U_k M_m \zeta = U_k \xi \quad (4.8)$$

and

$$u_e = U_e M_m \zeta = U_e \xi, \quad (4.9)$$

where, the kernel matrices U_k and U_e satisfy

$$\begin{bmatrix} U_k \\ U_e \end{bmatrix} \times M_m \times \begin{bmatrix} \nu_k^t \\ \nu_e^t \end{bmatrix} = U \times M_m \times \nu^t = \mathbf{0}, \quad (4.10)$$

with diagonal M_m stores the molar masses of all species.

If we only consider the equilibrium species in the equilibrium components, we have pure equilibrium components

$$u_{ee} = U_{ee} M_{me} \zeta_e = U_{ee} \xi_e = u_e - U_{ek} \xi_k, \quad (4.11)$$

in which, diagonal \mathbf{M}_{me} stores the molar mass of equilibrium species, the kernel matrix for equilibrium species in equilibrium components \mathbf{U}_{ee} is $(n_e - n_E) \times n_e$ matrix and the kernel matrix for kinetic species in equilibrium components \mathbf{U}_{ek} is $(n_e - n_E) \times n_k$ matrix. \mathbf{U}_{ee} and \mathbf{U}_{ek} are obtained by extracting the columns corresponding to equilibrium species and kinetic species from \mathbf{U}_e , respectively. The method of calculating \mathbf{U} is already given in Chapter 3.

The temporal development of kinetic species follows

$$\frac{d\xi_k}{dt} = \mathbf{M}_{mk} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{kk}^t \mathbf{r}_k, \quad (4.12)$$

where, diagonal \mathbf{M}_{mk} stores the molar mass of kinetic species, $\boldsymbol{\nu}_{kk}$ only consists the columns of $\boldsymbol{\nu}_k$ corresponding to the kinetic species, and \mathbf{r}_k stores the kinetic reaction rates for n_K kinetic reactions. \mathbf{r}_k is a function of all kinetic and equilibrium species. The temporal change of the pure equilibrium components is

$$\frac{d\mathbf{u}_{ee}}{dt} = \mathbf{U}_{ee} \mathbf{M}_{me} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{ke}^t \mathbf{r}_k, \quad (4.13)$$

where $(n_K \times n_e)$ matrix $\boldsymbol{\nu}_{ke}$ only consists the columns of $\boldsymbol{\nu}_k$ corresponding to the equilibrium species. Here, we cannot explicitly calculate the equilibrium species in the same way as kinetic species. The mass of the equilibrium species is calculated by solving the (n_E) equilibrium reactions (i.e., Equation (4.3)) with the mass action law, which requires $(n_e - n_E)$ constraints based on $(n_e - n_E)$ pure equilibrium components (i.e., Equation (4.11)).

Here, instead of using \mathbf{u}^* , we use \mathbf{u} to solve the partial equilibrium. \mathbf{u} is defined as

$$\mathbf{u} = [\xi_k, \mathbf{u}_{ee}]. \quad (4.14)$$

We note that \mathbf{u} can be readily obtained from \mathbf{u}^* . On the basis of Equations (4.12) and (4.13) we have the governing equation for kinetic-equilibrium reactions

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{d\xi_k}{dt} \\ \frac{d\mathbf{u}_{ee}}{dt} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{mk} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{kk}^t \\ \mathbf{U}_{ee} \mathbf{M}_{me} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{ke}^t \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}_k. \quad (4.15)$$

The governing equations (4.15) is solved by using Newton-Raphson method. The Newton-Raphson form of the governing equations is

$$\mathbf{0} = \mathcal{F} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d\xi_k}{dt} \\ \frac{d\mathbf{u}_{ee}}{dt} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{mk} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{kk}^t \\ \mathbf{U}_{ee} \mathbf{M}_{me} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{ke}^t \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}_k, \quad (4.16)$$

and the Jacobian matrix of this equation system is

$$\mathbf{J} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \mathbf{u}} = \frac{1}{dt} \mathbf{I} - \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{mk} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{kk}^t \\ \mathbf{U}_{ee} \mathbf{M}_{me} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{ke}^t \end{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_k}{\partial \mathbf{u}}. \quad (4.17)$$

The solution is

$$\mathbf{u}^{i+1,j+1} = \mathbf{u}^{i+1,j} + \delta \mathbf{u}^{i+1,j}, \quad (4.18)$$

where $\delta \mathbf{u}^{i+1,j}$ is obtained by solving

$$\mathbf{J}^{i+1,j} \delta \mathbf{u}^{i+1,j} = -\mathcal{F}^{i+1,j}, \quad (4.19)$$

where, superscript i denotes time step and j denotes the iteration step. Initially, $\mathbf{u}^{i+1,0} = \mathbf{u}^i$.

The key to solving Equations (4.16) to (4.19) is solving $\frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_k}{\partial \mathbf{u}}$. As we know the $\mathbf{r}_k = \mathbf{r}_k(\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta)$, we need to know the molar abundances of all species to calculate the \mathbf{r}_k and its derivative $\frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_k}{\partial \mathbf{u}}$, which can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_k}{\partial \mathbf{u}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_k}{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}}{\partial \mathbf{u}}, \quad (4.20)$$

where

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}}{\partial \mathbf{u}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}_k} & \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}_e} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}_e}{\partial \mathbf{u}_{ee}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.21)$$

Here, $\partial \mathbf{r}_k / \partial \boldsymbol{\xi}$ is obtained with the explicit empirical expression for kinetic reaction rate, given in the end of this subsection. The only unknown is $\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}_e / \partial \mathbf{u}_{ee}$.

Since the equilibrium species satisfy

$$\mathbf{0} = \mathcal{F}_e = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{ee} \ln \mathbf{a}_e - \ln \mathbf{K}_e \\ \mathbf{U}_{ee} \boldsymbol{\xi}_e - \mathbf{u}_{ee} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4.22)$$

$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}_e}{\partial \mathbf{u}_{ee}}$ is obtained by taking derivative of Equation (4.22) with respect to the pure equilibrium components, that is,

$$\mathbf{0} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_e}{\partial \mathbf{u}_{ee}} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{ee} \frac{\partial \ln \mathbf{a}_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}_e} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}_e}{\partial \mathbf{u}_{ee}} \\ \mathbf{U}_{ee} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}_e}{\partial \mathbf{u}_{ee}} - \mathbf{I}_e \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.23)$$

Here, \mathbf{a}_e stores the activities of equilibrium species, and \mathbf{K}_e stores the equilibrium constant for equilibrium reactions. (We note that for a general expression $\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{x})$, we cannot get $\partial \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{x}) / \partial \mathbf{x} = 0$ from $\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{x}) = 0$. However, for the specific case of equilibrium reaction, Equation (4.22) is inherently equal to zero for any value of equilibrium components \mathbf{u}_{ee} ; this means, $\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_e}{\partial \mathbf{u}_{ee}} = 0$.) Rearranging Equation (4.23), we get

$$\begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{ee} \frac{\partial \ln \mathbf{a}_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}_e} \\ \mathbf{U}_{ee} \end{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}_e}{\partial \mathbf{u}_{ee}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{I}_e \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4.24)$$

where $\frac{\partial \ln a_e}{\partial \xi_e}$ has been calculated when solving Equation (4.22) with the mass action law given in Table 4.1. In virtue of the obtained $\frac{\partial \xi_e}{\partial \mathbf{u}_{ee}}$ and Equations (4.16) to (4.21), we can calculate the temporal development of all the kinetic species. During this process we actually have also solved the temporal development of the equilibrium species with Equation (4.22).

The algorithm for solving the partial equilibrium system is summarized in Table 4.2, which has employed Table 4.1 for solving the pure equilibrium reactions. This chemical reaction module is inserted into the transport module as constitution equations, from which we can obtain the mass compositions of all species based on the kinetic species and full conservative components.

Time Step Control

The time step for the kinetic reaction (dt_r) should be limited to avoid negative values for the chemical species, as well as to improve the accuracy. In this work the time step for kinetic reaction is calculated as

$$dt_r = \min \left(t_{tot} - t_r, \eta_c \min_{i=1, \dots, N_r} \frac{\xi_i}{M_i \nu_{ik} |r_{ik}|} \right), \quad (4.25)$$

where, t_{tot} is the total time for kinetic reaction and t_{tot} is equal to the transport time step (Δt) in reactive transport issues; $\eta_c < 1$ is the number limiting the time step length; ξ_i and M_i are, respectively, the mass and molar mass of i th reactant; ν_{ik} is the stoichiometric entry of i th reactant in the kinetic reaction; r_{ik} is the reaction rate of the kinetic reaction related to the i th reactant; and N_r is the total number of the reactants. Here, the time step is calculated based on the constraint that the mass of the kinetic species should be non-negative. The reaction time is updated according to

$$t_r^{new} = t_r^{old} + dt_r. \quad (4.26)$$

The calculation of the chemical reaction is terminated when $t_r = t_{tot} = \Delta t$.

Kinetic Reaction Rate

For a given kinetic dissolution/precipitation reaction, the kinetic reaction rate (r_k [$\text{mol}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]) is given as (*Steeffel and Lasaga, 1994; Steefel and Mäher, 2009; Palandri and Kharaka, 2004; Lasaga, 2014; Leal, 2014*)

$$r_k(T_k, p_l, p_g, \zeta) = \mathcal{A}(\zeta) \sum_i \mathcal{K}_i(T_k, p_l, p_g, \zeta), \quad (4.27)$$

where, \mathcal{A} [m^2] is the surface area of the mineral, \mathcal{K}_i [$\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] is the i th kinetic mechanism function, p_l and p_g are, respectively, liquid and gas pressures, and T_k is temperature in Kelvin. Some common kinetic reaction mechanisms are neutral, acid, base and carbonate, etc (*Palandri and Kharaka, 2004*). For the case of calcite dissolution there

Table 4.1: Algorithm MAL-E2: Mass action law for solving equilibrium reactions in partial equilibrium system (based on mass component).

Input: constraints on the mass component $[\mathbf{u}_C]^n$; warm initial guess $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta]^n$; primary independent variables: $[p_l]^n, [p_g]^n$; temperature $[T_k]^n$; kernel matrix for pure equilibrium mass components \mathbf{U}_{ee} ; stoichiometric matrix for equilibrium reactions $\boldsymbol{\nu}_{ee}$; % note: $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta]^n$ contains the masses of all the kinetic and equilibrium species, but only the masses of equilibrium species $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_e]^n$ are used; theoretically, the initial guess of the masses of equilibrium species can be arbitrary because the solution converges fast with the Newton-Raphson iteration, but here we use the warm initial guess from the previous step, i.e., $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_e]^n$; $[\mathbf{u}_C]^n$ contains the masses of both the kinetic and equilibrium components, but only the masses of equilibrium components $[\mathbf{u}_e]^n$ are used; the sizes of \mathbf{U}_{ee} and $\boldsymbol{\nu}_{ee}$ are $((n_e - n_E) \times n_e)$ and $(n_E \times n_e)$, respectively; the size of $[\mathbf{u}_C]^n, [\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta]^n, [\boldsymbol{\xi}_e]^n$ and $[\mathbf{u}_e]^n$ are $n_s - n_E - n_K, n_s, n_e, n_e - n_E$, respectively;
0: extract the masses of equilibrium species $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_e]^n$ from $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta]^n$; the initial guess of masses of the equilibrium species is then $\boldsymbol{\xi}_e^0 = [\boldsymbol{\xi}_e]^n$; extract equilibrium mass components \mathbf{u}_e from $[\mathbf{u}_C]^n$; only consider the equilibrium species in the equilibrium components, and we have $\mathbf{u}_{ee} = \mathbf{U}_{ee}\boldsymbol{\xi}_e (= \mathbf{u}_e - \mathbf{U}_{ek}\boldsymbol{\xi}_k)$; set $l = 0$ and $\delta_\xi^0 = \text{inf}$;
1: while $\max \frac{\delta_\xi^l}{\xi_e^{l+1}} < \epsilon_\xi$, do 2 to 4; % here ϵ_ξ is the tolerance for convergence;
2: in virtue of the activities $([\mathbf{a}_e]^l)$ calculated by using the models given in Appendix D, the equilibrium coefficients given in Appendix D, calculate the residual vector (\mathcal{F}_e^l) and the Jacobian matrix (\mathbf{J}_e^l) , respectively, using Equations
$\mathbf{0} = \mathcal{F}_e^l = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{ee} \ln \mathbf{a}_e - \ln \mathbf{K}_e \\ \mathbf{U}_{ee}\boldsymbol{\xi}_e - \mathbf{u}_{ee} \end{bmatrix}^l \text{ and } \mathbf{J}_e^l = \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_e^l}{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}_e} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{ee} \frac{\partial \ln \mathbf{a}_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}_e} \\ \mathbf{U}_{ee} \end{bmatrix}^l;$
3: calculate $\delta_\xi^{l+1} = -[\mathbf{J}_e^l]^{-1} \cdot \mathcal{F}_e^l$; and then $\boldsymbol{\xi}_e^{l+1} = \boldsymbol{\xi}_e^l + \eta_d \delta_\xi^{l+1}$;
4: $l = l + 1$;
5: endwhile ¹
6: $\boldsymbol{\xi}_e = \boldsymbol{\xi}_e^{l+1}$; $\mathbf{J}_e = \mathbf{J}_e^{l+1}$; % $\boldsymbol{\xi}_e$ is used to update the masses of the equilibrium species in $\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta$ and \mathbf{J}_e will be used to calculate the derivative of the kinetic reaction rate;
Output: $\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta$ and \mathbf{J}_e .

Table 4.2: Algorithm MAL-PE: Mass action law for solving partial equilibrium system (based on mass component).

<p>Input values: primary independent variables $[p_l; p_g]^n$; secondary independent variables $[\xi_k, \mathbf{u}_c]^n$; and other dependent variables $[\xi_\beta]^n$; kernel matrix for pure equilibrium mass components \mathbf{U}_{ee} (only the equilibrium species is considered); stoichiometric matrix for equilibrium species in equilibrium reactions ν_{ee}; stoichiometric matrix for kinetic species in kinetic reactions ν_{kk}; stoichiometric matrix for equilibrium species in kinetic reactions ν_{ke}; temperature T_k; time step $[\Delta t]^n$;</p> <p>0: set $i = j = 0$, and the initial kinetic reaction time $t_r^0 = 0$; $\mathbf{u}^{0,0} = \begin{bmatrix} \xi_k \\ \mathbf{u}_c \end{bmatrix}^n$, $\delta \mathbf{u}^{0,0} = \text{inf}$;</p> <p>% here, i denotes the ith sub time step, and j denotes the jth Newton-Raphson iteration inside the ith sub time step; we note that the time step $([\Delta t]^n)$ for solving the transport equations might be too large for the kinetic reaction so $[\Delta t]^n$ is split into smaller dt^i; the reaction time is updated with $t_r^{i+1} = t_r^i + dt^i$ and the kinetic reaction is terminated when $t_r^{i+1} = [\Delta t]^n$; this time splitting may not be necessary if the transport time step $[\Delta t]^n$ is not larger than the maximum allowed time step for chemical reaction;</p> <p>1: while $t_r^i < [\Delta t]^n$, do steps 2 to 9;</p> <p>2: calculate sub time step dt^i, with Equation (4.25);</p> <p>3: while $\max \delta \mathbf{u}^{i+1,j+1} / \mathbf{u}^{i+1,j} > \epsilon_k$, do steps 4 to 6 ; % where ϵ_k (e.g. 10^{-9}) is the tolerance for Newton-Raphson iteration;</p> <p>4: only solve the equilibrium system with the Algorithm MAL-E2 given in Table 4.1, which gives $\xi_e^{i+1,j+1}$ and $\mathbf{J}_e^{i+1,j+1}$; % $\xi_e^{i,j}$ serves as the initial guess of the molar abundance of the equilibrium system;</p> <p>5: calculate the kinetic reaction rate $[\mathbf{r}_k]^{i+1,j+1}$ with Equation (4.27); calculate $[\frac{\partial \xi_e}{\partial \mathbf{u}_e}]^{i+1,j+1}$ with Equation (4.24); then, calculate $[\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \mathbf{u}}]^{i+1,j+1}$ with Equation (4.21); finally, $[\frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_k}{\partial \mathbf{u}}]^{i+1,j+1}$ is obtained with Equation (4.20);</p> <p>6: calculate residual vector $[\mathcal{F}]^{i+1,j+1}$ with Equation (4.16) and its Jacobian matrix $[\mathbf{J}]^{i+1,j+1}$ with Equation (4.17); then obtain $\delta \mathbf{u}^{i+1,j+1}$ with Equation (4.19); finally, update the $\mathbf{u}^{i+1,j}$ to $\mathbf{u}^{i+1,j+1}$ with Equation (4.18); $[\xi_\beta]^{i+1,j+1}$ and $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^{i+1,j+1}$ have also been calculated; $j = j + 1$;</p> <p>% note that dt^i is used in calculating $[\mathcal{F}]^{i+1,j+1}$ and $[\mathbf{J}]^{i+1,j}$;</p> <p>7: endwhile³</p> <p>8: $\mathbf{u}^{i+1} = \mathbf{u}^{i+1,j+1}$; $[\xi_\beta]^{i+1} = [\xi_\beta]^{i+1,j+1}$; $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^{i+1} = [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^{i+1,j+1}$; $j = 0$;</p> <p>9: update $t_r^{i+1} = t_r^i + dt^i$; $i = i + 1$;</p> <p>10: endwhile¹;</p> <p>11: $\mathbf{u}^{n+1} = \mathbf{u}^{i+1}$; $[\xi_\beta]^{n+1} = [\xi_\beta]^{i+1}$; $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^{n+1} = [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^{i+1}$;</p> <p>12: change the gas pressure by δp_g and repeat steps 0 to 11; we then get $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^{n+1'}$;</p> <p>13: calculate $\frac{\partial [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^{n+1}}{\partial p_g} = \frac{[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^{n+1'} - [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^{n+1}}{\delta p_g}$;</p>
<p>Output: $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^{n+1}$; $[\partial \mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}} / \partial p_g]^{n+1}$; $[\xi_k, \mathbf{u}_c]^{n+1}$; $[\xi_\beta]^{n+1}$.</p>

are three involved kinetic reaction mechanisms: neutral, acid and carbonate.

The surface area, \mathcal{A} , changes as the mineral dissolves or precipitates. The dynamic model for \mathcal{A} is complex even in batch reactions. *Parkhurst and Appelo* (2013b) offer a simple dynamic model for surface area of the minerals:

$$\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_0 \left(\frac{V}{V_0} \right)^{\eta_V} = \mathcal{A}_s \cdot V_0 \cdot \left(\frac{V}{V_0} \right)^{\eta_V}, \quad (4.28)$$

where, \mathcal{A}_0 is the initial surface area of the (solid) mineral species, V_0 [m³] is the initial volume of the mineral species, and \mathcal{A}_s [m²·m⁻³] is the effective reactive area per volume of minerals. $\eta_V = 2/3$ for spheres and cubes that uniformly react with liquid phase.

A general empirical rate equation for the i th kinetic mineral mechanism is given as

$$\mathcal{K}_i = \text{sgn}(1 - I_S) |1 - I_S^{\eta_{i,1}}|^{\eta_{i,2}} \eta_{i,c} k_i, \quad (4.29)$$

where, I_S is the saturation index, given as

$$\ln I_S = \sum_i \nu_i \ln a_i - \ln K, \quad (4.30)$$

where, a_i and ν_i are, respectively, the activity and stoichiometric value of aqueous species involved in the dissolution/precipitation of the mineral (*Sjöberg, 1976; Nancollas and Reddy, 1971*), and K is the equilibrium constant for the interested mineral dissolution/precipitation. The exponents $\eta_{i,1}$ and $\eta_{i,2}$ are usually lacking in literature. Note, the activity of the solid mineral species is assumed to be unit. Here, we use $\eta_{i,1} = 1$ and $\eta_{i,2} = 1$.

$\eta_{i,c}$ is a function to model the aforementioned kinetic mineral mechanisms, given as

$$\eta_{c,i} = \prod_j a_j^{\theta_j} \prod_k p_k^{\theta_k}, \quad (4.31)$$

where, p_k is the partial pressure of the k -th gaseous species, the exponents θ_j and θ_k are from experiment. Positive and negative exponents, respectively, indicate catalyst and inhibitor. For example, θ_{H^+} is nonzero for acid kinetic mechanism, $\theta_{p_{CO_2}}$ is nonzero for carbonate mechanism, and all θ_j and θ_k are zeros for neutral mechanism (*Leal, 2014*).

The reaction rate constant k_i [mol·m⁻²·s⁻¹] is given as

$$k_i = k_{0,i} \exp \left[-\frac{E_i}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_k} - \frac{1}{298.15} \right) \right], \quad (4.32)$$

where $k_{0,i}$ is the reaction rate constant at 298.15 K, E_i [J·mol⁻¹] is the apparent activation energy, and R is universal gas constant (8.314 J·K⁻¹·mol⁻¹). (The relation between rate

constant and apparent activation energy for the dissolution reaction is given as

$$\ln k = -\frac{E}{RT_k} + \ln \eta_A, \quad (4.33)$$

where η_A is pre-exponential factor. E can be obtained by fitting the data $\ln k$ versus $-1/(RT_k)$, and the slope is E .)

For calcite dissolution (*Palandri and Kharaka, 2004*), the $k_{0,i}$ for acid, neutral and carbonate kinetic mineral mechanisms are, respectively, $10^{-0.3}$, $10^{-5.81}$ and $10^{-3.48}$. The activation energies are 14400, 23500 and 35400 J · mol⁻¹ for these three mechanisms, respectively. The exponents for acid (a_{H^+}) and carbonate (p_{CO_2}) kinetic mechanisms are both 1.0. More data on other kinetic reactions can be found in *Palandri and Kharaka (2004)* and *Hellevang et al. (2013)*. In some simplified models for GCS process, the detailed information on different reaction mechanisms is not considered. For instance, results from *Smith et al. (2013)* suggest that when pH variation is relatively small (e.g., pH ranges from 4 to 6), which is common at the CO₂ storage site (*Emberley et al., 2005; Raistrick et al., 2006*), the carbonate kinetic rate can be assumed to be independent of either pH or p_{CO_2} , and the kinetic reaction rate is (*Berner and Morse, 1974; Sjöberg, 1976; Wang et al., 2016a*)

$$r_k = \left(1 - \frac{I_S}{K}\right) \mathcal{A}_s V \mathcal{K}. \quad (4.34)$$

For instance, in *Smith et al. (2013)*, the \mathcal{K} is $10^{-5.38}$ for calcite and $10^{-6.57}$ for dolomite, and the \mathcal{A}_s ranges from 0.65 to 4 [10⁶ m⁻¹]. *Vialle et al. (2014)* use $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469$ [10⁶ m⁻¹] and $\mathcal{K} = 10^{-4.21}$ [mol · m⁻² s⁻¹].

4.2.1.2 Transport Module

We first claim that the independent variables for solving the transport equations are the mass of kinetic species, the mass of conservative (equilibrium and kinetic) components, gas pressure, liquid pressure and porosity. Because the transport system may involve a large amount of independent variables, it would be formidable to solve them in a single step with a big Jacobian matrix. Thus, we need to classify independent variables into different groups, and solve these groups sequentially. Here, we classify the independent variables into two groups.

$$[\mathbf{x}] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_l \\ \mathbf{p}_g \\ \phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.35)$$

and

$$[\mathbf{y}] = [\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_c]^t, \quad (4.36)$$

where, \mathbf{p}_l and \mathbf{p}_g are liquid pressure and gas pressure, respectively; ϕ is the porosity; vector \mathbf{x} stores primary independent variables; and matrix \mathbf{y} stores secondary independent variables. The primary independent variables and secondary independent variables are actually the independent transport variables and independent reaction variables defined in Chapter 3. From the primary independent variables we can get information on the phase fractions, and from the secondary independent variables we can calculate detailed species compositions with the chemical reaction module. These primary independent variables are firstly implicitly solved with the transport equations, which are constructed on the basis of the mass balances of the selected conservative components. Having obtained these primary variables, we can calculate the flux at each face, with which the secondary independent variables are explicitly updated. We note that the transport equations are constructed based on the mass balance of conservative components that are stored in secondary independent variables. We use mass balances of the components to build the governing equations, because their quantities are independent of all the existing chemical reactions. The number of the governing equations for the primary independent variables should be equal to the number of primary independent variables, which should be equal to the number of phases. The number of the components could be larger than the number of the needed governing equations. In our case of three-phase flow, we only need three components to, respectively, construct three governing equations. Thus, we need to choose three most efficient conservative components to construct the three governing equations. We assume these three governing equations are based on the mass balances of three components called, (w, c, m) , which, respectively, correspond to liquid phase, gas phase and solid phase.

Here, gas pressure, liquid pressure and porosity are selected as the primary independent variables, and are stored in vector \mathbf{x} . This is because, from these primary independent variables, we can easily calculate the volume fractions of gas, water and rock, all of which are the most important information for transport module. Therefore, these three variables can give us basic knowledge of the three phases. This combination of independent variables is very efficient in reactive transport process experiencing the appearance and disappearance of gas phase. The masses of kinetic species and conservative components, stored in \mathbf{y} , are selected as secondary independent variables. This is because they are essential in solving the partial equilibrium reactions. We also add a group of dependent variables, denoted as \mathbf{z} , to connect the information for the transport and that for the chemical reactions. \mathbf{z} is defined as

$$[\mathbf{z}] = [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^K, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^C, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^\mathcal{X}]^t, \quad (4.37)$$

where, \mathbf{X}_α^K and \mathbf{X}_α^C are, respectively, the mass fraction of kinetic species and conservative components and $\mathbf{X}_\alpha^\mathcal{X}$ represents the mass fraction of related \mathcal{X} species or variable (e.g.,

the $CO_2(aq)$ and salinity could be needed to calculate the density and viscosity). From \mathbf{z} we can easily read the distribution of the kinetic species and conservative components in different phases, and we can thus calculate the convection-dispersion of the kinetic species and conservative components in each phase.

Before constructing the final governing equations for the mass balance of the components, we first give the original governing equations for the mass balance of β -species in α -fluid-phase and solid phase, given as

$$0 = \mathcal{F}_\alpha^\beta = \frac{\partial(\phi_\alpha \rho_\alpha X_\alpha^\beta)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^\beta \mathbf{q}_\alpha) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_\alpha \mathbf{D}_\alpha \rho_\alpha \nabla X_\alpha^\beta) - \mathbf{M}_m(\beta, \beta) \boldsymbol{\nu}(:, \beta)^t \mathbf{r} - Q^\beta, \quad \alpha = l, g, s; \quad (4.38)$$

where, $\phi_l = \phi S_l$ and $\phi_g = \phi S_g$ [-] are the volumetric fractions of liquid and gaseous phases, respectively; $\phi_s = 1 - \phi$ [-] is the volumetric fraction of solid phase; S [-] represents the saturation; ρ [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$] represents the density; X_α^β [-] represents the mass fraction of species β in phase α ; t [s] is time; \mathbf{q} [$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] is the Darcy discharge; \mathbf{D} [$\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] is the dispersion tensor; \mathbf{M}_m [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$] is the diagonal matrix with the (β, β) entry stores the molar mass of the β -species; $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ is the $(n_E + n_K) \times n_s$ stoichiometric matrix and $\nu_{j\beta}$ [-] is stoichiometric coefficient of species β ($\beta = 1, \dots, n_s$) participating in reaction j ($j = 1, \dots, (n_E + n_K)$); $\boldsymbol{\nu}(:, \beta)^t$ denotes the transpose of β -th column vector of stoichiometric matrix $\boldsymbol{\nu}$; \mathbf{r} [$\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] is the $(n_E + n_K) \times 1$ vector containing $(n_E + n_K)$ equilibrium and kinetic reaction rates; and Q^β [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] is the external source term. Diagonal matrix \mathbf{M}_m is used to transfer the unit of chemical reaction rate from [$\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] to [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] (see also Section 4.2.1.1). For solid phase, $\mathbf{q}_s = \mathbf{D}_s = 0$.

The aforementioned system of transport equations includes n_s equations and each equation contains source term due to (kinetic or equilibrium) chemical reaction. Obviously, it is formidable to solve this system of governing equations, not only because the number of equations is too large, but also because the equilibrium reaction rate is unknown. Instead of studying the n_s advection dispersion reaction equations (ADREs) for n_s species, we can simplify our problem to $(n_s - n_E - n_K)$ advection diffusion equations (ADEs) for $(n_s - n_E - n_K)$ components. In literature, only equilibrium reaction rates are eliminated (*Saaltink et al., 1998*). Here, we eliminate both the equilibrium and kinetic reaction rates. In this way, the chemical reaction and transport are totally separated, and the kinetic and equilibrium reactions can be solved together with method given in the preceding section. To this end, we construct a system of transport equations based on $(n_s - n_E - n_K)$ components by multiplying a $(n_s - n_E - n_K) \times n_s$ component matrix, \mathbf{U} , so that $\mathbf{U} \mathbf{M}_m \boldsymbol{\nu}^t = \mathbf{0}$. Then we have

$$0 = \mathcal{F}_C = \sum_{\alpha=l,g,s} \left[\frac{\partial(\phi_\alpha \rho_\alpha X_\alpha^C)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^C \mathbf{q}_\alpha) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_\alpha \mathbf{D}_\alpha \rho_\alpha \nabla X_\alpha^C) \right] - \sum_{\beta=1}^{n_s} (U_{C\beta} Q^\beta), \quad (4.39)$$

where, the component is defined as

$$X_\alpha^C = \sum_{\beta \in \alpha} U_{C\beta} X_\alpha^\beta. \quad (4.40)$$

Note that source terms due to (kinetic and equilibrium) reactions have been removed. Equation (4.39) has $n_1 + n_2$ independent variables, where n_1 and n_2 denote the total number of primary and secondary independent variables, respectively. n_1 equals to the number of the phases, and n_2 equals the number of the kinetic species and conservative components. Obviously, $n_1 = 3$, and n_2 hinges on the number of reactions and species.

Solving Equation (4.39) needs three steps. First, the three primary independent variables are solved based on three of the $(n_s - n_E - n_K)$ governing transport equations. Since the number of the governing equations, which is equal to the number of the components, is usually greater than three (i.e., the number of the phases), we need to select three governing equations to solve the three primary independent variables stored in \mathbf{x} . We use the governing equations based on the mass balances for (w, c, m) components. Second, the secondary independent variables, stored in \mathbf{y} , are explicitly calculated based on the flux and mass composition, which can be calculated with the updated primary independent variables in the first step. Third, repeat the first and second steps until the solution converges.

To close the transport system we need constitution equations. The constitution equation for solving partial equilibrium reactions is the Algorithm MAL-PE (see Table 4.2). From this algorithm we can calculate dependent variables \mathbf{z} from primary independent variables \mathbf{x} and secondary independent variables \mathbf{y} . The constitution equations for the density and viscosity are given in Appendix A, in which the mass composition of the liquid phase has been calculated with Algorithm MAL-PE. The saturation and the relative permeability are calculated with the model given in Appendix C. For the liquid phases, the discharge rate (\mathbf{q}_α , $\alpha = l, g$) is given as extended Darcy's law

$$\mathbf{q}_\alpha = -\frac{\kappa_{r\alpha}}{\mu_\alpha} \kappa (\nabla p_\alpha - \rho_\alpha g \nabla z), \quad (4.41)$$

where, κ_r [-] is the relative permeability; μ [pa · s] is the viscosity; κ [m²] is the intrinsic permeability; p [pa] is the pressure; z [m] is the depth; and g [m · s⁻²] is the gravitational acceleration.

Newton-Raphson method is used to calculate the independent variables (p_l, p_g, ϕ) in Equation (4.39). Because one injection well can pierce more than one grid, it is better

to write the injection well separately (c.f. Equation (2.31)). The system of governing equations (4.39) and (2.31) is rewritten as

$$\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (4.42)$$

with

$$[\mathbf{x}] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_l \\ \mathbf{p}_g \\ \phi \\ \mathbf{p}_{bh} \end{bmatrix}; [\mathbf{y}] = [\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_c]^t; [\mathcal{F}] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{F}_w \\ \mathcal{F}_c \\ \mathcal{F}_m \\ \mathcal{F}_W \end{bmatrix}; \quad (4.43)$$

where, the governing equations for the injection wells (\mathbf{f}_W) and their bottom hole pressures (\mathbf{p}_{bh}) are used to distinguish the governing equations and pressures for the field grids. Here, \mathcal{F}_w , \mathcal{F}_c and \mathcal{F}_m , respectively, store the \mathcal{F}_w , \mathcal{F}_c and \mathcal{F}_m (c.f. Equation (4.39)) for all the field grids. Similarly, \mathbf{p}_l , \mathbf{p}_g and ϕ , respectively, store the liquid pressure, gas pressure and porosity for all the field grids.

The Newton-Raphson solution of Equation (4.42) is given as

$$\mathbf{J}^{n+1,k} [\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k} = -[\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k}, \quad (4.44)$$

where the Jacobian matrix

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{J}^{n+1,k} &= \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right]^{n+1,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \mathbf{p}_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \mathbf{p}_{bh}} \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{11} & \mathbf{M}_{12} & \mathbf{M}_{13} & \mathbf{M}_{1W} \\ \mathbf{M}_{21} & \mathbf{M}_{22} & \mathbf{M}_{23} & \mathbf{M}_{2W} \\ \mathbf{M}_{31} & \mathbf{M}_{32} & \mathbf{M}_{33} & \mathbf{M}_{3W} \\ \mathbf{M}_{W1} & \mathbf{M}_{W2} & \mathbf{M}_{W3} & \mathbf{M}_{WW} \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k} = \mathbf{M}^{n+1,k}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.45)$$

Here, we only give the key information on calculating Jacobian matrix (4.45). During the calculation of \mathbf{J} , we should bear in mind that the density and viscosity of the liquid phase is affected by the dependent variables stored in \mathbf{z} , which is affected by the gas pressure. Thus, Jacobian matrix (4.45) should account for

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{z}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}, \frac{\partial \rho_l}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{\partial \rho_l}{\partial \mathbf{z}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{z}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} \text{ and } \frac{\partial \mu_l}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{\partial \mu_l}{\partial \mathbf{z}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{z}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}, \quad (4.46)$$

where, $\partial \mathbf{z} / \partial \mathbf{p}_g$ is solved numerically. With the primary independent variables stored in \mathbf{x}

and secondary independent variables stored in \mathbf{y} , we can calculate the dependent variables stored in \mathbf{z} . Then only change the gas pressure by $\delta\mathbf{p}_g$ and again calculate the dependent variables \mathbf{z}' with \mathbf{y} and \mathbf{x}' ; in \mathbf{x}' the gas pressure is replaced with $\mathbf{p}'_g = \mathbf{p}_g + \delta\mathbf{p}_g$. $\partial\mathbf{z}/\partial\mathbf{p}_g$ is then given as

$$\frac{\partial\mathbf{z}}{\partial\mathbf{p}_g} = \frac{\mathbf{z}' - \mathbf{z}}{\delta\mathbf{p}_g}. \quad (4.47)$$

Having obtained $[\delta\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k}$ with Equation (3.34), we can update $[\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k}$ according to

$$[\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k+1} = [\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k} + [\delta\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k}. \quad (4.48)$$

As can be seen from the foregoing calculation, we have to calculate dependent variable \mathbf{z} before we calculate the primary variable \mathbf{x} . When \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{z} are updated, we then calculate the flux and dispersion tensor of each interface. The secondary independent variables (i.e., masses of the kinetic species and conservative components) are then updated with

$$[\xi_k]^{n+1,k+1} = [\xi_k]^n - \Delta t^{n+1} \cdot \sum_{\alpha=l,g,s} \left[\nabla \cdot (\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^k \mathbf{q}_\alpha) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_\alpha \mathbf{D}_\alpha \rho_\alpha \nabla X_\alpha^k) \right]^n + \Delta t^{n+1} \cdot \sum_{\alpha=l,g,s} [Q_\alpha^k]^n, \quad (4.49)$$

$$[u_c]^{n+1,k+1} = [u_c]^n - \Delta t^{n+1} \cdot \sum_{\alpha=l,g,s} \left[\nabla \cdot (\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^c \mathbf{q}_\alpha) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_\alpha \mathbf{D}_\alpha \rho_\alpha \nabla X_\alpha^c) \right]^{n+1,k+1} + \Delta t^{n+1} \cdot \sum_{\beta=1}^{n_s} [U_{c\beta} Q_\alpha^\beta]^{n+1,k+1}, \quad (4.50)$$

where, superscript n and k denote the time step and iteration step, respectively; Δt^{n+1} is the length of the time step. Here, for transport of the conservative components we use the backward implicit method, but for the transport of the kinetic species we use forward explicit method. We note that in calculating the transport of kinetic species, we do not include the source term due to kinetic reaction, because the kinetic reaction has already been implicitly included in the chemical reaction module. The updated \mathbf{y} is then used to calculate the \mathbf{z} when we calculate the Jacobian matrix.

The Newton-Raphson iteration is terminated if the maximum change of the gas and liquid pressures is smaller than the tolerance value ϵ_p , or if the maximum residual value is smaller than the tolerance value ϵ_{err} .

The initial distributions of the primary and secondary independent variables are obtained as follows. The liquid and gas pressures are easily obtained from the density and depth, increasing in the downward direction due to gravity (c.f. Equations (2.29) and (2.30)). We give an initial gas and liquid pressures at the top layer of the domain, from which we could calculate the mass fractions of all species (X_α^β) and components (X_α^c) based on the equilibrium reaction. With X_α^β and pressures, we can calculate the densities of liquid and gas phases. Then with densities and X_α^c , we can calculate the mass of the

component u_c and thus all species (ξ). The aforementioned process is repeated to adjust the gas and liquid pressures until they do not change, and we move to the next layer according to Equations (2.29) and (2.30). This algorithm is given as Subroutine I3F in Table 4.5. The natural geological system has been assumed to be in equilibrium state before perturbation.

Table 4.3: Subroutine NR3F. Newton-Raphson algorithm for reactive three-phase flow system.

Input: primary independent variables $[\mathbf{p}_l; \mathbf{p}_g; \phi; \mathbf{p}_{bh}]^n$, secondary independent variables $[\xi_k, \mathbf{u}_c]^n$; dependent variables $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^k, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^c, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^x]^n$ and other dependent variables $[\xi_\beta]^n, \boldsymbol{\kappa}^n, [\rho_\alpha]^n, [\mu_\alpha]^n$ and $[\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^n$; time step Δt^n ; grid system \mathbf{G} , which includes initial permeability $\boldsymbol{\kappa}^0$ and initial porosity ϕ^0 ; and injection rate $\mathbf{Q}_{W,\alpha}$
0: set $k = 0$; $N_{kmax} = 15$; $[\delta \mathbf{p}_g]^{n+1,0} = [\delta \mathbf{p}_l]^{n+1,0} = [\delta \mathbf{p}_{bh}]^{n+1,0} = \text{inf}$; $[\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,0} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_l \\ \mathbf{p}_g \\ \phi \\ \mathbf{p}_{bh} \end{bmatrix}^n; [\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,0} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{F}_w \\ \mathcal{F}_c \\ \mathcal{F}_m \\ \mathcal{F}_W \end{bmatrix}^n = \mathbf{0};$ $[\rho_\alpha, \mu_\alpha, \mathbf{S}_\alpha, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_\alpha, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_{r\alpha}, \mathbf{q}_\alpha]^{n+1,0} = [\rho_\alpha, \mu_\alpha, \mathbf{S}_\alpha, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_\alpha, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_{r\alpha}, \mathbf{q}_\alpha]^n;$ $[\mathbf{y}]^{n+1,0} = [\xi_k, \mathbf{u}_c]^n; [\mathbf{z}]^{n+1,0} = [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^k, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^c, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^x]^n;$ % here, \mathcal{F}_α ($\alpha = w, c, m$) is calculated with equation (4.39) and \mathcal{F}_W is calculated with equation (2.31);
1: while $\max([\delta \mathbf{p}_l]^{n+1,k}, [\delta \mathbf{p}_g]^{n+1,k}, [\delta \mathbf{p}_{bh}]^{n+1,k}) > \epsilon_p$ & $k < N_{kmax}$, do steps 2 to 3 2: sequentially calculate (1) the dependent variables $[\mathbf{z}]^{n+1,k+1} = [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^k, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^c, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^x]^{n+1,k+1}, [\xi_\beta]^{n+1,k+1}$, and the derivatives of \mathbf{z} over gas pressure $\left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{z}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}\right]^{n+1,k+1} = \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_\alpha^k}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_\alpha^c}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_\alpha^x}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g}\right]^{n+1,k+1}$ with Algorithm MAL-PE given in Table 4.2, (2) the fluid densities ($[\rho_\alpha]^{n+1,k}$) and their derivatives over the primary independent variables with the formulas in Appendix A, (3) fluid viscosities ($[\mu_\alpha]^{n+1,k}$) and their derivatives over the primary independent variables with the formulas in Appendix A, (4) saturations ($[\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^{n+1,k}$) and their derivatives over the primary independent variables with retention curve given in Appendix C, (5) the intrinsic permeability ($[\boldsymbol{\kappa}]^{n+1,k}$) and its derivatives over the primary independent variables with Közeny-Carman model given by formula (3.14), (6) relative permeabilities ($[\boldsymbol{\kappa}_{r\alpha}]^{n+1,k}$) and their derivatives over the primary
Continued on next page

Table 4.3: Subroutine NR3F. Newton-Raphson algorithm for reactive three-phase flow system. - continued

independent variables with the models given in Appendix C,

(7) the fluxes ($[\mathbf{q}_\alpha]^{n+1,k}$) of each face and their derivatives over the primary independent variables with Darcy's law,

and (8) the dispersion tensor (\mathbf{D}) and its derivatives over the primary independent variables with the model given in Appendix B; then calculate

the primary independent variables with $[\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k} = -[[\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \mathbf{x}}]^{n+1,k}]^{-1}[\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k}$ and $[\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k+1} = [\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k} + [\delta \mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k}$, where, residual vector ($[\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k}$) and the Jacobian matrix ($[\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \mathbf{x}}]^{n+1,k}$) are given as

$$[\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{F}_w \\ \mathcal{F}_c \\ \mathcal{F}_m \\ \mathcal{F}_W \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k}; \quad [\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \mathbf{x}}]^{n+1,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial p_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial p_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_w}{\partial p_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial p_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial p_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_c}{\partial p_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial p_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial p_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_m}{\partial p_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial p_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial p_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial p_{bh}} \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k};$$

calculate the secondary independent variables $[\mathbf{y}]^{n+1,k+1}$ with Equations (4.49) and (4.50);

3: $k = k + 1$;

4: endwhile¹;

5: if $k = N_{kmax}=15$ % the algorithm does not converge after N_{kmax} NR iterations;

6: then $\Delta t^n = t_s$; and go to step 0; % reduce Δt^n to a very small value t_s (e.g., $t_s=0.1$ second) and restart from t^n with t_s ;

7: endif⁵;

$$8: \begin{bmatrix} p_l \\ p_g \\ \phi \\ p_{bh} \end{bmatrix}^{n+1} = [\mathbf{x}]^{n+1,k+1}; \quad [\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_C]^{n+1} = [\mathbf{y}]^{n+1,k+1}; \quad [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^k, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^C, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^\mathcal{X}]^{n+1} = [\mathbf{z}]^{n+1,k+1};$$

$$[\boldsymbol{\rho}_\alpha, \boldsymbol{\mu}_\alpha, \mathbf{S}_\alpha, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_\alpha, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_{r\alpha}, \mathbf{q}_\alpha]^{n+1} = [\boldsymbol{\rho}_\alpha, \boldsymbol{\mu}_\alpha, \mathbf{S}_\alpha, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_\alpha, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_{r\alpha}, \mathbf{q}_\alpha]^{n+1,k}$$

$$9: \text{calculate } \Delta \mathbf{p}^n = [p_l; p_g; p_{bh}]^{n+1} - [p_l; p_g; p_{bh}]^n; \quad \Delta \mathbf{S}_\alpha^n = [\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^{n+1} - [\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^n;$$

% this will be used to update the time step;

Output: $[p_l; p_g; \phi; p_{bh}]^{n+1}$; $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_k; \mathbf{u}_C]^{n+1}$; $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^k, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^C, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^\mathcal{X}]^{n+1}$; $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta]^{n+1}$;
 $[\boldsymbol{\rho}_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $[\boldsymbol{\mu}_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $[\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $[\mathbf{q}_\alpha]^{n+1}$; $\Delta \mathbf{p}^n$; $\Delta \mathbf{S}_\alpha^n$; and Δt^n ;

Table 4.4: Main routine for kinetic three-phase flow model.

Require: $[\mathbf{p}_l]^{top,0}$, $[\mathbf{p}_g]^{top,0}$, \mathbf{p}_{bh}^0 , $\mathbf{Q}_{W,\alpha}$, $t^0 = 0$ and Δt^0 ; the grid discretization (\mathbf{G}); the field property (i.e., initial permeability κ^0 and initial porosity ϕ^0);
0: initialize the system with Subroutine I3F, given in Table: 4.5; $n = 0$;
1: while $t^n < t_{tot}$,
2: update primary independent variables $[\mathbf{x}]^n$, i.e. $[\mathbf{p}_l; \mathbf{p}_g; \phi; \mathbf{p}_{bh}]^n$ (c.f. (4.42) to (4.48)), secondary independent variables $[\mathbf{y}]^n$, i.e., $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_C]^n$ (c.f. (4.36)), dependent variables $[\mathbf{z}]^n$, i.e., $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^k, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^C, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^X]^n$ (c.f. (4.37)) and probably Δt^n with Subroutine NR3F, given in Table 4.3; in this procedure, dependent variables density ($[\boldsymbol{\rho}_\alpha]^n$), viscosity ($[\boldsymbol{\mu}_\alpha]^n$), saturation ($[\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^n$) and flux of each phase through each face ($[\mathbf{q}_\alpha]^n$) are calculated and saved; the mass of each species in the cell ($[\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta]^n$) is also calculated and saved to offer a warm initial guess of the species in calculating the partial equilibrium chemical system.
3: $t^{n+1} = t^n + \Delta t^n$;
4: update Δt^n with Subroutine UT given in Table 2.4;
5: $n=n+1$;
6: endwhile ¹ .
Output: $[\mathbf{p}_l; \mathbf{p}_g; \phi; \mathbf{p}_{bh}]^n$; $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_C]^n$; $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^k, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^C, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^X]^n$; $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta]^n$; $[\boldsymbol{\rho}_\alpha]^n$; $[\boldsymbol{\mu}_\alpha]^n$; $[\mathbf{S}_\alpha]^n$; $[\mathbf{q}_\alpha]^n$.

4.2.2 Specific Reactive Three-Phase Flow Model for GCS System

Partial Equilibrium Chemical System

In this section we employ the foregoing method to GCS, which is a reactive three-phase flow process with two fluid phases (i.e., gas and liquid) and one solid phase. We assume the gas phase only contains $CO_2(g)$, the liquid phase contains multiple aqueous species, and the solid phase only contains calcite. This chapter uses a chemical system similar to that in Chapter 3. The only difference is that in this chapter, the heterogeneous reaction between calcite and brine is treated as kinetic reaction while the other reactions are still treated as equilibrium reactions (*Steefel and Van Cappellen, 1990; Steefel and Lasaga, 1994*). The chemical system is given as

In this case, we consider 9 reactive species: H_2O , $CO_2(g)$, $CaCO_3(s)$, H^+ , Ca^{2+} , HCO_3^- , $CO_2(aq)$, CO_3^{2-} and OH^- . We also add Na^+ and Cl^- to adjust the salinity of the brine. This is necessary because the salinity of brine can significantly affect the dissolution of

CO_2 by changing the ionic strength, as well as change the brine viscosity and density. Here, we assume that the molalities of Na^+ and Cl^- are constant, so they will not appear in the reaction or transport equations. The reactions have been classified into kinetic reaction and equilibrium reactions to increase the efficiency (*Helgeson, 1968; Helgeson et al., 1969; Langmuir, 1996; Lasaga, 2014; Leal, 2014*). We did this classification of the partial equilibrium system based on the fact that the time scale of the heterogeneous reaction involving solid calcite could be similar to the time scale of transport, while the time scales of the rest reactions are negligible. This assumption has been widely used in geological chemical systems (*Saaltink et al., 1998, 2001*). We note that the geological system (4.51) could be modified according to the field data on the fluid and rock compositions (*Forster et al., 2006*). For instance, we can add the dissolution/precipitation of magnesite and dolomite to (4.51), if the field data show the rock-forming mineral contains high mass fractions of magnesite and dolomite.

The stoichiometric matrices for the kinetic reaction and equilibrium reactions in the partial equilibrium chemical system (4.51) are, respectively,

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}_k = \begin{matrix} & H_2O & CO_2(g) & CaCO_3(s) & H^+ & Ca^{2+} & HCO_3^- & CO_2(aq) & CO_3^{2-} & OH^- \\ K1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & -1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{matrix} \quad (4.52)$$

and

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}_e = \begin{matrix} & H_2O & CO_2(g) & CaCO_3(s) & H^+ & Ca^{2+} & HCO_3^- & CO_2(aq) & CO_3^{2-} & OH^- \\ E1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ E2 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ E3 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ E4 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{matrix} . \quad (4.53)$$

The stoichiometric matrix for partial equilibrium chemical system (4.51) is thus

$$\boldsymbol{\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\nu}_k \\ \boldsymbol{\nu}_e \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.54)$$

When calculating the equilibrium reaction we only need the columns corresponding to the equilibrium species in $\boldsymbol{\nu}_e$; that is

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}_{ee} = \begin{matrix} & H_2O & CO_2(g) & H^+ & HCO_3^- & CO_2(aq) & CO_3^{2-} & OH^- \\ E1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ E2 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ E3 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ E4 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{matrix} . \quad (4.55)$$

The kernel matrix (\mathbf{U}) for the mass components has been given in Chapter 3:

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{array}{c} \\ w \\ c \\ m \\ \text{pH} \end{array} \begin{array}{cccccccccc} H_2O & CO_2(g) & CaCO_3(s) & H^+ & Ca^{2+} & HCO_3^- & CO_2(aq) & CO_3^{2-} & OH^- \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.44950 & 0.29525 & 0 & 0.30020 & 1.05921 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1.09811 & 0.7212 & 1 & 0.73339 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 2.49730 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0.05029 & -0.01652 & 0 & -0.03359 & -0.05925 \end{array} . \quad (4.56)$$

The kernel matrix for mass components should be further split into kinetic kernel matrix (\mathbf{U}_k) and equilibrium kernel matrix (\mathbf{U}_e):

$$\mathbf{U}_k = \begin{array}{c} \\ m \end{array} \begin{array}{cccccccccc} H_2O & CO_2(g) & CaCO_3(s) & H^+ & Ca^{2+} & HCO_3^- & CO_2(aq) & CO_3^{2-} & OH^- \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 2.49730 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \quad (4.57)$$

and

$$\mathbf{U}_e = \begin{array}{c} \\ w \\ c \\ \text{pH} \end{array} \begin{array}{cccccccccc} H_2O & CO_2(g) & CaCO_3(s) & H^+ & Ca^{2+} & HCO_3^- & CO_2(aq) & CO_3^{2-} & OH^- \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.44950 & 0.29525 & 0 & 0.30020 & 1.05921 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1.09811 & 0.7212 & 1 & 0.73339 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0.05029 & -0.01652 & 0 & -0.03359 & -0.05925 \end{array} . \quad (4.58)$$

The columns corresponding to the kinetic and equilibrium species are further extracted from \mathbf{U}_e :

$$\mathbf{U}_{ek} = \begin{array}{c} \\ w \\ c \\ \text{pH} \end{array} \begin{array}{cc} CaCO_3(s) & Ca^{2+} \\ 0 & -0.44950 \\ 0 & -1.09811 \\ 0 & 0.05029 \end{array} \quad (4.59)$$

and

$$\mathbf{U}_{ee} = \begin{array}{c} \\ w \\ c \\ \text{pH} \end{array} \begin{array}{ccccccc} H_2O & CO_2(g) & H^+ & HCO_3^- & CO_2(aq) & CO_3^{2-} & OH^- \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0.29525 & 0 & 0.30020 & 1.05921 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0.7212 & 1 & 0.73339 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -0.01652 & 0 & -0.03359 & -0.05925 \end{array} . \quad (4.60)$$

In virtue of the kinetic reaction rate for calcite, which can be calculated with the empirical model in Section 4.2.1, we can solve the partial equilibrium system by using Algorithm MAL-PE given in Table 4.2. To solve this chemical system we need ($n_s - n_E = 9 - 4 = 5$) independent variables. Our system, however, has 2 kinetic species ($CaCO_3(s)$ and Ca^{2+}) and 4 components (w, c, m, pH), which means we need to select 5 independent variables from these 6 candidate independent variables. We note that the 4 components must be used to assure the transport equations are independent on all the chemical

reactions. If two kinetic species are involved in one kinetic reaction, we only need to know the mass of one kinetic species and the other kinetic species can be calculated by using the conservative component related to the kinetic reaction and the designated kinetic species. Here, we drop the mass of kinetic species Ca^{2+} , because it can be calculated with the mineral component (c.f. the third row of kernel matrix \mathbf{U}) and the mass of kinetic species $CaCO_3(s)$. Then the secondary independent variables, which are used to solve the chemical reactions, are

$$\mathbf{y} = [\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_c]^t = [\boldsymbol{\xi}_{calcite}, \mathbf{u}_w, \mathbf{u}_c, \mathbf{u}_m, \mathbf{u}_{pH}]^t. \quad (4.61)$$

Transport Equations

As above-mentioned, because this system has three phases, we need three primary independent variables, which means we need three governing equations to solve the primary independent variables. Here, the injection well is considered so we also need to introduce the governing equation for the injection well and the bottom hole pressure, \mathbf{p}_{bh} . We prefer to separate the bottom hole pressure of the injection well from the pressure of the field grid. Therefore, we have in total four primary independent variables

$$[\mathbf{x}] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_l \\ \mathbf{p}_g \\ \phi \\ \mathbf{p}_{bh} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.62)$$

Then we should determine how to construct the corresponding four governing equations. Here, three governing equations are constructed based on the mass balances of three components (w, c, m), which, respectively, correspond to the major compositions of the liquid, gas and solid phases. The fourth governing equation is constructed based on the mass balance of the $CO_2(g)$ in the injection well. The four governing equations are

$$0 = \mathcal{F}_w = \frac{\partial(\phi S_l \rho_l X_l^w)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (X_l^w \rho_l \mathbf{q}_l) - \nabla \cdot (\phi S_l \rho_l \mathbf{D}_l \nabla X_l^w) - \sum_{mw=1}^{MW} [U_{w,C}(Q^C)^{(mw)}]_{n+1,k+1}, \quad (4.63)$$

$$0 = \mathcal{F}_c = \frac{\partial(\phi S_l \rho_l X_l^g)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\phi S_g \rho_g)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (X_l^g \rho_l \mathbf{q}_l) + \nabla \cdot (\rho_g \mathbf{q}_g) - \nabla \cdot (\phi S_l \rho_l \mathbf{D}_l \nabla X_l^g) - \sum_{mw=1}^{MW} [U_{c,C}(Q^C)^{(mw)}]_{n+1,k+1}, \quad (4.64)$$

$$0 = \mathcal{F}_m = \frac{\partial(\phi S_l \rho_m X_l^m)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial((1-\phi)\rho_m)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (X_l^m \rho_l \mathbf{q}_l) - \nabla \cdot (\phi S_l \rho_l \mathbf{D}_l \nabla X_l^m) - \sum_{mw=1}^{MW} [U_{m,C}(Q^C)^{(mw)}]_{n+1,k+1}, \quad (4.65)$$

$$0 = \mathcal{F}_W = -Q^C + \sum_{mw=1}^{MW} \left[\rho_{\alpha,W} W I^{(mw)} \frac{K_{rgMAX}}{\mu_{\alpha}} (p_{bh} - \rho_{g,W} g (z_{bh} - z^{(mw)}) - p_g^{mw}) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{mw}) \right], \quad (4.66)$$

and the source term for m -th grid pierced by the injection well can be given as

$$(Q^C)^{(mw)} = \rho_{g,W} W I^{(mw)} \frac{K_{rgMAX}}{\mu_{\alpha}} (p_{bh} - \rho_{g,W} g (z_{bh} - z^{(mw)}) - p_g^{mw}) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{mw}), \quad (4.67)$$

where, the superscript mw denotes the mw th pierced grid, Q^C denotes the source rate of $CO_2(g)$ and $U_{c,C}$ ($C = w, c, m$) means the $CO_2(g)$ in component C ; here, $U_{c,C} = 1$ while $U_{w,C} = U_{m,C} = 0$. Here, we have assumed that the gas phase only contains $CO_2(g)$, the solid phase only contains calcite, and we only inject pure $CO_2(g)$.

Dependent variables (\mathbf{z}), which are used to assist the construction of the Jacobian matrix, are selected as

$$[\mathbf{z}] = [\mathbf{X}_l^w, \mathbf{X}_l^c, \mathbf{X}_l^m, \mathbf{X}_l^{pH}, \mathbf{X}_l^C] = [\mathbf{X}_l^C, \mathbf{X}_l^C], \mathcal{C} = w, c, m, pH, \quad (4.68)$$

where we also use the mass fraction of $CO_2(aq)$ (X_l^C) in liquid phase. This is because X_l^C could affect the density and viscosity of the brine.

When we construct the Jacobian matrix for Equations (4.63) to (4.67), we consider the effect of gas pressure on the mass fraction of the dependent variables \mathbf{z} ,

$$\left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{z}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_g} \right] = \left[\partial \mathbf{X}_l^C / \partial \mathbf{p}_g, \partial \mathbf{X}_l^C / \partial \mathbf{p}_g \right], \mathcal{C} = w, c, m, pH, \quad (4.69)$$

which is calculated with the Algorithm MAL-PE given in Table 4.2.

When we have solved the four primary independent variables based on the four governing equations (4.63) to (4.66), we then update the flow fields (i.e., convection flux, dispersion flux and source term), with which we can update the secondary independent variables stored in \mathbf{y} (i.e., one kinetic species and four components) with

$$[\xi_{calcite}]^{n+1,k} = [\xi_{calcite}]^n, \quad (4.70)$$

$$[u_w]^{n+1,k+1} = [u_w]^n - \Delta t^{n+1} [\nabla \cdot (\rho_l X_l^w \mathbf{q}_l) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_l \mathbf{D}_l \rho_l \nabla X_l^w)]^{n+1,k+1} + \Delta t^{n+1} \sum_{mw=1}^{MW} [U_{w,C} Q^C]^{n+1,k+1}, \quad (4.71)$$

$$[u_c]^{n+1,k+1} = [u_c]^n - \Delta t^{n+1} [\nabla \cdot (\rho_l X_l^c \mathbf{q}_l) + \nabla \cdot (\rho_g \mathbf{q}_g) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_l \mathbf{D}_l \rho_l \nabla X_l^c)]^{n+1,k+1} + \Delta t^{n+1} \sum_{mw=1}^{MW} [U_{c,C} Q^C]^{n+1,k+1}, \quad (4.72)$$

$$[u_m]^{n+1,k+1} = [u_m]^n - \Delta t^{n+1} [\nabla \cdot (\rho_l X_l^m \mathbf{q}_l) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_l \mathbf{D}_l \rho_l \nabla X_l^m)]^{n+1,k+1} + \Delta t^{n+1} \sum_{mw=1}^{MW} [U_{m,C} Q^C]^{n+1,k+1}, \quad (4.73)$$

$$[u_{pH}]^{n+1,k+1} = [u_{pH}]^n - \Delta t^{n+1} [\nabla \cdot (\rho_l X_l^{pH} \mathbf{q}_l) - \nabla \cdot (\phi_l \mathbf{D}_l \rho_l \nabla X_l^{pH})]^{n+1,k+1} + \Delta t^{n+1} \sum_{mw=1}^{MW} [U_{pH,C} Q^C]^{n+1,k+1}. \quad (4.74)$$

The secondary independent variables are used to solve the chemical system (c.f. Subroutine NR3F in Table 4.3).

We note that, in Equation (4.70), the mass of calcite species in the $(n + 1)$ th step is always equal to its mass in the previous n th step, so that the kinetic reaction starts from the initial amount; otherwise, if we have n_I Newton-Raphson iterations, the reaction time is actually $n_I \cdot \Delta t$. Besides, when calculating the transport of the kinetic species calcite, we do not consider its chemical reaction, because all the chemical reactions are calculated in the chemical reaction module; however, the mass balance of kinetic species is satisfied because the kinetic component (u_m) is used to calculate the transport of the kinetic species. This is very important. This reactive flow system can be solved with the main routine given in Table 4.4

4.3 Benchmark Test and Simple Sensitive Analysis

The developed numerical model is tested against the one-dimensional theoretical solution proposed by *McWhorter and Sunada* (1990), which is given in Appendix H, though we can also test against the two-dimensional theoretical solution by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006). After having performed benchmark against the theoretical model, this section gives simple sensitive analysis on the effect of the kinetic reaction rate on the reactive transport process.

4.3.1 Setup Description

The one-dimensional domain is shown in Figure 4.1. The descriptions of the domain design, the fluid characters and chemical characters are given as follows.

Domain design: The left boundary is closed while the right boundary has constant liquid pressure, zero gradients of saturation and porosity. One injection well, of which the radius is r_w , is added to the left of the domain. The mass injection rate of CO_2 is $Q_{g,m} = \bar{\rho}_g A / \sqrt{t}$, from which we can see that the injection rate decreases from the initial infinite value to zero; here, $\bar{\rho}_g$ is the mean gas density, and A depends on the maximum expected gas saturation, S_{g0} , which appears at the injection point, i.e., $x = 0$

Table 4.5: Subroutine I3F. Initialization for reactive three-phase flow system.

Input: initial liquid pressure of the top cells $[\mathbf{p}_l]^{top,0}$, initial gas pressure of the top cells $[\mathbf{p}_g]^{top,0}$ and grid system \mathbf{G} (e.g., the number of layers n_L , the (x, y, z) location of each cell, etc.);
1: $\mathbf{p}_l^{i=1} = \mathbf{p}_l^{top,0}, \mathbf{p}_g^{i=1} = \mathbf{p}_g^{top,0}$; % here, superscript i denotes the i th layer; 2: for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n_L - 1$, do 3 to 9; % n_L denotes number of layers; 3: $\mathbf{p}_l^{i+1,j=0} = \mathbf{p}_l^i, \mathbf{p}_g^{i+1,j=0} = \mathbf{p}_g^i$; 4: calculate $\mathbf{p}_l^{i+1,j+1}, \mathbf{p}_g^{i+1,j+1}$ with Equations (2.29) and (2.30); calculate $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_C]^{i+1,j+1}, [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^k, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^C, \mathbf{X}_\alpha^\mathcal{X}]^{i+1,j+1}, [\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta]^{i+1,j+1}$ with Algorithm MAL-E2 given in Table 4.1; % initially, the system is at equilibrium state; calculate the densities $\rho_l^{i+1,j+1}$ and $\rho_g^{i+1,j+1}$ with Equations (A.5) and (A.12); calculate the viscosities $\mu_l^{i+1,j+1}$ and $\mu_g^{i+1,j+1}$ with Equations (A.16) and (A.17); % Algorithm MAL-E2 is used to solve the chemical reactions because initially the system is assumed to be in equilibrium state. 5: while $\max(\mathbf{p}_l^{i+1,j+1} - \mathbf{p}_l^{i+1,j}, \mathbf{p}_g^{i+1,j+1} - \mathbf{p}_g^{i+1,j}) > \epsilon_p$, do 6 to 7; % ϵ_p is the tolerance value; 6: $j=j+1$; 7: repeat Step 4; 8: endwhile ⁵ ; 9: $\mathbf{p}_{l,g}^{i+1} = \mathbf{p}_{l,g}^{i+1,j+1}, \rho_{l,g}^{i+1} = \rho_{l,g}^{i+1,j+1}, [\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta]^{i+1} = [\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta]^{i+1,j+1}$, $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_C]^{i+1} = [\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_C]^{i+1,j+1}, [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^{i+1} = [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^{i+1,j+1}$; 10: endfor ² ; 11: $[\mathbf{p}_{l,g}]^0 = [\mathbf{p}_{l,g}^1; \mathbf{p}_{l,g}^2; \dots; \mathbf{p}_{l,g}^{n_L}]$, $[\rho_{l,g}]^0 = [\rho_{l,g}^1; \rho_{l,g}^2; \dots; \rho_{l,g}^{n_L}]$, $[\mu_{l,g}]^0 = [\mu_{l,g}^1; \mu_{l,g}^2; \dots; \mu_{l,g}^{n_L}]$, $[\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^0 = [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^1; [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^2; \dots; [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{l,C,\mathcal{X}}]^{n_L}$, $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_C]^0 = [\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_C]^1; [\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_C]^2; \dots; [\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_C]^{n_L}$; $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta]^0 = [\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta^1; \boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta^2; \dots; \boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta^{n_L}]$; Output: $[\mathbf{p}_{l,g}]^0, [\rho_{l,g}]^0, [\mu_{l,g}]^0, [\mathbf{X}_\alpha^{k,C,\mathcal{X}}]^0, [\boldsymbol{\xi}_k, \mathbf{u}_C]^0$ and $[\boldsymbol{\xi}_\beta]^0$.

Figure 4.1: Setup design.

(c.f. Appendix H). The initial time step Δt^0 should be as small as possible to capture the large initial injection rate.

Fluid characters: The relative permeability and retention curves are given by van Genuchten model (c.f. Appendix C), and (α_p, m_p) are the related parameters. The densities (ρ_l, ρ_g) and viscosities (μ_l, μ_g) are calculated with the empirical models given in Appendix A. The hydrodynamic dispersion is not included and only the molecular diffusion (D_m) is considered.

Chemical characters: We use the geochemical system given in Section 4.2.2. The dissolution of calcite is controlled by acid, neutral and carbonate kinetic mineral mechanisms, of which the rate constants at 25 °C are, respectively, $(k_{0,1}, k_{0,2}, k_{0,3})$. The activation energies of these three mechanisms are, respectively, (E_1, E_2, E_3) . θ_{H^+} is the exponent for acid kinetic mechanism and θ_{pCO_2} is the exponent for carbonate mechanism. The shape factor for the reactive surface area is η_V . The effective reactive area per volume of mineral is \mathcal{A}_s . We use different values of \mathcal{A}_s to adjust the kinetic reaction rate. The infinite value of \mathcal{A}_s means that the dissolution of calcite is treated as equilibrium reaction, while the zero value of \mathcal{A}_s means that the dissolution of calcite is not considered. The reference value of \mathcal{A}_s is $0.0469 \cdot 10^6$ [m⁻¹] (Vialle *et al.*, 2014). This value generates a very fast reaction rate. The aforementioned parameters are listed in Table 4.7

Initially, the liquid pressure and gas pressure are p_l^i and p_g^i , respectively, and the system is at equilibrium chemical state. The molality of *NaCl* is constant m_l^S and the temperature is constant T_c . The simulation is terminated at T_s when the saturation change at the inlet becomes insignificant.

Regarding the benchmark test, the numerical model and the theoretical model are not totally the same, but the major characters are consistent. The theoretical model is a simple conservative incompressible two-phase flow model. Slightly different from the theoretical model, the numerical considers the reactions among the gas, liquid and rock, as well as the compressibilities of the fluids. However, the two solutions are comparable because the main influencing factors- the injection rate, the relative permeability and retention curves- are the same. The discrepancies of density and viscosity due to the compressibility is very small. We also minimize the effect of gaseous *CO*₂ on the chemical reaction, by using already quasi *CO*₂-saturated brine, i.e., the initial gas pressure is close to the liquid pressure. In the benchmark simulations, the initial gas pressure is set as 145 bar which is close to the liquid pressure 150 bar. Therefore, we can use the theoretical solution as a benchmark for the numerical model. As we will see, the numerical result agrees well with the theoretical one.

Regarding the simple sensitive analysis, we only analyze the effect of kinetic reaction rate. To get an obvious comparison between different kinetic reaction rates, we set initial gas pressure to 1 [bar], which is much smaller than the initial liquid pressure, 150 [bar].

Table 4.6: Parameter settings for the flow system.

Parameters	Symbol	Units	Values
Section area	A_f	[m ²]	1
Length	L	[m]	10
Grid discretization	N	[-]	500
Initial permeability	κ^0	[m ²]	1×10^{-11}
Initial porosity	ϕ^0	[-]	0.2
Initial liquid pressure	p_l^i	[bar]	150
Initial gas pressure	p_g^i	[bar]	145(1 ^a)
Initial brine/gas saturation	$(S_{l,i}, S_{g,i})$	[-]	(1,0)
Salinity	m_l^S	[molal]	0.5
Temperature	T_c	[°C]	60
Molecular diffusion coefficient	D_m	[m ² ·s ⁻¹]	10^{-9}
Mean brine/gas viscosity	$(\bar{\mu}_l, \bar{\mu}_g)$	[mpa·s]	(1.5,0.045)
Mean brine/gas density	$(\bar{\rho}_l, \bar{\rho}_g)$	[kg·m ⁻³]	(1010,590)
Parameter for Eq. (C.1)	α_p	[bar ⁻¹]	5
Parameter for Eq. (C.1)	m_p	[-]	0.8
Well radius	r_w	[m]	0.01
Max expected gas saturation	S_{g0}	[-]	0.101
Initial time step	Δt^0	[s]	10^{-6}
Reference injection rate	A	[kg·s ⁻¹]	0.1012
Total simulation time	T_s	[s]	9839

^a 1 bar is used for the test of the effect of reaction rate.

In addition to the reference value of $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^6$ [m⁻¹], we also use smaller values, $0.0469 \cdot 10^2$ and $0.0469 \cdot 10^{-2}$ [m⁻¹], for \mathcal{A}_s , to observe a visual effect of the kinetic reaction rate on the injection process. We also use $\mathcal{A}_s = 0$ [m⁻¹] to test if the program will give zero change of the porosity when there is no calcite dissolution.

4.3.2 Results

Benchmark with Theoretical Model by McWhorter and Sunada (1990)

The comparison of the saturation distribution calculated with the theoretical model by

Table 4.7: Parameter settings for kinetic reaction.

Parameter	Value
\mathcal{A}_s [m ⁻¹]	(inf, $0.0469 \cdot 10^6$, $0.0469 \cdot 10^2$, $0.0469 \cdot 10^{-2}$, 0) ^a
$\theta_{H^+}, \theta_{pCO_2}, \eta_V$ [-]	1, 1, 2/3
(E_1, E_2, E_3) [10 ³ J·mol ⁻¹]	(14.4, 23.5, 35.4)
$(k_{0,1}, k_{0,2}, k_{0,3})$ [mol·m ⁻² ·s ⁻¹]	($10^{-0.3}$, $10^{-5.81}$, $10^{-3.48}$)

^a different \mathcal{A}_s are used to adjust the reaction rate.

Figure 4.2: Comparison between the theoretical result by *McWhorter and Sunada* (1990) and the numerical results.

McWhorter and Sunada (1990) and the numerical results is given in Figure 4.2. In the numerical simulations the initial liquid pressure is 150 bar and initial gas pressure is 145 bar, which means the brine is almost saturated with CO_2 and it can only dissolve a very small amount of injected CO_2 . The numerical results are obtained when the reaction rate is zero and infinite, i.e., $\mathcal{A}_s = 0$ and inf . When the reaction rate is zero, we do not consider the calcite dissolution, while when the reaction rate is infinite, the precipitation/dissolution of calcite is at equilibrium state. From Figure 4.2, we can see that the numerical results agree very well with the theoretical solution. Because of very small dissolution of CO_2 into brine, the results from numerical simulations are slightly smaller than the theoretical solution, but the discrepancy between the numerical and theoretical results is negligible.

Simple Sensitive Analysis on Reaction Rate

We also analyze the effect of the kinetic reaction rate on CO_2 injection, by changing the reaction rate through changing the specific area, \mathcal{A}_s . In the following simulations, the initial gas pressure of the domain is set to 1 [bar], and initially the system is at chemical equilibrium state. The reference value of $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^6$ [m^{-1}] leads to a reaction time scale of around 10^{-3} [s] (c.f. Appendix G). This chemical reaction time scale is quite smaller than the transport time scale, which means the kinetic reaction is quasi equilibrium reaction.

The saturation distributions of gas phase are given in Figure 4.3, from which we can see that the results for different \mathcal{A}_s are quite the same. This means the dissolution of CO_2 is insensitive to the dissolution of calcite.

However, as can be seen from Figure 4.4, different \mathcal{A}_s can lead to significantly different changes of porosity, i.e., different dissolution of calcite. If we compare the porosity changes in Figure 4.4, we can find that the results for $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^6$ and $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^2$ are quite the same, and both of them are larger than the result for $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^{-2}$. This means that the kinetic dissolution of calcite can be treated as equilibrium reaction when $\mathcal{A}_s > 0.0469 \cdot 10^2$. When $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^{-2}$, the dissolution of calcite is so slow that we can only observe very small change of porosity, and the change of the porosity

Figure 4.3: Comparison of the effect of reaction rate on saturation.

decreases with the distance to the injection point because the time of exposure to the $CO_2(g)$ decreases with this distance. In Figure 4.4, we also show that the porosity change is around 10^{-14} , which is quite close to zero, when $\mathcal{A}_s = 0$. This means the precision of solution is at order of 10^{-14} when predicting the porosity change. The small change of the porosity can cause relatively large change of permeability, as can be seen from Figure 4.5.

From Figure 4.4, we can also find that the porosity change is very small even for the cases with fast reaction rates; this is because only injecting CO_2 cannot continuously change the saturation index of calcite in brine. To further increase the dissolution of the calcite, we need to inject water without Ca^{2+} . This indicates that the porosity change due to gas injection cannot be explained with the traditional erosion model, where acidified brine is continuously injected into the initially brine-saturated domain. The traditional model will significantly enhance the dissolution because the injected ‘fresh’ acidified brine does not contain Ca^{2+} .

The results for pH and molality of $CO_2(aq)$ are shown in Figures 4.6 and 4.7, from which we can see that the pH is higher when the kinetic reaction rate is high (i.e., \mathcal{A}_s is large), but the molalities of $CO_2(aq)$ are the same for all the cases. This is because the dissolution of CO_2 is fast equilibrium reaction, which instantly decreases the pH value, while the generated H^+ reacts with the calcite at different rates.

The gas pressure, as shown in Figure 4.8, is closely related to the molality of $CO_2(aq)$ given in Figure 4.7. The capillary pressure, given in Figure 4.9, is closely related to the saturation distribution given in Figure 4.3.

The reaction time scales are 10^{-3} and 10^1 [s] for $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^6$ and $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^2$, respectively, and the maximum transport time step is <60 [s]. This means that in the large scale simulation with large time step (e.g. 1 hour) the calcite dissolution can be fairly treated as equilibrium reaction. Finally, by observing that the gas saturation in the case with high initial gas pressure (c.f. Figure 4.2) is much larger than that in the case with low initial gas pressure (c.f. Figure 4.3), we can conclude that dissolution of CO_2 can strongly affect the GCS process.

 Figure 4.4: Comparison of the effect of reaction rate on porosity, ϕ .

 Figure 4.5: Comparison of the effect of reaction rate on permeability, κ .

Figure 4.6: Comparison of the effect of reaction rate on pH.

 Figure 4.7: Comparison of the effect of reaction rate on molality of $CO_2(aq)$.

Figure 4.9: Comparison of the effect of reaction rate on capillary pressure, p_c .

Figure 4.10: Setup design.

Figure 4.11: Initial distribution of log permeability ($\log \kappa_0$).

4.4 Simple Application to Analysis of Partial Dissolution

In GCS process, because the injected $CO_2(g)$ will indirectly react with the formation rock via dissolving into brine, it may change the formation porosity and permeability, developing high permeable channels that significantly affect the CO_2 migration process.

This section will apply the developed specific reactive multi-component three-phase flow model to qualitatively analyze of the effect of dissolution rate on the development of partial dissolution. In order to be consistent with the traditional study on partial dissolution, we also inject acidified brine rather than CO_2 gas. As such, we only have rock and brine phases.

4.4.1 Setup Description

The simulation domain is shown in Figure 4.10. The descriptions of the domain design, the fluid characters and chemical characters are given as follows.

Table 4.8: Parameter settings for the flow system.

Parameter	Symbol	Units	Values
Domain size	(L_x, L_y, L_z)	$[10^{-3}\text{m}]$	(20, 10, 5)
Grid discretization	(N_x, N_y, N_z)	[-]	(40,20,1)
Initial geometric mean permeability	κ_g^0	$[\text{m}^2]$	1×10^{-11}
Correlation length of permeability	(l_x^0, l_y^0)	$[10^{-3}\text{m}]$	(13.3,5)
Variance of log permeability	$(\sigma_Y^0)^2$	[-]	0.1,1
Initial porosity	ϕ^0	[-]	0.2
Molecular diffusion coefficient	D_m	$[\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}]$	10^{-9}
Mass fraction of <i>NaCl</i>	m_l^S	[molal]	0.5
Temperature	T_c	[°C]	60
Initial liquid pressure	p_l^i	[bar]	150
Initial gas pressure	p_g^i	[bar]	1
Gas pressure of injected brine	$p_{g,inj}$	[bar]	145
Injection rate	q_{inj}	$[\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}]$	$5 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Total simulation time	T_s	[s]	2000

Domain design: Figure 4.11 shows the initial distribution of log permeability (κ_0). The correlation lengths of the permeability in (x, y) -directions are respectively $(l_x^0, l_y^0) = (1.33, 0.5)$ [cm]. The variances of the log permeability are 0.1 and 1. Here different variances are employed to test the effect of the permeability distribution on the partial erosion. The left boundary is constant flux boundary with average Darcian flux $q_{lb} = 10^{-5}$ [$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]. The right boundary has constant liquid pressure, p_{lb} , which is equal to the initial liquid pressure. The rest boundaries are impermeable.

Fluid characters: The mean viscosity of brine is $\bar{\mu}_l$, and the mean density of the brine phase is $\bar{\rho}_l$. The hydrodynamic dispersion is not included and only the molecular diffusion (D_m) is considered.

Chemical characters: The chemical characters are the same as those in Section 4.3. Here, we also adjust the reaction rate by changing \mathcal{A}_s . In addition to the reference value of $\mathcal{A}_s = 0.0469 \cdot 10^6$ [m^{-1}], we also use smaller value, $0.0469 \cdot 10^{-2}$ [m^{-1}], for \mathcal{A}_s , to observe a visual effect of the kinetic reaction rate on the injection process.

Initially, the liquid pressure and gas pressure $(p_l^i, p_g^i) = (150, 1)$ [bar], and the system is at equilibrium chemical state. The molality of *NaCl* (m_l^S) is constant 0.5 [molal] and the temperature (T_c) is constant 60 °C. The injected brine ($p_{g,inj}$) has a gas pressure of 145 [bar], and it does not contain Ca^{2+} . The total volume rate through the left boundary $q_{inj} = 5 \cdot 10^{-10}$ [$\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]. This injection rate generates a mean Darcian flux of 10^{-5} [$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]. The simulation is terminated at $T_s = 2000$ [s]; that is, 5 pore volumes are injected at the end of the simulation.

All the aforementioned values are listed in the Table 4.8.

4.4.2 Results

We first discuss the results in the field with large heterogeneity, i.e., $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 1$. Figure 4.12 shows the distributions of the porosity change, the pH, the molality of $CO_2(aq)$ and the molality of the Ca^{2+} in the field with $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 1$; the left column gives results for the case with slow chemical reaction, while the right column gives results for the case with normal chemical reaction. If we compare the results for the porosity changes, we can see that (1) when the reaction rate is slow, the porosity change is obvious in the region with higher initial permeability (c.f. Figure 4.11), and (2) when normal reaction rate is employed, the porosity change only appears at the entrance. This is because when the reaction rate is high, the injected acidified brine instantaneously reacts with the calcite, the saturation index of the calcite instantaneously reaches one, and the generated Ca^{2+} decreases the erosion ability of the injected liquid. If we compare the results for the pH value, we can see that pH value in the case with slow reaction rate is slightly lower, because the dissolution of calcite, which consumes H^+ (c.f. Equation (4.51)), is slower. If we compare the results for the molality of $CO_2(aq)$, we can see negligible difference between the cases with different reaction rate; this means that the dissolution of calcite has negligible effect on the molality of $CO_2(aq)$. If we observe the result for the molality of Ca^{2+} ($m_l^{Ca^{2+}}$) in the case with slow reaction rate, we can see that $m_l^{Ca^{2+}}$ is lower in the invaded region; this is because the injected brine has no Ca^{2+} and the generation rate of Ca^{2+} is small due to the slow reaction rate. If we observe the result for the molality of Ca^{2+} ($m_l^{Ca^{2+}}$) in the case with normal reaction rate, we can see that $m_l^{Ca^{2+}}$ is higher in the invaded region; this is because the injected brine instantaneously reacts with the calcite and generates a huge amount of Ca^{2+} .

Figure 4.13 gives the temporal development of the partial erosion for the field with $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 1$. From Figure 4.13, we can see that if the reaction rate is slow, the acidified brine can generate wormhole along the high permeable region (c.f. Figure 4.11). If the reaction rate is high, the acidified brine only erodes the calcite at the inlet. This indicates that, for a given injection rate, the dissolution pattern is affected by the reaction rate.

Similarly, we show, in Figures 4.14 and 4.15, the results for the field with $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 0.1$. Figure 4.14 shows the distributions of porosity change $((\phi - \phi_0)/\phi_0)$, pH, molality of $CO_2(aq)$ ($m_l^{CO_2(aq)}$) and molality of Ca^{2+} ($m_l^{Ca^{2+}}$). From Figures 4.12 and 4.14, we can see that the result for the field with small heterogeneity (i.e., $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 0.1$) shows similar distribution of the $((\phi - \phi_0)/\phi_0)$, pH, molality of $CO_2(aq)$ ($m_l^{CO_2(aq)}$) and molality of Ca^{2+} ($m_l^{Ca^{2+}}$), except that the profile is more uniform in the field with $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 0.1$. The temporal developments of porosity for the slow and normal reaction rates are shown in Figure 4.15.

If we compare the results for gas injection given in Figure 4.4 and those for acidified brine injection given in Figures 4.13 and 4.15, we can see that (1) the erosion can penetrate

Figure 4.12: Distributions of porosity change $((\phi - \phi_0)/\phi_0)$, pH, molality of $CO_2(aq)$ ($m_i^{CO_2(aq)}$) and molality of Ca^{2+} ($m_i^{Ca^{2+}}$) in the field with $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 1$; the left column lists the results for the simulation with slow reaction, while the right column lists the results for the simulation with normal reaction; the simulation time is 0.1×10^3 [s].

Figure 4.13: Temporal development of partial erosion, $(\phi - \phi_0)/\phi_0$ in the field with $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 1$; the left column lists the results for the simulation with slow reaction, while the right column lists the results for the simulation with normal reaction.

longer but the total erosion is small in the case of gas injection with normal reaction rate, while (2) the erosion only exists at the entrance but the total erosion is large in the case of acidified brine injection with normal reaction rate. Thus we can conclude that the traditional two-phase (i.e., rock and brine) model cannot represent the three-phase (i.e., rock, brine and gas) case in GCS.

4.5 Conclusions

In this chapter, we offer a numerical model for simulating Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS). This numerical model accounts for the kinetic as well as the equilibrium reactions among gas/brine/rock phases. Based on this model, we develop a numerical program for a specific reactive transport system in GCS. This program is then tested against the

Figure 4.14: Distributions of porosity change $((\phi - \phi_0)/\phi_0)$, pH, molality of $CO_2(aq)$ ($m_l^{CO_2(aq)}$) and molality of Ca^{2+} ($m_l^{Ca^{2+}}$) in the field with $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 0.1$; the left column lists the results for the simulation with slow reaction, while the right column lists the results for the simulation with normal reaction; the simulation time is 0.1×10^3 [s].

Figure 4.15: Temporal development of partial erosion, $(\phi - \phi_0)/\phi_0$ in the field with $(\sigma_Y^0)^2 = 0.1$; the left column lists the results for the simulation with slow reaction, while the right column lists the results for the simulation with normal reaction.

one-dimensional theoretical solution given by *McWhorter and Sunada* (1990). Sensitive analysis is conducted to analyze how dissolution rate affects the erosion process in one-dimensional gas injection process. Finally, we offer a simple application of this program to partial dissolution in the two-dimensional field. The conclusions are listed as follows.

(1) We propose a general numerical model for simulating the reactive three-phase flow in the subsurface formation, where the chemical system includes both kinetic and equilibrium reactions. In this model, the reaction and transport are split into two modules, and correspondingly the independent variables are also split into independent reaction variables and independent transport variables. The independent transport variables are implicitly solved based Newton-Raphson method and the independent reaction variables are solved based on the updated independent transport variables. In this model, no variable substitution is needed to cope with phase appearance/disappearance, which simplifies the structure of the program.

(2) Based on the general model, we develop a numerical program for a specific reactive three-phase transport system in GCS. In this system, the rock formation only includes calcite that kinetically reacts with the brine, and the rest reactions are at equilibrium state. The partial equilibrium reaction system is solved based on mass action law, and Newton-Raphson method is used to implicitly solve the kinetic/equilibrium reactions.

(3) The numerical program is tested against the one-dimensional theoretical solution given in *McWhorter and Sunada* (1990), and good agreement approves the correctness of the program.

(4) Sensitive analysis is performed on the one-dimensional gas injection in an initially brine-saturated formation. From the numerical results we can see that (a) the gas dissolution is negligibly affected by the rock dissolution rate, (b) the fractional porosity increase due to gas injection is only around 10^{-3} at normal reaction rate, and (c) the calcite dissolution can be treated as equilibrium reaction at reservoir condition.

(5) We also apply the numerical program to simulate wormhole development in two-dimensional heterogeneous fields. In this application, the heterogeneous field is initially saturated with brine at low gas pressure (i.e., low $CO_2(aq)$ concentration and high pH), and brine saturated with high gas pressure is injected through the left boundary. Results show that (a) the calcite dissolution only appears at the inlet when the reaction rate is high, (b) the pH and $CO_2(aq)$ due to acidified brine injection can affect a longer distance even if the dissolution only appears at the inlet when the reaction rate is high, (c) wormhole develops through the region of high initial permeability when the reaction rate is small, and (d) the dissolution is relatively uniform when the permeability heterogeneity is small.

(6) The traditional two-phase (i.e., rock and brine) model, in which acidified brine is injected into the formation, cannot represent the three-phase (i.e., rock, brine and gas) case in GCS, in which gaseous CO_2 is injected into the formation. When the reaction

rate is high, the two-phase model may generate face dissolution at the entrance, while the erosion penetrates further in the three-phase flow model.

Chapter 5

Application of Reactive Two-Phase Flow Model I: Numerical Analysis of How Gravity Driven Convection Enhances Dissolution of CO_2 in Heterogeneous Fields

Description: This chapter is based on a manuscript- Wang Y., Fernandez-Garcia D. & Saaltink M. (2022), *Numerical Analysis of How Gravity Driven Convection Enhances Dissolution of CO_2 in Heterogeneous Fields*- to be submitted to *Water Resources Research*.

5.1 Introduction

Dissolution trapping of gaseous CO_2 ($CO_2(g)$) plays an important role in increasing the safety of Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS). During the later stage of GCS, the injected $CO_2(g)$ is expected to override denser brine, continuously move upward and accumulate beneath the low permeable caprock after injection. Because the less dense $CO_2(g)$ is immiscible but soluble with the resident brine in the formation, the injected $CO_2(g)$ is sequestered in four ways: (1) being sealed by low permeable caprock (hydrodynamic trapping), (2) being trapped by capillarity (residual trapping), (3) dissolving in brine at the interface between the $CO_2(g)$ and denser brine (dissolution trapping) and (4) reacting with rock formation (mineral trapping) (*Kumar et al.*, 2005; *Riaz et al.*, 2006b; *Bachu et al.*, 2007; *Gasda et al.*, 2011, 2012; *Macminn and Juanes*, 2013; *Soltanian et al.*, 2017). The hydrodynamic trapping is most rapid but unstable, because the relatively light $CO_2(g)$ would escape the storage formation when there exist seismic activities, faults or failed wellbore casings. The mineral trapping is most stable but slow. At a certain long

time scale, the safety of the GCS is governed by the dissolution trapping, which is free from the non-integrity of the formation (*Nordbotten and Celia, 2006; Strandli and Benson, 2013*). Therefore, due to its safety and relatively high efficiency, the dissolution of $CO_2(g)$ into brine makes an important mechanism in reducing the leakage of $CO_2(g)$ for long-term sequestration (*Anbar and Akin, 2011; Xiao et al., 2019*).

The dissolution process is complicated by the Gravity-Driven Convection (GDC). Dissolution of overlying $CO_2(g)$ into the brine will increase the brine density and thus the brine density at the upper portion of the saline formation is greater than that at the lower position, causing GDC in the brine phase and enhancing the downward movement of aqueous CO_2 ($CO_2(aq)$) (*Weir et al., 1996; Vella and Hupper, 2006; Pritchard, 2007; Pruess and Zhang, 2008*). Moreover, the nonuniform downward flux of $CO_2(aq)$ -saturated brine is accompanied by the upward flux of $CO_2(aq)$ -unsaturated brine, increasing the contact between $CO_2(g)$ and unsaturated brine and further enhancing dissolution of $CO_2(g)$ (*Pruess, 2005; Gilfillan et al., 2009; Pau et al., 2010*). In contrast to pure molecular diffusion, which fades away fast as the concentration profile reaches a Gaussian bell profile, the GDC can fuel the vertical exchange of the concentration at a high constant rate for a certain long time until the whole domain is close to fully saturated (*Slim, 2014*). Therefore, GDC-induced dissolution can substantially reduce the time required for totally dissolving the $CO_2(g)$ plume and increase the security of GCS.

Currently, researchers have done a large quantity of investigations on GDC-induced dissolution. These researches, ranging from theoretical analysis (e.g., *Elenius et al., 2012*), laboratory experiment (e.g., *Rasmusson et al., 2017*) to numerical simulations (e.g., *Elenius et al., 2015*), are gradually bringing to light the intrinsic mechanism of GDC, which depends to a large extent on: (1) the property of the formation (e.g., the permeability and porosity), (2) the property of the brine phase (e.g., viscosity and molecular diffusion coefficient), and (3) density change of brine due to CO_2 dissolution (*Hassanzadeh et al., 2007, 2008; Neufeld et al., 2010; Elenius and Johannsen, 2012a; Emami-Meybodi and Hassanzadeh, 2015*). Researchers have found that dissolution rate can be predicted based on the parameters of the system. For instance, the dissolution rate by GDC is proportional to the intrinsic permeability (*Rasmusson et al., 2015b*).

Nevertheless, more work on GDC is still needed for two reasons. Firstly, most of the current researches are on (isotropically or anisotropically) homogeneous fields, and only a few researches quantitatively study the effect of heterogeneity on the GDC-driven dissolution process (*Ennis-King and Paterson, 2005b; Pruess and Nordbotten, 2011; Cheng et al., 2012; Ranganathan et al., 2012; Taheri et al., 2012; Elenius and Gasda, 2013; Wang et al., 2021*). The sample in the experimental study usually mimics (isotropically or anisotropically) homogeneous media, and the permeability field in the numerical study is also usually homogeneous with negligible random perturbation of permeability or

porosity (*Pau et al.*, 2010). Some experimental studies consider the effect of heterogeneity but only give qualitative analysis (*Agartan et al.*, 2015; *Wang et al.*, 2021). *Farajzadeh et al.* (2011) conducted numerical simulations of the GDC in brine phase in isotropically heterogeneous media, but found no quantitative correlation between the CO_2 dissolution and the heterogeneity measures. *Elenius and Gasda* (2013) offered good hints on the relation between heterogeneity and GDC by conducting numerous numerical simulations in the fields with horizontal barriers, but the anisotropic effect is not considered in their empirical formula. *Green and Ennis-King* (2014) took into account the anisotropic effect but in an improper way; this will be discussed in the following sections. We are still missing a more sound quantitative relation between GDC and heterogeneity measures. Secondly, the results from literature are not consistent with each other. Even for GDC in homogeneous fields, as shown in Table 5.1, the dissolution rate, the finger size and especially the onset time vary in different researches. The difference could stem from the boundary condition, initial condition, liquid property and setup setting (*Jafari Raad et al.*, 2016; *Rasmusson et al.*, 2017). For GDC in heterogeneous fields, *Green and Ennis-King* (2010), *Farajzadeh et al.* (2011) and *Chen et al.* (2013) found that heterogeneity can enhance the GDC, but *Elenius and Gasda* (2013) reported that horizontal barriers, such as layered mudstone inclusions or shale deposits in sandstone formations, can suppress GDC, of which the strength is proportional to the effective vertical permeability of the system. These discrepancies among literature motivate this research.

The objective of this chapter is to quantitatively analyze the effect of permeability heterogeneity on the GDC, based on a large amount of numerical simulations in a wide range of (isotropically and anisotropically) heterogeneous fields. Because in real application the permeability, characterized by variance and correlation length, varies in a wide range, it is thus important to quantitatively analyze the effect of permeability heterogeneity on the GDC. Here, we focus on how the GDC-induced dissolution rate is affected by the transport connectivity, the flow connectivity, vertical finger tip velocity and ratio of horizontal to vertical flow connectivity. Two physically sound formulas are obtained to predict the GDC-induced dissolution rate based on representative characters of the permeability, through quantitative analysis of the numerical results. The onset time and characteristic wave length scale of GDC are not the focus of this study.

The program developed in Chapter 2 is used to simulate the GDC in heterogeneous fields generated with the Sequential Gaussian Simulation method implemented in the SGSIM code (*Journel and Huijbregts*, 1976). In terms of the numerical simulations for GDC, both two-phase and single-phase models have been used in literature (*Pruess and Zhang*, 2008; *Pau et al.*, 2010; *Elenius and Johannsen*, 2012a; *Martinez and Hesse*, 2016; *Kim et al.*, 2019). For the reason of simplification, we study the GDC with single-phase model, although our program also applies to two-phase systems. We note that the

developed program can detect whether a grid is in two-phase or single-phase state, and can automatically cope with phase appearance and disappearance.

The rest of this chapter is organized as follows. Section 5.2 gives description of the numerical method, setup design and measures of permeability and GDC; Section 5.3 gives the results and discussions; and major conclusions are listed in Section 5.4.

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 Numerical Method

Governing Equations

When gas phase does not exist, the governing equations (2.3) and (2.4), on the basis of the mass balances of H and C elements, degenerate to:

$$0 = \frac{\partial(\phi\rho X^H)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho X^H \mathbf{q}) - \nabla \cdot (\phi \mathbf{D} \rho \nabla X^H) - Q_W^H, \quad (5.1)$$

$$0 = \frac{\partial(\phi\rho X^C)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho X^C \mathbf{q}) - \nabla \cdot (\phi \mathbf{D} \rho \nabla X^C) - Q_W^C, \quad (5.2)$$

where, ϕ [-] represents the porosity of the saline formation; ρ [$\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$] represents the density of brine; X [$\text{kg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$] represents the mass fraction; superscripts (H, C) represent the water and $\text{CO}_2(aq)$ species, respectively; t [s] represents time; \mathbf{D} [$\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] represents the dispersion tensor; Q_W [$\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] represents the source/sink term; and \mathbf{q} [$\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] represents the Darcian discharge. The dimensionless form of Equations (5.1) and (5.2) are given in the Appendix I.

Constitutional Equations

The discharge rate (\mathbf{q}) is given as extended Darcy's law

$$\mathbf{q} = -\frac{\kappa}{\mu}(\nabla p_l - \rho g \nabla z), \quad (5.3)$$

where, μ [$\text{pa}\cdot\text{s}$] is the brine viscosity, κ [m^2] the intrinsic permeability, p_l [pa] the liquid pressure, z [m] the depth, and g [$\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$] the gravitational acceleration. Besides, we have the following constraints:

$$X^S = 0.05844 X^H m^S \quad (5.4)$$

and

$$X^H + X^C + X^S = 1, \quad (5.5)$$

where, m^S denotes the molality of salt. Here, we assume that the salt is only comprised of

$NaCl$ and that the molality of $NaCl$ (m^S) is fixed. Define $\omega = (1 + 0.05844m^S)$ and then Equations (5.4) and (5.5) merge to

$$\omega X^H + X^C = 1. \quad (5.6)$$

The methodology of solving the aforementioned equations has been given in Chapter 2. Liquid pressure p_l and gas pressure p_g are used as the two independent variables. All the other variables (e.g., ρ , μ , X^C and X^H) and their derivatives can be directly or indirectly expressed from p_l and p_g (see Chapter 2). The independent variables p_l and p_g are updated by solving two transport equations (5.1) and (5.2) with Newton-Raphson method. In this program, Boussinesq assumption is not needed because the model is highly coupled, and the brine density model is not a simplified linear model used in literature (see e.g. *Slim* (2014)). This difference maybe explain why the results from this study are slightly different from those in literature. We note that in this chapter p_g is smaller than p_l , and thus only liquid phase exists. If p_g is getting larger than p_l , the gas phase will appear with a saturation calculated from the retention curve by Van Genuchten model. Here we suppress the appearance of $CO_2(g)$ phase.

5.2.2 Setup Design

Here, a vertically two-dimensional domain is used to simulate the development of GDC (see Figure 5.1).

Boundary Conditions

The boundary conditions are defined as following: the bottom and lateral boundaries are no-flow boundaries while the top boundary is constant pressure boundary (i.e., concentrations on the top boundary are constant). This top boundary condition is different from that used in some literature where the convection of the CO_2 -saturated layer is suppressed (*Hesse*, 2008; *Pau et al.*, 2010; *Elenius and Johannsen*, 2012a; *Slim*, 2014). For instance, in *Pau et al.* (2010), the top constant concentration boundary only allows CO_2 to go inside the domain via diffusion; that top boundary condition generates a much lower prediction of the dissolution rate. In some literature the top boundary is partially permeable and larger dissolution rate is obtained (*Hesse*, 2008; *Elenius et al.*, 2014b). Different top boundary conditions can also generate different onset time for GDC. Our numerical tests (not shown here) indicate that allowing the convection through the top boundary can reduce the onset time, as well as increase the dissolution rate. The lateral boundaries can be constant pressure boundaries or periodic boundaries, which only generates slight difference in the statistic behavior of the GDC (*Li et al.*, 2015; *Zhang et al.*, 2011b).

Domain Size and Grid Discretization

Figure 5.1: Sketch of setup design.

An optimum setup design could represent the GDC with smallest number of grids, i.e., smallest size of domain and largest size of grids. To get a good setup design we need to know both the behavior of the GDC and the characters of the field and the fluid.

First, two basic characters of GDC are used as references in designing the simulation setup. We use characteristic wave length (or earliest finger width) l_c to design the grid and domain sizes, and use the characteristic onset time t_c to estimate the simulation time. They are, respectively, given as

$$l_c = l_c^* \frac{\mu\phi D_m}{\Delta\rho g \kappa_g} \quad (5.7)$$

and

$$t_c = t_c^* \frac{(\mu\phi)^2 D_m}{(\Delta\rho g \kappa_g)^2}, \quad (5.8)$$

where, l_c^* and t_c^* are, respectively, dimensionless characteristic wavelength and onset time, which are constants obtained from theoretical, numerical or experimental studies; $\Delta\rho$ is the density increase due to CO_2 dissolution; κ_g is the geometric mean permeability; and D_m is molecular diffusion coefficient. For homogeneous media, the empirical values for l_c^* and t_c^* are listed in Table 5.1, which also contains the results from this study. The domain size should be large enough to cover enough number of convection fingers, while

Figure 5.2: Analysis of the effect of grid size on the the dissolution rate.

the grid size should be smaller than or close to the size of convection fingers. From our testing simulations (see Figures 5.2 and 5.3), we find that the domain size of $30l_c \times 30l_c$ and grid size of $0.3l_c \times 0.3l_c$ are enough to describe the GDC. Increasing the domain size to $60l_c \times 30l_c$ and $30l_c \times 60l_c$ or reducing the grid size to $0.15l_c \times 0.3l_c$, $0.3l_c \times 0.15l_c$ and $0.15l_c \times 0.075l_c$ does not systematically affect the onset time and dissolution rate. We notice that reducing or increasing the (especially vertical) grid size could significantly affect the characteristic wave length (i.e., the width of earliest unstable fingers) but this does not affect the statistic dissolution rate. Results from *Elenius et al.* (2015) show that the dissolution can be correctly simulated even if the grid size is several times larger than the characteristic wave length, although the concentration profile is not precisely represented. For homogeneous fields, a simulation time of $6t_c$ is enough to obtain the asymptotic dissolution rate. For heterogeneous fields, the simulation is not terminated until the fast unstable finger touches the bottom, to make sure the finger has ergodically traveled the heterogeneous domain; here, we define the finger has touched the bottom when the maximum $CO_2(aq)$ concentration on the bottom increases to 5% of the maximum $CO_2(aq)$ concentration.

Second, for numerical simulations in heterogeneous fields, we need also to take into account the correlation length scale. The domain size should be, if possible, 3 times larger than the correlation length scale which should be at least 5 times larger than the grid size. Because the domain size is $30l_c$, the correlation length should be less than $10l_c$. Because the grid size is $0.3l_c$, the minimum correlation length is $1.5l_c$. Additionally, the horizontally layered formation is used to represent the infinite correlation length in the horizontal

Figure 5.3: Analysis of the effect of grid size on the finger size (for the case of $(L, B) = (60l_c, 30l_c)$, $(dx, dz) = (0.3l_c, 0.15l_c)$, we only show $x \in (0, 30l_c)$).

Table 5.1: Published data for dimensionless onset time (t_{c0}^*), dimensionless wave length (l_{c0}^*) and dimensionless dissolution rate (F_{c0}^*) for (isotropic) homogeneous field.

Onset time (t_{c0}^*)	Wave length (l_{c0}^*)	Dissolution rate (F_{c0}^*)	Top boundary	Method	Reference
30,75	95	-	-	Theor.	<i>Ennis-King et al. (2005)</i>
78	92	-	-	Theor.	<i>Ennis-King and Paterson (2005b)</i>
75	96	-	-	Theor.	<i>Xu et al. (2006b)</i>
1,156- 1,412	34-38	0.015-0.017	diff. only ^a	Num.	<i>Pruess and Zhang (2008)</i>
146	90	-	-	Theor.	<i>Riaz et al. (2006b)</i>
-	-	0.017	diff. only	Num.	<i>Hesse et al. (2008)</i>
1,000- 5,000	-	0.017-0.018	diff. only	Num.	<i>Pau et al. (2010)</i>
-	-	$0.12Ra^{-0.16}$	-	Num.,Exp.	<i>Neufeld et al. (2010)</i>
-	-	$0.045Ra^{-0.24}$	Permeable	Exp.	<i>Backhaus et al. (2011)</i>
47.9	115.3	-	-	Theor.	<i>Cheng et al. (2012)</i>
3,500	-	0.017	diff. only	Num..	<i>Cheng et al. (2012)</i>
4,860	170	0.02	diff. only	Num.	<i>Elenius and Johannsen (2012b)</i>
31	73	-	-	Theor.	<i>Elenius and Johannsen (2012a)</i>
5800	-	0.02	diff. only	Num.	<i>Elenius and Johannsen (2012a)</i>
2500	-	0.075	CTZ ^b	Num.	<i>Elenius and Johannsen (2012a)</i>
845	-	-	diff. only	Num.	<i>Azin et al. (2013)</i>
-	-	$0.037Ra^{-0.16}$	Permeable	Exp.	<i>Tsai et al. (2013)</i>
-	-	$0.0794Ra^{-0.168}$	diff. only	Theor.	<i>Farajzadeh et al. (2013)</i>
1,200	80-140	0.017	diff. only	Num.	<i>Slim (2014)</i>
-	-	0.025	($0.2\kappa^c$)	Num.	<i>Slim (2014)</i>
-	-	0.044	($0.6\kappa^d$)	Num.	<i>Slim (2014)</i>
56	-	-	-	Theor.	<i>Jafari Raad et al. (2016)</i>
-	-	0.065	CTZ	Num.	<i>Martinez and Hesse (2016)</i>
-	-	0.018-0.019	diff. only	Num.	<i>Martinez and Hesse (2016)</i>
$Ra^{0.8573}$	-	$Ra^{-0.2154}, 0.06$	Permeable	Exp.	<i>Rasmusson et al. (2017)</i>
500	70	0.09	Permeable	Num.	This study

^a The top boundary only allows mass go through the boundary via diffusion.

^b The top boundary is capillary transition zone.

^c The permeability of the top boundary is 0.2 the permeability of the domain.

^d The permeability of the top boundary is 0.6 the permeability of the domain.

direction.

Table 5.2 lists the following parameters that are used in the numerical simulations. The brine pressure at the top boundary is fixed to $p_{l,top}$ and the gas pressure at the top boundary is fixed to $p_{g,top}$, which result in a fixed concentration ($X^{C,top}$) of $CO_2(aq)$ at the top boundary. Initially, the system is at stable state under gravity and the concentration of the $CO_2(aq)$ is $X^{C,0}$ in the whole domain; this corresponds to constant initial gas pressure of $p_{g,0}$ everywhere. The density of CO_2 -saturated brine in the top layer is ρ^{top} and the mean viscosity of brine is $\bar{\mu}$. When the mass fraction of $CO_2(aq)$ increases from $X^{C,0}$ to $X^{C,top}$, the density of brine increases by $\Delta\rho$. The domain length is L and the domain depth is B . The grid size is Δl . We note that both the density and the viscosity of the brine change with the gas pressure and liquid pressure.

Table 5.3 lists the design of the permeability heterogeneity, which is generated with the Sequential Gaussian Simulation method implemented in the SGSIM code (*Journel and Huijbregts, 1976*). The permeability is described by the horizontal and vertical correlation lengths (l_h, l_v), variance of log permeability (σ_Y^2) and geometric mean (κ_g). The κ_g is fixed and given in Table 5.2. σ_Y^2 varies from 0.1 to 4. l_v/l_c varies from 2 to 4. l_h/l_v varies

Table 5.2: Parameter settings.

Parameters	Symbol	Units	Value
Domain size	$L \times B$	[m \times m]	7.5×7.5
Grid discretization	$n_x \times n_z$	[-]	100 \times 100
Porosity	ϕ	[-]	0.15
Permeability	κ_g	[m ²]	10^{-12}
Initial liquid pressure at top layer	$p_{l,top0}$	[bar]	150
Initial gas pressure	$p_{g,0}$	[bar]	1
Boundary liquid pressure at top layer	$p_{l,top}$	[bar]	150
Boundary gas pressure at top layer	$p_{g,top}$	[bar]	140
Initial $CO_2(aq)$ concentration	$X^{C,0}$	[kg \cdot kg ⁻¹]	~ 0.0006
$CO_2(aq)$ concentration at top boundary	$X^{C,top}$	[kg \cdot kg ⁻¹]	0.041
Brine density at top boundary	ρ^{top}	[kg \cdot m ⁻³]	1017
Brine density increase due to increased $CO_2(aq)$ concentration	$\Delta\rho$	[kg \cdot m ⁻³]	8.2
Salinity	m^S	[molal]	0.5
Mean viscosity	$\bar{\mu}$	[mpa \cdot s]	0.95
Molecular diffusion coefficient	D	[m ² \cdot s ⁻¹]	2×10^{-9}

from 1.0 to infinite. In total, 515 fields are used. Figure 5.4 illustrates four representative permeability distributions of the 515 fields.

Several notes about the setup design are given as follows. First, the dissolution rate is not decreased when the finger tip touches the bottom but decreased when the finger tip is reflected to the top, i.e., the dissolution rate starts to decrease when the finger tip has travelled a distance of $2B$. Second, for heterogeneous fields, we use geometric mean permeability as the reference permeability, which is used to normalize the effective permeability. Third, the variance of the porosity is small, and thus the porosity can be assumed to be constant. Fourth, the wavelength obtained with numerical method is the wavelength of the earliest observable waves, while the wavelength given in theoretical

Table 5.3: Permeability heterogeneity.

Field	l_v/l_c	l_h/l_v	σ_Y^2	Number
Homogeneous	-	-	-	15
Isotropic	2	1	1	50
Isotropic	4	1	1	50
Isotropic	4	1	4	50
Isotropic	2	1	4	50
Anisotropic	2	2	0.1	50
Anisotropic	2	2	1	50
Anisotropic	2	4	0.1	50
Anisotropic	2	4	1	50
Anisotropic	2	4	4	50
Anisotropic	2	Infinite	1	50

Figure 5.4: Representative log permeability distribution.

studies is obtained with linear stability analysis. We do not distinguish between the wave length in theoretical studies and that in numerical studies because they are quite close. Fifth, the onset time from theoretical study is the onset of linear instabilities, while the onset time from numerical study is the onset of the fully nonlinear regime. The former is called linear onset time at which the vertical finger velocity starts to increase, while the latter is called the nonlinear onset time at which the dissolution rate starts to increase due to GDC (*Elenius and Johannsen, 2012b*). The linear onset time is shorter than the nonlinear onset time. Here, we are only interested in the nonlinear onset time, although it is sensitive to the perturbation used to trigger the convective instability. It is however not necessary or possible to give an exact value for nonlinear onset time, and we only need to know the range of nonlinear onset time to assist the design of high-resolution numerical simulations. In the regional scale, the onset time is negligible and useless.

5.2.3 Measures of GDC and Permeability

As to the GDC process, we focus on the GDC-induced dissolution rate (F), which is described as the CO_2 flux through the top boundary. To facilitate the analysis, we use the normalized characteristic dissolution efficiency (F_{nc}^*). Characteristic onset time and characteristic wavelength, are only briefly given for the homogeneous case without further discussion, because they have limited utility in engineering aspect.

In order to perform quantitative analysis between permeability heterogeneity and GDC-induced dissolution, we need to find efficient measures for permeability. Here, flow connectivity and transport connectivity are used to describe the permeability distribution (*Knudby and Carrera, 2005*). In literature, vertical flow connectivity (C_{fv}) and horizontal flow connectivity (C_{fh}) have been used to estimate the dissolution rate (*Elenius and Gasda, 2013; Green and Ennis-King, 2014*). Here, we also use C_{fv} and C_{fh} to predict the dissolution rate. Moreover, the vertical transport connectivity (C_{tv}), horizontal transport connectivity (C_{th}) and normalized characteristic dimensionless vertical finger tip ($v_{ncf,v}^*$) velocity are introduced to predict the dissolution rate. In total, five candidate measures are used to describe the field property. We note that C_{fv} , C_{fh} , C_{tv} and C_{th} can be easily obtained for a formation by using independent flow simulations and tracer test while $v_{ncf,v}^*$ has to be obtained by doing GDC simulations.

The aforementioned variables are defined as follows.

Normalized Characteristic Dimensionless Dissolution Rate

The normalized characteristic dimensionless dissolution rate (F_{nc}^*) is given as

$$F_{nc}^* = \frac{F_c^*}{F_{c0}^*}, \quad (5.9)$$

where subscript ‘0’ denotes the homogeneous case and the characteristic dimensionless

dissolution rate

$$F_c^* = \frac{\int_{\frac{2}{3}t_b}^{t_b} F^* dt}{\frac{1}{3}t_b}, \quad (5.10)$$

where the dimensionless dissolution rate

$$F^* = \frac{F}{X^{C,top} \rho^{top} \frac{\Delta \rho g \kappa_g}{\bar{\mu}}}; \quad (5.11)$$

here, the characteristic dimensionless dissolution rate (F_c^*) is obtained by averaging the dimensionless dissolution rate (F^*) over the period from $\frac{2}{3}t_b$ to t_b , with t_b denoting the time when the earliest finger of aqueous CO_2 touches the bottom, i.e., the maximum bottom CO_2 mass fraction reaches 5% of CO_2 mass fraction in the top boundary.

Vertical and Horizontal Flow Connectivities

The vertical flow connectivity (C_{fv}) is actually the dimensionless effective vertical permeability (κ_{ev}) given in *Elenius and Gasda (2013)*. C_{fv} is calculated by using independent numerical simulations, described as following. Set the field water-saturated, close the left-side and right-side boundaries, set the top and bottom boundaries as constant pressure boundary with constant pressure p_{in} and p_{out} , respectively, deactivate the gravity, and then when the flux on the top boundary (q_t) is steady, we can obtain

$$C_{fv} = \frac{\kappa_{ev}}{\kappa_g} = \frac{q_t \mu B}{L(p_{in} - p_{out})} \cdot \frac{1}{\kappa_g}. \quad (5.12)$$

Similarly, we can obtain horizontal flow connectivity C_{fh} .

Ratio of Horizontal to Vertical Flow Connectivity

The ratio of vertical to horizontal flow connectivity is defined as

$$a_f = \frac{C_{fv}}{C_{fh}}. \quad (5.13)$$

Vertical and Horizontal Transport Connectivities

The tracer test algorithm proposed by *Pollock (1989)* is used to calculate the transport connectivities. Regarding the vertical transport connectivity, N_p particles are uniformly put on the top boundary. These particles then moves according to the flow field, which has been obtained when we calculated the vertical flow connectivity. The position of the particle is updated according to

$$x(t + \Delta t) = x(t) + \frac{v_h(t)}{A_x} [\exp(A_x \Delta t) - 1], \quad (5.14)$$

$$z(t + \Delta t) = z(t) + \frac{v_v(t)}{A_z} [\exp(A_z \Delta t) - 1], \quad (5.15)$$

where,

$$A_x = \frac{v_h(x = x_2) - v_h(x = x_1)}{\Delta x} \quad (5.16)$$

$$A_z = \frac{v_v(z = z_2) - v_v(z = z_1)}{\Delta z}, \quad (5.17)$$

$$v_h(t) = v_h(x = x_1) + A_x \cdot x(t), \quad (5.18)$$

$$v_v(t) = v_v(z = z_1) + A_z \cdot z(t), \quad (5.19)$$

and

$$\Delta t = \min \left(\frac{1}{A_x} \ln \frac{v_h(x = x_2)}{v_h(t)}, \frac{1}{A_z} \ln \frac{v_v(z = z_2)}{v_v(t)} \right).$$

Here, x_1 and x_2 are, respectively, the minimum and maximum x-positions of downwind cell that contains the particle; z_1 and z_2 are, respectively, the minimum and maximum z-positions of downwind cell that contains the particle. The particle can only jump from one face to another face of the downwind cell. The tracer test is terminated when all the particles have arrived the bottom boundary. The vertical transport connectivity is then calculated as

$$C_{tv} = \frac{t_m}{t_5}, \quad (5.20)$$

where, t_m is the mean arrival time of all the particles and t_5 is the time when 5% of the particles have arrived the bottom boundary. Similarly, we can obtain the horizontal transport connectivity C_{th} . The nuance between C_{tv} and C_{fv} is the former prefers the flow rate in high permeable region while the latter prefers the mean flow rate.

Normalized Characteristic Dimensionless Vertical Finger Tip Velocity

Normalized characteristic dimensionless vertical finger tip velocity ($v_{ncf,v}^*$) represents maximum cross-sectional mean absolute vertical velocity (*Elenius and Johannsen, 2012b*). $v_{ncf,v}^*$ is given as

$$v_{ncf,v}^* = \frac{v_{cf,v}^*}{v_{cf0,v}^*}, \quad (5.21)$$

where $v_{cf,v}^*$ is the characteristic (asymptotic) dimensionless vertical finger tip velocity and subscript '0' denotes the homogeneous case. The characteristic dimensionless vertical finger tip velocity is given as

$$v_{cf,v}^* = \frac{\int_{\frac{2}{3}t_b}^{t_b} v_{f,v}^* dt}{\frac{1}{3}t_b}, \quad (5.22)$$

where, $v_{f,v}^*$ is dimensionless vertical finger tip velocity, defined as

$$v_{f,v}^* = \max_{z \in (0,B)} \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L |v_v^*(x, z)| dx, \quad (5.23)$$

with

$$v_v^*(x, z) = \frac{v_v(x, z)}{\frac{\Delta\rho g \kappa_g}{\phi \bar{\mu}}}, \quad (5.24)$$

where, v_v [$\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] is the dimensional vertical velocity of the brine.

In the same way, if we replace v_v with horizontal v_h , we obtain the normalized characteristic dimensionless horizontal expansion rate of the finger tip, $v_{nef,h}^*$.

Moreover, we also use the dimensionless form of time, distance and concentration in the following analysis.

Dimensionless Time, Distance and Concentration

The dimensionless time, distance and concentration are given as (see also the Appendix I)

$$t^* = \frac{t(\Delta\rho g \kappa_g)^2}{(\bar{\mu}\phi)^2 D}, \quad (5.25)$$

$$(x^*, z^*) = \frac{(x, z)\Delta\rho g \kappa_g}{\mu\phi D} \quad (5.26)$$

and

$$X^{C*} = \frac{X^C}{X^{C,top}}. \quad (5.27)$$

5.3 Results and Discussions

5.3.1 Qualitative Analysis of Numerical Results

5.3.1.1 Results for Reference Homogeneous Fields

Although the major focus of this research is not on GDC in homogeneous fields, the results for the homogeneous cases are briefly given for two reasons. First, in literature, the results on the GDC in homogeneous field with permeable top boundary are scarce and inconsistent. Second, they serve the reference for the analysis of GDC in heterogeneous fields.

The temporal development of dissolution rate is given in the top panel of Figure 5.5, from which we can see that the numerical results start to diverge from the pure-diffusion curve at $t_{c0}^* \approx 500$. The mean dimensionless characteristic dissolution rate $F_{c0}^* \approx 0.09$.

Figure 5.5: Homogeneous case: temporal developments of (a) dimensionless dissolution rate, (b) dimensionless vertical finger tip velocity and (c) dimensionless horizontal expansion rate of finger tip.

These results are also listed in Table 5.1. This result for dimensionless characteristic dissolution rate is slightly larger than 0.075 in *Elenius and Johannsen* (2012a) and 0.065 in *Martinez and Hesse* (2016); in the latter the CTZ boundary is employed.

The dimensionless vertical finger tip velocity and dimensionless horizontal expansion

velocity are given in the middle and bottom panels of Figure 5.5. Comparison of the middle panel and bottom panel of Figure 5.5 indicates that the dimensionless vertical finger velocity is around 0.28 and that the horizontal finger tip expansion speed is around $1/5$ of the vertical finger tip velocity. The development of dimensionless concentration is shown in Figure 5.6, from which we can see that the width of the finger is around $2/5$ of the length of the finger.

Figure 5.6: Homogeneous case: temporal development of normalized CO_2 mass fraction, X^{C*} .

Finally, Figure 5.7 shows the relation among the distributions of concentration, vertical velocity and horizontal velocity, at $t^* = 1509$. As can be seen from Figure 5.7, the cross-sectional mean dimensionless absolute horizontal velocity ($\overline{v_h^*}$) reaches minimum at the vertical position where the cross-sectional mean dimensionless absolute vertical velocity ($\overline{v_v^*}$) reaches maximum; this position is the inflection point of cross-sectional mean

Figure 5.7: First column: profiles of dimensionless concentration (X^{C*}), dimensionless vertical velocity (v_v^*) and dimensionless horizontal velocity (v_h^*); second column, profiles of cross-sectional mean dimensionless concentration ($\overline{X^{C*}}$), cross-sectional mean dimensionless absolute vertical velocity ($\overline{v_v^*}$) and cross-sectional mean of dimensionless absolute horizontal velocity ($\overline{v_h^*}$); at $t^* = 1509$.

dimensionless concentration ($\overline{X^{C*}}$). The $\overline{v_h^*}$ has two maximum values, one at the root of the finger and the other one at the tip of the finger.

5.3.1.2 Results for Heterogeneous Fields

For reason of simplicity, we only show the results of two representative heterogeneous cases: the isotropic case with $l_h = l_v = 2l_c$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 1$ and the anisotropic case with $l_h = \text{infinite}$, $l_v = 2l_c$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 1$.

Figure 5.8 gives the temporal developments of dimensionless flux, dimensionless vertical finger velocity and dimensionless horizontal expansion rate of finger tip in isotropic case with $l_h = l_v = 2l_c$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 1$. Comparison of Figures 5.5 and 5.8 shows that the mean asymptotic dissolution rate in heterogeneous media is a little higher than that in homogeneous media with the same geometric mean permeability, but the variance

Figure 5.8: Isotropic case with $l_h = l_v = 2l_c$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 1$: temporal developments of (a) dimensionless dissolution rate, (b) dimensionless vertical finger tip velocity and (c) dimensionless horizontal expansion rate of finger tip.

of the asymptotic dissolution rate in heterogeneous media is much greater than that in homogeneous media; this means that it would be improper to use σ_Y^2 to predict the dissolution rate, because the uncertainty increases with σ_Y^2 . The horizontal expansion rate of finger tip in isotropically heterogeneous medium is closer to the vertical finger tip velocity; this means that the relative effect of lateral mixing in isotropically heterogeneous medium is larger than that in homogeneous medium.

Figure 5.9 gives the temporal developments of dimensionless flux, dimensionless vertical finger velocity and dimensionless horizontal expansion rate of finger tip in anisotropic case with $l_h = \text{infinite}$, $l_v = 2l_c$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 1$. Comparison of Figures 5.5 and 5.9 shows that the asymptotic dissolution rate in layered formation is in general smaller than that in homogeneous media with the same geometric mean permeability; this is because of the low effective vertical permeability in the layered formation. Comparing Figures 5.8 and 5.9, we can find that the horizontal expansion rate of finger tip in anisotropic medium is much closer to the vertical finger tip velocity; this means that the relative effect of lateral

Figure 5.9: Anisotropic case with $l_h = \text{infinite}$, $l_v = 2l_c$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 1$: temporal developments of (a) dimensionless dissolution rate, (b) dimensionless vertical finger tip velocity and (c) dimensionless horizontal expansion rate of finger tip.

mixing in anisotropic media is larger than that in isotropically heterogeneous media with the same variance and geometric mean permeability. If we compare the homogeneous case, isotropically heterogeneous case and the anisotropically heterogeneous case, we can see that the variance of intrinsic permeability (σ_Y^2) can either enhance or suppress the mixing, depending on the correlation length (l_h, l_v). This indicates that the combined mechanism of σ_Y^2 , l_h and l_v is quite complex (*Kalia and Balakotaiah, 2009*), and thus we do not suggest use these parameters to predict the dissolution rate. An extreme explanation of this statement is that the correlation length can hardly affect the flow process if the variance is very small (*Kalia and Balakotaiah, 2009*).

Figure 5.10 gives the concentration profiles of CO_2 mass fraction for isotropic case with $l_h = l_v = 2l_c$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 1$ and Figure 5.11 gives the concentration profiles for anisotropic case with $l_h = \text{infinite}$, $l_v = 2l_c$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 1$. Comparing Figures 5.6 and 5.10, we can see that distribution of the fingers are uniform in homogeneous media while the fingers in isotropically heterogeneous media form preferential channels and fast reach the bottom. Comparing Figures 5.6 and 5.11, we can see that the lateral expansion of the fingers in layered formation is more significant than that in homogeneous media and that the vertical

penetration of fingers is hindered by the low permeable layers.

Figure 5.10: Isotropic case $l_h = l_v = 2l_c$ with $\sigma_Y^2 = 1$: temporal development of normalized CO_2 mass fraction, X^{C*} .

Figure 5.11: Anisotropic case $l_h = \text{infinite}$, $l_v = 2l_c$ with $\sigma_Y^2 = 1$: temporal development of normalized CO_2 mass fraction, X^{C*} .

5.3.2 Empirical Predictors for the Dissolution Rate in Heterogeneous Fields

5.3.2.1 Selection of Most Relevant Parameters

Because we have numerous parameters to describe the porous media and liquids, finding the most relevant parameters is a key step in deriving an efficient and elegant predictor for normalized characteristic dissolution rate, F_{nc}^* . In the following, we will explain how we select the most relevant parameters for predicting the F_{nc}^* .

First, we select five candidate parameters- $\ln(C_{tv}, C_{th}, C_{fv}, C_{fh}, v_{ncf,v}^*)$. Here, we propose that the dissolution rate, which is governed by the mass convection in the vertical

direction, should be closely related to the vertical conductivity, which is reflected by $v_{ncf,v}^*$, C_{tv} and C_{fv} . The GDC is caused by instability (i.e. non-uniformity) in the horizontal direction, so the instability is affected by the horizontal mass exchange. Therefore, we also propose that the dissolution rate is affected by the horizontal flow conductivity, which is reflected by C_{th} and C_{fh} . Here, we have assumed the relation between the F_{nc}^* and these five independent variables is log linear. The first four (C_{tv} , C_{th} , C_{fv} , C_{fh}) are representative field parameters of a porous medium while the last one ($v_{ncf,v}^*$) is a character specialized for the GDC. From the five independent field parameters we can derive two linearly dependent parameters, ratio of transport connectivity $\ln a_t = \ln(C_{tv}/C_{th})$ and ratio of flow connectivity $\ln a_f = \ln(C_{fv}/C_{fh})$. Actually, from these five independent candidate parameters, we can also derive many other dependent parameters based on linear combination.

Second, determine the how many parameters should be used. The predictor would be have a very complex form if all the five candidate parameters are used. A good predictor should have a simple form with minimum number of parameters. To this end, we need to remove the parameter if this parameter is linearly dependent on the other parameters. Therefore, we should first determine the maximum number of independent parameters that can be used. To this end, we need to analyze the dimension of the variable space. The number of the independent variables should be no larger than the dimension of the variable space. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is conducted to analyze the dimension of the variable space ($\ln C_{fv}$, $\ln C_{fh}$, $\ln C_{tv}$, $\ln C_{th}$, $\ln v_{ncf,v}^*$, $\ln F_{nc}^*$). Six independent variables correspond to six independent principal components. The PCA result show that the six components, respectively, explain 49.5%, 24.0%, 18.4%, 4.3%, 2.4% and 1.3% of the variance of the variable space; from this, we can see that the first three components almost explain 92% of the variance of the variable space and including the fourth component does not significantly increase the explanation of the variance of the variable space. This means the dimension of the variable space is three and we need at most three variables to explain the total variable space. We only show the details of first two principal components $PC1$ and $PC2$, given in Figure 5.12, a biplot of the component vectors and the distances from the origin to the projection points of the variation vectors on the principal components. From Figure 5.12, we can see that the vector for the first principal component is $PC1 = (0.52, -0.06, 0.18, -0.34, 0.52, 0.55)$, which are the distances from the origin to the projection points of component vectors on the axis of $PC1$, which means $\ln F_{nc}^*$ is proportional to $(\ln C_{fv}, \ln C_{tv}, \ln v_{ncf,v}^*)$ and inversely proportional to $(\ln C_{fh}, \ln C_{th})$; moreover, because the coefficient values for the $\ln v_{ncf,v}^*$ and $\ln C_{fv}$ are larger than that for $\ln C_{tv}$, we conclude that $v_{ncf,v}^*$ and C_{fv} have stronger effect on the F_{nc}^* . From Figure 5.12, we can also see that the absolute values of the distances from the origin to the projection points of the variation vectors on the axis of the $PC1$ are generally larger

than those on the axis of $PC2$, which means the $PC1$ explains more variation of the data distribution. Finally, we conclude that a three dimensional variable space can efficiently explain the relation among six variables; that is we need at most three parameters to predict the dissolution efficiency.

Third, once we know that we can use at most three parameters, we need to determine which three parameters should be used. The fact that we have in total five candidate parameters means some parameters are strongly linearly dependent on each other and the linearly dependent parameters offer redundant information. The rule of selecting the parameters is that the selected variables should have least correlation to each other. As we know using the linearly dependent parameters will only increase the complexity of the formula without significantly increasing the accuracy, because they contain quite similar information. Again, PCA test is conducted on each pair of the five candidate parameters to analyze the relation between any two variables. For instance, the PCA result on $(\ln C_{fv}, \ln C_{fh})$ shows that the two principal components, respectively, explain 57.1% and 42.9%, which means these two parameters are not significantly linearly dependent; the PCA result on $(\ln C_{fv}, \ln v_{ncf,v}^*)$ shows that the two principal components, respectively, explain 89.6% and 10.4%, which means these two parameters are significantly linearly dependent. This means if we have selected $\ln C_{fv}$ as one parameter to construct the predictor, we can use $\ln C_{fh}$ as another parameter, but we cannot use $\ln v_{ncf,v}^*$. Finally, from the PCA results on every pair of the five candidate parameters (detailed information is not shown here), we find that we can use $(\ln C_{tv}, \ln C_{fv}, \ln C_{fh})$ or $(\ln C_{tv}, \ln v_{ncf,v}^*, \ln C_{fv}/C_{fh})$ to construct the predictor. Besides, we also used the simple combination $(\ln C_{fv}, \ln C_{fh})$, which has been used in literature, to construct the predictor.

Here, we employ parameterized approach to obtain the empirical predictor for GDC-induced dissolution rate in heterogeneous fields. The parameterized approach requires a pre-given form of formula. The parameterized approach is easy to implement but it needs sophisticated knowledge of the physical system to give a reasonable form of the predictor. If the problem is not well studied, a simpler formula with less complexity is preferred over a complex formula, because the complex formula usually suffers from overfitting, i.e., high instability. Although the precision increases with the number of parameters, the number of coefficients and the complexity of the formula, a too complex formula cannot filter out the noise of the data and could blur the physical meaning of the predictor. In the case of GDC-induced dissolution in heterogeneous media, existing formulas have quite simple form, due to the fact that sophisticated knowledge on GDC is lacking. Here, we prudently attempt to extract a simple but a little more sophisticated predictor for the GDC-induced dissolution in heterogeneous fields with a small number of parameters.

Finally, we use three pairs of parameters to generate three empirical formulas for

Figure 5.12: The PCA for $\ln(C_{tv}, C_{th}, C_{fv}, C_{fh}, v_{ncf,v}^*, F_{nc}^*)$.

predicting the dissolution rate. They are

$$\ln F_{nc}^* = \eta_1 \ln C_{tv} + \eta_2 \ln C_{fv} + \eta_3 \ln C_{fh} + \ln \eta_4, \quad (5.28)$$

$$\ln F_{nc}^* = \eta'_1 \ln C_{tv} + \eta'_2 \ln v_{ncf,v}^* + \eta'_3 \ln a_f + \ln \eta'_4, \quad (5.29)$$

$$\ln F_{nc}^* = \eta''_1 \ln C_{fv} + \eta''_2 \ln C_{fh} + \ln \eta''_3, \quad (5.30)$$

i.e.,

$$F_{nc}^* = \eta_4 C_{tv}^{\eta_1} C_{fv}^{\eta_2} C_{fh}^{\eta_3}, \quad (5.31)$$

$$F_{nc}^* = \eta'_4 C_{tv}^{\eta'_1} v_{ncf,v}^{*\eta'_2} a_f^{\eta'_3}, \quad (5.32)$$

$$F_{nc}^* = \eta''_3 C_{fv}^{\eta''_1} C_{fh}^{\eta''_2}, \quad (5.33)$$

where, η , η' and η'' are the constants to be obtained by fitting the data from numerical simulations and $\ln a_f = \ln C_{fv} - \ln C_{fh}$.

In summary, we propose three formulas- (5.31), (5.32) and (5.33)- to estimate the

dissolution rate.

5.3.2.2 Data Regression

Here, we assume the relation between dissolution rate satisfies Formulas (5.31), (5.32) or (5.33). When these three formulas are used to fit the simulation results based on the field and fluid characters listed in Tables 5.2 and 5.3, we have the following results:

$$F_{nc}^* = 0.86 \cdot C_{fv}^{1.17} C_{fh}^{-0.14} C_{tv}^{0.09}, \quad (5.34)$$

$$F_{nc}^* = 1.02 \cdot a_f^{0.375} v_{ncf,v}^{*1.00} C_{tv}^{0.01} \approx v_{ncf,v}^* a_f^{0.375} \approx v_{ncf,v}^* a_f^{\gamma_f}, \text{ with } \gamma_f \in (0, 0.5), \quad (5.35)$$

$$F_{nc}^* = 0.99 \cdot C_{fv}^{1.31} C_{fh}^{-0.34} \approx C_{fv} a_f^{0.3} \approx C_{fv} a_f^{\gamma_p}, \text{ with } \gamma_p \in (0, 0.5). \quad (5.36)$$

When deriving Formulas (5.35) and (5.36), we have made simplifications. We eliminate from Formula (5.35) the vertical transport connectivity, of which the power is relatively small. Especially, when $\gamma_p = 0$, i.e., $F_{nc}^* = C_{fv}$, Formula (5.36) turns out to be the formula given in *Elenius and Gasda (2013)*. Rearranging the formulas (5.35) and (5.36) in such a way only negligibly affect their performance. Formulas (5.35) and (5.36) are attractive because their forms are physically sound, indicating that the dissolution rate is linearly proportional to vertical finger tip velocity, proportional to the vertical flow connectivity and proportional to the γ_f or γ_p power of vertical to horizontal flow connectivity. From Equations (5.34) to (5.36) we can see that the horizontal mixing will undermine the dissolution rate driven by GDC. This phenomenon is similar to the hydrodynamic dispersion which is driven by longitudinal convection and transverse diffusion; the transverse diffusion suppresses the longitudinal dispersion, which is driven by the nonuniform of the velocity profile and nonuniform of the concentration profile. For horizontally layered fields, the horizontal mixing can be enhanced by the horizontal channeling, which means the nonuniformity in the horizontal direction is suppressed; as such, vertical mass exchange (i.e., dissolution) will be suppressed.

When simplified forms of (5.35) and (5.36) are used and $\gamma_f = \gamma_p = 0.5$, the root mean square errors (RMSEs) of Formula (5.34), (5.35) and (5.36) are, respectively, 39%, 27% and 40%. Formula (5.35) obviously outperforms Formulas (5.34) and (5.36). The performances of Formulas (5.34) and (5.36) are almost the same, while the latter has quite elegant form. Therefore, we drop Formula (5.34). The RMSEs are acceptable considering the fact that the dissolution rate can vary by 15% even in the homogeneous field due to very small random perturbation (*Pau et al., 2010*). In the following section we will discuss in detail

the performance of Formulas (5.35) and (5.36).

5.3.3 Discussion and Comparison with the Existing Formulas

Currently, to our best, only two studies offer empirical formulas for estimating the GDC-induced dissolution rate in heterogeneous fields, while the rest studies are only qualitative analyses. The first formula, given by *Elenius and Gasda* (2013), is

$$F_{nc}^* = C_{fv}, \quad (5.37)$$

which is equivalent to Formula (5.36) when $\gamma_p = 0$.

The second formula, given by *Green and Ennis-King* (2014), is

$$F_{nc}^* = \sqrt{C_{fv}C_{fh}} = \frac{C_{fv}}{\sqrt{a_f}}. \quad (5.38)$$

Elenius and Gasda (2013) assume the dissolution rate is only controlled by the vertical flow connectivity, without considering the effect of effective horizontal flow connectivity. *Green and Ennis-King* (2014) proposed that the dissolution rate is controlled by the geometric mean of horizontal flow connectivity and vertical flow connectivity. From Formula (5.38) we can see that *Green and Ennis-King* (2014) assumed that the horizontal permeability can increase the dissolution rate. The form of Formula (5.38) is contrary to the form of Formulas (5.34), (5.35) and (5.36), the latter three indicating that horizontal permeability can suppress the dissolution rate. We will see that Formula (5.38) obviously overestimates the numerical results.

The performance of Formulas (5.35) to (5.38) are shown in Figures 5.13 and 5.14. In Formulas (5.35) and (5.36), we respectively choose $\gamma_f = 0.375$ and $\gamma_p = 0.3$. When $\gamma_p = 0$, Formula (5.36) turns out to be the formula of *Elenius and Gasda* (2013), i.e., Formula (5.37).

For isotropic cases, the RMSEs for formulas (5.35) with $\gamma_f = 0.375$, (5.36) with $\gamma_p = 0.3$, (5.37) and (5.38) are, respectively, 18%, 36%, 36% and 42%. The performances of these formulas for the isotropic fields are given in Figure 5.13, from which we can see that the performances of formulas (5.36), (5.37) and (5.38) are quite similar. This is because the in isotropic cases the horizontal flow connectivity (C_{fh}) and vertical flow connectivity (C_{fv}) are quite similar (i.e., $a_f \approx 1$). If the $C_{fh} = C_{fv}$, then these three formulas are the same. The performance of Formula (5.35) is much better than those of formulas (5.36), (5.37) and (5.38). This means the dissolution rate is significantly related to the vertical finger tip velocity.

The performances of these formulas for the anisotropic fields are shown Figure 5.14. The RMSEs for Formulas (5.35) with $\gamma_f = 0.375$, (5.36) with $\gamma_p = 0.3$, (5.37) and (5.38) are, respectively, 31%, 41%, 64% and 152%. From Figure 5.14, we can see that the

Figure 5.13: Comparison of the performances of Formulas (5.35) with $\gamma_f = 0.375$, (5.36) with $\gamma_p = 0.3$, (5.37) and (5.38) for isotropic fields; note that Formula (5.37) is Formula (5.36) with $\gamma_p = 0$.

Figure 5.14: Comparison of the performances of Formulas (5.35) with $\gamma_f = 0.375$, (5.36) with $\gamma_p = 0.3$, (5.37) and (5.38) for anisotropic fields; note that Formula (5.37) is Formula (5.36) with $\gamma_p = 0$.

performance of Formula (5.35) degenerates slightly in the anisotropic fields, but it is still the best estimator. Formula (5.38) obviously overestimates the anisotropic cases. Formula (5.36) with $\gamma_p = 0.3$ performs better than the formula of *Elenius and Gasda* (2013) when the dissolution rate is small. In general, the formula of *Elenius and Gasda* (2013) tends to slightly overestimate the dissolution rate because it neglects the anisotropic effect..

Overall, Formulas (5.35) and (5.36) offer satisfactory estimation of the dissolution rate in heterogeneous media. The formula of *Elenius and Gasda* (2013), which is a part of Formula (5.36), tends to slightly over estimate the dissolution rate. The formula of *Green and Ennis-King* (2014), which is contrary to Formula (5.36), obviously fails to estimate the dissolution rate.

If we define

$$J(t^*) = \ln \left\langle \frac{F_n^*(t^*)}{F_{nc,estimated}^*} \right\rangle, \quad (5.39)$$

where, $F_{nc,estimated}^*$ is the estimated dimensionless characteristic dissolution rate from predictors (5.35) with $\gamma_f = 0.5$, (5.36) with $\gamma_p = 0.5$, (5.37) or (5.38); $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes the ensemble average (moving average) of all the simulations. $J > 0$ means the predictor underestimates the dissolution. The temporal development of J is given in Figure 5.15. We note that when $t^* < 10000$, the ensemble average is obtained from almost all the 415 simulations listed in Table 5.3, while when $t^* > 10000$, most data are from the anisotropic cases, because the simulations for the isotropic cases have ceased (the fingers in the isotropic cases has touched the bottom) at around $t^* = 10000$. From Figure 5.15 we can see that Formulas (5.37) (i.e., Formula (5.36) with $\gamma_p = 0$) slightly overestimates the dissolution rate, while Formula (5.36) with $\gamma_p = 0.5$ slightly underestimates the dissolution rate. This means the γ_p should be in the range of (0,0.5). We can also see from Figure 5.15 that Formula (5.38) significantly overestimates because Formula (5.38) improperly represents the anisotropy. Both Formula (5.35) offers quite satisfactory estimation of the simulation results.

In order to show how γ_p and γ_f vary in different setups, we select γ_p and γ_f for each group of anisotropic fields so that the predicted dissolution rate agrees with the simulated one. The selected γ_p and γ_f are listed in Table 5.4. All the selected values for the γ_p and γ_f are within the range (0,0.5). We note that for the cases with $\sigma_Y^2 = 0.1$, the anisotropic ratio is close to unit and thus the results are not sensitive to the γ_f and γ_p . The performance of the predictors (5.35) and (5.36) with the selected γ_f and γ_p is given in Figure 5.16. From Figure 5.16 we can see that with the parameters listed in Table 5.4, Formulas (5.35) and (5.36) can well predict the dissolution rate for the anisotropic cases.

For the purpose of comparison, we also show in Figure 5.17 the performance of the formulas proposed by *Elenius and Gasda* (2013) and *Green and Ennis-King* (2014). Looking at the anisotropic cases in Figure 5.17, we can see that *Green and Ennis-King* (2014) significantly overestimates the dissolution rate when the $\sigma_Y^2 \geq 1$, and that *Elenius*

Figure 5.15: Comparison of the performance of formulas (5.35), (5.36), (5.37) and (5.38).

Table 5.4: Permeability heterogeneity.

Field	l_v/l_c	l_h/l_v	σ_Y^2	γ_f	γ_p
Anisotropic	2	2	0.1	0.5	0.5
Anisotropic	2	4	0.1	0.5	0.5
Anisotropic	2	4	1	0	0
Anisotropic	2	4	4	0.3	0
Anisotropic	2	Infinite	1	0.5	0.4

and Gasda (2013) overestimates the cases of $l_h = inf$, $l_v = 2l_c$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 1$, where the permeability has strongly layered distribution. If we compare the results for the isotropic cases in Figures 5.16 and 5.17, we can see that the results for Formula (5.36), (5.37) and (5.38) are nearly the same, because the anisotropic effect is negligible when $\sigma_Y^2 = 0.1$.

In the end of this section, we claim that Formulas (5.35) and (5.36), with elegant and physically sound forms, outperform the existing predictors for GDC-driven dissolution rate. Both formulas (5.35) and (5.36) indicate that the dissolution rate will decrease if we fix the vertical permeability and increase the horizontal permeability. Formulas (5.35) and (5.36), respectively, indicate the dissolution rate is proportional to the vertical flow connectivity and the vertical finger tip velocity. The physical explanation is given in the following. The dissolution is driven by unstable convection in vertical direction, and this instability can be visually described as the finger width, with small finger representing strong instability. On the one hand, if we fix the vertical permeability and increase the horizontal permeability, the horizontal expansion rate of the unstable fingers is enhanced and the unstable fingers become less sharp and penetrate less deep. If the vertical mass exchange rate is smaller than the horizontal mass exchange rate, we cannot see unstable finger (or the finger width is infinite), because the instability is wiped out by lateral mixing. For instance, when the permeability is very low we can hardly see the unstable fingers because the horizontal mass exchange is close to the vertical mass exchange, both of which

Figure 5.16: The performance of formulas (5.35) and (5.36) for each individual group of fields.

Figure 5.17: The performance of formulas (5.37) and (5.38) for each individual group of fields.

are close to the diffusion rate. On the other hand, increasing the vertical flow connectivity of course will increase the vertical mass exchange and thus increase the dissolution rate. Therefore, we conclude the GDC-induced dissolution can be enhanced by the vertical flow connectivity and the ratio of vertical to horizontal flow connectivity. Nevertheless, the proposed formulas may not be able to completely and precisely reflect the sophisticated mechanism of the GDC process, but it can at least offer acceptable results for engineering purpose. We do not doubt that there exists a more sophisticated formula with more proper form and parameter selection.

5.4 Conclusions

Although there are numerous theoretical, numerical and experimental studies on GDC in GCS process, there are still two issues to clarify.

(1) For the homogeneous field, the dimensionless characteristic dissolution rate (F_{c0}^*) varies in different literature even the same boundary conditions are used. For instance, in the case of impermeable (i.e. diffusion only) top boundary condition, the F_{c0}^* in *Elenius and Johannsen* (2012a) is 0.02, being 25% larger than 0.015 to 0.017 in *Pruess and Zhang* (2008). The difference could be attributed to different setup designs or numerical models. If different boundary conditions are considered, the results of the researches are more different but the number of literature is very small, which means we need more researches to validate the results of current researches. For instance, if the top boundary condition is changed from impermeable boundary to CTZ, the numerical researches are only *Elenius and Johannsen* (2012a) and *Martinez and Hesse* (2016), and their results are different from each other and from those experimental studies in *Backhaus et al.* (2011) and *Rasmusson et al.* (2015c) (see Table 5.1). It is therefore necessary to introduce more data to the data pool as reference for future applications.

(2) For the heterogeneous field, the study on GDC is even more scarce and usually only qualitative results are given. These qualitative results conflict with each other. For instance, the results from *Green and Ennis-King* (2010), *Farajzadeh et al.* (2011), *Chen et al.* (2013) and *Kong and Saar* (2013) show that heterogeneity can enhance the dissolution, but actually, heterogeneity can also suppress the GDC. Several researchers have attempted to quantitatively study the dissolution in the heterogeneous field, but the field design may not be general (*Chen et al.*, 2013; *Elenius and Gasda*, 2013; *Green and Ennis-King*, 2014). For instance, the simulations in *Elenius and Gasda* (2013) are only conducted in fields with horizontal barriers. Moreover, different variables (e.g. variance of log permeability, Dykstra-Parsons coefficient and effective vertical permeability) are used to predict the GDC process. However, we need to justify if these variables are feasible or efficient to predict GDC process and if there are other more efficient variables.

Several basic conclusions are given as following.

(1) For isotropically homogeneous fields, when the top boundary is open and the pressure and concentration are fixed, the dimensionless characteristic dissolution rate (F_{c0}^*) is obtained to be 0.09; that is, the dimensional characteristic dissolution rate (F_{c0}) for homogeneous fields is

$$F_{c0} = 0.09 X^{C,top} \rho^{C,top} \frac{\Delta \rho g \kappa_g}{\mu}.$$

(2) For heterogeneous fields, we have obtained two elegant formulas that can be used to predict the normalized dimensionless characteristic dissolution rate:

$$F_{nc}^* = v_{ncf,v}^* a_f^{\gamma_f}, \text{ with } \gamma_f \in (0, 0.5) \quad (5.35)$$

and

$$F_{nc}^* = C_{fv} a_f^{\gamma_p}, \text{ with } \gamma_p \in (0, 0.5). \quad (5.36)$$

Especially, Formula (5.36) degenerates to the formula of *Elenius and Gasda* (2013) if $\gamma_p = 0$. These two formulas apply for anisotropic fields as well as isotropic fields.

(3) The obtained formulas are physically sound, although they are obtained by linear regression. The obtained formulas indicate that (1) F_{nc}^* is proportional to the vertical flow connectivity and vertical finger tip velocity, and (2) F_{nc}^* is proportional to the γ_p or γ_f power of the ratio of vertical to horizontal flow connectivity. The dissolution rate is more related to the vertical finger tip velocity rather than the vertical flow connectivity. The proposed formulas are superior to the two existing formulas, which either ignoring the anisotropic effect or improperly representing the anisotropic effect.

(4) The results from this study offer the small scale dissolution rate for upscaled study on CO_2 storage. In regional-scale simulation with very long time scale, the employed large grid size and long time step fail to correctly reveal GDC, because very fine grid discretization and short time scale are required to capture GDC (*Pruess and Nordbotten*, 2011; *Gasda et al.*, 2012). An often-used upscaled method incorporates GDC by adding a sink rate to the CO_2 plume in the regional-scale simulation. This sink rate is important in estimating the fate of CO_2 plume. Results show that neglecting the GDC-induced dissolution trapping can lead to improper estimation of the fate of CO_2 plume (*Gasda et al.*, 2011). Formulas (5.35) and (5.36) can be used to estimate the sink rate in regional-scale simulations.

Several notes on GDC are also given as following.

(1) We cannot draw a conclusion that formations of high vertical permeability should be given preference in order to increase dissolution efficiency and reduce possibilities of CO_2 leakage. Although the results show lower dissolution efficiency in layered ‘mille-feuille’ systems, the overall dissolution efficiency may be enhanced by the layered system

considering that the layered ‘mille-feuille’ formation could increase the contact area between the CO_2 and brine during the injection period. If the field is isotropic, the injected CO_2 plume will move upward and form a thick plume beneath the caprock; the interface between CO_2 and brine phase is smooth and relatively small. If the field has layered permeability distribution, the plume will tend to move laterally in several high permeable layers; the interface between CO_2 and brine phase is sharp and relatively large. Next chapter shows that layered permeability can enhance the dissolution by around 40% during the injection process. Moreover, the vertical effective permeability is decreased in layered formation, hindering the upward movement of the CO_2 plume. Thus the layered formation can provide longer time for the gaseous CO_2 to dissolve into the brine, although the dissolution rate is relatively small. If the high permeable layers locate at the bottom of the reservoir, then the vertical exchange of the CO_2 plume and the brine can further enhance the dissolution.

(2) As the GDC is driven by convection due to gravity difference, the density and viscosity models are really important. The density and viscosity models are affected by salinity, temperature, pressure (formation depth) as well as the CO_2 concentration. For different temperatures, salinities and pressures, the density and viscosity are affected by the CO_2 concentration in different ways. In literature, due to the limitation of the numerical model, some researchers have to assume that the density increase is linearly proportional to the mass fraction; this simplification makes it difficult to reproduce the dissolution in the real field. We assume here temperature is a constant of 60 Celsius, which is applicable when we the formation is around 1.5 km. A more precise model should take into account the temperature as well as salinity and pressure. The temperature gradient can also generate non-negligible effect on the density change and thus affect the GDC (*Rasmusson et al.*, 2015b). When the temperature is high (e.g. >120 Celsius), the dissolution of CO_2 may decrease the brine density and thus depress the unstable mixing (*Lu et al.*, 2009; *Li et al.*, 2015).

(3) The effect of natural background flow and capillary transition zone, which can have impact on the GDC, needs further analysis (*Elenius and Johannsen*, 2012a; *Li et al.*, 2013; *Elenius et al.*, 2014b; *Emami-Meybodi et al.*, 2015).

(4) The results from this study apply also to other subsurface systems, such as contaminant migration, geothermal exploitation, saltwater intrusion and mineral precipitation/dissolution, where the density difference exists (*Zhang and Schwartz*, 1995; *Simmons et al.*, 1999; *Nield et al.*, 2008).

(5) We also note that we can include more parameters and use more sophisticated form to build the predictor for the GDC-induced dissolution rate, but we should not increase the complexity of the predictor if increasing the complexity does not significantly increase the precision; this is especially true when our knowledge on the target system is limited

and the process is highly nonlinear, because a complex predictor usually suffers from overfitting. Moreover, one should be aware that some parameters do affect the dissolution rate but they may not be used to predict the dissolution rate. For instance, the statistic characters of the heterogeneous field- correlation lengths (l_h and l_v) and variance of log permeability (σ_Y^2)- can significantly affect the dimensionless dissolution rate (F^*), but there does not exist direct log-linear relation between F^* and statistic characters l_h , l_v and σ_Y^2 . It has possibility that the proposed formula will be abandoned and replaced by a more sophisticated formula with more reasonable form and more related variables.

Chapter 6

Application of Reactive Two-Phase Flow Model II: CO_2 Dissolution Efficiency during Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS) in Randomly Stratified formations

Description: This chapter is based on a manuscript- Wang Y., Fernandez-Garcia D. & Saaltink M. (2022), *CO_2 Dissolution Efficiency during Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS) in Randomly Stratified Formations*- submitted to *Water Resources Research* (<https://doi.org/10.1002/essoar.10510964.1>).

6.1 Introduction

Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS), which reduces carbon emissions to the atmosphere by storing the captured CO_2 in deep geologic formations, is a promising technique to mitigate climate change (IPCC, 2005, 2008; Szulczewski *et al.*, 2012b). Four trapping mechanisms, taking place at different time-scales, are typically distinguished to confine the CO_2 in the subsurface (Kumar *et al.*, 2005; Riaz *et al.*, 2006b; Bachu *et al.*, 2007; Vilarrasa *et al.*, 2010; Gasda *et al.*, 2012). Structural trapping, which consists of sealing the $CO_2(g)$ with a low permeable caprock, is the most rapid but unstable mechanism because $CO_2(g)$ can potentially escape the formation through faults or failed wellbore casings during seismic activities. Mineral trapping, which considers that CO_2 can dissolve in brine and react with the rock-forming minerals, is the most stable but typically slow. At intermediate time-scales, the safety of GCS is attributed to capillary trapping (residual $CO_2(g)$) and dissolution trapping (dissolved aqueous $CO_2(aq)$ in brine). These two

trapping mechanisms do not directly depend on the integrity of the formation (*Van der Meer, 1995; Flett et al., 2004; Nordbotten and Celia, 2006; Bryant et al., 2008; Strandli and Benson, 2013*). Capillary trapping has been well studied in the literature (*Juanes et al., 2006; Ide et al., 2007*), but fewer studies address dissolution trapping even though a substantial amount of CO_2 can potentially dissolve in the formation due to the existence of large amounts of brine solvent (e.g., *Flett et al., 2004; Lee et al., 2010*). Numerical results reported by *Flett et al. (2004)* have shown that dissolution can trap up to 33% of the injected CO_2 , which is quite close to the capillary trapping efficiency reported in the same field setting. *Lee et al. (2010)* have shown that dissolution trapping is more important than capillary trapping.

In homogeneous formations, the injected CO_2 is known to generate a smooth CO_2 plume, rising to the top of the formation by buoyant forces, and spreading laterally underneath the low permeability cap rock due to advection and dispersion; in the meanwhile, CO_2 dissolves into the brine over a long time (*Lenormand et al., 1988; Bryant et al., 2008; Cottin et al., 2010; Green and Ennis-King, 2010; Mouche et al., 2010; Michael et al., 2010; Bandara et al., 2011; Oldenburg and Rinaldi, 2011; Strandli and Benson, 2013; Plampin et al., 2014; Trevisan et al., 2014; Mori et al., 2015; Trevisan et al., 2015*). However, natural formations are ubiquitously heterogeneous, affecting dissolution estimates in realistic settings. The literature in stochastic contaminant transport in saturated porous media has extensively demonstrated that heterogeneity can strongly deform solute plumes (e.g., *Zinn and Harvey, 2003; Knudby and Carrera, 2005; Fernández-García et al., 2008; Dentz et al., 2011; Henri et al., 2015*). This deformation leads to the stretching and folding of the solute plume, which can increase the surface contact between the solute plume and the ambient groundwater. During the injection of CO_2 , similar effects are expected, potentially enhancing the capacity for CO_2 dissolution. Yet, results obtained in solute transport through saturated porous media cannot be directly extrapolated to CO_2 migration during geological carbon sequestration for two major reasons: the problem involves two fluid phases controlled by viscous and gravity forces with strong nonlinear constitutive equations, and the $CO_2(g)$ plume is affected by dissolution and evaporation.

The effect of permeability stratification during the injection of $CO_2(g)$ in GCS has been observed in several works, which have demonstrated that, after injection, a major proportion of CO_2 -rich phase can enter and move preferentially through relatively high permeability conduits or channels, creating erratic patterns (*Stalkup and Crane, 1994; McGuire et al., 1995; Chadwick and Noy, 2010; Chadwick et al., 2010; Oh et al., 2015; Rasmusson et al., 2015a; Tsang et al., 2001; Obi and Blunt, 2006*). Data from Sleipner field site (*Gregersen, 1998*) in the North Sea, which is a reservoir formed by interbedded sandstones and mudstones, indicated that the injected $CO_2(g)$ was mostly present in several disconnected layers of relatively high permeability with a thickness of about 10

meters (*Chadwick et al.*, 2004, 2005). This illustrates that the stratification of permeability at the meter scale (in the vertical direction) can significantly affect the fate and transport of the $CO_2(g)$ plume. Little is known about the effect that these features have on CO_2 dissolution. Although a host of literature has assessed the fate and transport of the $CO_2(g)$ plume in GCS (e.g., *Gunter et al.*, 2004; *Humez et al.*, 2011; *Kabera and Li*, 2011; *Oh et al.*, 2015), systematic high-resolution stochastic simulations of dissolution trapping in heterogeneous porous media remains lacking. The works of *Ide et al.* (2007), *Hayek et al.* (2009) and *Oh et al.* (2015) studied the effect of heterogeneity on capillary trapping, ignoring dissolution. Other authors (*Doughty et al.*, 2001; *Doughty and Pruess*, 2004; *Gershenson et al.*, 2015a) have only analyzed dissolution trapping in a few idealized depositional settings. In numerical modeling studies, the small-scale variability of permeability is often not explicitly represented (*Birkholzer et al.*, 2009; *Hayek et al.*, 2009; *Lee et al.*, 2010; *Pruess and Nordbotten*, 2011; *Rasmusson et al.*, 2015a; *Onoja et al.*, 2019). Qualitative or quantitative analysis of the impact of discounting the small-scale variability in modeling prediction estimates of geological carbon sequestration has not been reported.

In this chapter, we present high-resolution two-phase flow numerical simulations of injected $CO_2(g)$ moving through a deep saline formation during geological carbon sequestration with the objective to: (i) study the effect of heterogeneity on CO_2 dissolution; and (ii) evaluate the impact of upscaling permeability on dissolution predictions. For this, we consider one of the simplest conceptual models of heterogeneity, that is, a perfectly stratified formation system in which the permeability varies only along the vertical direction. From a practical standpoint, we note that even though perfect stratification of permeability in natural field settings is seldom observed over large horizontal distances, this model can properly represent processes over relatively short distances compared to the horizontal integral scale of permeability, which can vary from few meters to thousands of meters (e.g., *Schwartz*, 2014). Moreover, well-connected geological formations have been shown to behave similar to a perfectly stratified system, as both exhibit continuous paths of relatively high velocity (*Zinn and Harvey*, 2003). This type of heterogeneity has been also used in a number of investigations that explore solute transport behavior in subsurface systems (*Fernández-García et al.*, 2008; *Mouche et al.*, 2010). The numerical simulations we present consider a stochastic framework with multiple realizations of the permeability field, which are represented by a random space function and different degrees of heterogeneity. Dissolution efficiency is then characterized by the first two statistical moments to represent the mean behavior and its uncertainty. We show that heterogeneity and gravity forces control dissolution efficiency, and that for typical gravity forces, heterogeneity may substantially enhance dissolution efficiency. We also show that upscaling permeability can strongly compromise CO_2 dissolution predictions in highly heterogeneous systems.

The chapter is organized as follows. We first present the problem and the mathematical description in Sections 6.2 and 6.3, respectively. We then introduce the computational approach adopted during simulations in Section 6.4. After this, in Section 6.5, we present the results. Section 6.5.1 shows how buoyant forces and heterogeneity affect CO_2 dissolution efficiency, and Section 6.5.2 illustrates how upscaling the permeability impacts on CO_2 dissolution efficiency. Finally, conclusions are summarized in Section 6.6.

6.2 Problem Statement

We consider the injection of supercritical CO_2 through a fully-penetrating well in a deep confined saline formation. The formation is conceptualized as a perfectly stratified formation. Heterogeneity is represented by the spatial variability of the intrinsic permeability, which is assumed to vary in space only as a function of the z -coordinate. We consider the existence of two immiscible fluid phases, the brine phase (l) and the CO_2 -rich phase (g), which are separated by a distinct interface, characterized by a spatially varying retention curve. Brine is represented by a high-concentration solution of Sodium Chloride ($NaCl$) in water (H_2O). Initially, the formation is considered to be fully saturated with brine. Once injected, the CO_2 enters into the formation, displacing the brine and rising towards the top of the formation by buoyant forces. During the migration of CO_2 , dissolution of CO_2 into brine and evaporation of water into the CO_2 -rich phase takes place. The time scale for dissolution and evaporation is smaller than the time scale for transport, and therefore, we consider that reactions are always in local equilibrium (*Xu et al.*, 2004, 2011; *Leal et al.*, 2013). Other reactions are not considered and the temperature is assumed constant. For brevity, the injected supercritical CO_2 is called gas.

6.3 Mathematical Description

6.3.1 Chemical System

The chemical system is composed of three chemical components $\{CO_2, H_2O, NaCl\}$. The first two chemical components $\{CO_2, H_2O\}$ can exist in both liquid and gas phases according to the equilibrium constants of dissolution and evaporation. Thus, mutual solubility between brine and CO_2 -rich phases is taken into account. $NaCl$ remains only in the brine phase. The changes in salinity due to dissolution/evaporation is assumed to be negligible and thereby the molality of $NaCl$ is assumed constant. In total, we have five chemical species: $CO_2(g)$, $CO_2(aq)$, $H_2O(g)$, $H_2O(l)$ and $NaCl(aq)$. The partition of the chemical species between phases is determined by the following equilibrium chemical reactions,

where the subscripts l , g and aq denote the liquid, the gas and the aqueous state, respectively, and the superscript C and H denote the CO_2 and H_2O components, respectively. K^H and K^C are the equilibrium constants, and f_g^β and a_l^β respectively denote the fugacity and the activity of the β chemical component. We follow the partitioning model for CO_2 -brine mixtures presented by *Spycher and Pruess* (2005) to estimate mass compositions in liquid and gas phases (c.f. Chapter 2).

6.3.2 Mass Balance equations

The migration of CO_2 in the saline formation is simulated using a compositional approach. Given that the salinity is constant, we only need two mass balance equations. The macroscopic mass balance equations for the two chemical components of interest $\{CO_2, H_2O\}$ can be written as

$$0 = \mathcal{F}_1 = \sum_{\alpha=l,g} \left[\frac{\partial(\phi S_\alpha \rho_\alpha X_\alpha^H)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^H \mathbf{q}_\alpha) - \nabla \cdot (\phi S_\alpha \mathbf{D}_{\alpha\rho_\alpha} \nabla X_\alpha^H) \right] - Q_g^H, \quad (6.3)$$

$$0 = \mathcal{F}_2 = \sum_{\alpha=l,g} \left[\frac{\partial(\phi S_\alpha \rho_\alpha X_\alpha^C)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^C \mathbf{q}_\alpha) - \nabla \cdot (\phi S_\alpha \mathbf{D}_{\alpha\rho_\alpha} \nabla X_\alpha^C) \right] - Q_g^C, \quad (6.4)$$

where ϕ [-] is the formation porosity, S_α [-] is the saturation of the α -phase, ρ_α [$\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$] is the density of the α -phase, X_α^β [-] represents the mass fraction of component β in phase α , \mathbf{D} [$\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] is the hydrodynamic dispersion tensor, Q_g^H and Q_g^C [$\text{kg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] are the source terms, and \mathbf{q}_α is the fluid flux associated with the α phase given by Darcy's law,

$$\mathbf{q}_\alpha = -\frac{\kappa\kappa_{r\alpha}}{\mu_\alpha} (\nabla p_\alpha + \rho_\alpha g \nabla z), \quad (6.5)$$

where κ [m^2] is the intrinsic permeability, $\kappa_{r\alpha}$ [-] is the relative permeability of phase α , μ_α [$\text{pa}\cdot\text{s}$] is the viscosity, p_α [pa] is the fluid pressure, and g [$\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$] is the gravitational acceleration; herein, the z -axis points upward. Mass balance equations are subject to the following constraints,

$$\omega X_l^H + X_l^C = 1, \quad (6.6)$$

$$X_g^H + X_g^C = 1, \quad (6.7)$$

$$S_l + S_g = 1, \quad (6.8)$$

where $\omega = 1 + 0.05844m_l^S$. Here, we have assumed that the salt only comprises *NaCl*, and the molality of *NaCl* (m_l^S) is fixed.

6.3.3 Constitutive Equations

The saturation of the liquid phase is assumed to be known from the capillary pressure through the $CO_2 - H_2O$ retention curve. In this work, we used the *van Genuchten* (1980) model, given in Appendix C, for the retention and relative permeabilities curves. The dispersion tensor is given in Appendix B. The density and viscosity of the two fluids is affected by the fluid pressures and their mass compositions according to Appendix A.

6.3.4 Numerical Solution

Here, the finite difference code, developed in Chapter 2, is used to simulate reactive two-phase flow system, (6.1) to (6.4). Two state variables, gas pressure and liquid pressure, are updated by solving Equations (6.3) and (6.4) with the aid of constitution equations, through which all the rest variables, such as saturation and $CO_2(aq)$ concentration in brine, can be explicitly expressed with these two independent variables. The constitution equations consist of the formulas for densities, viscosities, relative permeabilities, capillary pressure, Darcy's discharges and mutual solubility. This model has strong advantage in solving the reaction transport of two-phase flow, especially in dealing with phase appearance and disappearance (*Bourgeat et al.*, 2010; *Angelini et al.*, 2011; *Ern and Mozolevski*, 2012; *Neumann et al.*, 2013; *Saaltink et al.*, 2013).

6.4 Computational Approach

6.4.1 Model Setup

We consider a confined saline formation with an isolated fully-penetrating well centered in the middle. The system is represented by an axisymmetric model defined by cylindrical coordinates (r, φ, z) . The z -axis coincides with the center of the fully-penetrating well. Figure 6.1 shows a sketch diagram of the model setup. By symmetry, the solution does not depend on the angular coordinate φ . The top and bottom boundaries are impermeable boundaries, and the outer boundary has constant liquid pressure and zero saturation

Table 6.1: Summary of the parameters adopted during Monte Carlo simulations.

Parameters	Symbol	Units	Values
Domain size	(R, b)	[m]	(5000, 100)
Grid discretization	(N_r, N_z)	[-]	(100, 100)
Porosity	ϕ	[-]	0.1
Initial liquid pressure	p_{li}	[bar]	150
Initial gas pressure	p_{gi}	[bar]	1
Well radius	r_w	[m]	0.1
Total injection mass	M_{inj}	[Mt]	2.5
Parameter for Eq. (C.1)	α_p	[bar ⁻¹]	5
Parameter for Eq. (C.1)	m_p	[-]	0.8
Parameters for Eqs. (C.3)-(C.4)	$(\kappa_{rlm}, \kappa_{rgm})$	[-]	(1,1)
Parameters for Eqs. (C.3)-(C.4)	(ϵ_p, γ_p)	[-]	(0.5,0.5)
Residual saturations	(S_{lr}, S_{gr})	[-]	(0.2,0)
Hydrodynamic dispersivities	(α_L, α_T)	[m]	(5,1)
Molecular diffusion coefficient	D_m	[m ² .s ⁻¹]	10 ⁻⁹
Salinity	m_l^S	[molal]	0.5
Temperature	T_c	[°C]	60

gradient. The system is initially saturated with brine, which is assumed to be at hydrostatic state, i.e., the liquid pressure increases downward with a vertical gradient given by the specific gravity of the liquid phase, $\rho_l g$. The injected $CO_2(g)$ is saturated with water vapor. This is mostly the case in real applications because dry CO_2 can trigger the dissolution of minerals, such as halite, and reduce well injectivity. The radius of the injection well is 0.1 [m]. The initial liquid pressure is $p_{li} = 150$ [bar] on the top layer, and the initial gas pressure is $p_{gi} = 1$ [bar] everywhere. CO_2 is injected at a constant mass injection rate Q_{well} . The parameters adopted during the simulations are summarized in Table 6.1. With these parameters, $Q_{well} \approx Q_g^C$ and Q_g^H is very small ($\sim 0.2\%$). The simulation is terminated when the total injected mass of CO_2 reaches a value of $M_{inj} = 2.5$ [Mt]. The concentration of $NaCl$ (m_l^S) is fixed to 0.5 [molal] and the temperature (T_c) is 60 [°C]. The axisymmetric model grid discretization consists of N_z layers and N_r coaxial rings around the z-axis. The discretization is uniform in the vertical direction but increases linearly with r .

Figure 6.1: Sketch of the simulation setup.

6.4.2 Performance Metric

The analysis of the simulation results is based on the quantification of the total amount of CO_2 dissolved into brine with respect to the total amount of CO_2 injected per unit of time. We therefore define the following performance metric for measuring dissolution efficiency,

$$E(t) = \frac{\mathcal{M}_d(t + \Delta t) - \mathcal{M}_d(t)}{\mathcal{M}_{inj}(t + \Delta t) - \mathcal{M}_{inj}(t)}, \quad (6.9)$$

where $\mathcal{M}_{inj}(t)$ is the total injected mass of CO_2 at time t , $\mathcal{M}_d(t)$ is the total dissolved mass of CO_2 at time t , and Δt is the time step. Numerically, the mass of dissolved CO_2 into brine is indirectly calculated from the mass of undissolved CO_2 as

$$E(t) = \frac{Q_g^C \Delta t - \sum_i [X_g^C S_g \phi V_c \rho_g]_i^{t+\Delta t} + \sum_i [X_g^C S_g \phi V_c \rho_g]_i^t}{Q_g^C \Delta t}, \quad (6.10)$$

where V_c is grid cell volume, i denotes the i th grid cells, and Q_g^C is the mass injection rate of CO_2 .

6.4.3 Stochastic Framework

The simulation approach considers a stochastic description of the natural log of the intrinsic permeability $Y(\mathbf{x}) = \ln \kappa(\mathbf{x})$. The $Y(\mathbf{x})$ random field follows a correlated random space function, characterized by an anisotropic exponential covariance function with mean \bar{Y} , variance σ_Y^2 , vertical correlation length I_v , and a very large horizontal integral scale I_h . We consider that I_h is much larger than the domain size and therefore, for practical purposes, $I_h \rightarrow \infty$. The geometric mean of the permeability is $\kappa_g = 1 \cdot 10^{-13}$ [m²]. The integral scale in the vertical direction l_v is fixed to 5 [m]. We used three different variances σ_Y^2 and six different mass injection rates Q_{well} to analyze the effect of heterogeneity and buoyant forces under different degrees of heterogeneity. Buoyant forces are characterized by the gravity factor G , which is defined as the ratio of gravity forces resulting from fluid density differences to the viscous forces (*Nordbotten and Celia, 2006*), that is,

$$G = \frac{2\pi \Delta \rho \rho_g g \kappa_h b^2}{Q_{well} \mu l}, \quad (6.11)$$

where $\Delta \rho = \rho_l - \rho_g$, b is the thickness of the formation, and κ_h is the effective vertical permeability, which is the harmonic mean in this case. The density of the fluids and the viscosity slightly change with time during the simulations. Based on this, to estimate the gravity factor, we chose to use the spatial mean of these properties obtained at the end of the injection. Synthetic test cases are summarized in Table 6.2. Larger values of G indicate larger density differences between the two fluids and therefore a higher potential for vertical segregation of CO_2 .

Random fields are simulated with the following procedure. We first generate 50 equally likely realizations of a standardized multiGaussian random field $Y_{std}(\mathbf{x})$, characterized by a zero mean and unit variance, with the Sequential Gaussian Simulation method implemented in the SGSIM code (*Journal and Huijbregts, 1976*). For each test case, these 50 standardized realizations are rescaled by $Y(\mathbf{x}) = \bar{Y} + \sigma_Y Y_{std}(\mathbf{x})$ to satisfy the target statistical properties. We then simulate the injection of CO_2 in each realization. The dissolution trapping efficiency $E(t)$ is then characterized by their statistical moments (mean behavior and coefficient of variation). A review of typical statistical properties, mass injection rates and inherent gravity forces from real GCS field applications is shown in Table 6.3. The parameters adopted in our simulations in terms of mass injection rates and gravity forces are representative of real field applications.

Table 6.2: Statistical properties of the random fields and mass injection rates in the different simulated cases.

Case	Q_{well} [Mt/y]	κ_g [m ²]	σ_Y^2 [-]	I_v [m]	$\langle G \rangle$ [-]
1	6.92	10^{-13}	0.1	5.0	0.13
2	2.50	10^{-13}	1.0	5.0	0.13
3	1.80	10^{-13}	4.0	5.0	0.13
4	0.69	10^{-13}	0.1	5.0	1.3
5	0.25	10^{-13}	1.0	5.0	1.3
6	0.18	10^{-13}	4.0	5.0	1.3

Table 6.3: Review of formation statistical properties, mass injection rates and gravity forces from real geological carbon sequestration field sites.

Reservoir	Changhua Coastal Industrial Park ¹	Buzzard's Bench ²	Ordos Basin ³	Sleipner ⁴	Tubåen ⁵	In Salah ⁶
Location	Taiwan	US	China	Norway	Norway	Algeria
Depth [m]	~2220	~2025	~1845	~950	~2470	~1860
Thickness [m]	~1000	~150	~290	~300	~60	~20
κ_g [m ²]	9.8×10^{-15}	2.6×10^{-14}	2.7×10^{-16}	1×10^{-12}	5×10^{-13}	1×10^{-14}
σ_Y^2 [-]	6.9 ^a	5.5 ^b	2.9 ^a	10.6 ^a	5.5 ^b	-
ϕ [-]	0.16	0.16	0.11	0.35	0.13	0.15
m_i^S [molal]	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.6	2.4	-
Q_{well} [Mt/year]	1.0	1.87	0.1	0.84	0.77	1.0
G [-]	0.07	0.03	0.04	$< 10^{-3}$	1.12	0.002

Reference: ¹*Sung et al. (2014)*, ²*Xiao et al. (2019)*, ³*Wang et al. (2016b)*, *Jing et al. (2019)*, ⁴*Arts et al. (2008b)* and *Michael et al. (2010)*, ⁵*Maldal and Tappel (2004)* and *Grude et al. (2013)*, and ⁶*Mathieson et al. (2009, 2011b)*.

^a calculated from log data. ^b calculated from $\sigma_Y^2 \approx R^2/3$, where $R = \log(\kappa_{max}/\kappa_{min})$, as given by *Fogg and Zhang (2016)*.

6.4.4 Upscaling of Permeability

Since the scale of heterogeneity is typically smaller than the size of the numerical discretization used in most groundwater models, numerous authors have investigated whether one can simplify the flow system by substituting the heterogeneous distribution of κ by a representative value. Results in this matter are well established in the literature and reviewed in several papers and books (e.g., *Wen and Gómez-Hernández, 1996; Renard and de Marsily, 1997; Sanchez-Vila et al., 2006*). In particular, it is well-known that the equivalent permeability of a perfectly stratified medium is the arithmetic mean κ_a of the point permeabilities when the flow is parallel to the stratification and the harmonic mean κ_h when the flow is perpendicular to the strata. In our system, that is to say that the equivalent permeability is a second-order symmetric tensor exactly given by

$$\mathbf{K}^e = \begin{bmatrix} \kappa_a & 0 \\ 0 & \kappa_h \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6.12)$$

In this context, this work also evaluates the effect of upscaling permeability on CO_2 dissolution. To achieve this, for each realization of the $Y(\mathbf{x})$ field and test case, we also simulate the injection of CO_2 assuming that the system is homogeneous and characterized by an equivalent anisotropic permeability tensor given by \mathbf{K}^e . The rest of the parameters are kept the same.

6.5 Results

To facilitate the interpretation, results are presented using dimensionless variables, defined according to *Nordbotten and Celia (2006), Silin et al. (2009)* and *Zhao et al. (2014)* as

$$t^* = \frac{t}{t_c}, \quad \zeta = \frac{z}{b}, \quad \xi = \frac{r}{\ell}, \quad S_{ge} = \frac{S_g - S_{gr}}{1 - S_{lr} - S_{gr}}, \quad (6.13)$$

where b is the thickness of the geological formation, S_{ge} is the effective gas saturation, and t_c and ℓ are the characteristic time and length scales, respectively defined as

$$t_c = \frac{\phi\mu_l b}{\Delta\rho g \kappa_g}, \quad \ell^2 = \frac{M_{inj}}{2\pi\phi\rho_g b}. \quad (6.14)$$

In accordance with *Zhao et al. (2014)*, t_c is an approximate estimate of the time needed for the CO_2 to migrate from the bottom of the formation to the top due to buoyant forces. ℓ is a measure of the radial penetration of CO_2 due to advection only.

6.5.1 Effect of Heterogeneity and Buoyant Forces

In this section, we present the effect of heterogeneity and buoyant forces, and their interplay, on CO_2 dissolution. Figures 6.2 and 6.3 show the temporal evolution of the ensemble average of dissolution efficiency and its uncertainty (expressed by the coefficient of variation) for a relatively small and large gravity factor, respectively. In all cases, the temporal evolution exhibits two clear dissolution regimes, characterized by the characteristic time of gravity segregation t_c . At early times ($t < t_c$), gravity segregation controls CO_2 migration, and dissolution efficiency strongly declines with time. After this, for $t > t_c$, when gravity segregation has already developed, the less dense $CO_2(g)$ is overriding the brine, and $CO_2(g)$ plume is mostly spreading laterally. At this point, dissolution efficiency reaches a quasi steady-state behavior with a clear asymptotic value. The decline of dissolution efficiency is attributed to the following. At the very beginning, all the injected CO_2 dissolves into the brine (dissolution efficiency is 100%) until brine becomes saturated and the gas phase appears. After this, the rising of $CO_2(g)$ due to buoyant forces enhances the contact between the brine and gas phases, favoring the mixing between them and therefore dissolution. This process decays with the segregation of $CO_2(g)$ at the top of the formation. After this, $CO_2(g)$ is forced to move laterally by viscous forces, which leads to a steady growth of the interface and thus dissolution efficiency.

Results show that dissolution efficiency generally increases with σ_Y^2 . This effect is more pronounced when the gravity factor is relatively small ($\langle G \rangle = 0.13$). In order to visually understand this effect, in the left panels of Figures 6.4 and 6.5, we present the spatial distribution of $CO_2(g)$ saturation obtained at the end of the injection in a representative realization of the permeability field for different σ_Y^2 and mean gravity factors. Note that, by construction, the underlying heterogeneous structure of the permeability field is the same. Results corroborate the hypothesis that heterogeneity tends to stretch the interface between the gas and liquid phases through preferential channels, increasing the contact between them, and therefore, effectively increasing the mutual solubility between the two phases.

Importantly, results also show that heterogeneity and buoyant forces constitute two important competing factors that control dissolution efficiency. When buoyant forces are relatively low compared to the degree of heterogeneity ($G < \sigma_Y^2$), heterogeneity is the dominant factor and CO_2 migration mostly takes place laterally through high permeability layers, regardless of the buoyant forces. In contrast, when the gravity factor is relatively large compared to the degree of heterogeneity ($G > \sigma_Y^2$), gravity segregation is the dominant process. In this case, vertical segregation is overwhelming and the CO_2 gas plume floats to the top of the formation regardless of the permeability stratification. These features can also be seen in Figures 6.4 and 6.5 by contrasting, for instance, the results obtained with $\langle G \rangle = 0.13$ against those with $\langle G \rangle = 1.3$ for $\sigma_Y^2 = 1$. In this case, the CO_2 gas

Figure 6.2: (a) Temporal evolution of the ensemble average dissolution efficiency $\langle E \rangle$ as a function of the degree of heterogeneity for a mean gravity factor of 0.13 (normal injection rate); (b) Temporal evolution of the corresponding coefficient of variation of the dissolution efficiency.

plume tends to segregate on top of the formation for $\langle G \rangle = 1.3$, while preferentially moving through a high permeability layer when $\langle G \rangle = 0.13$. In all cases, when $\sigma_Y^2 = 4$, the CO_2 gas plume preferentially concentrates in the most permeable layer.

Our simulated dissolution efficiency values are consistent with those reported in the literature. When $\langle G \rangle = 1.3$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 1$, we obtain that the dissolution efficiency is around 20%, which is similar to those reported by *Li et al.* (2017a) and *Li et al.* (2018a) for a synthetic test case with $G \approx 10^3$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 1.5$. *Al-Khdheawi et al.* (2017) also reported an average solubility trapping of approximately 20% in several synthetic homogeneous aquifers with $G \approx 68$. Numerical simulations of the Changhua Coastal Industrial Park field site (*Sung et al.*, 2014) reported a dissolution efficiency of 15.6%. Smaller values are also reported in the literature. *Zhou et al.* (2008) and *Zhou et al.* (2010) obtained that approximately 7% of the injected CO_2 dissolves into brine when the gravity factor ranges between 0.7 and 2.2. We attribute this to the high brine salinity used (around 4 [molal]), which reduces the mass fraction of $CO_2(aq)$ in brine to only around 2.5%. Finally, we

Figure 6.3: (a) Temporal evolution of the ensemble average dissolution efficiency $\langle E \rangle$ as a function of the degree of heterogeneity for a mean gravity factor of 1.3 (relatively slow injection rate); (b) Temporal evolution of the corresponding coefficient of variation of the dissolution efficiency.

notice that in agreement with our results, *Zhang et al. (2017)* also concluded that the dissolution efficiency was insensitive to heterogeneity for $G \approx 19$ and σ_Y^2 smaller than 4.5.

The uncertainty associated with dissolution efficiency is shown in the bottom panels of Figures 6.2 and 6.3. The temporal evolution of CV_E also exhibits two differentiated regimes characterized by t_c . In general, CV_E increases with time as the dissolution efficiency decreases. At large times, when $t > t_c$, CV_E approaches a relatively constant value. As expected, CV_E is larger when dissolution is controlled by the heterogeneity, i.e., when $\sigma_Y^2 > G$. In this case, we can see that the uncertainty increases with σ_Y^2 . When the process is controlled by the gravity segregation, i.e., $G > \sigma_Y^2$, the uncertainty due to σ_Y^2 is reduced. The reason is that when the system is controlled by buoyant forces, the CO_2 tends to float and segregate on the top of the formation, following more or less the same pattern regardless of the distribution of permeability. As a result, the variability in permeability is not strongly transferred to the spatial distribution of CO_2 . This is clearly seen in Figure 6.5, which shows that the distribution of gas saturation for $\sigma_Y^2 = 0.1$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 1.0$ still

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Figure 6.4: Spatial distribution of $CO_2(g)$ saturation obtained with a large gravity factor at the end of the injection ($t=1.2t_c$): (left column) in a representative heterogeneous realization with different rescaled σ_Y^2 ; and (right column) in the corresponding equivalent homogeneous medium.

shared very similar features.

6.5.2 Impact of Upscaling the Permeability

In this section, we present the impact that upscaling the permeability has on dissolution efficiency. To achieve this, for each realization, we substitute the heterogeneous distribution of permeability by an equivalent homogeneous porous medium, characterized by an anisotropic permeability tensor defined by equation (6.12). The dissolution efficiency obtained in the equivalent homogeneous medium is denoted as E_0 . The loss of dissolution efficiency during the upscaling process is expressed by the reduction factor E/E_0 . Figures 6.6 and 6.7 show the temporal evolution of the ensemble average of E/E_0 as a function of σ_Y^2 for the two different gravity factors. Results indicate that upscaling can lead to a significant underestimation of dissolution efficiency in heterogeneity-controlled problems, i.e., $G < \sigma_Y^2$. In these cases, the homogenization of the permeability field does not properly preserve the interplay between the small-scale spatial variability of permeability and dissolution, which is characterized by abrupt changes in permeability that enhance the contact between the gas and brine phases. This is emphasized by the nonlinear nature of the CO_2 -Brine system; the less viscous $CO_2(g)$ preferentially enters into high permeable layers, increasing the mobility of $CO_2(g)$ and thus further enhancing the $CO_2(g)$ flux (Rasmusson *et al.*, 2015a). This nonuniform displacement is also partially attributed to

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Figure 6.5: Spatial distribution of $CO_2(g)$ saturation obtained with a small gravity factor at the end of the injection ($t=12t_c$): (left column) in a representative heterogeneous realization with different rescaled σ_Y^2 ; and (right column) in the corresponding equivalent homogeneous medium.

the low capillary entry pressure in the high permeable layers. For $G = 0.13$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 4$, we found that dissolution efficiency is reduced by a factor close to 1.5 due to upscaling. This reduction factor increases with σ_Y^2 and decreases with G . When $G > \sigma_Y^2$, the problem is gravity-controlled and the upscaling of permeability does not introduce an obvious discrepancy in the estimation of the dissolution efficiency.

In order to visually understand the effect of upscaling on dissolution, Figures 6.4 and 6.5 compare the spatial distribution of CO_2 gas saturation obtained in heterogeneous field (left panels) with their corresponding equivalent homogeneous simulations (right panels). The profile of $CO_2(aq)$ concentration in brine is similar to the profile of saturation distribution, and therefore we only show the profile of saturation distribution. When $G > \sigma_Y^2$, the effect of gravity segregation controls CO_2 plume migration and the injected $CO_2(g)$ floats to the top of the formation regardless of stratification. In this case, buoyant forces destroy the action of heterogeneity, causing an apparent homogenization of the porous media. As a result, the simulated CO_2 plumes obtained in heterogeneous porous media resembles those of the equivalent homogeneous porous medium. This explains why the reduction factor E/E_0 is close to 1 in this case. When $G < \sigma_Y^2$, gravity segregation is overwhelmed by the stratification of permeability. In this case, the injected CO_2 mostly enters into high-permeable layers and dissolves therein, and the $CO_2(g)$ plume distribution departs from the equivalent homogeneous medium. In this case, the CO_2 plume fringe looks

Figure 6.6: (a) Temporal evolution of the reduction factor $\langle E/E_0 \rangle$ in dissolution efficiency for a mean gravity factor of 0.13 due to the upscaling of permeability; (b) Temporal evolution of the corresponding coefficient of variation of the reduction factor in dissolution efficiency.

erratic with CO_2 preferentially flowing through several highly conductive layers without apparently floating to the top of the formation. Therefore, small-scale inclusions of high permeable layers fundamentally control the shape, dynamics and hence the dissolution of CO_2 (Gershenson *et al.*, 2015b,c,a). In this case, the reduction factor of dissolution efficiency increases with σ_Y^2 .

6.5.3 Implications

From a practical point of view, our results indicate that dissolution efficiency can be quite important in complex heterogeneous systems when $G \ll \sigma_Y^2$. Under these conditions, we find that dissolution efficiency can reach values over 30%. At this stage, it is important to highlight that, in most geological formations, the permeability varies in space over 3 orders of magnitude, which means that σ_Y^2 can easily exceed a value of 3 (Fogg and Zhang, 2016). Consequently, the enhancement of dissolution efficiency observed in our simulations

Figure 6.7: (a) Temporal evolution of the reduction factor $\langle E/E_0 \rangle$ in dissolution efficiency for a mean gravity factor of 1.3 due to the upscaling of permeability; (b) Temporal evolution of the corresponding coefficient of variation of the reduction factor in dissolution efficiency.

due to small-scale heterogeneity might be the rule rather than the exception in real field settings. To illustrate this, we map the properties associated with the GCS field sites reviewed in Table 6.3 in a behavior diagram, shown in Figure 6.8. The $\sigma_Y^2 - G$ diagram has been qualitatively drawn from a limited number of simulations and therefore uncertainties associated with transition lines are expected. Nevertheless, the diagram clearly shows that most field sites are heterogeneity-controlled, meaning that dissolution efficiency might be larger than expected. This is consistent with *Goodman et al.* (2013) and *Gershenson et al.* (2015a), who suggest that incorporating the small-scale heterogeneity is critical to reproduce GCS processes.

Figure 6.8: $\sigma_Y^2 - G$ diagram with the simulated test cases, summarized in Table 6.2, and the GCS field sites reviewed in Table 6.3.

6.6 Conclusions

We have investigated dissolution trapping efficiency and its uncertainty during Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS) in randomly stratified saline formations through a set of Monte Carlo two-phase flow compositional simulations involving the dissolution of CO_2 into brine and evaporation of water into the CO_2 -rich phase under different degrees of heterogeneity and gravity factors. Simulation results have provided a statistical description of dissolution efficiency as well as an examination of the impact of upscaling the permeability in numerical models. The following main findings are highlighted:

1. The interplay between heterogeneity and buoyant forces are shown to control the behavior of CO_2 migration and therefore dissolution efficiency. When buoyant forces G are relatively small compared to the degree of heterogeneity σ_Y^2 , lateral CO_2 migration through high permeability layers dominates the overall behavior and dissolution efficiency increases with σ_Y^2 due to the stretching of the CO_2 plume that enhances mixing. In contrast, when buoyant forces dominate, CO_2 vertical segregation controls the behavior, diminishing the influence of heterogeneity on dissolution. A tentative behavior diagram is proposed with a transition line approximately given by $G = \sigma_Y^2$.

2. The temporal evolution of dissolution efficiency is shown to exhibit two clear regimes characterized by the characteristic segregation time t_c . Dissolution efficiency declines with time until the CO_2 gas phase rises to the top of the formation and segregates from the brine phase. After this, when $t \gg t_c$, CO_2 is forced to move laterally (viscosity forces dominate) and dissolution efficiency reaches an almost asymptotic value.
3. We have shown that the upscaling of permeability leads to an underestimation of the dissolution efficiency. This effect is more pronounced in highly heterogeneous systems with small gravity effects ($G < \sigma_Y^2$) due to the fact that lateral finger-like CO_2 plume is generated in this case following the stratification. On the contrary, when $G > \sigma_Y^2$, a single compact $CO_2(g)$ plume floats to the upper portion of the formation regardless of heterogeneity, and upscaling is not significantly affected.
4. We have shown that most GCS field sites operate under $G \ll \sigma_Y^2$, meaning that heterogeneity typically controls dissolution efficiency in real field settings. Knowing that most numerical models that simulate CO_2 dissolution cannot properly represent the small-scale heterogeneity due to an unfeasible discretization of the domain, our results suggest that dissolution efficiency can be underestimated by a factor close to 1.5.

Chapter 7

Summary and Future Work

7.1 Summary

This work studies the Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS) process through numerical modeling. Herein, we first offer three numerical models, all of which have been approved through benchmark tests, and then apply one of them to two specific studies.

The first numerical model is a reactive two-phase flow model that accounts for the mutual solubility between CO_2 -rich phase and brine. This model also considers the density and viscosity change due to the change of pressure and the change of the mass composition in each phase. This model takes advantage of the benefit that all the variables can be directly or indirectly expressed with the two independent variables- gas pressure and liquid pressure- through constitution equations. The Jacobian matrix for solving gas pressure and liquid pressure are based on two governing equations for mass balances of two selected conservative components. Moreover, the proposed model naturally circumvents the complex situation when gas phase is about to appear or disappear.

The second numerical model is simplified reactive three-phase flow model. Compared to the aforementioned reactive two-phase flow model, this second model also considers the dissolution/precipitation of solid phase. In order to simplify the model, we assume the rock is only comprised of calcite and all the reactions are at equilibrium state. However, we still need a complex chemical system to describe the partition among gas, brine and solid phases. To avoid the time-consuming calculation of the complex chemical reaction cell by cell at every time step, we further assume that, at equilibrium state, the mass compositions of different components in brine phase are empirical functions of the gas pressure. These empirical functions are obtained by first calculating the mass compositions of components at different gas pressures and then fitting the results with polynomials. Here, the mass action law is used to calculate the mass compositions of the components, and least square regression is used to get the polynomials. The obtained polynomials are used as constitution equations that express the chemical reactions with only gas pressure. The

process is solved by solving three independent variables- gas pressure, liquid pressure and porosity- based on the mass balances of three selected conservative components. All the rest variables can be obtained with these three independent variables through constitution equations.

The third numerical model is a full reactive three-phase flow model that is comprised of a reaction module and a transport module. The reactive transport process is updated by solving the governing equations in the transport module, where the related chemical reactions are calculated with the chemical reaction module. The chemical reaction module contains all the (kinetic or equilibrium) chemical reactions, through which we can calculate the dependent variables (i.e., masses compositions of all the species) based on independent variables. The transport module contains three implicit transport equations and other explicit transport equations; the three implicit equations are solved to update the three primary independent variables (i.e., gas pressure, liquid pressure and porosity), while the other explicit functions are solved to calculate the secondary independent variables (e.g., the masses of conservative components and the kinetic species). Firstly, the primary independent variables are implicitly solved based on the mass balances of three selected components; secondly, the secondary independent variables are explicitly solved with the updated primary independent variables; finally, the dependent variables are calculated with the updated primary and secondary independent variables. These dependent and independent variables are updated in the same Newton-Raphson loop.

In the first application, the reactive two-phase flow model is used to quantitatively analyze dissolution rate of CO_2 at the interface of the brine and CO_2 -rich phases. The dissolution rate of the overlying $CO_2(g)$ into brine is enhanced due to the gravity-driven-convection (GDC). Here, with aid of systematically numerical simulations, we study how GDC is affected by the effect of permeability heterogeneity, and obtain two physically sound empirical formulas to predict the dissolution rate based on the field characters. Analysis of the results shows that (1) the GDC-induced dissolution rate (F) is proportional to the vertical flow connectivity, which is characterized by the dimensionless effective vertical permeability; (2) F is proportional to the vertical finger tip velocity, which is characterized by the dimensionless maximum cross-sectional mean absolute vertical velocity; (3) in anisotropic formation, the dissolution rate is also proportional to the $\gamma \in (0, 0.5)$ power of the ratio of vertical to horizontal flow connectivity. All the simulations are conducted on length and time scales much smaller than those in the regional scale. The results from these small-scale simulations can be employed as a source term for the regional-scale simulations, where the coarse grid size may not precisely capture the GDC.

In the second application, the reactive two-phase flow model is used to systematically analyze the effect of layered permeability distribution on the dissolution trapping efficiency by using field-scale simulations. This application addresses the injection of CO_2 in perfectly

stratified saline formations under uncertainty. Monte Carlo two-phase flow compositional simulations involving the dissolution of CO_2 into brine and evaporation of water into the CO_2 -rich phase are presented. We systematically analyzed the interplay between heterogeneity and buoyant forces, which is shown to control the migration of the CO_2 plume as well as the temporal evolution of dissolution efficiency. Results show that (1) dissolution trapping plays an important role in GCS, representing around 20% of the injected CO_2 ; (2) the interplay between heterogeneity and buoyant forces controls the behavior of CO_2 migration and dissolution efficiency; (3) in heterogeneity-controlled systems, permeability stratification enhances CO_2 dissolution efficiency by stretching the interface between gas and brine phases; and (4) the upscaling of permeability can lead to an underestimation of the dissolution efficiency. These results offer reference for designing the resolution for large-scale numerical simulations

7.2 Future Work

7.2.1 Effect of Capillary Trapping on GCS

Aside from the dissolution trapping (c.f. Chapters 5 and 6), capillary trapping also plays an important role in determining the safety of GCS (*Doughty and Pruess, 2004; Hovorka et al., 2005; Hesse et al., 2008; Krause et al., 2011; Perrin and Benson, 2010*). Capillary trapping, denoted by residual gas saturation, describes the amount of CO_2 trapped in the CO_2 -rich region that experiences water encroachment. During the post-injection period, the CO_2 plume majorly expands beneath the aquitards and minorly penetrates into the aquitards, under the buoyancy force (*Kumar et al., 2004; Lyle et al., 2005; Mo et al., 2005a,b; Bickle et al., 2007; Singh et al., 2010; Boait et al., 2012*). The buoyancy-driven displacement of the CO_2 by brine is incomplete, due to capillary pressure, which changes relative permeability of water and CO_2 and blocks the CO_2 flow in the form of disconnected bubbles in front of the pore throat. The region of high initial gas saturation will finally decrease to a non-zero residual saturation under the balance between gravity and capillarity (note: after sufficiently long time, this residual saturation will disappear because of dissolution) (*Altundas et al., 2011; Iglaier et al., 2009, 2011, 2015*). The numerical results from *Flett et al. (2004)* show that capillarity can trap 36% of the total injected CO_2 . A brief introduction to capillary trapping is given as follows.

The mass of the CO_2 trapped by capillarity is calculated with

$$\mathcal{M}_c(t) = \sum_i [X_g^C S_{gr} \phi V_c \rho_g]_i^t, \quad (7.1)$$

where, subscript i indicates the i th grid, t the time, X_g^C the mass fraction of $CO_2(g)$ in

gas phase, S_{gr} the residual saturation, ϕ the porosity, V_c is the volume of grid cell and ρ_g the gas density.

In analyzing the capillary trapping, i.e., Equation (7.1), the key is estimating the residual saturation (S_{gr}), which can be approximately estimated by using *Land* (1968) model or *Spiteri et al.* (2008) model, where S_{gr} is a function of maximum gas saturation before imbibition (*Agarwal*, 1967; *Spiteri et al.*, 2008; *Liang and Clarens*, 2018). If *Land* (1968) model is employed, this relation is given as

$$S_{gr} = \frac{S_{gi}}{1 + \eta_S S_{gi}}, \quad (7.2)$$

where, S_{gi} is gas saturation in the beginning of the imbibition and η_S is the parameter determined by the specific field. Experimental results show that the residual saturation of nonwetting phase in supercritical CO_2 /water system is consistent with that in decane/water, oil/water and gas/water systems (*Oak et al.*, 1990; *Pentland et al.*, 2011; *Krevor et al.*, 2012; *Liang and Clarens*, 2018). S_{gr} is affected by the wettability of the formation rock. For a water-wetting rock formation, *Liang and Clarens* (2018) gave $\eta_S \in (1.01, 1.78)$, while *Krevor et al.* (2012) included the mixed or intermediate-wet samples and obtained a larger range for $\eta_S \in (1.0, 2.1)$. *Krevor et al.* (2012) observed that the range of residual CO_2 is between 10% to 33% for different samples. For sandstone samples *Suekane et al.* (2008) obtained the residual gas saturation between 24% and 28%, and *Shi et al.* (2011) obtained residual gas saturation of 28%. *Bachu and Bennion* (2008) reported relatively low values, from 10% to 30%, for residual gas saturation in low permeability sandstones. Oilfield studies (*Kralik et al.*, 2000) show the trapped gas saturation varies from 20% to 40%, while studies also show the trapped gas saturation can vary from 5% to 85% (*Keelan and Pugh*, 1975; *Hamon et al.*, 2001).

The residual gas saturation is then used to modify the retention and relative permeability curves. We note that the residual saturation impacts retention and relative permeability curves (c.f. Appendix C), which could significantly affect the GCS process (*Juanes et al.*, 2006; *Li et al.*, 2013).

Inspired by the fact that the capillary trapping can be altered by using different sequestration strategy, researchers have proposed that the capillary trapping can be enhanced by using water-alternating-gas (WAG) strategy (*Juanes et al.*, 2006; *Ide et al.*, 2007). The goal of WAG is finding the optimum frequency and ratio of water injection to get the maximum capillary trapping. The cost of the additional brine injection may affect the decision making. Future study could analyze how to improve the residual gas trapping with low cost, through a large quantity of numerical simulations.

7.2.2 Effect of Wormhole on GCS

Chemical and biological reactions- for instance, dissolution of mineral and organic matter, adsorption and biomass growth- are ubiquitous in geological systems, such as geological carbon sequestration, enhanced oil recovery, karst formation, saline water intrusion, geological thermal circulation and water storage, etc (*Dillard Nogaret and Blunt, 2000; Zhou et al., 2000; Held and Celia, 2001; Dupin et al., 2001a,b; Acharya et al., 2005; Rezaei et al., 2005; Li et al., 2015, 2018b*). The reaction pattern is controlled by competition among longitudinal convection, transverse dispersion and chemical reaction. High injection rate can generate uniform dissolution patterns where the dissolution occurs uniformly throughout the porous medium, while low injection rate will generate compact dissolution in the inlet. The former case (reaction-rate limited) is dominated by the longitudinal convection while the latter case (mass-transfer limited) is dominated by the transverse dispersion and chemical reaction (*Golfier et al., 2002*). When a moderate injection rate is assigned, the interplay among the three mechanisms may generate partially local dissolution that forms a connected channel called wormhole, which can significantly increase the effective permeability (*Williams et al., 1979; Chang et al., 2001*).

In the GCS process, which is accompanied with chemical reaction among fluids and the formation rock, neglecting the change of the formation rock can lead to unreal results (*André et al., 2007; Szymczak and Ladd, 2009; Vialle and Vanorio, 2011*). Although the scale of the wormhole is very small (ranging from pore size to millimeters) compared to field scale, it can significantly increase the effective conductivity of the formation because the permeability of the wormhole is usually orders of magnitude larger than that of the surrounding unaffected formation (*Golfier et al., 2002; Ott and Oedai, 2015*). This small change in the structure change can also affect the mechanical property of the formation rock, adding uncertainties in geological CO_2 sequestration, such as geological subsidence and response to earthquakes (*Noiriel et al., 2007; Duan and Li, 2008; Vanorio et al., 2008; Bemmer and Lombard, 2010; Egermann et al., 2010; Vanorio et al., 2010; Vialle and Vanorio, 2011; Li et al., 2018b*). Experiments from *Singh et al. (2018)* show that injecting CO_2 -rich brine can locally increase the porosity by one order of magnitude while increase the permeability by 2 times. Experiments from *Vialle et al. (2014)* show that after injecting 290 pore sample volumes of saline water with saturated CO_2 at 1 bar gas pressure, porosity is increased by 7% (from 0.29 to 0.31), and whole permeability is increased by 1 order of magnitude (from $0.12 \times 10^{-12}m^2$ to $0.97 \times 10^{-12}m^2$). Therefore, predicting the alteration of the rock formation due to dissolution/precipitation is important in GCS, because reaction-induced changes in rock porosity fundamentally affect the quantity and quality of CO_2 storage (*Izgec et al., 2008a,b; Hao et al., 2013*).

The dissolution/precipitation pattern is affected by Péclet (Pe) number, Damköhler (Da) number and the kinetic number (N_k). Pe represents the ratio of convection to lateral

dispersion, Da describes the ratio of reaction to convection, and $N_k = Pe \cdot Da$. These numbers are defined as follows.

$$Pe = \frac{ql}{D}, \quad (7.3)$$

$$Da = \frac{\mathcal{A}_s \mathcal{K} l}{q c_{eq}} \quad (7.4)$$

and

$$N_k = Pe \cdot Da = \frac{\mathcal{A}_s \mathcal{K} l^2}{D c_{eq}}, \quad (7.5)$$

here, q [$\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] is the discharge, l [m] the length scale of pore (or the core), D [m^2s^{-1}] the diffusion coefficient, \mathcal{A}_s [m^{-1}] the effective area per unit volume of rock, \mathcal{K} [$\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] the reaction rate per unit area, and c_{eq} [$\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$] the equilibrium concentration of the mineral species (*Smith et al.*, 2013; *Ott and Oedai*, 2015). Different conditions may result in different types of dissolution such as compact dissolution, uniform dissolution and ramified wormholes (*Kang et al.*, 2003; *Golfier et al.*, 2002; *Pereira Nunes et al.*, 2016; *Molins et al.*, 2017). The results from *Fredd and Scott Fogler* (1998) showed that a minimum erosive fluid is needed to breakthrough the core when the Damköhler number is neither too large nor too small.

While a large amount of literature focus on the wormhole development in two-phase (liquid and solid) systems ranging from pore scale (*Daccord*, 1987; *Wells et al.*, 1991; *Kelemen et al.*, 1995; *Dijk and Berkowitz*, 1998) to Darcy scale (*Steeffel and Lasaga*, 1994; *Aharonov et al.*, 1995, 1997), only a little literature attempt to study the wormhole development in three-phase (gas, liquid and rock) systems (*Ott and Oedai*, 2015; *Molins et al.*, 2017; *Singh et al.*, 2018). *Ott and Oedai* (2015), via experimental observations, proposed that the wormhole developments are distinct in two-phase and three-phase systems. In the two-phase system, for instance HCl /rock system, the local dissolution is enhanced in the higher permeable region, not only because the dissolution is initially stronger in the high permeable region with high flux of HCl , but also because the dissolution will positively feedback the permeability. However, in the three-phase system, for instance $CO_2(g)$ /brine/rock system, the dissolution is suppressed if we only inject $CO_2(g)$ into the formation, because the $CO_2(g)$ cannot directly react with the rock unless it dissolves into the brine, of which the amount is quite limited. In this $CO_2(g)$ /brine/rock system, the dissolution of rock is not only affected by the volume of $CO_2(g)$ but also affected by the the volume of the brine. The brine losses its erosion ability as soon as it has reacted with the rock, and it will not gain new erosion ability however we inject $CO_2(g)$. As such, the reaction between the rock and the acidified brine stops because there is no supply of 'fresh' acid brine. Moreover, in the three-phase flow system, the low entry pressure of $CO_2(g)$ in the high permeable portion with larger porosity may further

enhance the irregular erosion.

The dissolution pattern, which is affected by the competition among reaction, diffusion and convection, is significantly affected by the heterogeneity of the formation. *Hao et al.* (2013) show that the initial heterogeneity dominates the wormhole development and the power-law based permeability-porosity relation is sensitive to the initial heterogeneity. When permeability heterogeneity is considered, the dissolution/precipitation effect would be more remarkable (*Liu et al.*, 2017). As such, only Pe , Da and N_k may not be enough to characterize the dissolution/precipitation process in strongly heterogeneous porous media (*Panga et al.*, 2005; *Hao et al.*, 2013).

Therefore, because the development of wormhole in three-phase flow systems is quite different from that in two-phase systems, the experience of wormhole in two-phase flow system cannot be directly used for studying the wormhole in three-phase flow systems. Moreover, because the wormhole is significantly affected by the heterogeneity, more work is needed to study the behavior of wormhole in the heterogeneous medium. The programs developed in Chapters 3 and 4 can be employed to study the wormhole in GCS.

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Appendix A

Density and Viscosity

Brine Density

We assume the brine phase density, ρ_l [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$], depends on brine phase pressure, temperature, molality of *NaCl* and concentration of $\text{CO}_2(\text{aq})$. The following implementation can be found in *Garcia* (2003) and references therein. The expression for brine phase is given as below:

$$\rho_l = \rho_{lr} + c \cdot M_{\text{CO}_2} - c \cdot \rho_{lr} \cdot V_\phi, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where, c [$\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$] is number of moles of $\text{CO}_2(\text{aq})$ per unit volume of brine phase; M_{CO_2} [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$] is the molar mass of CO_2 ; V_ϕ [$\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$], the apparent molar volume of $\text{CO}_2(\text{aq})$, is given as

$$V_\phi = 3.751 \times 10^{-5} - 9.585 \times 10^{-8} T_c + 8.74 \times 10^{-10} T_c^2 - 5.044 \times 10^{-13} T_c^3, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where T_c is temperature in Celsius ($^\circ\text{C}$); ρ_{lr} , the brine phase density when there is no CO_2 dissolution, can be calculated with (*Phillips et al.*, 1982)

$$\rho_{lr} = -3.033405 \times 10^3 + 1.0128163 \times 10^4 \iota - 8.750567 \times 10^3 \iota^2 + 2.66310 \times 10^3 \iota^3, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \iota = & -9.9595 \exp(-4.539 \times 10^{-3} m_l^S) + 7.0845 \exp(-1.638 \times 10^{-4} T_c) \\ & + 3.9093 \exp(2.551 \times 10^{-10} p_l), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where, m_l^S [molal] is molality of *NaCl* and p_l [pa] is the pressure of brine. Equation (A.1) applies to $5 < T_c < 297$ [$^\circ\text{C}$] and $p_{sv} < p_l < 300$ [bar]. Equation (A.3) applies to $10 < T_c < 350$ $^\circ\text{C}$, $0.25 < m_l^S < 5$ [molal] and $p_{sv} < p_l < 500$ [bar] (*Phillips et al.*, 1982). Here, p_{sv} is saturated vapor pressure. Rearranging Equation (A.1), we have

Figure A.1: Distributions of ρ_l [$\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$] (left) and ρ_g [$\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$] (right) in (p_l, p_g) field; $T_c = 60[^\circ\text{C}]$ and $m_i^S = 0.5$ [molal].

(*Riano-Vilarrasa, 2012*)

$$\rho_l = \rho_{lr} \frac{1}{1 - X_l^C f_\delta} \approx \rho_{lr} (1 + X_l^C f_\delta), \quad (\text{A.5})$$

with

$$f_\delta = 1 - \rho_{tr} \frac{V_\phi}{M_{CO_2}}. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Because X_l^C , which can also be solved via equilibrium reaction, is a function of gas pressure, liquid pressure and temperature, we can obtain the density of brine phase at any pressures.

For three-phase flow, we assume the dissolution of calcite contributes little on the brine density, and that the brine density is only a function of the molality of $NaCl$ and aqueous CO_2 . This assumption is reasonable, because the concentrations of aqueous species other than Na^+ , Cl^- and $CO_2(aq)$ are negligible compared to the concentration of Na^+ , Cl^- and $CO_2(aq)$ (c.f. Figure 3.1). Therefore, the model by *Garcia (2003)* also applies to the brine density in three-phase flow model where negligible amount of Ca^{2+} and other aqueous species exist. In order to apply formula (A.5) to the simplified equilibrium model in Chapter 3, we only need to put in formula (A.5) the empirical formula for mass fraction of $CO_2(aq)$, i.e., formula (3.30)

CO₂ Density

The density of CO_2 -rich phase is solved by first obtaining the molar volume of CO_2 phase (V [$\text{m}^3\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$]) through solving the cubic form of Redlich-Kwong equation (*Redlich and Kwong, 1949*):

Figure A.2: Distributions of $\frac{d\rho_l}{dp_l}$ (top left), $\frac{d\rho_g}{dp_g}$ (top right), $\frac{d\rho_l}{dp_g}$ (bottom left) and $\frac{d\rho_g}{dp_l}$ (bottom right) in $(\log p_l, \log p_g)$ field; the solid lines are obtained by strictly following the chain rule while the dash lines by finite difference; $T_c = 60[^\circ\text{C}]$ and $m_i^S = 0.5$ [molal].

$$V^3 - V^2\left(\frac{RT_k}{p_g}\right) - V\left(\frac{RT_k b}{p_g} - \frac{a}{p_g T_k^{0.5}} + b^2\right) - \left(\frac{ab}{p_g T_k^{0.5}}\right) = 0. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where, a [$\text{bar}\cdot\text{cm}^6\cdot\text{K}^{0.5}\cdot\text{mol}^{-2}$] and b [$\text{cm}^3\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$] are, respectively, the intermolecular attraction and repulsion of the CO_2 -rich phase; T_k [K] is temperature in Kelvin. For simplification, making the assumption of infinite dilution of water vapor, we use the intermolecular attraction and repulsion of pure CO_2 , a^C and b^C , to represent a and b . This is reasonable as we will see that the fraction of water vapor in CO_2 rich phase is usually less than 1%. Therefore, according to *Spycher et al.* (2003), we have

$$a = a^C = 7.54 \times 10^7 - 4.13 \times 10^4 T_k, \quad (\text{A.8})$$

and

$$b = b^C = 27.8. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Here, we note that Equation (A.7) may have more than one real solutions. The selection of the value depends on which phase- gas or liquid-is more stable. If the more stable phase is gas then we choose the maximum value; otherwise, we choose the minimum value. To

Figure A.3: Distributions of $\log \mu_l$ and $\log \mu_g$ in (p_l, p_g) field; $T_c = 60[^\circ\text{C}]$ and $m_l^S = 0.5$ [molal].

determine which phase is more stable, we need to calculate two works (w_1 and w_2) for phase transition:

$$w_1 = p_g(V_{max} - V_{min}), \quad (\text{A.10})$$

and

$$w_2 = RT \ln \frac{V_{max} - b}{V_{min} - b} + \frac{a}{T^{0.5}b} \ln \frac{(V_{max} + b)V_{min}}{(V_{min} + b)V_{max}}. \quad (\text{A.11})$$

If $w_2 \geq w_1$, then gaseous state is more stable and we choose V_{max} ; otherwise, we choose V_{min} . Multiplying the reciprocal of molar volume by weighed molar mass of CO_2 phase, we obtain the density of CO_2 phase:

$$\rho_g = \frac{M_{\text{CO}_2} x_g^C + M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} x_g^H}{V}. \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Here, the molar fraction of CO_2 and water vapor are calculated with

$$x_g^C = \frac{\frac{X_g^C}{M_{\text{CO}_2}}}{\frac{X_g^C}{M_{\text{CO}_2}} + \frac{X_g^H}{M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

and

$$x_g^H = \frac{\frac{X_g^H}{M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}}{\frac{X_g^C}{M_{\text{CO}_2}} + \frac{X_g^H}{M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}}, \quad (\text{A.14})$$

where, $M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ [$\text{kg} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$] is the molar mass of water; X_g^C and X_g^H are the mass fractions of $\text{CO}_2(g)$ and $\text{H}_2\text{O}(g)$ in CO_2 -rich phase, respectively. Substitution of Equations (A.13)

Figure A.4: Distributions of $\frac{d\mu_l}{dp_l}$ (top left), $\frac{d\mu_g}{dp_g}$ (top right), $\frac{d\mu_l}{dp_g}$ (bottom left) and $\frac{d\mu_g}{dp_l}$ (bottom right) in $(\log p_l, \log p_g)$ field; the solid lines are obtained by strictly following the chain rule while the dash lines by finite difference; $T_c = 60[^\circ\text{C}]$ and $m_i^S = 0.5$ [molal].

and (A.14) into Equation (A.12) gives

$$\rho_g = \frac{1}{X_g^H M_{CO_2} + X_g^C M_{H_2O}} \frac{M_{CO_2} M_{H_2O}}{V}. \quad (\text{A.15})$$

Because X_g^H and X_g^C , which can also be solved via equilibrium reaction, are functions of pressure and temperature, we can obtain the density of CO_2 -rich phase at any pressures. The density obtained by Equations (A.7) to (A.12) applies to temperatures from 283 [K] to 380 [K] and pressures up to 600 [bar].

Densities of Brine and CO_2 -rich phases (in log scale) at different pressure combinations are given in the right panel of Figure A.1, where $T_c = 40$ [$^\circ\text{C}$] and $m_i^S = 0.5$ [molal]. As can be seen from Figure A.1, CO_2 dissolution, due to gas pressure change, has an almost equivalent effect as compressibility on the density of brine phase. However, the density of CO_2 -rich phase is mainly affected by the gas pressure, because the evaporation of H_2O is very small. In virtue of chain rule, we can easily obtain the derivatives of ρ_l and ρ_g with respect to p_l and p_g , given in Figure A.2. In order to check the accuracy of the derivatives, we also give the numerical results for these derivatives, obtained through finite difference $\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x}$. As can be seen from Figure A.2, the results obtained by chain rule agree well

with the finite difference results.

Brine Viscosity

The viscosity of brine phase is calculated by (Garcia, 2003; Kumagai and Yokoyama, 1999)

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_l = & (3.85971 - 1.32561 \times 10^{-2} T_k) m_l^S + (-5.37539 + 1.90621 \times 10^{-2} T_k) (m_l^S)^{1/2} \\ & + (8.79552 - 3.17229 \times 10^{-2} T_k) m_l^C + (-7.22796 + 2.64498 \times 10^{-2} T_k) (m_l^C)^2 \\ & + 1.69956 \times 10^{-9} (p_l - 1 \times 10^5) + \mu_w(T_k, p_l = 10^5 [\text{Pa}]), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.16})$$

where, the liquid pressure is in [Pa], and μ_l [mPa·s] is the viscosity of pure water.

For three-phase flow, we assume the dissolution of calcite contributes little on the brine viscosity, and that the brine viscosity is only a function of the molality of *NaCl* and mass fraction of aqueous *CO₂*. This assumption has been used when we calculated the density of brine. In order to apply formula (A.16) to the simplified equilibrium model in Chapter 3, we only need to put into formula (A.16) the empirical formula for mass fraction of *CO₂*(aq), i.e., formula (3.30)

CO₂ Viscosity

The viscosity of *CO₂*-rich phase (μ_g [$\mu\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$]) is assumed to be a function of temperature and pressures. The effect of water vapor is implicitly considered as it affects the density of gas phase. The formula is given as (Sovova and Prochazka, 1993; Riano-Vilarrasa, 2012)

$$\mu_g = \mu_0 \exp\left(\sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=0}^1 \frac{a_{i,j} \rho_R^i}{T_R^j}\right), \quad (\text{A.17})$$

where,

$$\mu_0 = T_R^{0.5} \left(27.2246461 - \frac{16.346068}{T_R} + \frac{4.66920556}{T_R^2} \right). \quad (\text{A.18})$$

Here, reduced density $\rho_R = \rho_g / \rho_{cr}$ and reduced temperature $T_R = T_k / T_{cr}$; the critical density of *CO₂* $\rho_{cr} = 468$ [$\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$] and the critical temperature of *CO₂* $T_{cr} = 304$ [K]; The coefficients: $a_{1,0} = 0.248566120$, $a_{1,1} = 0.004894942$, $a_{2,0} = -0.373300660$, $a_{2,1} = 1.22753488$, $a_{3,0} = 0.363854523$, $a_{3,1} = -0.774229021$, $a_{4,0} = -0.0639070755$ and $a_{4,1} = 0.142507049$. We note that the unit of viscosity obtained by Equation (A.17) is [$\mu\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$]. Formula [A.17] applies to temperatures from 220 to 1300 [K] and pressures up to 120 [MPa].

The results for μ_l and μ_g (in logarithm scale) at different pressure combinations are shown in Figure A.3. Correspondingly, in Figure A.4, one can see the derivatives of μ_l and μ_g with respect to p_l and p_g . In Figure A.4, we show both the results obtained by chain rule and those by finite difference method. As can be seen that, the results obtained by chain rule agree well with the finite difference results.

Appendix B

Numerical Discretization of Governing Equations

This section offers details in constructing the Jacobian matrix and right-hand-side residual vector for Newton-Raphson iteration, which is used for solving the transport equations in Chapter 2. The discretization consists of two major parts: one larger part in charge of the mass balance in field grid and one smaller part in charge of the mass balance of the injection well.

The mass balance of the field grid is controlled by two governing equations, i.e., Equations (2.3) and (2.4), which are based on the mass balance of two components. The two governing equations actually are combinations of four transport equations. However, these four transport equations have the same discretization form, so we could discretize the four transport equation in a general way. We use \mathcal{F}_α^β to describe transport of β species in α phase; here, $\alpha = (l, g)$ and $\beta = (H, C)$. Then for each grid we have

$$\mathcal{F}_1 = \sum_{\alpha=l,g} \mathcal{F}_\alpha^H, \quad (\text{B.1})$$

and

$$\mathcal{F}_2 = \sum_{\alpha=l,g} \mathcal{F}_\alpha^C. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

The mass balance in the injection well is governed by one function, based on the mass balance of the injected phase. If injection wells are added to the system, then for each injection well we have

$$\mathcal{F}_W = \sum_{\beta=H,C} \mathcal{F}_W^\beta. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Here, we note that we construct the control equations \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{F}_2 on the basis of the mass balances of components, while we construct the control equation \mathcal{F}_W on the basis of the mass balance of total mass of injected fluid. In this work, the injection well only inject

single phase, that is, we can inject $CO_2(g)$ with water vapor or inject water with $CO_2(aq)$ but we cannot together inject $CO_2(g)$ and liquid water in the same well. As a result, each field grid is governed by two Equations (B.1) and (B.2), while each injection well is only governed by one Equation (B.3).

The discretization of \mathcal{F}_α^β is given as follows.

$$[\mathcal{F}_\alpha^\beta]_i^{n+1,k} = V_i \frac{[\phi S_\alpha \rho_\alpha X_\alpha^\beta]_i^{n+1,k} - [\phi S_\alpha \rho_\alpha X_\alpha^\beta]_i^n}{\Delta t} + \sum \mathcal{J}_{i+1/2}^{n+1,k} - \sum \mathcal{J}_{i-1/2}^{n+1,k} - \left[\sum_{j=1}^{NW} [Q_\alpha^\beta]^j \right]^{n+1,k}, \quad (\text{B.4})$$

where the flux through the faces are

$$\mathcal{J}_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} = \pm [\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^\beta \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha}}{\mu_\alpha}]_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} [T_\kappa]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} [(p_\alpha)_i^{n+1,k} - (p_\alpha)_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k}] \quad (\text{B.5})$$

$$\pm [\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^\beta \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha}}{\mu_\alpha}]_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} [T_\kappa \rho_\alpha]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} g(z_{i\pm 1} - z_i) \quad (\text{B.6})$$

$$\pm [T_{D\alpha} \phi S_\alpha \rho_\alpha]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} [(X_\alpha^\beta)_i^{n+1,k} - (X_\alpha^\beta)_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k}], \quad (\text{B.7})$$

where subscript i means grid, and subscript $up\alpha$ means upwind grid for α phase, superscript n and k mean the time step and Newton-Raphson iteration step, respectively, and T_κ and $T_{D\alpha}$ are respectively the transmissibility and the dispersion at the interface. The initial guess of the value is the value at the current step, i.e.,

$$[\cdot]_i^{n+1,0} = [\cdot]_i^n. \quad (\text{B.8})$$

To reduce the numerical dispersion, the fluid property in the upwind cell is used to calculate the mass flux, i.e.,

$$[\cdot]_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} = [\cdot]_{i=up\alpha}^{n+1,k}. \quad (\text{B.9})$$

The harmonic mean half transmissibility of two adjacent cells is used as the transmissibility of the interface, i.e.,

$$[T_\kappa]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} = \frac{1}{\left[\frac{1}{T_\kappa} \right]_{i+1}^{n+1,k} + \left[\frac{1}{T_\kappa} \right]_{i-1}^{n+1,k}} \quad (\text{B.10})$$

and

$$[T_\kappa \rho_\alpha]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} = \frac{1}{\left[\frac{1}{T_\kappa} \right]_{i+1}^{n+1,k} + \left[\frac{1}{T_\kappa} \right]_{i-1}^{n+1,k}} \frac{[\rho_\alpha]_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} + [\rho_\alpha]_i^{n+1,k}}{2}, \quad (\text{B.11})$$

where, the arithmetic average of the fluid density has been used to calculate gravitational term.

The half transmissibility is calculated as

$$[T_{\kappa}]_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} = A_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} \kappa_{i\pm 1} \frac{\vec{c}_{i\pm 1}}{|\vec{c}_{i\pm 1}|^2} \cdot \vec{n}_{i\pm 1}, \quad (\text{B.12})$$

where $\vec{c}_{i\pm 1}$ is the vector from the center of the $i \pm 1$ th cell to the center of the interface, and $\vec{n}_{i\pm 1}$ is the direction of the face pointing out of the $i \pm 1$ th cell. Similarly, if we substitute κ with dispersion tensor $\mathbf{D}\alpha$, we can calculate the dispersion at the interface. Detailed calculation of transmissibility can be found in *Lie* (2019, p. 131).

To assure that the dispersion flux is zero when one of the two adjacent grids has a saturation of zero, harmonic mean saturation is used as the saturation of the interface, i.e.,

$$[T_{D\alpha} \phi S_{\alpha} \rho_{\alpha}]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} = [T_{D\alpha}]_{i\pm 1/2} \frac{\phi_{i\pm 1} + \phi_i}{2} \frac{2[S_{\alpha}]_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} [S_{\alpha}]_i^{n+1,k}}{[S_{\alpha}]_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} + [S_{\alpha}]_i^{n+1,k}} \frac{[\rho_{\alpha}]_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} + [\rho_{\alpha}]_i^{n+1,k}}{2}. \quad (\text{B.13})$$

If j th injection well pierces M field grids, then the source term for m -th grid pierced by j -th injection well can be given as

$$[Q_{\alpha}^{\beta}]^{(j,m)} = X_{\alpha,W}^{\beta} \rho_{\alpha,W} W I^{(j,m)} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}}{\mu_{\alpha}} (p_{bh}^j - \rho_{\alpha,W} g(z_{bh}^j - z^{(j,m)}) - p_{\alpha}^m) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{j,m}), \quad (\text{B.14})$$

where, superscript (j, m) means the m -th grid pierced by the j -th well, $X_{\alpha,W}^{\beta}$ is the mass fraction of β -species in α -phase in the well, $\rho_{\alpha,W}$ is the density of α -phase in the well (here, we assume the density in the well is only a function of bottom hole pressure), $\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}$ is the maximum relative permeability of the injected α -phase, p_{bh}^j is the bottom hole pressure at reference depth z_{bh}^j for the j -th well and the well index $W I^{(j,m)}$ is defined as

$$W I^{(j,m)} = \frac{2\pi \kappa^{(j,m)} \Delta L^{(j,m)}}{\ln\left(\frac{r_e^j}{r_w^j}\right) + s}, \quad (\text{B.15})$$

where, $\Delta L^{(j,m)}$ is the length scale of the pierced grid parallel to the axis of the well, r_e^j and r_w^j are the effective radius and physical radius of the j -th well, respectively, and s is the skin factor of the well. For vertical well, effective radius is defined as

$$r_e = 2 \cdot 0.14 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{\Delta L_x^2 \sqrt{\kappa_y/\kappa_x} + \Delta L_y^2 \sqrt{\kappa_x/\kappa_y}}}{(\kappa_x/\kappa_y)^{1/4} + (\kappa_y/\kappa_x)^{1/4}}. \quad (\text{B.16})$$

The discretization of \mathcal{F}_W^j is given as

$$\mathcal{F}_W^j = \sum_{\beta=H,C} [\mathcal{F}_W^{\beta}]^j = -[Q_{\alpha,inj}]^j + \sum_{\beta=H,C} \sum_{m=1}^M [Q_{\alpha}^{\beta}]^{j,m}, \quad (\text{B.17})$$

where, $Q_{\alpha,inj}$ is the given mass injection rate of α phase. $[Q_{\alpha}^{\beta}]^{j,m}$ has been calculated in

Equation (B.14).

The derivative of \mathcal{F}_α^β with the pressure of α' phase ($\alpha' = (l, g)$) is given as

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_\alpha^\beta}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right]_i^{n+1,k} &= \frac{V_i \phi}{\Delta t} \left[\frac{\partial S_\alpha}{p_{\alpha'}} \rho_\alpha X_\alpha^\beta + S_\alpha \frac{\partial \rho_\alpha}{p_{\alpha'}} X_\alpha^\beta + S_\alpha \rho_\alpha \frac{\partial X_\alpha^\beta}{p_{\alpha'}} \right]^{n+1,k} \\ &+ \left[\frac{\partial \sum \mathcal{J}_{i+1/2}}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} - \frac{\partial \sum \mathcal{J}_{i-1/2}}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right]^{n+1,k} - \frac{\partial \sum_{j=1}^{NW} [Q_\alpha^\beta]^j}{\partial p_{\alpha'}}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.18})$$

In Equation (B.18), the derivative of storage term is obvious. In order to clarify the grid location of the derivative of interface flux $\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}_{i\pm 1/2}}{\partial p_{\alpha'}}$, we use $\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}_{i\pm 1/2}}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} (\delta p_{\alpha'})^{n+1,k}$, where, $(\delta p_{\alpha'})^{n+1,k}$ denotes the grid location of derivatives.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}_{i\pm 1/2}}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} (\delta p_{\alpha'})^{n+1,k} &= \pm \left[\frac{\partial \rho_\alpha}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \frac{X_\alpha^\beta \kappa_{r\alpha}}{\mu_\alpha} \right]_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} [T_\kappa]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} \left[(p_\alpha)_i^{n+1,k} - (p_\alpha)_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} \right] \\ &\pm \left[\rho_\alpha \frac{\partial X_\alpha^\beta}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha}}{\mu_\alpha} \right]_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} [T_\kappa]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} \left[(p_\alpha)_i^{n+1,k} - (p_\alpha)_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} \right] \\ &\pm \left[\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^\beta \frac{\partial \kappa_{r\alpha}}{\partial S_l} \frac{\partial S_l}{\partial p_c} \frac{\partial p_c}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \frac{1}{\mu_\alpha} \right]_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} [T_\kappa]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} \left[(p_\alpha)_i^{n+1,k} - (p_\alpha)_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} \right] \\ &\pm \left[\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^\beta \kappa_{r\alpha} \frac{-1}{\mu_\alpha^2} \frac{\partial \mu_\alpha}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right]_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} [T_\kappa]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} \left[(p_\alpha)_i^{n+1,k} - (p_\alpha)_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} \right] \\ &\pm \left[\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^\beta \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha}}{\mu_\alpha} \right]_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} [T_\kappa]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} \left[\left(\frac{\partial p_\alpha}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right)_i^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_i^{n+1,k} - \left(\frac{\partial p_\alpha}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right)_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} \right] \\ &\pm \left[\frac{\partial \rho_\alpha}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} X_\alpha^\beta \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha}}{\mu_\alpha} \right]_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} [T_\kappa \rho_\alpha]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} g(z_{i\pm 1} - z_i) \\ &\pm \left[\rho_\alpha \frac{\partial X_\alpha^\beta}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha}}{\mu_\alpha} \right]_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} [T_\kappa \rho_\alpha]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} g(z_{i\pm 1} - z_i) \\ &\pm \left[\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^\beta \frac{\partial \kappa_{r\alpha}}{\partial S_l} \frac{\partial S_l}{\partial p_c} \frac{\partial p_c}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \frac{1}{\mu_\alpha} \right]_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} [T_\kappa \rho_\alpha]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} g(z_{i\pm 1} - z_i) \\ &\pm \left[\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^\beta \kappa_{r\alpha} \frac{-1}{\mu_\alpha^2} \frac{\partial \mu_\alpha}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right]_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} [T_\kappa \rho_\alpha]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} g(z_{i\pm 1} - z_i) \\ &\pm \left[\rho_\alpha X_\alpha^\beta \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha}}{\mu_\alpha} \right]_{i\pm 1/2, up\alpha}^{n+1,k} [T_\kappa]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} \left[\frac{\partial \rho_\alpha}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} [\delta p_{\alpha'}]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} g(z_{i\pm 1} - z_i) \\ &\pm [T_{D\alpha} \phi \rho_\alpha]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} \left[\frac{\partial S_\alpha}{\partial S_\alpha} \frac{\partial S_\alpha}{\partial S_l} \frac{\partial S_l}{\partial p_c} \frac{\partial p_c}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} [\delta p_{\alpha'}]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} \left[(X_\alpha^\beta)_i^{n+1,k} - (X_\alpha^\beta)_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} \right] \\ &\pm [T_{D\alpha} \phi S_\alpha]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} \left[\frac{\partial \rho_\alpha}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} [\delta p_{\alpha'}]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} \left[(X_\alpha^\beta)_i^{n+1,k} - (X_\alpha^\beta)_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\pm [T_{D\alpha} \phi S_\alpha \rho_\alpha]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} \left[\left(\frac{\partial X_\alpha^\beta}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right)_i^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_i^{n+1,k} - \left(\frac{\partial X_\alpha^\beta}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right)_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} \right]. \quad (\text{B.19})$$

Note that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{\partial S_\alpha}{\partial S_\alpha} \frac{\partial S_\alpha}{\partial S_l} \frac{\partial S_l}{\partial p_c} \frac{\partial p_c}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} [\delta p_{\alpha'}]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} = \frac{2(S_\alpha)_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k}}{[(S_\alpha)_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} + (S_\alpha)_i^{n+1,k}]^2} \left[\frac{\partial S_\alpha}{\partial S_l} \frac{\partial S_l}{\partial p_c} \frac{\partial p_c}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right]_i^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_i^{n+1,k} \\ & + \frac{2(S_\alpha)_i^{n+1,k}}{[(S_\alpha)_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} + (S_\alpha)_i^{n+1,k}]^2} \left[\frac{\partial S_\alpha}{\partial S_l} \frac{\partial S_l}{\partial p_c} \frac{\partial p_c}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right]_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} (\delta p_{\alpha'})_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k}; \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.20})$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial \rho_\alpha}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} [\delta p_{\alpha'}]_{i\pm 1/2}^{n+1,k} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\partial \rho_\alpha}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right]_i^{n+1,k} [\delta p_{\alpha'}]_i^{n+1,k} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\partial \rho_\alpha}{\partial p_{\alpha'}} \right]_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k} [\delta p_{\alpha'}]_{i\pm 1}^{n+1,k}. \quad (\text{B.21})$$

Derivatives of source term over bottom hole pressure (p_{bh}^j) and field pressure at m th grid (p_α^m) are, respectively, given as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial [Q_\alpha^\beta]^{(j,m)}}{\partial p_{bh}^j} &= \frac{\partial X_{\alpha,W}^\beta}{\partial p_{bh}^j} \rho_{W,\alpha} W I^{(j,m)} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}}{\mu_\alpha} (p_{bh}^j - \rho_\alpha g(z_{bh}^j - z^{(j,m)}) - p_\alpha^m) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{j,m}) \\ &+ X_{\alpha,W}^\beta \frac{\partial \rho_{\alpha,W}}{\partial p_{bh}^j} W I^{(j,m)} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}}{\mu_\alpha} (p_{bh}^j - \rho_\alpha g(z_{bh}^j - z^{(j,m)}) - p_\alpha^m) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{j,m}) \\ &- X_{\alpha,W}^\beta \rho_{\alpha,W} W I^{(j,m)} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}}{\mu_\alpha^2} \frac{\partial \mu_\alpha}{\partial p_{bh}^j} (p_{bh}^j - \rho_\alpha g(z_{bh}^j - z^{(j,m)}) - p_\alpha^m) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{j,m}) \\ &+ X_{\alpha,W}^\beta \rho_{\alpha,W} W I^{(j,m)} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}}{\mu_\alpha} \left(1 - \frac{\partial \rho_{\alpha,W}}{\partial p_{bh}^j} g(z_{bh}^j - z^{(j,m)}) \right) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{(j,m)}), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.22})$$

and

$$\frac{\partial [Q_\alpha^\beta]^{(j,m)}}{\partial p_\alpha^m} = -X_{\alpha,W}^\beta \rho_{\alpha,W} W I^{(j,m)} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}}{\mu_\alpha} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{(j,m)}). \quad (\text{B.23})$$

The derivative of \mathcal{F}_W^j is then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W^j}{\partial p_{bh}^j} &= \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{\partial \rho_{\alpha,W}}{\partial p_{bh}^j} W I^{(j,m)} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}}{\mu_\alpha} (p_{bh}^j - \rho_\alpha g(z_{bh}^j - z^{(j,m)}) - p_\alpha^m) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{j,m}) \\ &- \sum_{m=1}^M \rho_{\alpha,W} W I^{(j,m)} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}}{\mu_\alpha^2} \frac{\partial \mu_\alpha}{\partial p_{bh}^j} (p_{bh}^j - \rho_\alpha g(z_{bh}^j - z^{(j,m)}) - p_\alpha^m) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{j,m}) \\ &+ \sum_{m=1}^M \rho_{\alpha,W} W I^{(j,m)} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}}{\mu_\alpha} \left(1 - \frac{\partial \rho_{\alpha,W}}{\partial p_{bh}^j} g(z_{bh}^j - z^{(j,m)}) \right) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{(j,m)}) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.24})$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W^j}{\partial p_\alpha^m} = - \sum_{m=1}^M \rho_{\alpha,W} W I^{(j,m)} \frac{\kappa_{r\alpha MAX}}{\mu_\alpha} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{(j,m)}). \quad (\text{B.25})$$

In the preceding discretization, to avoid cumbersome, we do not include the lateral

dispersion. However, one should bear in mind that lateral dispersion should be considered. Hydrodynamic dispersion is an important solute transport mechanism that arises from an interplay between non-uniform advection and molecular diffusion. In geologic media, velocities of fluid phases are spatially variable due to heterogeneities on multiple scales, from pore scale to basin scale. The dispersion tensor is given as

$$D_{\alpha}^{i,j} = a_{L_{\alpha}}|v_{\alpha}|\delta_{i,j} + (a_{L_{\alpha}} - a_{T_{\alpha}})\frac{v_{\alpha_i}v_{\alpha_j}}{v_{\alpha}} + \tau_{\alpha}D_{\alpha}^*\delta_{i,j}, \quad (\text{B.26})$$

where, i and j denote the Cartesian coordinates, and $i, j = (x, y, z)$; $\alpha (= (l, g))$ denotes the (brine or CO_2 -rich) phase; $a_{T_{\alpha}}$ [m] and $a_{L_{\alpha}}$ [m] denote the transverse and longitudinal dispersivities for the phase, respectively; v_{α} [$m \cdot s^{-1}$] is the absolute value of the interstitial fluid velocity for α phase; v_{α_i} [$m \cdot s^{-1}$] is the component value of the interstitial fluid velocity in i -th direction for α phase; $\delta_{i,j}$ is Kronecker delta; D_{α}^* [$m^2 \cdot s^{-1}$] is molecular diffusion coefficient for α phase; τ_{α} [-] accounting for the porosity and tortuosity, based on Millington and Quirk (1961) model, is given as

$$\tau_{\alpha} = \phi^{1/3}(S_{\alpha})^{7/3}. \quad (\text{B.27})$$

Finally, we can construct the Jacobian matrix and the residual vector. In virtue of Equations (B.4) to (B.16), we can calculate \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{F}_2 for each grid with Equations (B.1) and (B.2). If the field is discretized into N grids, then we use N -dimensional vectors \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{F}_2 to store the \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{F}_2 of each grid, respectively. If we have NW injection wells, NW -dimensional vector \mathcal{F}_W is used to store the \mathcal{F}_W of each well. The $(2N + NW)$ -dimensional residual vector (i.e. expression (2.34)) is obtained as

$$[\mathcal{F}]^{n+1,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{F}_1 \\ \mathcal{F}_2 \\ \mathcal{F}_W \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k}. \quad (\text{B.28})$$

The nine sub-matrices of the Jacobian matrix (i.e., expression (2.37)) is also obtained:

$$\left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right]^{n+1,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_1}{\partial p_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_1}{\partial p_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_1}{\partial p_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_2}{\partial p_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_2}{\partial p_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_2}{\partial p_{bh}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial p_l} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial p_g} & \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_W}{\partial p_{bh}} \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{11} & \mathbf{M}_{12} & \mathbf{M}_{1W} \\ \mathbf{M}_{21} & \mathbf{M}_{22} & \mathbf{M}_{2W} \\ \mathbf{M}_{W1} & \mathbf{M}_{W2} & \mathbf{M}_{WW} \end{bmatrix}^{n+1,k} = \mathbf{M}^{n+1,k}. \quad (\text{B.29})$$

Appendix C

Retention and Relative Permeability Curves

C.1 Classic Van Genuchten Model

Van Genuchten model is employed to describe the capillary pressure and relative permeabilities of liquid brine and gaseous CO_2 -rich phases (*McWhorter and Sunada, 1990*). The retention curve is given as

$$S_{le}(p_c) = \begin{cases} 1, p_c < 0 \\ \frac{1}{\left[1 + \left(\sqrt{\frac{\kappa_g \bar{\phi}}{\kappa_g \bar{\phi}}} \alpha_p p_c\right)^{n_p}\right]^{m_p}}, p_c \geq 0. \end{cases} \quad (C.1)$$

where, $\bar{\phi}$ and κ_g are mean porosity and geometric mean intrinsic permeability, respectively, $m_p = 1 - 1/n_p$, α_p [bar⁻¹] is scaling parameter for the retention curve, and S_{le} [-] is the effective saturation of brine phase. S_{le} is given as

$$S_{le} = \begin{cases} 1, S_l > 1 - S_{gr}; \\ \frac{S_l - S_{lr}}{1 - S_{lr} - S_{gr}}, S_{lr} \leq S_l \leq 1 - S_{gr}; \\ 0, S_l < S_{lr}, \end{cases} \quad (C.2)$$

where, S_{lr} [-] and S_{gr} [-] are the effective saturations of brine and gas phases. The Leverett J-function has been employed to describe entry pressure as a function of the porosity and permeability of the porous medium (*Juanes et al., 2006; Plug and Bruining, 2007; Krevor et al., 2011, 2015*), and thus each grid block has its own retention curve, scaled from a reference curve for the geometric mean permeability and mean porosity.

The relative permeabilities for liquid brine and gaseous CO_2 -rich phases are, respectively, given as

$$\kappa_{rl} = \kappa_{rlm} \cdot (S_{le})^{\epsilon_p} [1 - (1 - S_{le}^{1/m_p})^{m_p}]^2 \quad (C.3)$$

Table C.1: Parameters for retention and relative permeability curves.

m_p [-]	0.4/0.8	$\bar{\phi}$ [-]	0.15
S_{gr} [-]	0	γ_p [-]	0.5
S_{lr} [-]	0	ϵ_p [-]	0.5
α_p [bar ⁻¹]	5	κ_{rlm} [-]	1.0
κ_g [md]	20	κ_{rgm} [-]	1.0

Figure C.1: Retention and relative permeability curves; derivatives of the corresponding curves.

and

$$\kappa_{rg} = \kappa_{rgm} \cdot (1 - S_{le})^{\gamma_p} (1 - S_{le}^{1/m_p})^{2m_p}, \quad (\text{C.4})$$

where, κ_{rlm} , κ_{rgm} , ϵ_p , γ_p are the scaling parameters.

When the related parameters in Table C.1 are used, the retention and the relative permeability curves are given in Figure C.1. Also given in the figure are derivatives of the these curves.

C.2 Extended Van Genuchten Model

To our best, in literature, the Van Genuchten model cannot express the entry pressure. In order to include the entry pressure, one has to resort to the Brooks-Corey model. Herein, we extend the Van Genuchten model so that it can also account for the entry pressure:

$$S_{le}(p_c) = \begin{cases} 1, p_c < p_{en} \\ \frac{1}{\left[1 + \left(\sqrt{\frac{\kappa_{\phi}}{\kappa_g}} \alpha_p (p_c - p_{en}) \cdot 10^{-5}\right)^{n_p}\right]^{m_p}}, p_c \geq p_{en}, \end{cases} \quad (\text{C.5})$$

where, p_{en} [Pa] is the entry pressure.

Appendix D

Fugacity, Activity and equilibrium constant

D.1 Fugacity

The fugacity is calculated as

$$f_g^\beta = F^\beta \frac{p_g^\beta}{p^0}, \quad (\text{D.1})$$

where, β denotes gaseous species; p_g^β is the partial gas pressure of species β ; the reference pressure $p^0 = 1$ bar; In this work we consider that the gas phase only includes CO_2 and H_2O . According to *Spycher et al.* (2003), fugacity coefficients of gaseous species are calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \ln F^\beta = & \ln \frac{V}{V - b^{mix}} + \frac{b^\beta}{V - b^{mix}} - \ln \frac{V + b^{mix}}{V} \frac{2}{RT_k^{1.5} b^{mix}} \sum_{\beta'=C,H} (x_g^\beta a^{\beta'-\beta}) \\ & + \frac{a^{mix} - b^\beta}{RT_k^{1.5} (b^{mix})^2} \left(\ln \frac{V + b^{mix}}{V} - \frac{b^{mix}}{V + b^{mix}} \right) - \ln \frac{p_g V}{RT_k}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.2})$$

where, $\beta = (C, H, mix)$ represent the species CO_2 , H_2O and $CO_2 - H_2O$ mixture, respectively; V is obtained from Equation (A.7); from assumption of infinity dilution, $a^{mix} = a^C$ and $b^{mix} = b^C$; a^C and b^C are defined as formulas (A.8) and (A.9), respectively; $b^H = 1.818 \times 10^{-5} [\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}]$ and $a^{H-C} = 7.89 [\text{Pa} \cdot \text{m}^6 \cdot \text{K}^{0.5} \cdot \text{mol}^{-2}]$. We assume infinite dilution of water vapor, that is, $x_g^H = 0$, so we do not need a^H .

D.2 Activity

For *aqueous species* the activity is calculated as

$$a_i^\beta = \gamma_\beta m_i^\beta \quad (\text{D.3})$$

where, m represents the molality and γ represents the activity coefficient. We note that the *aqueous species* includes *ionic species* and *neutral species*

For *ionic species*, the activity coefficient is calculated by using the HKF model (*Helgeson et al.*, 1981), which is expressed as

$$\log \gamma_j = -\frac{A_\gamma Z_j^2 \sqrt{\bar{I}}}{\Lambda} + \log x_l^H + \left[\omega_j^{abs} b_{NaCl} + b_{Na^+Cl^-} - 0.19(|Z_j| - 1) \right] \bar{I}, \quad (D.4)$$

where, x_l^H represents the molar fraction of water; Λ is Debye-Hückel function given as

$$\Lambda = 1 + \mathring{a} B_\gamma \sqrt{\bar{I}}, \quad (D.5)$$

in which

$$\mathring{a} = \frac{\sum_k^{N_k} \sum_j^{N_j} \nu_{kj} r_{e,j}}{\sum_k^{N_k} \sum_j^{N_j} \nu_{kj}}, \quad (D.6)$$

$$\bar{I} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{N_j} m_j^* Z_j^2 \quad (D.7)$$

and

$$m_j^* = \sum_{k=1}^{N_k} \nu_{kj} m_k. \quad (D.8)$$

Here, the Born coefficient ω_j^{abs} and the effective electrostatic radius $r_{e,j}$ can be found in Table 3 of *Helgeson et al.* (1981); N_j and N_k are the number of ions and aqueous complexes, respectively; ν_{kj} denotes the stoichiometry of the j th ion in the k -th complex; Z_j is the electrical charge of the j -th ion; m_j^* is the stoichiometric molality of the j -th ion; \mathring{a} denotes the ion-size parameter; and \bar{I} is stoichiometric ionic strength of an aqueous solution. The parameters A_γ , B_γ , b_{NaCl} and $b_{Na^+Cl^-}$ can be found in the tables in Appendix of *Leal et al.* (2013); these parameters are insensitive to the pressure range in this study and are assumed to be constant.

For *neutral species* the activity coefficient is calculated approximately using the Setschenow model

$$\log \gamma_\beta = b_i \bar{I} + \log x^H, \quad (D.9)$$

where, $b_i = 0.1$ is adopted for neutral species other than $CO_2(aq)$. For $CO_2(aq)$ the activity coefficient is extensively studied in a host of researches (*Spycher and Pruess*, 2005), among which we chose the *Drummond* (1981) model and *Duan and Sun* (2003) model.

The *Drummond* (1981) model for activity coefficient of aqueous CO_2 (γ_C) is given as

$$\ln \gamma_C = (-1.0312 + 1.2806 T_k + 255.9/T_k) \bar{I} - (0.4445 - 0.001606 T_k) \frac{\bar{I}}{\bar{I} + 1}. \quad (D.10)$$

This equation is valid for temperature from 293 to 673 [K] and salinity from 0 to 6.5 [molal].

The *Duan and Sun* (2003) model for activity coefficient of aqueous CO_2 (γ_C) is given as

$$\ln \gamma'_C = 2\lambda(m_i^{Na} + m_i^K + 2m_i^{Mg}) + \xi m_{Cl}(m_i^{Na} + m_i^K + m_i^{Ca} + m_i^{Mg}) - 0.07m_i^{SO_4}, \quad (D.11)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda = & -0.411370585 + 6.07632013 \cdot 10^{-4} T_k + \frac{97.5347708}{T_k} - \frac{0.0237622469 p_l}{T_k} \times 10^{-5} \\ & + \frac{0.0170656236 p_l}{630 - T_k} \times 10^{-5} + 1.41335834 \times 10^{-5} T_k \ln(p_l \times 10^{-5}) \end{aligned} \quad (D.12)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \xi = & 3.36389723 \times 10^{-4} - 1.98298980 \times 10^{-5} T_k + \frac{2.12220830 \times 10^{-3} p_l}{T_k} \times 10^{-5} \\ & - \frac{5.24873303 \times 10^{-3} p_l}{630 - T_k} \times 10^{-5}. \end{aligned} \quad (D.13)$$

Here, p_l is in [Pa] and T_k is in [K]. This equation is valid within the pressure, temperature, and salinity ranges of 0- 2000 [bar], 0- 260 [°C], and 0-4.3 [molal], respectively. We note the activity coefficient by *Duan and Sun* (2003) is not a *true* coefficient but a coefficient defined as the ratio of molality of CO_2 in pure water to molality of CO_2 in brine.

For *water species*, the activity can be calculated with two approaches. The first one, based on a fully ionized salt, is (*Spycher and Pruess*, 2005)

$$a_l^H = x_l^H. \quad (D.14)$$

Here, we denote this approach as Spycher-Pruess approach. The second one, calculated by using Helgeson-Kirkham-Flowers model, is given as (*Helgeson et al.*, 1981)

$$\ln a_l^H = \frac{2.303}{55.508} \sum_{j=1}^{N_j} m_j^* \psi_j, \quad (D.15)$$

where,

$$\psi_j = \frac{A_\gamma Z_j^2 \sqrt{I}}{3} \sigma + \frac{x_l^H}{1 - x_l^H} \log x_l^H - \frac{1}{2} [\omega_j b_{NaCl} + b_{Na+Cl^-} - 0.19(|Z_j| - 1)] \bar{I}, \quad (D.16)$$

with

$$\sigma = \frac{3}{(\hat{a} B_\gamma \sqrt{I})^3} \left(\Lambda - \frac{1}{\Lambda} - 2 \ln \Lambda \right). \quad (D.17)$$

The selection of different approaches for a_l^H does not affect the results for X_l^C and affect negligibly the results for X_g^H in this study, as can be seen in Figure D.1. For Spycher-Pruess approach, in Figure D.2, we give the derivatives of X_l^C and X_g^H with respect to p_l and p_g . In the Figure D.2, we show both the results obtained by chain rule and those by finite difference method. As can be seen from Figure D.2, the results obtained by chain rule agree well with the finite difference results.

Figure D.1: Distributions of $\log X_l^C$ and $\log X_g^H$ in $(\log p_l, \log p_g)$ field; the solid lines are for Spycher-Pruess approach while the dash lines are for Helgeson-Kirkham-Flowers approach; $T_c = 40$ [°C] and $m_l^S = 0.5$ [molal].

D.3 Equilibrium Constants

The equilibrium constants of two reaction equations (2.13) and (2.14) are calculated as

$$K^\beta = K^{\beta_0} \exp \frac{(p_l - p^0) \bar{V}_\beta}{RT_c}, \quad (\text{D.18})$$

with

$$K^{\beta_0} = 10^{a_\beta + b_\beta T_c + c_\beta T_c^2 + d_\beta T_c^3}, \quad (\text{D.19})$$

where, T_c is temperature in °C; \bar{V}_β [$\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$] denotes the mean molar volume of pure condensed species β when pressure changes from p^0 to p_l , and here we assume \bar{V}_β is a constant. The parameters, given in *Spycher et al.* (2003), are listed in Table D.1. The other equilibrium constants are assumed to be constant (c.f. phreeqc.dat from www.usgs.gov); in Table D.2 we only list the equilibrium constants for the following four reactions:

Figure D.2: Distributions of $\frac{dX_l^C}{dp_l}$ (top-left), $\frac{dX_g^H}{dp_g}$ (top-right), $\frac{dX_l^C}{dp_g}$ (bottom-left) and $\frac{dX_g^H}{dp_l}$ (bottom-right) in $(\log p_l, \log p_g)$ field; the solid lines are obtained by strictly following the chain rule while the dash lines are by finite difference; $T_c = 40$ [°C] and $m_l^S = 0.5$ [molal].

Table D.1: Parameters for equilibrium constants.

β	a_β	b_β	c_β	d_β	\bar{V}_β [cm ³ ·mol ⁻¹]
$H_2O_{(g)}$	-2.209	3.097×10^{-2}	-1.098×10^{-4}	2.048×10^{-7}	18.1
$CO_{2(g)}$	1.189	1.304×10^{-2}	-5.446×10^{-5}	0	32.6

(D.20)

Table D.2: Parameters for equilibrium constants.

K_1	K_2	K_3	K_4
$10^{1.849}$	$10^{6.352}$	$10^{-10.329}$	10^{-14}

Appendix E

Performance of *Spycher and Pruess* (2005) Model for $H_2O - CO_2 - NaCl$ System

The mutual solubility model given by *Spycher and Pruess* (2005) is checked against the experimental data from *Wiebe and Gaddy* (1939, 1940, 1941), *King et al.* (1992), *Hou et al.* (2013a,b), *Tong et al.* (2013), *Kiepe et al.* (2002) and *Rumpf et al.* (1994). *Duan and Sun* (2003) model is used to calculate the activity of aqueous CO_2 . In these researches, the liquid phase is either pure water or saline water with $NaCl$. The comparison results are listed in Tables E.1 to E.4 and Figures E.1 to E.6.

From the results we can see that the *Spycher and Pruess* (2005) model can well predict the mutual solubility of brine/ CO_2 system. The accuracy for X_l^C is not obviously affected by the salinity, but the accuracy for x_g^H could be a bit low when the salinity is high.

Table E.1: Compare *Spycher & Pruess* (2005) model with the experimental data for pure water in *Tong et al.* (2013).

T_k [K]	p_g [bar]	x_l^C (exp. ^a) [%]	x_l^C (SP ^b) [%]	ERR [%]
349.19	252.2	2.148	2.187	2.148
349.13	183.1	2.017	1.8783	-0.502
374.41	72.1	1.105	1.0349	0.803
374.18	144.4	1.711	1.6012	1.793
374.91	188.6	1.924	1.7927	2.088
374.15	223.4	2.048	1.9126	2.233
374.99	272.6	2.189	2.0529	2.731

^a means experimental data:

^b calculated with *Spycher and Pruess* (2005) model.

Table E.2: Compare Spycher & Pruess (2005) model with the experimental data in *Wiebe and Gaddy* (1940) (left column) and *Wiebe and Gaddy* (1941) (right column); no salt exists.

T_k [K]	p_g [bar]	x_l^C (exp.) [%]	x_l^C (SP) [%]	ERR [%]	T_k [K]	p_g [bar]	x_g^H (exp.) [%]	x_g^H (SP) [%]	ERR [%]
285.15	50.7	2.7790	2.7610	-0.64	298.15	1.0	2.8598	3.1853	11.38
-	76.0	2.8390	2.8209	-0.63	-	25.3	0.1641	0.1574	-4.08
-	101.3	2.8720	2.8757	0.12	-	50.7	0.1293	0.1066	-17.55
-	152.0	2.9950	2.9752	-0.66	-	101.3	0.3320	0.3245	-2.25
-	202.7	3.0990	3.0649	-1.10	-	152.0	0.3593	0.3529	-1.78
-	304.0	3.1970	3.2234	0.82	-	202.7	0.3768	0.3699	-1.83
291.15	25.3	1.5450	1.5066	-2.48	-	456.0	0.4004	0.4023	0.47
-	50.7	2.5110	2.4853	-1.02	-	481.3	0.3991	0.4034	1.07
-	76.0	2.6500	2.5947	-2.08	-	506.6	0.3966	0.4043	1.94
-	101.3	2.6600	2.6516	-0.31	304.19	1.0	3.9789	4.5271	13.77
-	152.0	2.7950	2.7529	-1.50	-	25.3	0.2275	0.2213	-2.72
-	202.7	2.9030	2.8430	-2.06	-	50.7	0.1604	0.1462	-8.85
-	304.0	3.0650	3.0012	-2.08	-	101.3	0.3643	0.3691	1.31
298.15	50.7	2.1430	2.1498	0.31	-	202.7	0.4203	0.4351	3.52
-	76.0	2.4450	2.4320	-0.53	-	405.3	0.4762	0.4739	-0.48
-	101.3	2.4900	2.4947	0.18	-	506.6	0.4800	0.4803	0.06
-	405.3	3.0120	3.0010	-0.36	-	532.0	0.4750	0.4812	1.30
304.1900	25.3	1.1280	1.1246	-0.30	-	557.3	0.4775	0.4819	0.92
-	50.7	1.9050	1.9101	0.26	323.15	1.0	11.5637	12.3989	7.22
-	76.0	2.3040	2.2983	-0.24	-	25.3	0.6192	0.5934	-4.16
-	101.3	2.3690	2.3690	0	-	50.7	0.3830	0.3698	-3.44
-	152.0	2.4780	2.4841	0.24	-	60.8	0.3569	0.3402	-4.67
-	202.7	2.5600	2.5822	0.86	-	76.0	0.3494	0.3284	-6.01
-	506.6	3.0160	3.0223	0.20	-	101.3	0.4489	0.4366	-2.74
308.15	25.3	1.0310	1.0369	0.57	-	152.0	0.6093	0.6300	3.39
-	50.7	1.7550	1.7742	1.09	-	202.7	0.6764	0.6931	2.46
-	76.0	2.1900	2.2131	1.05	-	405.3	0.7585	0.7798	2.80
-	101.3	2.2890	2.9090	27.08	-	608.0	0.7921	0.7976	0.69
-	152.0	2.3960	2.4120	0.66	-	709.3	0.8008	0.7977	-0.38
-	202.70	2.4960	2.5131	0.68	348.15	1.0	30.0905	38.4484	27.77
-	405.3	2.7930	2.8310	1.36	-	25.3	1.0631	1.7687	66.37
-	506.6	2.9650	2.9607	-0.14	-	101.3	0.8281	0.8232	-0.59
313.15	25.3	0.9260	0.9406	1.57	-	111.5	0.8107	0.8383	3.40
-	50.7	1.6100	1.6235	0.83	-	126.7	0.8542	0.8885	4.01
-	76.0	2.0330	2.0572	1.19	-	152.0	0.9549	1.0063	5.38
-	101.3	2.1880	2.1964	0.38	-	202.7	1.1315	1.1752	3.86
-	126.6	2.2570	2.2666	0.42	-	405.3	1.3180	1.3812	4.79
-	152.0	2.3090	2.3272	0.78	-	608.0	1.3926	1.4173	1.77
-	202.7	2.4890	2.4325	-2.27	-	709.3	1.3988	1.4167	1.27
-	405.3	2.7280	2.7583	1.11					
-	506.6	2.8690	2.8903	0.74					

Table E.3: Compare Spycher & Pruess (2005) model with the experimental data for pure water in *Hou et al.* (2013a).

T_k [K]	p_g [bar]	x_l^C (exp.) [%]	x_l^C (SP) [%]	ERR [%]	x_g^H (exp.) [%]	x_g^H (SP) [%]	ERR [%]
323.15	10.89	0.333	0.363	9.009	2.811	1.223	-50.49
-	29.80	0.901	0.907	0.666	0.507	0.518	2.170
-	74.06	1.829	1.763	-3.609	0.350	0.328	-6.285
-	100.21	2.054	2.007	-2.288	0.403	0.426	5.707
-	129.73	2.141	2.116	-1.168	0.533	0.581	8.262
-	175.33	2.255	2.234	-0.931	0.614	0.664	8.143
348.15	11.01	0.222	0.252	13.51	3.132	3.711	18.49
-	29.21	0.608	0.634	4.276	1.422	1.572	10.55
-	71.23	1.267	1.298	2.447	0.845	0.881	4.260
-	101.67	1.593	1.615	1.381	0.805	0.824	2.360
-	132.82	1.856	1.821	-1.886	0.836	0.916	9.569
-	169.18	1.993	1.969	-1.204	0.996	1.077	8.133
373.15	11.07	0.169	0.196	13.775	8.8020	9.444	7.294
-	24.26	0.390	0.433	9.931	4.6910	4.622	-1.471
-	70.88	1.085	1.104	1.721	2.1020	2.079	-1.094
-	102.35	1.365	1.431	4.612	1.7470	1.780	1.889
-	133.52	1.626	1.674	2.867	1.6750	1.726	3.045
-	170.70	1.872	1.883	0.584	1.7120	1.813	5.899

 Table E.4: Compare Spycher & Pruess (2005) model with the experimental data in *Hou et al.* (2013b); the salt is NaCl.

T_k [K]	m_l^S [molal]	p_g [bar]	x_l^C (exp.) [%]	x_l^C (SP) [%]	ERR [%]	x_g^H (exp.) [%]	x_g^H (SP) [%]	ERR [%]
323.15	2.5	27.82	0.492	0.493	0.203	0.3630	0.5028	38.5124
-	-	57.39	0.875	0.860	-1.665	0.2330	0.3208	37.6824
-	-	87.3	1.146	1.090	-4.885	0.2180	0.3190	46.3303
-	-	117.73	1.238	1.827	-4.467	0.2660	0.5006	88.1955
-	-	150.2	1.293	1.236	-4.393	0.3740	0.5805	55.2139
-	-	182.11	1.335	1.281	-4.045	0.4090	0.6228	52.2738
373.15	2.5	26.13	0.254	0.279	9.843	2.9030	3.9845	37.2546
-	-	57.42	0.532	0.553	4.023	1.1720	2.1739	85.4863
-	-	87.89	0.739	0.760	2.842	1.0640	1.7285	62.4530
-	-	118.67	0.899	0.918	2.114	0.9550	1.5989	67.4241
-	-	149.21	1.032	1.034	0.194	1.0830	1.6177	49.3721
-	-	180.13	1.139	1.219	7.024	1.1560	1.7061	47.5865
323.15	4.0	29.83	0.403	0.391	-2.978	0.2940	0.4549	54.7279
-	-	59.54	0.689	0.657	-4.644	0.1910	0.3022	58.2199
-	-	89.53	0.871	0.821	-5.798	0.1640	0.3114	89.8780
-	-	120.17	0.956	0.885	-7.427	0.2400	0.4869	102.8750
-	-	149.59	0.997	0.923	-7.4223	0.3490	0.5545	58.8825
-	-	179.54	1.025	0.956	-6.732	0.3910	0.5927	51.5857
373.15	4.0	29.51	0.251	0.241	-3.9841	1.4190	3.4276	141.5504
-	-	60.68	0.446	0.444	-0.448	0.9020	2.0022	121.9734
-	-	89.16	0.620	0.587	-5.323	0.8110	1.6405	102.2811
-	-	120.03	0.752	0.707	-5.984	0.7420	1.5252	105.5526
-	-	149.24	0.857	0.792	-7.585	0.8470	1.5451	82.4203
-	-	181.62	0.934	0.864	-7.495	0.9450	1.6346	72.9735

Figure E.1: Comparison between Spycher-Pruess model and the experimental data from *Wiebe and Gaddy* (1939, 1940, 1941) and *King et al.* (1992); no salt exists.

Figure E.2: Comparison between Spycher-Pruess model and the experimental data from *Wiebe and Gaddy* (1939, 1940, 1941) and *King et al.* (1992); no salt exists.

Figure E.3: Comparison between Spycher-Pruess model and the experimental data from *Hou et al.* (2013a).

Figure E.4: Comparison between Spycher-Pruess model and the experimental data from *Hou et al.* (2013a).

Figure E.5: Comparison between Spycher-Pruess model and the experimental data from *Kiepe et al.* (2002).

Figure E.6: Comparison between Spycher-Pruess model and the experimental data from *Rumpf et al.* (1994).

Appendix F

Theoretical Model by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006)

The theoretical model by *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006) is used as the reference for benchmark test for the equilibrium-reactive two-phase flow model and equilibrium-reactive three-phase flow model in Chapters 2 and 3. In this section, we concisely give the final results of the solutions in *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006), where one can find the detailed information on the derivation of the solution.

Defining the following dimensionless numbers:

$$\Gamma = 2\pi\kappa\lambda_l H^2 \Delta\rho g / Q, \lambda = \frac{\lambda_g}{\lambda_l}, \quad (\text{F.1})$$

and dimensionless variables

$$\tau = \frac{Qt}{2\pi\kappa\phi H(1 - S_r)}, \eta = \frac{r}{\sqrt{\kappa}}, h' = \frac{h}{H}, \quad (\text{F.2})$$

where, κ [m²] is the intrinsic permeability, subscript $\alpha = (l, g)$, respectively, denote liquid and gas phases, λ_α [(pa·s)⁻¹] is $\kappa_{rMAX,\alpha} / \mu_\alpha$, with $\kappa_{rMAX,\alpha} = 1$, H [m] is the thickness of the formation, density difference $\Delta\rho = \rho_l - \rho_g$, Q [m³·s⁻¹] is the injection rate, t [s] is injection time, ϕ [-] is the porosity, S_r [-] is the residual gas saturation, r [m] is the radial distance from the injection well, h [m] is the depth of the interface between liquid and gaseous phases.

At steady state, we have the following equation.

$$0 = \chi - \frac{2\lambda}{[\lambda h' + (1 - h')]^2} \left[1 + \Gamma \lambda \chi \frac{d(h'^2)}{d\chi} \right] + \frac{4\Gamma \lambda (1 - h')}{\lambda h' + (1 - h')} \left[h' + \chi \frac{dh'}{\partial\chi} + h' \chi \frac{d^2 h'}{d\chi^2} \left(\frac{\partial h'}{\partial\chi} \right)^{-1} \right], \quad (\text{F.3})$$

where $\chi = \eta^2 / \tau$. Equation (F.3) is subjected to constraint arising from mass balance of

CO_2 , which is given as

$$\int_0^{R_0} \phi(1 - S_r)h2\pi r dr = Qt, \quad (\text{F.4})$$

where, R_0 is the point where the interface intercepts the r - axis, i.e., $h(R_0, t) = 0$. The dimensionless form of (F.4) is given as

$$\int_0^{X_0} h' d\chi = 2, \quad (\text{F.5})$$

where, $X_0 = \eta^2(R_0)/\tau$. (F.3) subjected to (F.5) can be solved numerically.

An example of the *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006) solution is given for the following condition: $H = 15$ [m], $\phi = 0.15$, $\kappa = 2 \cdot 10^{-14}$ [m²], $S_r = 0$, $\mu_l = 0.511$ [mpa], $\mu_g = 0.061$ [mpa], $\rho_l = 1099$ [kg·m⁻³] and $\rho_g = 733$ [kg·m⁻³]. We inject CO_2 gas with different injection rates $Q = 12.1, 0.243, 0.061, 0.030$ [$10^{-3}\text{m}^3\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] for a period $t = 14.206$ [year]. The corresponding gravity parameters are $\Gamma = 0.16, 0.82, 3.27, 6.54$. The results are given in Figure F.1.

Figure F.1: *Nordbotten and Celia* (2006) solution for $\Gamma = 0.16, 0.82, 3.27, 6.54$.

Appendix G

Partial Equilibrium Reaction Based on Molar Abundance

This section gives the kinetic reaction solution based on molar components. This derivation is parallel to the derivation based on mass components in Chapter 4.

In a partial equilibrium system, the independent variables are molar abundances of kinetic species (ζ_k) and pure equilibrium components (ω_{ee}). The independent variables are stored in vector

$$\omega = \begin{bmatrix} \zeta_k \\ \omega_{ee} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{G.1})$$

where, ω_{ee} is $(n_e - n_E)$ -dimensional vector, defined as

$$\omega_{ee} = \Omega_{ee} \zeta_e, \quad (\text{G.2})$$

in which, the kernel matrix for pure equilibrium component matrix Ω_{ee} is $(n_e - n_E) \times n_e$ matrix. Ω_{ee} is obtained by extracting the columns corresponding to equilibrium species from Ω_e , which is the component matrix for equilibrium reactions, i.e., $\Omega_e \nu^t = \mathbf{0}$. The method of calculating Ω_e is already given in Chapter 3.

The temporal development of kinetic species follows

$$\frac{d\zeta_k}{dt} = \nu_{kk}^t \mathbf{r}_k, \quad (\text{G.3})$$

where ν_{kk} only consists the columns of ν_k corresponding to the kinetic species, and \mathbf{r}_k stores the kinetic reaction rates for n_K kinetic reactions. \mathbf{r}_k is a function of all kinetic and equilibrium species. The temporal change of the pure equilibrium components is

$$\frac{d\omega_{ee}}{dt} = \Omega_{ee} \nu_{ke}^t \mathbf{r}_k, \quad (\text{G.4})$$

where $(n_K \times n_e)$ matrix ν_{ke} only consists the columns of ν_k corresponding to the equilibrium

species. Here, we cannot explicitly calculate the equilibrium species in the same way as kinetic species. The molar abundance of the equilibrium species is calculated by solving the (n_E) equilibrium reactions (i.e. Equation (4.3)) with the mass action law, which requires ($n_e - n_E$) constraints based on ($n_e - n_E$) pure equilibrium components (i.e., Equation (G.2)).

On the basis of Equations (G.3) and (G.4) we have the governing equation for kinetic-equilibrium reactions

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{d\zeta_k}{dt} \\ \frac{d\omega_{ee}}{dt} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \nu_{kk}^t \\ \Omega_{ee}\nu_{ke}^t \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{r}_k. \quad (\text{G.5})$$

The governing equations (G.5) is solved by using Newton-Raphson method. The Newton-Raphson form of the governing equations is

$$\mathbf{0} = \mathcal{F} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{d\zeta_k}{dt} \\ \frac{d\omega_{ee}}{dt} \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \nu_{kk}^t \\ \Omega_{ee}\nu_{ke}^t \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{r}_k, \quad (\text{G.6})$$

and the Jacobian matrix of this equation system is

$$\mathbf{J} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \omega} = \frac{1}{dt} \mathbf{I} - \begin{pmatrix} \nu_{kk}^t \\ \Omega_{ee}\nu_{ke}^t \end{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_k}{\partial \omega}. \quad (\text{G.7})$$

The solution is

$$\omega^{i+1,j+1} = \omega^{i+1,j} + \delta\omega^{i+1,j}, \quad (\text{G.8})$$

where $\delta\omega^{i+1,j}$ is obtained by solving

$$\mathbf{J}^{i+1,j} \delta\omega^{i+1,j} = -\mathcal{F}^{i+1,j}, \quad (\text{G.9})$$

where, superscript i denotes time step and j denotes the iteration step. Initially, $\omega^{i+1,0} = \omega^i$.

The key to solving Equations (G.6) to (G.9) is solving $\frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_k}{\partial \omega}$. As we know the $\mathbf{r}_k = \mathbf{r}_k(\zeta)$, we need to know the molar abundance of equilibrium species to calculate the \mathbf{r}_k and its derivative $\frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_k}{\partial \omega}$, which can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_k}{\partial \omega} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_k}{\partial \zeta} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \omega}, \quad (\text{G.10})$$

where

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \omega} = \left[\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \zeta_k}, \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \zeta_e}, \frac{\partial \zeta_e}{\partial \omega_{ee}} \right]. \quad (\text{G.11})$$

Here, $\partial \mathbf{r}_k / \partial \boldsymbol{\zeta}$ is obtained with the explicit empirical expression for kinetic reaction rate, given in Chapter 4. The only unknowns are $\partial \boldsymbol{\zeta}_e / \partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_{ee}$.

Since the equilibrium species satisfy

$$\mathbf{0} = \mathcal{F}_e = \begin{bmatrix} \nu_{ee} \ln a_e - \ln K_e \\ \Omega_{ee} \boldsymbol{\zeta}_e - \boldsymbol{\omega}_{ee} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{G.12})$$

$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\zeta}_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_{ee}}$ is obtained by taking derivative of Equation (G.12) with respect to the equilibrium components, that is,

$$\mathbf{0} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_{ee}} = \begin{bmatrix} \nu_{ee} \frac{\partial \ln a_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\zeta}_e} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\zeta}_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_{ee}} \\ \Omega_{ee} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\zeta}_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_{ee}} - \mathbf{I}_e \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{G.13})$$

Rearranging Equation (G.13), we get

$$\begin{bmatrix} \nu_{ee} \frac{\partial \ln a_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\zeta}_e} \\ \Omega_{ee} \end{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\zeta}_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_{ee}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{I}_e \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{G.14})$$

where $\frac{\partial \ln a_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\zeta}_e}$ has been calculated when solving Equation (G.12) with the mass action law given in Table 3.1 of Chapter 3.

An example solution of the aforementioned algorithm is given as follows. In this example we will show that the numerical algorithm is insensitive to the time step. The chemical system contains one kinetic reaction and four equilibrium reactions, which are

The molality of Na^+ and Cl^- are constant $m_{Na^+} = m_{Cl^-} = 0.5$ [molal]. The initial molar abundances of the nine reactive species are $\zeta_{H_2O} = 55.472$, $\zeta_{CO_2} = 13.232$, $\zeta_{CaCO_3(s)} = 14.972$, $\zeta_{H^+} = 1.789 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $\zeta_{Ca^{2+}} = 0.028$, $\zeta_{HCO_3^-} = 0.056$ and $\zeta_{CO_2(aq)} = 1.7397$, $\zeta_{CO_3^{2-}} = 1.8723 \cdot 10^{-7}$ and $\zeta_{OH^-} = 6.3039 \cdot 10^{-10}$ [mol]. These nine species are in equilibrium state at initial gas pressure $p_g = 1$ [bar] and liquid pressure $p_l = 100$ [bar]. The volume of water is $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m³. The parameters for the kinetic reaction rate are listed in Table G.1 while other parameters related to the reactions can be found in Appendix D.

The system is perturbed by increasing the gas pressure to 200 [bar]. The total simulation time is $t = 1$ [s]. Three simulations are conducted with three time steps to test the accuracy of this algorithm is insensitive to the time step. In these three simulations, the total simulation time is split in 10^5 , 10^4 and 10^3 steps, respectively; they correspond to three

time steps $\Delta t = 10^{-5}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-3}$, respectively. The comparison of the effect of time steps is given in Figure G.1. Figure G.2 gives the temporal developments of four species when $\Delta t = 10^{-4}$ [s].

Table G.1: Parameter settings.

Parameter	Value
T_c [°C]	60
\mathcal{A}_s [10^6m^{-1}]	0.0469
$\theta_{H^+}, \theta_{pCO_2}, \eta_V$ [-]	1, 1, 2/3
(E_1, E_2, E_3) [$10^3 \text{J} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$]	(14.4, 23.5, 35.4)
$(k_{1,0}, k_{2,0}, k_{3,0})$ [$\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]	($10^{-0.3}, 10^{-5.81}, 10^{-3.48}$)

Figure G.1: Numerical results of the calcite dissolution for three different time steps.

 Figure G.2: Temporal developments of four aqueous species ($\Delta t = 10^{-4}$ [s]).

Appendix H

McWhorter and Sunada (1990) Solution for One-Dimensional Displacement

The theoretical solution given by *McWhorter and Sunada (1990)* is used to benchmark the developed numerical model in Chapter 4. This theoretical solution applies to the displacement of wetting (or non-wetting) phase by non-wetting (or wetting) phase in one-dimensional (radial or linear) domain. The gravity is not considered. Here we only employ the displacement of wetting phase by non-wetting phase in a linear domain.

The whole derivation is based on the Darcy's law

$$q_\alpha = -\kappa\lambda_\alpha \frac{\partial p_\alpha}{\partial x} \quad (\text{H.1})$$

and the retention curve

$$p_g - p_l = p_c(S_l), \quad (\text{H.2})$$

where, $\alpha = (l, g)$ represent wetting and nonwetting phases, respectively; $\lambda_\alpha = \kappa_{r\alpha}/\mu_\alpha$ is the mobility of α phase. The detailed derivation of the *McWhorter and Sunada (1990)* solution is not repeated here, and only the final results are given.

We define the fractional flow of gaseous nonwetting phase is

$$F_g(x, t) = \frac{q_g/q_{g0} - f_{gi}R_g}{1 - f_{gi}R_g}, \quad (\text{H.3})$$

where, $q_{g0} = q_g(0, t)$, $f_{gi} = f_g(S_i)$ and $R_g = q_t/q_{g0}$. Here,

$$q_g = f_g q_t - D \frac{\partial S_g}{\partial x}, \quad (\text{H.4})$$

$$D(S_g) = \kappa \frac{\lambda_l \lambda_g}{\lambda_l + \lambda_g} \frac{\partial p_c}{\partial S_g}, \quad (\text{H.5})$$

$$f_\alpha(S_g) = \frac{\lambda_\alpha}{\lambda_l + \lambda_g}. \quad (\text{H.6})$$

The normalized fractional flow of gaseous non-wetting phase is

$$f_{gn} = \frac{f_g R_g - f_{gi} R_g}{1 - f_{gi} R_g}. \quad (\text{H.7})$$

The initial and boundary conditions are given as

$$q_{g0} = q_g(0, t) = At^{-1/2}; S_g(\infty, t) = S_{gi}; S_g(x, 0) = S_{gi}. \quad (\text{H.8})$$

The solution is then given as

$$x(S_g, t) = \frac{2A(1 - f_{gi} R_g)}{\phi} \frac{dF_g}{dS_g} t^{1/2}, \quad (\text{H.9})$$

where, A and dF_g/dS_g are given as

$$A^2 = \frac{\phi}{2(1 - f_{gi} R_g)^2} \int_{S_{gi}}^{S_{g0}} \frac{(S_g - S_{gi})D}{F_g - f_{gn}} dS_g \quad (\text{H.10})$$

and

$$\frac{dF_g}{dS_g} = \int_{S_g}^{S_{g0}} \frac{D}{F_g - f_{gn}} d\beta \left[\int_{S_{gi}}^{S_{g0}} \frac{(S_g - S_{gi})D}{F_g - f_{gn}} dS_g \right]^{-1}, \quad (\text{H.11})$$

where,

$$F_g(S_g) = 1 - \int_{S_g}^{S_{g0}} \frac{(\beta - S_g)D}{F_g - f_{gn}} d\beta \left[\int_{S_{gi}}^{S_{g0}} \frac{(S_g - S_{gi})D}{F_g - f_{gn}} dS_g \right]^{-1}. \quad (\text{H.12})$$

An example solution for different m_p are given in Figure H.1. The related parameters are given as follows. $\mu_l = 0.5[\text{mpa}]$, $\mu_g = 0.061[\text{mpa}]$, $\alpha_p = 5[\text{pa}^{-1}]$, $S_{gr} = S_{lr} = 0$, $\kappa = 10^{-11}[\text{m}^2]$, $S_{g0} = 0.5$, $S_{gi} = 0$ and $\phi = 0.2$. $m_p = 0.6, 0.7, 0.8$ are used, and the corresponding $A^2 = 1.58 \times 10^{-4}, 3.89 \times 10^{-5}, 1.08 \times 10^{-5}$.

Figure H.1: Effect of m_p on the saturation profile for displacement of wetting phase.

Appendix I

Dimensionless Form

This section gives the dimensionless form of the convection-diffusion equation of Chapter 5. With aid of the following scaling scheme:

$$X^{C*} = \frac{X^C}{X^{C,top}}, t^* = \frac{t(\Delta\rho g\kappa)^2}{(\mu\phi)^2 D}, \nabla^* = \frac{\mu\phi D}{\Delta\rho g\kappa} \nabla, q^* = \frac{q\mu}{\Delta\rho g\kappa} \text{ and } Q^{C*} = \frac{Q^C \mu^2 \phi D}{X^{C,top} (\Delta\rho g\kappa)^2 \rho}. \quad (\text{I.1})$$

the dimensionless governing equation for the CO_2 species is then

$$\frac{\partial X^{C*}}{\partial t^*} = -\nabla^*(X^{C*} u^*) + (\nabla^*)^2 X^{C*} + Q^{C*}, \quad (\text{I.2})$$

where

$$u^* = -(\nabla p^* - \rho^* \nabla^* z^*), \quad (\text{I.3})$$

with

$$p^* = \frac{p\kappa}{\mu\phi D} \text{ and } \rho^* = \frac{\rho}{\Delta\rho}. \quad (\text{I.4})$$

Similarly, we can obtain the dimensionless governing equation for the water species.

Appendix J

Enhanced NAPL Removal and Mixing with Engineered Chaotic Advection

Description: This chapter is based on a project for '*Enhanced NAPL Removal and Mixing with Engineered Injection and Extraction*', which is parallel to the Geological Carbon Sequestration (GCS). The content of this chapter has been published on *Water Resources Research* (<https://doi.org/10.1029/2021WR031114>).

J.1 Abstract

Aquifer remediation with in-situ soil washing techniques and enhanced oil removal typically involve the injection of liquid solutions into the geological formation to displace and mobilize non-aqueous phase liquids (NAPLs). The efficiency of these systems is oftentimes low because the displacing fluid bypasses large quantities of NAPL due to the inherent complexity of a heterogeneous natural system. Here, Engineered Injection and Extraction (EIE) generated by rotating periodic injection is proposed as a method to enhance NAPL removal and mixing. To evaluate the method, we perform two-phase flow simulations in multiple realizations of random permeability fields with different correlation structures and connectivity between injection and extraction wells embedded in a five-spot pattern. Results show that EIE can significantly improve removal efficiency and mixing depending on several controlling factors. The effects of EIE are more significant under unfavorable conditions, i.e., when injection and extraction wells are well-connected through preferential channels, permeabilities are highly heterogeneous, and/or the mobility ratio between the wetting and the non-wetting fluids is larger than one. Removal efficiency reaches its maximum value when the Kubo number is close to one, i.e., when the saturation front travels one range of the permeability field in an injection pulse. These effects can develop

in just a few cycles. However, removal efficiency should undergo first an early stage with detrimental effects in order to maximize removal in the long term. EIE not only enhances NAPL removal and mixing, but also reduces the uncertainty, making the system more reliable and less dependent on heterogeneity.

J.2 Introduction

Non-aqueous phase liquid (NAPL) removal from complex geological formations is of great interest in aquifer remediation with in situ soil washing techniques (*Huling and Weaver, 1991; NRC, 2005*). These techniques typically involve the injection of liquid solutions into the geological formation to displace and mobilize the target NAPL contaminant source (e.g., hydrocarbons, chlorinated solvents, mineral oil and other products from chemical industry) towards extraction wells (*Rao et al., 1997; Martel et al., 2004; Smalley et al., 2009; Davies et al., 2014; Jackson, 2014; Jin et al., 2017; Welkenhuysen et al., 2017*). The injected fluid can be water or liquid solutions with cosolvents (e.g., hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin), surfactants (e.g., sodium dihexyl sulfosuccinate) or polymers (e.g., partially hydrolyzed polyacrylamid), which are meant to improve sweeping and flushing by either reducing capillary trapping, increasing dissolution or reducing water mobility (*Falta et al., 1999; Mccray and Brusseau, 1999; Dugan et al., 2003; Yousefvand and Jafari, 2015; Javanbakht et al., 2017*). An early removal of NAPL can substantially eliminate the main contaminant source, improving the overall cleanup efficiency at later stages of the remediation process (*Huling and Weaver, 1991; Soga et al., 2004*).

NAPL removal is more efficient in relatively homogeneous porous media and low mobility ratios (*Fayers and Hewett, 1992; Soga et al., 2004; Smalley et al., 2009; Stroo et al., 2012*). However, aquifer heterogeneity (the spatial distribution of permeability) often exhibits well-organized high permeability geological structures that concentrate the flow in the form of preferential channels (e.g., *de Marsily, 1985; Western et al., 2001; Zheng and Gorelick, 2003; Knudby and Carrera, 2005; Le Borgne and Gouze, 2008; Fernàndez-Garcia et al., 2010; Bianchi et al., 2011; Fiori and Jankovic, 2012; Renard and Allard, 2013a; Essaid et al., 2015; Nicolaidis et al., 2015*). In a multiphase flow problem, these channels will cause the displacing fluid to bypass large quantities of the NAPL in place, resulting in a significant reduction of the sweeping efficiencies and the mixing between the wetting and the non-wetting phase (*Pruess and Tsang, 1990; Wan et al., 1996; Glass et al., 1998; Amundsen et al., 1999; Bertels et al., 2001; Rangel-German and Kouscek, 2006; Arshadi et al., 2017, 2018; Kim et al., 2019*). The latter is crucial for chemical flooding with surfactants and cosolvents during the remediation of an aquifer contaminated with NAPL, as dissolution directly depends on the contact between liquid phases. In the petroleum industry, channeling will cause huge losses in recovered oil and monetary income (*Craig*

et al., 1957; *Craig*, 1971; *Fayers and Hewett*, 1992; *Chang et al.*, 1994; *Paez Yanez et al.*, 2007). The injection of fluids in a multiphase system is also important for studying the sequestration of anthropogenic CO_2 in deep saline aquifers (e.g., *Bachu*, 2000; *Bolster et al.*, 2009; *Vilarrasa et al.*, 2010; *Saaltink et al.*, 2013), which constitutes an interesting alternative for reducing greenhouse gas emissions to the atmosphere.

Engineered Injection and Extraction (EIE) has been demonstrated to be an efficient technique for enhancing in situ groundwater remediation technologies (e.g., *Zhang et al.*, 2009; *Mays and Neupauer*, 2012; *Trefry et al.*, 2012; *Lester et al.*, 2013; *Neupauer et al.*, 2014; *Rodriguez-Escales et al.*, 2017; *Di Dato et al.*, 2018). This is attributed to the fact that EIE in contaminant transport has been shown capable to create chaotic advection (*Neupauer et al.*, 2014), which is known to enhance mixing. The concept of chaotic advection was described by *Ottino* (1990) and *Ottino et al.* (1994). Essentially, EIE generates transient flow fields by means of time-dependent water injection and extraction systems creating erratic transport paths that enhance mixing by folding and stretching the solute plume. Results in this area have shown that applying EIE increases considerably the contact area between the contaminants and the injected treatment solutions during in situ remediation of contaminated groundwater, promoting the degradation of toxic compounds, including emerging organic contaminants. Applications of EIE in groundwater can be found in *Bagtzoglou and Oates* (2007), *Luo et al.* (2008), *Rodriguez-Escales et al.* (2017) and *Libera et al.* (2017). There are different ways to operate EIE in aquifers. One of them is by using a rotated potential mixing flow (RPM). This form of EIE consists in the assembly of several dipole injection/extraction wells operating in a plane with the same flow rate (*Metcalfe et al.*, 2006; *Lester et al.*, 2009, 2010; *Metcalfe et al.*, 2010; *Trefry et al.*, 2012). The simplest RPM-generating sequence consists in activating a dipole injection/extraction well for a certain time, then rotating the active dipole around the origin by an angle, and repeating periodically. However, the RPM flow is not the only form of EIE in groundwater polluted sites. Many other kinds of EIE well networks and stirring protocols have been proposed in literature with the objective to enhance the mixing of solutions in groundwater (e.g., *Bagtzoglou and Oates*, 2007; *Zhang et al.*, 2009; *Piscopo et al.*, 2013; *Neupauer et al.*, 2014).

Although some authors (*Falta et al.*, 1999) have already observed that altering the flow direction can improve NAPL remediation, there are no works aimed at evaluating the improvement of EIE during in situ NAPL remediation. The study of this problem requires the simulation of a multiphase flow system, which at least should describe the movement of the wetting (injected fluid) and the non-wetting fluid (NAPL) through the porous medium (*Abriola and Pinder*, 1985; *Sleep and Sykes*, 1989; *Celia et al.*, 2015). Under some simplifying conditions, the governing equation of saturation of immiscible fluids resembles the advection-dispersion equation (ADE) in porous media (*Sleep and*

Sykes, 1993a,b; Bolster et al., 2009). However, the advective and the dispersive terms in the saturation equation are nonlinear functions of saturation, making impossible a direct extrapolation of the results obtained in solute transport. In addition, we highlight that the role of channeling (connectivity) during engineered injection and extraction in heterogeneous porous media has not been previously studied in the literature, even for the simple case of solute transport in single-phase flow systems.

Motivated by the success of an engineered sequence of injections and extractions in contaminant transport, this paper explores the use of EIE in two-phase flow systems. More specifically, we evaluate the effect of EIE in the removal of NAPL using a five-spot injection-extraction well pattern in random heterogeneous porous media with different correlation structures and connectivities. To achieve this goal we have evaluated different synthetic cases where different scenarios of EIE have been tested in two-phase flow systems. We have defined performance metrics to analyze the impact of EIE on NAPL remediation, its effect on connectivity, and the role of heterogeneity and mobility ratio in EIE configurations. Performance metrics are designed to quantify recovery efficiency of NAPL and the degree of mixing between NAPL and the injected fluid. A stochastic framework is used to evaluate the uncertainty associated with the performance of EIE.

J.3 Methods

J.3.1 The Engineered Injection and Extraction System

We evaluate an Engineered Injection and Extraction (EIE) system designed for extracting NAPL in a water-wet heterogeneous aquifer. We consider an aquifer contaminated with significant amounts of NAPL, which can be partially mobilized by external forces that drive flow (the saturation of NAPL is larger than the residual state). Injection and extraction wells are organized to form a canonical five-spot pattern (*Satkin and Bedient, 1988; Juanes and Lie, 2008*). This organization of wells is frequently used for extracting NAPL in contaminated sites (*Nicolaidis et al., 2015*), and oil in petroleum fields (*Craig, 1971*) as well as for carbon storage associated with CO_2 enhanced oil recovery (EOR) in residual oil zones (*Ren and Duncan, 2019*). In the five-spot pattern, injection and extraction wells are uniformly distributed in such a way that each extraction well is surrounded by 4 injection wells, and an injection well is surrounded by 4 extraction wells (Figure J.1). The wetting fluid is injected through the injection wells to displace the non-wetting fluid (NAPL) towards the central extraction well.

Let us denote the injection rate of the wetting fluid associated with the j th injection well of a given five-spot pattern as $Q_{w_j}^i(t)$, $j = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$. EIE operates by periodically fluctuating the injection rates $Q_{w_j}^i(t)$ in such a way that each injection well is out of phase

with the others. In order to simplify the fluctuation system and reduce the number of parameters, we consider that injection rates follow a rectangular wave function with a time period T . This can be formulated by using the rectangular function f_j ,

$$Q_{w_j}^i(t) = Q_t^e f_j(t, T), \quad 0 \leq t < T, \quad (\text{J.1})$$

$$f_j(t, T) = H(t - (j - 1)T/4) - H(t - jT/4), \quad (\text{J.2})$$

together with the statement of periodicity,

$$Q_{w_j}^i(t) = Q_{w_j}^i(t - T), \quad t \geq T, \quad (\text{J.3})$$

where $H(\cdot)$ is the Heaviside function. Note that the rectangular function $f_j(t, T)$ is equal to 1 in the time interval $[jT/4 - T/4, jT/4]$ and zero otherwise. That is to say that the pulse duration τ is equal to $T/4$. Q_t^e is a constant value that specifies the injection rate of the wetting fluid when the well is active (when $f_j = 1$). In short, the EIE system set-up has two main features: (1) the injection rate is constant and equal to Q_t^e for a time interval $\tau = T/4$; and (2) each injection well is periodically activated with a period T . Thus, each injection period is divided into 4 equal subintervals of duration $T/4$. In each subinterval, only one injection well is active. That is, we first only activate the injection well 1 during the first time subinterval, while keeping the other injection wells deactivated. Then, we deactivate injection well 1 and only activate injection well 2 in the second time subinterval, and so on (see Figure J.1).

J.3.2 Two-Phase Flow Model

We consider the movement of two immiscible liquids in a horizontal two-dimensional heterogeneous aquifer. Mass transfer (e.g., volatilization and dissolution) between the two liquid phases is assumed negligible. The governing equations used to simulate the two-phase flow system are determined by the mass conservation equation of the two liquids and the generalized Darcy's law. Assuming that the porous medium and the fluids are incompressible (constant porosity and fluid densities), we have the following coupled system of partial differential equations in two dimensions,

$$\phi b \frac{\partial S_w}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\kappa \lambda_w b \nabla p_w) + \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} Q_{w_j}^i(t) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_j^i) - \sum_{j=1}^{n_e} Q_{w_j}^e(t) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_j^e), \quad (\text{J.4})$$

$$\phi b \frac{\partial S_{nw}}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\kappa \lambda_{nw} b \nabla p_{nw}) - \sum_{j=1}^{n_e} Q_{nw_j}^e(t) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_j^e), \quad (\text{J.5})$$

Figure J.1: General five-spot arrangement of extraction and injection wells; the triangle symbols refer to the injection wells, whereas the circle symbols refer to the extraction wells; the region shown in solid lines is the domain of the synthetic test case TC1, and the region in dashed lines is the domain of the synthetic test case TC2.

where ϕ is the porosity, b is the aquifer thickness, $\mathbf{x} = (x, y)^t$, S_w and S_{nw} are the saturations of the wetting and the non-wetting fluids, $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac delta function, n_i is the number of injection wells, n_e is the number of extraction wells, \mathbf{x}_j^i is the position of the j th injection well, \mathbf{x}_j^e is the position of the j th extraction well, κ is the intrinsic permeability, λ_w and λ_{nw} are the mobilities of the wetting and the non-wetting fluids, p_w and p_{nw} are the pressures of the wetting and the non-wetting fluids, $Q_{w_j}^i$ is the injection rate of the wetting fluid at the j th injection well, and $Q_{w_j}^e$ and $Q_{nw_j}^e$ are the extraction rates of the wetting and the non-wetting fluids at the j th extraction well. The total extraction rate associated with the j th extraction well is $Q_{t_j}^e = Q_{w_j}^e + Q_{nw_j}^e$. Fluid mobility is defined as the ratio of the relative permeability to the viscosity of the fluid,

$$\lambda_w = \frac{\kappa_{rw}}{\mu_w}, \quad \lambda_{nw} = \frac{\kappa_{rnw}}{\mu_{nw}}, \quad (\text{J.6})$$

where κ_{rw} and κ_{rnw} are the relative permeabilities of the wetting and the non-wetting fluids, and μ_w and μ_{nw} are the viscosities of the wetting and the non-wetting fluids. The relative permeabilities of the non-wetting κ_{rnw} and wetting κ_{rw} phases are only functions of water saturation and they are described by the Corey correlation model,

$$\kappa_{rnw} = \kappa_{rnwm}(1 - S_e)^{n_{nw}}, \quad (\text{J.7})$$

$$\kappa_{rw} = \kappa_{rwm}S_e^{n_w}, \quad (\text{J.8})$$

where κ_{rwm} , n_w , κ_{rnwm} and n_{nw} are the scaling parameters of the relative permeability curves, and S_e is the effective saturation of the wetting fluid defined as

$$S_e = \frac{S_w - S_{wr}}{1 - S_{wr} - S_{nwr}}, \quad (\text{J.9})$$

where S_{wr} and S_{nwr} are the residual saturations of the wetting and the nonwetting phases, respectively. The extraction rate of the wetting and the non-wetting phase is determined by the fractional flow function $f_w(S_w)$ through

$$Q_{w_j}^e = Q_{t_j}^e f_w(S_w), \quad Q_{nw_j}^e = Q_{t_j}^e (1 - f_w(S_w)), \quad (\text{J.10})$$

where

$$f_w(S_w) = \frac{\lambda_w}{\lambda_w + \lambda_{nw}}. \quad (\text{J.11})$$

The difference between the two fluid pressures defines the capillary pressure,

$$p_c = p_{nw} - p_w, \quad (\text{J.12})$$

which is determined by the saturation-capillary pressure relationship or retention curve (see equation (J.16)). The system only considers the presence of two liquids and therefore the sum of saturations is equal to one, i.e., $S_w + S_{nw} = 1$.

J.3.3 Aquifer Heterogeneity

The intrinsic permeability and the retention curve are considered to vary in space. The natural log of the intrinsic permeability field, denoted as $Y(\mathbf{x}) = \ln \kappa(\mathbf{x})$, is considered to follow a stationary multi-Gaussian random distribution characterized by an exponential semivariogram model of variance contribution σ_Y^2 , defined as

$$\gamma(\mathbf{h}) = \sigma_Y^2 \left(1 - \exp\left(-3|\mathbf{h}'|\right)\right), \quad (\text{J.13})$$

where \mathbf{h} is the separation vector between two points of the aquifer, and \mathbf{h}' is the separation vector obtained by orienting the correlation structure along the coordinates and scaling the ranges to unitary values according to

$$\begin{pmatrix} h'_x \\ h'_y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_{\max}^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & a_{\min}^{-1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} h_x \\ h_y \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{J.14})$$

where a_{\max} and a_{\min} are the maximum and minimum ranges in the principal directions. The maximum correlation direction is oriented θ degrees counterclockwise from the positive x axis. The randomness of $Y(\mathbf{x})$ is transferred to the retention curve through the Leverett's function $J(S_e)$ (Leverett, 1939, 1941) that scales the capillary pressure via interfacial tension, porosity and intrinsic permeability (Brown, 1951; Demond and Roberts, 1991; Lie, 2014). The Leverett's function is an invariant property written as

$$J(S_e) = \frac{p_c}{\gamma \cos \alpha} \sqrt{\frac{\kappa}{\phi}}, \quad (\text{J.15})$$

where γ is interfacial tension, and α is the contact angle. From this, assuming that the saturation-capillary pressure relation follows the *Brooks and Corey* (1966) model, the retention curve is assumed to vary as a function of the intrinsic permeability and the effective saturation by

$$p_c(S_e, \kappa) = p_L S_e^{-1/\lambda} \sqrt{\frac{\kappa_g}{\kappa}}, \quad 0 < S_e \leq 1, \quad (\text{J.16})$$

where p_L is the characteristic Leverett entry pressure, and κ_g is the geometric mean of permeability.

J.3.4 Fluid Mobility Ratio

The displacement of NAPL during injection not only depends on aquifer heterogeneity but also on the fluid properties (*Nicolaides et al.*, 2015). The mobility ratio M is the average mobility of the injection fluid behind the displacing front divided by that of the non-wetting fluid ahead of the displacing front at breakthrough,

$$M = \frac{\kappa_{rw}^0 \mu_{nw}}{\mu_w \kappa_{rnw}^0}. \quad (\text{J.17})$$

To estimate the mobility ratio, in accordance with *Craig* (1971), the relative permeability of the wetting fluid is defined with the average wetting fluid saturation \bar{S}_{wBT} behind the displacing front at breakthrough (denoted as κ_{rw}^0), and the relative permeability of the non-wetting fluid is determined by the non-wetting fluid saturation ahead of the displacing front (denoted as κ_{rnw}^0), i.e., the initial saturation of NAPL. \bar{S}_{wBT} is obtained by laying a tangent line to the fractional flow curve $f_w(S_w)$ from S_{wr} and extrapolating this tangent line to $f_w = 1.0$.

When $M < 1$ fluid displacement is said to have favorable mobility conditions. In this case, for a given pressure gradient, the wetting fluid can travel at a lower velocity than the non-wetting fluid, effectively pushing the NAPL towards extraction wells. On the contrary, when $M > 1$ the wetting fluid can travel faster than the non-wetting fluid and there is a tendency for the NAPL to be bypassed. During the in situ remediation of a contaminated aquifer, liquid solutions with chemicals (e.g., surfactants, alkalis, or polymers) are sometimes injected into the aquifer to improve field conditions by decreasing the mobility ratio M (*Huling and Weaver*, 1991). Similar strategies are often used in petroleum engineering to enhanced oil recovery (*Abidin et al.*, 2012; *Raffa et al.*, 2016). Here, we analyze the effect of the mobility ratio on the performance of EIE by changing the viscosity of the wetting fluid so as to represent favorable and unfavorable mobility conditions. Thus, we consider three different mobility ratios, i.e., $M = 0.5, 1.4,$ and 2.2 . Considering that NAPL viscosity (e.g., Chlorohydrocarbons and oil products) typically ranges from 0.35 to 28 [mPa·s] (*Schwille*, 1981; *Huling and Weaver*, 1991; *Reid et al.*, 1997; *Boulding*, 1996), approximately equivalent to a mobility ratio range between 0.1 and 1.8, these values cover a wide range of real applications.

J.3.5 Synthetic Test Cases

The objective of the synthetic test cases is to compare EIE NAPL removal with a constant injection scheme (conventional situation) in complex geological formations. The effect of EIE is studied in a wide variety of permeability fields. For this, we consider two synthetic test cases, denoted as TC1 and TC2, that respectively represent two heterogeneous aquifers with different correlation structure of the permeability field and hydraulic connectivity

between injection and extraction wells. Let us consider the general arrangement of injection and extraction wells shown in Figure J.1. The distance between two adjacent injection or extraction wells is 212 m and the aquifer thickness is 20 m. The aquifer system is assumed to be initially saturated with NAPL and residual water; the initial water saturation is $S_{wi}=S_{wr}=0.2$ and the initial NAPL saturation is $S_{wni}=1-S_{wr}=0.8$. The injection-extraction system operates over 20 years. The model domain of TC1, denoted as V_1 , is delimited by the inner square region shown in Figure J.1. This test case involves 4 injectors and 1 central extraction well. TC1 represents a generic five-spot injection-extraction system embedded in an isotropic two dimensional heterogeneous $Y(\mathbf{x})$ field with $a_{\max} = a_{\min} = 51$ m. The model domain of TC2 is defined by the dashed lines shown in Figure J.1. The domain contains 5 extraction wells and 4 injectors. TC2 represents the same five-spot pattern but in this case the injection-extraction system is embedded in an anisotropic heterogeneous $Y(\mathbf{x})$ field with $a_{\max} = 225$ m, $a_{\min} = 22.5$ m, and $\theta = 45^\circ$. The maximum correlation direction is oriented along the line connecting injection and extraction wells to enhance the effect of hydraulic connectivity. The maximum range is smaller than the field scale to assure the effect of permeability heterogeneity is activated; otherwise, the field is relatively homogeneous. The two heterogeneous systems share the same geometric mean of the intrinsic permeability, $\kappa_g = 10^{-14}$ m², and we explore three different degrees of heterogeneity, $\sigma_Y^2 = 0.1, 2, \text{ and } 6$, which represent a mild, moderate, and highly heterogeneous aquifer. We chose to work with a low κ_g value to test EIE under adverse conditions with permeability values that fluctuate between 10^{-18} and 10^{-10} m². NAPL is typically difficult to recover in low permeability formations (*Mackay and Cherry, 1989*). We note though that the analysis is presented using dimensionless variables to make the results more general. The geostatistical parameters of the $Y(\mathbf{x})$ random fields are summarized in Table J.2.

All domain boundaries are set to no-flow conditions. The extents of V_1 and V_2 are 212×212 m² and 300×300 m², respectively. V_2 is larger than V_1 to allow aligning the domain boundaries with the stratification in the TC2 case. Note that, otherwise, the injected fluid would be forced to move through the stratification. Of course, some boundary effects are expected but the intent here is not to exactly reproduce a large field system but to compare EIE removal with a conventional scheme. The total extraction rate assigned to the central well is always constant and fixed to $Q_{t_5}^e = Q$ in all cases. EIE follows always a rectangular wave function with amplitude Q_t^e and period T . The constant injection scheme considers that $Q_{w_j}^i = Q/4$ in TC1 and $Q_{w_j}^i = Q/2$ in TC2 for $j = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$. In TC2, the total extraction rate of corner wells are fixed to $Q_{t_j}^e = Q/4$ for $j = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$. Parameters adopted during the simulations are listed in Table J.2. The pumping scheme adopted in the two test cases are summarized in Table J.1.

The domains of TC1 and TC2 are respectively discretized into 101 and 201 squared

Table J.1: Pumping schemes for the engineered injection and extraction system in the two test cases and the corresponding constant injection scheme.

Time	TC1: const. injection $(Q_{w_1}^i, Q_{w_2}^i, Q_{w_3}^i, Q_{w_4}^i)$	TC1: EIE $(Q_{w_1}^i, Q_{w_2}^i, Q_{w_3}^i, Q_{w_4}^i)$
$(0, T/4)$	$(Q/4, Q/4, Q/4, Q/4)$	$(Q, 0, 0, 0)$
$(T/4, T/2)$	$(Q/4, Q/4, Q/4, Q/4)$	$(0, Q, 0, 0)$
$(T/2, 3T/4)$	$(Q/4, Q/4, Q/4, Q/4)$	$(0, 0, Q, 0)$
$(3T/4, T)$	$(Q/4, Q/4, Q/4, Q/4)$	$(0, 0, 0, Q)$
Time	TC2: const. injection $(Q_{w_1}^i, Q_{w_2}^i, Q_{w_3}^i, Q_{w_4}^i)$	TC2: EIE $(Q_{w_1}^i, Q_{w_2}^i, Q_{w_3}^i, Q_{w_4}^i)$
$(0, T/4)$	$(Q/2, Q/2, Q/2, Q/2)$	$(2Q, 0, 0, 0)$
$(T/4, T/2)$	$(Q/2, Q/2, Q/2, Q/2)$	$(0, 2Q, 0, 0)$
$(T/2, 3T/4)$	$(Q/2, Q/2, Q/2, Q/2)$	$(0, 0, 2Q, 0)$
$(3T/4, T)$	$(Q/2, Q/2, Q/2, Q/2)$	$(0, 0, 0, 2Q)$

cells to represent the variability of the random fields. The resolution of the random fields vary between 15 and 150 cells per range, which is considered sufficient to represent the inherent spatial variability of permeability. Figure J.2 shows illustrative test fields and corresponding well arrangements. To improve visualization, TC2 is rotated 45° clockwise from the x positive axis.

The simulation approach is as follows. For each test case, we first consider a stochastic description of $Y(\mathbf{x})$ with 100 equally likely realizations characterized by $\sigma_Y^2 = 2$ and $M = 2.2$ to explore the range of uncertainty. Within each realization, two-phase flow simulations with constant-injection and EIE removal are conducted with different periods T , which vary from 0.5 to 20 years. Performance metrics are then characterized by their statistical moments (mean behavior and uncertainty) and sample probability density functions (PDFs). Finally, we investigate the effect of the degree of heterogeneity σ_Y^2 and mobility ratio M in individual realizations. The effect of σ_Y^2 is analyzed by re-scaling the variance of the $Y(\mathbf{x})$ values adopted in a given realization so as to always replicate the same specific heterogeneous patterns. The viscosity of the non-wetting fluid is kept constant to $13 \text{ mPa} \cdot \text{s}$, while the viscosity of the wetting fluid is changed from 1.0 to either 0.2 or $5.0 \text{ mPa} \cdot \text{s}$ (see Table J.2), which can represent, for instance, chemical flooding with polymers during NAPL remediation or enhanced oil recovery with CO_2 sequestration, respectively.

Random fields are generated with the Sequential Gaussian Simulation method implemented in the SGSIM code (*Journal and Huijbregts, 1976*). We use the open-source Matlab Reservoir Simulation Toolbox (MRST) (*Krogstad et al., 2015*) to simulate two-phase flow using the IMPLICIT Pressure Explicit Saturation (IMPES) algorithm (*Yanosik and McCracken, 1979; Chen et al., 2006; Lie, 2014*). The numerical discretization of the flow solution and the $Y(\mathbf{x})$ field is the same. The maximum time step for updating saturation

Figure J.2: Test fields and corresponding well arrangements; the first panel of the figure shows one realization of the isotropic random field used in the synthetic test case TC1, and the second panel shows one realization of the anisotropic random field used in the synthetic test case TC2 (the domain has been rotated 45° clockwise from the x positive axis to improve visualization).

is constraint by the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) condition to assure that the time step for updating saturation is smaller than that for updating pressure (*Courant et al.*, 1928; *Coats*, 2003). The two-point flux approximation (TPFA) is employed to solve the pressure equation. The one-point upstream weighting scheme is used to avoid artificial dispersion (*Forsyth and Sammon*, 1986; *Sammon*, 1988; *Allen*, 1985). This upstream weighting scheme has first-order spatial accuracy (*Sleep and Sykes*, 1993a,b).

J.3.6 Performance Metrics

We define two different performance metrics to evaluate the relative efficiency of the proposed EIE system involved in a five-spot pattern: the removal efficiency and the saturation distribution index. The removal efficiency $RE(t)$ measures the volume of NAPL recovered at time t relative to the initial volume of NAPL in the aquifer, and the distribution index $DI(t)$ quantifies the degree of uniformity of the wetting fluid saturation

Table J.2: Summary of the parameters adopted during the simulations for the two synthetic test cases.

Parameters	TC1	TC2	References
(n_e, n_i) [-]	(1, 4)	(5, 4)	<i>Craig (1971)</i>
V [m ³]	212 × 212 × 20	300 × 300 × 20	-
$n_x \times n_y \times n_z$ [-]	101 × 101 × 1	201 × 201 × 1	-
κ_g [m ²]	10 ⁻¹⁴	10 ⁻¹⁴	<i>Mackay and Cherry (1989); Wu et al. (1994)</i>
σ_Y^2 [-]	0.1 / 2.0 / 6.0	0.1 / 2.0 / 6.0	<i>Craig (1971); Dillard et al. (1997)</i>
(a_{\max}, a_{\min}) [m]	(51, 51)	(225, 22.5)	<i>Kitanidis (1997)</i>
θ [degrees]	0°	45°	-
ϕ [-]	0.2	0.2	<i>Wu et al. (1994)</i>
Q [10 ⁻³ m ³ /s]	0.228	0.228	-
(ρ_{nw}, ρ_w) [kg/m ³]	(898, 981)	(898, 981)	<i>Schwille (1981)</i>
μ_{nw} [mPa·s]	13.0	13.0	<i>Schwille (1981)</i>
μ_w [mPa·s]	0.2 / 1.0 / 5.0	0.2 / 1.0 / 5.0	<i>Schwille (1981)</i>
M [-]	2.2 / 1.4 / 0.5	2.2 / 1.4 / 0.5	<i>Schwille (1981)</i>
(S_{wi}, S_{nwi}) [-]	(0.2, 0.8)	(0.2, 0.8)	-
(S_{wr}, S_{nwr}) [-]	(0.2, 0.2)	(0.2, 0.2)	<i>Wu et al. (1994); Lie (2014)</i>
$(\kappa_{rwm}, \kappa_{rnwm})$ [-]	(0.2, 0.8)	(0.2, 0.8)	<i>Craig (1971); Lie (2014)</i>
(n_w, n_{nw}) [-]	(2, 2)	(2, 2)	<i>Sleep and Sykes (1993a)</i>
p_L [Pa]	8 ^a	8	<i>Zhong et al. (2001); Wipfler et al. (2004)</i>
λ [-]	0.5	0.5	<i>Sleep and Sykes (1993a)</i>

^a Low entry pressure is used considering the imbibition process.

distribution at time t (*Le Borgne et al., 2010; Nicolaidis et al., 2015*). The formal definition of these metrics can be written as,

$$RE(t) = \frac{1}{V_{nwi}} \int_0^t Q_{nw_5}(t) dt, \quad (\text{J.18})$$

$$DI(t) = 1 - \frac{\sigma^2(t)}{\sigma_{\max}^2(t)}, \quad (\text{J.19})$$

where Q_{nw_5} is the NAPL extraction rate obtained at the central well of the five-spot pattern (see Figure J.1), V_{nwi} is the initial volume of NAPL in the V_1 -domain,

$$V_{nwi} = \int_{V_1} \phi S_{nw}(t=0) dV, \quad (\text{J.20})$$

σ^2 is the variance of the S_w -distribution in the V_1 -domain, and σ_{\max}^2 is the maximum variance of S_w in the V_1 -domain. The variance of saturation associated with the wetting fluid is defined as

$$\sigma^2(t) = \frac{1}{V_1} \int_{V_1} S_w^2(t) dV - \left(\frac{1}{V_1} \int_{V_1} S_w(t) dV \right)^2. \quad (\text{J.21})$$

Note that the performance metrics only consider the simulated values obtained in the V_1 region. This intends to minimize boundary effects in TC2. The maximum variance σ_{\max}^2 is obtained when the distribution of saturation (wetting fluid) exhibits a bimodal distribution

with two segregated modes. In a multiphase injection-extraction removal system, this happens at early stages after injection, when the displacement is piston-like and the saturation of the injected fluid behind the displacement front is significantly different from the saturation ahead, which is close to the initial saturation. With time, driven by capillary dispersion and heterogeneity (and in our case by engineered injection and extraction), these two distinct saturations will mix. In an ideal case, when the saturation distribution is perfectly mixed, the saturation distribution approaches a unimodal distribution with $\sigma^2 = 0$ and $DI = 1$. Similar metrics of mixing (substituting S_w by solute concentrations) can be found in the literature of solute transport in porous media (*Jha et al.*, 2011). Here, knowing that S_w ranges between 0 and 1, we estimated σ_{\max}^2 by the following upper bound of variance (*Bhatia and Davis*, 2000),

$$\sigma_{\max}^2(t) = \frac{1}{V_1} \int_{V_1} S_w(t) dV - \left(\frac{1}{V_1} \int_{V_1} S_w(t) dV \right)^2. \quad (\text{J.22})$$

The EIE system results are compared with a standard injection-extraction removal system characterized by constant injection rates. Whenever necessary for a better interpretation of the results, performance metrics are presented as fractional increase with respect to the constant-injection solution. For any given performance metric χ , the fractional increase of χ is determined as

$$\Delta\chi = \frac{\chi_e - \chi_r}{\chi_r}, \quad (\text{J.23})$$

where the subscripts e and r denote the engineered injection and extraction and the reference constant injection rate simulation results, respectively.

J.3.7 Dimensionless Variables

To facilitate the interpretation, we present the results in terms of dimensionless variables. In statistical physics, the Kubo number Ku is a dimensionless measure of the correlation time of the fluctuations typically used for analyzing the behavior of moving particles in turbulent, random or chaotic velocity fields (*Kubo*, 1963; *Mazzino*, 1997; *Castiglione*, 2000; *Vlad et al.*, 2001). The Kubo number has been also used to study solute transport in temporally fluctuating flow through randomly heterogeneous porous media (*Dentz and Carrera*, 2005; *De Dreuzy et al.*, 2012). In solute transport, the Kubo number compares the average travel distance of a particle with the integral scale of $Y(\mathbf{x})$. Here, based on this, we define the following Kubo number in two-phase flow systems subject to periodic injection pulses,

$$Ku = \frac{v_f \tau}{\ell}, \quad (\text{J.24})$$

where τ is the pulse duration, v_f is the mean velocity of the saturation front, and ℓ is a measure of the correlation scale of $Y(\mathbf{x})$. The mean velocity of the saturation front is estimated by the breakthrough time of the saturation of the wetting fluid at the central extraction well of the five-spot pattern under constant injection conditions, denoted as t_{BT} ,

$$v_f \approx \frac{L}{\langle t_{BT} \rangle}, \quad (\text{J.25})$$

where L is the separation distance between injection and extraction wells, and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes the ensemble average of the Monte Carlo simulations. Note that this way the Kubo number directly includes the breakthrough time, which is known to control the efficiency of NAPL removal in real applications. Here, we choose to use the range of the $Y(\mathbf{x})$ field as a measure of correlation because it provides an indication of the average extent of low/high permeability zones. Since in our EIE removal setup the injected fluid moves half of the time along and transverse to the direction of stratification in an average sense, we have used $\ell = (a_{\max} + a_{\min})/2$ to estimate the Kubo number. We have also normalized the time by

$$t^* = \frac{v_f t}{\ell}. \quad (\text{J.26})$$

The number of cycles completed after a time t during EIE removal is defined as $N = t/T$. Dividing (J.26) by (J.24) and knowing that $T = 4\tau$, we have

$$N = \frac{t^*}{4\text{Ku}}. \quad (\text{J.27})$$

In the appendix we show that the governing equations of the two-phase flow system considered can be written in a dimensionless form that directly depends on the Kubo number and these dimensionless variables.

In a given realization of the random field, we expect the hydraulic connectivity between injection and extraction wells to also control the efficiency of the injection-extraction system; high connectivity can generate fast flow pathways between injection and extraction wells leading to early breakthrough times of the wetting fluid (e.g., *Silliman and Wright*, 1988; *Labolle and Fogg*, 2001; *Bianchi et al.*, 2011; *Renard and Allard*, 2013b; *Ederly et al.*, 2014). Numerous connectivity metrics have been proposed in subsurface hydrology for flow and contaminant transport through porous media (e.g. *Sanchez-Vila et al.*, 1999; *Fernandez-Garcia et al.*, 2002; *Knudby and Carrera*, 2005; *Trincherro et al.*, 2008; *Tyukhova et al.*, 2015; *Rizzo and de Barros*, 2017). An extensive review can be found in *Renard and Allard* (2013b). These authors distinguished between static and dynamic metrics. Static metrics provide a measure of connectivity based on the spatial patterns of the hydrogeological properties of an aquifer (e.g., permeability). Dynamic metrics go one step

further and include the effect that such patterns have on flow and transport. Dynamic metrics are typically richer in information (*Knudby and Carrera, 2005; Fiori and Jankovic, 2012*) but they are more difficult to measure in practice (requires the state variable response to a given stress). Effective static connectivity metrics can also be estimated from the least resistance pathway between two points of the aquifer without having to explicitly solve the flow and transport equation (*Tyukhova and Willmann, 2016; Rizzo and de Barros, 2017*). Here, we chose to work with a dynamic metric based on the wetting fluid breakthrough time because this variable typically controls the performance of NAPL removal. We therefore define the following metric for point-to-point connectivity in multiphase flow systems,

$$CS = \frac{t_0}{t_{BT}}, \quad (\text{J.28})$$

where t_0 is an expected or reference value of the wetting fluid saturation breakthrough time. This metric is similar in concept to the point-to-point connectivity metric defined for flow and transport in porous media (*Fernandez-Garcia et al., 2002; Trinchero et al., 2008; Fernàndez-Garcia et al., 2010*). Injection and extraction wells are well-connected in terms of saturation displacement when $CS > 1$, since the observed breakthrough time is more rapid than that its expected reference value. The larger the CS value, the better connection exists between injection and extraction wells, and one should expect geological bodies of high permeability connecting injection and extraction wells. We chose to measure t_0 by the expected value of the breakthrough time of saturation $\langle t_{BT} \rangle$ obtained in isotropic random fields under constant injection conditions. In practice, t_0 can also be estimated by the travel time of the wetting fluid saturation front in an equivalent homogeneous media.

J.4 Results and Discussions

J.4.1 Mean Behavior: The Role of the Fluctuation Period and the Kubo Number

The ensemble averages of the fractional increase of the removal efficiency $\langle \Delta RE \rangle$ and distribution index $\langle \Delta DI \rangle$ are shown in Figure J.3 as a function of the Kubo number for different removal times. Here, we only employ EIE periods smaller than the total recovery time to assure that EIE is active, otherwise the flow is effectively steady. Results show that $\langle \Delta RE \rangle$ increases to a maximum value when a specific pulse duration τ of a periodically applied rotating injection pulse yields a Kubo number close to one, i.e., $Ku \approx 1$. This result is analogous to the effect of temporal flow fluctuations on solute transport (single phase). *Dentz and Carrera (2005)* and *De Dreuzy et al. (2012)* found that the effective transverse dispersion coefficient of a solute plume is maximized when $Ku = 1$. This suggests that in

a two-phase flow system, when $Ku = 1$, advective transport and temporal fluctuations are synchronized to improve NAPL displacement towards the extraction well, most likely due to an enhancement of transverse dispersion of the displacing fluid saturation. In practice, this means that the saturation front should travel one range of the $Y(\mathbf{x})$ field (an average extent of low/high permeability zones) in an injection pulse to maximize NAPL removal. When $Ku \ll 1$, the frequency of temporal fluctuations is too high to properly sample the permeability field. When $Ku \gg 1$, EIE generates a highly nonuniform partial sweep of the porous medium.

Remarkably, a more pronounced peak is observed in the anisotropic case, which suggests that EIE removal works best under unfavorable field conditions, i.e., when some of the injectors are potentially correlated with the central well. In the anisotropic case we obtain a maximum fractional increase close to 12%, which is six times larger than that of the isotropic case. In particular, the pulse duration for maximizing removal efficiency in TC1 and TC2 are $\tau \approx 0.3\langle t_{BT} \rangle$ and $\tau \approx 0.8\langle t_{BT} \rangle$, respectively. It is logical to think that the pulse duration should be smaller than the breakthrough time, otherwise the wetting fluid can gain access to the extraction well in the first injection of the fluctuation cycle. Following this line of thought, it is not surprising that $\langle \Delta RE \rangle$ rapidly declines after passing through a maximum when the pulse duration, and therefore the Kubo number, becomes too large. In this case, $\langle \Delta RE \rangle$ can reach negative values in isotropic Y fields.

The ensemble average of the fractional increase of the distribution index $\langle \Delta DI \rangle$ is also shown in Figure J.3. EIE is also demonstrated to enhance mixing. However, a clear peak is only observed in the isotropic case after a long time (when $t^* > 15$) and at Kubo numbers larger than 1 (between 1.5 and 3). Probably, the peak cannot be seen in the other cases because the maximum Kubo number available is relatively small. These results highlights that maximum mixing does not necessarily imply maximum removal, most likely because the wetting fluid can only effectively displace the non-wetting fluid when $S_w \gg S_{wr}$ due to the non-linear nature of the relative permeability.

Figure J.4 depicts the temporal evolution of $\langle \Delta RE \rangle$ and $\langle \Delta DI \rangle$ for different Kubo numbers. EIE effects on $\langle \Delta RE \rangle$ require a certain time to develop during which sometimes it exhibits a valley, then reaches a maximum, and after this it slowly declines with time. These features are more intense for anisotropic fields. The valley displays negative values decreasing with the Kubo number. In general, the time needed to reach the valley and the peak is relatively smaller in anisotropic fields, meaning that EIE effects develop faster in well-connected permeability fields. From (J.27), we have that $N = t^*/4$, which means that the number of cycles required to reach maximum removal is only about 2 and 3 cycles in the anisotropic and isotropic case, respectively. The valley seems to take place in the first cycle. From a practical point of view, it is important to recognize that these results suggest that in order to maximize removal in the long term one should undergo first an early stage

Figure J.3: Ensemble average of the fractional increase of the removal efficiency and distribution index as a function of the Kubo number for different removal times (J.26) in isotropic (first panel) and anisotropic (second panel) random permeability fields with $\sigma_Y^2 = 2$ and $M = 2.2$.

with detrimental effects in removal efficiency. The temporal evolution of $\langle \Delta DI \rangle$ is similar to $\langle \Delta RE \rangle$, but in this case the valley and the peak take place at different times and with less intensity. In fact, the valley becomes only apparent when $Ku > 1$.

J.4.2 Uncertainty in NAPL Removal with Engineered Injection and Extraction

The inherent complexity of a heterogeneous geological system typically produces large uncertainties in the efficiency of NAPL removal in field applications (*De Barros et al.*, 2013). For instance, it is well known that DNAPL removal efficiencies of current remediation techniques are limited and highly variable when moving from laboratory to field scale (*Soga et al.*, 2004). In this section, we demonstrate that NAPL removal with EIE not only improves performance metrics, but also reduces uncertainty, making the application of in situ removal techniques more reliable and less sensitive to the underlying heterogeneity of the permeability field. To show this, Figure J.5 presents the coefficients of variation of the removal efficiency CV_{RE} and distribution index CV_{DI} as a function of the Kubo number for different removal times. For comparison purposes, the horizontal dashed lines shown in the figures indicate the corresponding coefficient of variation obtained with a constant injection scheme. In general, the coefficient of variation of RE is one order of magnitude larger than that of DI . Results demonstrate that EIE removal can significantly reduce the uncertainty of removal efficiency and distribution index relative to a constant injection

Figure J.4: Temporal evolution of the ensemble average of the fractional increase of removal efficiency and distribution index for different Kubo numbers in isotropic (first panel) and anisotropic (second panel) random permeability fields with $\sigma_Y^2 = 2$ and $M = 2.2$.

scheme. This effect is more pronounced in the anisotropic case with unfavorable conditions. In this case, the coefficients of variation of RE and DI are respectively reduced from 0.15 to 0.12 and from 0.023 to 0.008. The uncertainty in removal efficiency exhibits its minimum value when $\langle \Delta RE \rangle$ is maximum ($Ku \approx 1$). This suggests that the increase in removal efficiency and distribution index due to EIE always goes along with a reduction of their uncertainty. This is consistent with the result reported by *Libera et al. (2017)*. We attribute this reduction in uncertainty to the fact that EIE forces the wetting fluid to not strictly follow preferential channels. This promotes a better sampling of the permeability field, which partially destroys the strong effect of heterogeneity on the flow. Essentially, EIE increases the disorder of the permeability field sampled by the injected fluid, making the statistical performance of the flow process more stable and with less uncertainty.

The temporal evolution of the coefficient of variation of performance metrics is depicted in Figure J.6 for different Kubo numbers. For comparison, the dashed lines correspond to the constant injection scheme. In general, the uncertainty of RE and DI exhibits large fluctuations at early times, which ultimately vanish to approach a well-defined asymptotic value at large times. The effects of engineered injection and extraction are more pronounced in the anisotropic case with similar overall behavior. The time needed to reach an asymptotic value in removal efficiency strongly depends on the Kubo number. When $Ku \approx 1$, CV_{RE} approaches the asymptotic value more rapidly than in other cases, i.e., in less than one range of the $Y(\mathbf{x})$ field. The coefficient of variation of the distribution

Figure J.5: Coefficient of variation of the removal efficiency and distribution index as a function of the Kubo number for different removal times (J.26) in isotropic (first panel) and anisotropic (second panel) random permeability fields with $\sigma_Y^2 = 2$ and $M = 2.2$.

index, at late times, decreases with the Kubo number. This illustrates that low-frequency fluctuations can further reduce the uncertainty of mixing but at the expenses of removal efficiency and its uncertainty.

The probability density function (PDF) of RE and DI provides a broader description of the ensemble of realizations. This is shown in Figure J.7 for a removal time of 10 years, which corresponds to dimensionless time $t^*=9.2$. We compare the results obtained by using a constant injection with those obtained with EIE (Kubo numbers associated with maximum simulated performance). Note that the Kubo numbers reported for maximum recovery efficiency and distribution index are different. This illustrates again the fact that maximum recovery does not necessarily imply maximum mixing. In this case, the simulations with maximum $\langle RE \rangle$ performance exhibit a value of $Ku=0.92$ (close to 1), whereas maximum $\langle DI \rangle$ is obtained with $Ku= 2.31$. The PDFs were estimated through an iterative optimal kernel density estimator (*Engel et al., 1994*) to minimize spurious statistical fluctuations. As expected from our previous results, the central tendency of the PDFs is shifted towards larger removal efficiencies and distribution indexes due to engineered injection and extraction. In a constant injection scheme, removal efficiency exhibits a wide distribution with a long tail associated with relatively large removal efficiencies. In contrast, NAPL removal with EIE yields a more symmetric and narrower distribution of the removal efficiency with high probabilities centered at relatively large quantities.

Figure J.6: Temporal evolution of the coefficient of variation of the removal efficiency and distribution index as a function of the Kubo number for different removal times in isotropic (first panel) and anisotropic (second panel) random permeability fields with $\sigma_Y^2 = 2$ and $M = 2.2$.

Figure J.7: Comparison of the estimated probability density functions of the removal efficiency and distribution index obtained with EIE (Kubo numbers associated with maximum performance) and constant injection removal for anisotropic fields with $\sigma_Y^2 = 2$ and $M = 2.2$ at $t^* = 9.2$. Note that the Kubo numbers reported for maximum recovery efficiency and distribution index are different. This illustrates the fact that maximum recovery does not necessarily imply maximum mixing. Maximum recovery occurs when Ku is close to 1 (in this case, the set of simulations with maximum $\langle RE \rangle$ performance exhibit a value of $Ku = 0.92$), but maximum mixing typically requires larger values than this (in this case $Ku = 2.31$).

J.4.3 Impact of Engineered Injection and Extraction on Connectivity

The hydraulic connection between injection and extraction wells depends on the specific spatial patterns that the permeability field displays in a given realization. Within each realization, the measure of connectivity CS presented in section J.3.7 quantifies the presence of preferential channels or high permeability regions between injection wells and the central extraction well (*Trincheró et al.*, 2008; *Fernández-García et al.*, 2010). Within this context, in this section we analyze the dependence between EIE removal and connectivity. For this, we present in Figure J.8 the conditional expectation of the removal efficiency and distribution index (and corresponding fractional increase) relative to the connectivity indicator, i.e., $\langle RE|CS \rangle$ and $\langle DI|CS \rangle$, for different removal times. Here, the pulse duration is chosen to satisfy maximum performance.

Results agree with field observations in that removal efficiency decreases with connectivity. The inefficiency of NAPL removal is mainly attributed to the inability of the displacing fluid to sweep the NAPL trapped in low permeability regions, which is bypassed when the injection and extraction wells are well-connected (*De Dreuzy et al.*, 2012; *De Barros et al.*, 2013; *Ederý et al.*, 2014). As expected, the anisotropic random fields reflect large CS values (Figure J.2). TC2 exhibits elongated lenses of high/low permeabilities between the injectors and the central extraction well. Looking at both the removal efficiency and its fractional increase we see that even though the removal efficiency decreases with connectivity, the fractional increase due to engineered injection and extraction becomes important with increasing CS . That is, the fractional increase of the removal efficiency increases with unfavorable connectivity conditions, meaning that EIE removal works best in the worst case scenario. Hence, to some extent, results suggest that engineered injection and extraction can partially overcome channeling effects during NAPL removal.

Connectivity affects the distribution index (mixing of saturations) in a similar way. Recalling that the distribution index is a measure of mixing, results indicate that strong connectivity patterns in a heterogeneous aquifer tend to preclude the occurrence of mixing. It is logical to think that well-connected fields will concentrate the wetting fluid in small regions, making it difficult for mixing to occur (*De Barros et al.*, 2013). This is equally true for both injection modes, but one can easily appreciate that EIE removal renders the system less dependent on connectivity, because the engineered injection and extraction can partially break fast flow paths. Similar effects have been reported in solute transport (*De Dreuzy et al.*, 2012). DI decreases with CS but at a smaller rate during EIE removal.

Figure J.8: Removal efficiency and distribution index (and their corresponding fractional increase) as a function of point-to-point connectivity in two-phase flow systems for different removal times and injection-extraction method in isotropic and anisotropic random fields with $\sigma_Y^2 = 2$ and $M = 2.2$.

J.4.4 The roles of the Degree of Heterogeneity and Mobility Ratio

In this section we evaluate the roles that heterogeneity and mobility ratio have on removal efficiency and mixing. The effect of σ_Y^2 is analyzed by re-scaling the variance of the $Y(\mathbf{x})$ values adopted in a given realization. A similar approach was used by *Neupauer et al.* (2014). This way we make sure that we always deal with the same heterogeneous pattern, i.e., the same organization of permeability values. The $Y(\mathbf{x})$ fields used are shown in Figure J.2. We also changed the viscosity of the wetting fluid to analyze the effect of the mobility ratio on EIE removal. The mobility ratio is changed from $M = 2.2$ to $M = 1.4$ and $M = 0.5$. Figure J.9 shows the fractional increase of removal efficiency obtained in the isotropic and anisotropic case after 20 years as a function of the Kubo number for different σ_Y^2 and M values. The general behavior follows our previous results; maximum removal close or slightly larger than $Ku \approx 1$ followed by a rapid decline. The location of the peak slightly depends on the mobility ratio, indicating that unfavorable displacement ($M > 1$) may require slightly smaller frequencies of injection and extraction fluctuations. However, the important point here is to realize that EIE removal in two-phase flow systems is significantly affected by two competing factors: mobility ratio and heterogeneity. When the degree of heterogeneity is not significant ($\sigma_Y^2 < 2$), the unfavorable displacement caused by high mobility ratios controls removal efficiency, i.e., ΔRE increases with the mobility ratio. When heterogeneity is important ($\sigma_Y^2 > 2$), channeling controls the displacing

process regardless of the mobility ratio. We note also that engineered injection and extraction is more effective under unfavorable conditions of heterogeneity, i.e., high σ_Y^2 in well-connected anisotropic fields. This is because removal efficiency is typically small in highly heterogeneous systems due to channeling, thus leaving a large opportunity for improvement. In this case, for this realization of the random field, we obtain a fractional increase larger than 20% at peak values. In this context, we note that *Neupauer et al.* (2014) also found that engineered injection and extraction in solute transport (single phase) is most advantageous in highly heterogeneous fields with large σ_Y^2 .

Figure J.9: Fractional increase of the removal efficiency as a function of the Kubo number for different degrees of heterogeneity and mobility ratios in one realization of the isotropic (first panel) and anisotropic (second panel) random field.

To visually illustrate the benefits of EIE removal, Figures J.10 and J.11 offer the map of the NAPL saturation after 20 years of operation in the isotropic and anisotropic permeability fields shown in Figure J.2 for $M = 2.2$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 0.1, 2, \text{ and } 6$. Constant injection results are compared with those corresponding to the EIE sequences that yielded maximum removal (RE) and maximum mixing (DI). We can easily see that EIE removal with optimal fluctuations can significantly outperform the constant injection scheme. This is particularly notable when field conditions are unfavorable, i.e., large σ_Y^2 and injection-extraction wells oriented along the principal correlation direction. Note for instance that even though severe stratification (anisotropic case with $\sigma_Y^2=6$) controls the distribution of saturation in a constant injection scheme, the application of engineered injection and extraction can largely palliate this shortcoming. This figure also illustrates the dichotomy between maximizing removal efficiency or mixing. Results have shown that these two

conditions occur at different EIE periods and removal times. In practice, the use of one or another will depend on the project objectives. For instance, at early stages of remediation one may favor removal efficiency, but at late times, when liquid solutions with cosolvents, surfactants or polymers are meant to be used to alter fluid properties and improve performance, one may wish to promote mixing (*Huling and Weaver, 1991; Rao et al., 1997; Neupauer et al., 2014*).

Figure J.10: Spatial distribution of the NAPL saturation at $t^* = 20.9$ in one realization of the isotropic random field for different degrees of heterogeneity and injection-extraction method with $M = 2.2$.

Figure J.11: Spatial distribution of the NAPL saturation at $t^*=18.4$ in one realization of the anisotropic random field for different degrees of heterogeneity and injection-extraction method with $M=2.2$.

As an illustrative example of the method, we finally compare in Figure J.12 the temporal evolution of the NAPL flow rate recovered at the central well of the five-spot pattern produced by EIE with that of the constant injection scheme obtained in a given realization of the anisotropic permeability field for $\sigma_Y^2=6$ and $M = 2.2$ (worst case scenario). Once the non-wetting fluid breaks through the extraction well, the fractional flow rate of NAPL rapidly declines, generating a long tail of poor removal efficiencies with time. Instead, enhanced NAPL removal with EIE produces a more persistent NAPL extraction rate sequence characterized by important NAPL removal spikes. The net result in this case is a relative increase in removal efficiency of 22%. Note that, in this individual realization, the maximum performance in recovery efficiency occurs at $Ku = 2.9$, which is slightly larger than the optimal value ($Ku \approx 1$) that characterizes the mean behavior (presented in

section J.4.1). This suggests that caution should be taken in practice. The mean behavior only provides a preliminary estimate of the best fluctuation period. This parameter should be further optimized in real applications to account for the specific heterogeneous patterns of the given aquifer.

Figure J.12: Comparison of temporal evolution of the NAPL flow rate recovered at the central well of the five-spot pattern produced by EIE with that of the constant injection scheme obtained with the anisotropic permeability field for $\sigma_Y^2=6$ and $M = 2.2$. In this realization of the random field, the maximum performance in recovery efficiency occurs at $Ku = 2.9$.

J.5 Conclusions

We have proposed and evaluated the use of Engineered Injection and Extraction (EIE) to enhance non-aqueous phase liquid removal during in situ soil washing remediation techniques and enhanced oil recovery in complex geological formations. EIE is executed through the application of a rotating periodic injection pulse in a five-spot injection-extraction pattern. To evaluate the method, we have performed two-phase flow simulations in multiple realizations of randomly heterogeneous permeability fields with different correlation structures and connectivity structures between injection and extraction wells.

Performance metrics include removal efficiency and the distribution index of saturation (mixing). We have shown that EIE can significantly improve removal efficiency and mixing. The performance of the method depends on the Kubo number, the connectivity between injection and extraction wells, the degree of heterogeneity and the mobility ratio. The most important findings are listed as follows:

1. EIE improves NAPL removal efficiency and the mixing between the wetting and non-wetting phases. This is relatively more pronounced when the permeability field displays unfavorable conditions, i.e., when the injection and extraction wells are well-connected to each other through preferential channels, the permeability field is highly heterogeneous, and/or the mobility ratio between the wetting and the non-wetting fluid is larger than one (unfavorable displacement). This makes EIE extremely useful in worst-case field applications.
2. Removal efficiency increases to a maximum value when the pulse duration of a periodically applied rotating injection pulse satisfies that the Kubo number is close to one, i.e., when the saturation front travels one range of the permeability field (an average extent of low/high permeability zones) per injection pulse. This maximum value, in an ensemble average sense, is around 12% in unfavorable conditions of the permeability field with $\sigma_Y^2 = 2$.
3. EIE can fully develop maximum strength after a few injection cycles. However, results have shown that removal efficiency should first undergo an early stage with detrimental effects in order to maximize removal in the long term.
4. The application of EIE not only enhances non-aqueous phase liquid removal, but also reduces its uncertainty, making the removal system more reliable and less dependent on heterogeneity. Again, this reduction is higher in unfavorable conditions of the permeability field.
5. Maximum removal efficiency and mixing occur at different EIE periods and removal times. In practice, the use of one or another will depend on the project objectives. For instance, at early stages of remediation one may favor removal efficiency, but at late times one may wish to promote mixing when liquid solutions with cosolvents, surfactants or polymers are meant to be used to alter fluid properties and improve performance.
6. The mobility ratio and the degree of heterogeneity are two competing factors controlling the performance of EIE in two-phase flow systems. When σ_Y^2 is large the

performance of EIE is mainly controlled by heterogeneity. On the contrary, when σ_Y^2 is small, the mobility ratio controls the overall behavior of the system.

These results encourage the application of EIE in multiphase flow problems. In this context, we note that the application of EIE to NAPL polluted sites and/or enhanced oil removal comes at almost no additional cost since the removal system consisting of several wells is not necessarily modified with respect to standard practices, except for the way the technology (delivering of fluids) is put into practice. Moreover, this method can be easily implemented with other techniques to further improve removal efficiencies. The enhancement of mixing between phases can favor for instance surfactant dissolution and mobilization of NAPLs, chemical flooding or CO_2 sequestration through enhanced oil removal. Some simplifications used in this research may require further investigations. The two-dimensional assumption neglects vertical gravity segregation, which may also impact the removal process of NAPLs. Practical issues associated with fluid injection should also be explored in the future (*Payne et al.*, 2008).

J.6 Appendix: Governing Equations in Dimensionless Form

In this appendix we show that the governing equations of the two-phase flow system can be written in a dimensionless form. The appendix shows that the Kubo number and the dimensionless variables used in our analysis arise naturally from the mass conservation equations. These quantities have therefore an important role in analyzing EIE removal systems, defining the controlling parameters as well as the characteristic scales of the problem (in space and time). Let us define the following dimensionless variables,

$$x^* = \frac{x}{\ell}, \quad y^* = \frac{y}{\ell}, \quad t^* = \frac{v_f t}{\ell}. \quad (\text{J.29})$$

The Darcy flux and pressure of the wetting and non-wetting fluid are written in dimensionless form as

$$q_w^* = \frac{q_w}{v_f \phi}, \quad q_{nw}^* = \frac{q_{nw}}{v_f \phi}, \quad p_w^* = \frac{p_w \kappa_g}{\mu_w v_f \phi \ell}, \quad p_{nw}^* = \frac{p_{nw} \kappa_g}{\mu_w v_f \phi \ell}. \quad (\text{J.30})$$

With these definitions, Darcy's law is expressed as

$$q_w^* = -\kappa_{rw} \exp(Y') \nabla^* p_w^*, \quad (\text{J.31})$$

$$q_{nw}^* = -\frac{\gamma \kappa_{rnw}}{M} \exp(Y') \nabla^* p_{nw}^*, \quad (\text{J.32})$$

where $\nabla^* = [\partial/\partial x^*, \partial/\partial y^*]$, $\gamma = \kappa_{rw}^0/\kappa_{rmw}^0$, and Y' is the deviation of the natural log of the intrinsic permeability from the mean, i.e., $Y' = Y - \langle Y \rangle$. The geometric mean permeability is $\kappa_g = \exp(\langle Y \rangle)$. By construction, Y' mainly depends on the degree of heterogeneity σ_Y^2 , the two-point statistics (variogram), and the hydraulic connectivity CS . The injection and extraction flow rates are written in dimensionless form as

$$Q_{w_j}^{i*} = \frac{Q_{w_j}^i}{v_f \phi b l}, \quad Q_{w_j}^{e*} = \frac{Q_{w_j}^e}{v_f \phi b l}, \quad Q_{nw_j}^{e*} = \frac{Q_{nw_j}^e}{v_f \phi b l}, \quad Q^* = \frac{Q}{v_f \phi b l}. \quad (\text{J.33})$$

Substituting (J.29), (J.30) and (J.33) into (J.4) and (J.5), we have

$$\frac{\partial S_w}{\partial t^*} = -\nabla^* \cdot \mathbf{q}_w^* + \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} Q_{w_j}^{i*}(t^*) \delta(\mathbf{x}^* - \mathbf{x}_j^{i*}) - \sum_{j=1}^{n_e} Q_{w_j}^{e*}(t^*) \delta(\mathbf{x}^* - \mathbf{x}_j^{e*}), \quad (\text{J.34})$$

$$\frac{\partial S_{nw}}{\partial t^*} = -\nabla^* \cdot \mathbf{q}_{nw}^* - \sum_{j=1}^{n_e} Q_{nw_j}^{e*}(t^*) \delta(\mathbf{x}^* - \mathbf{x}_j^{e*}). \quad (\text{J.35})$$

Knowing by the properties of the Heaviside function that

$$H(t - (j-1)T/4) - H(t - jT/4) = H(t^* - (j-1)Ku) - H(t^* - jKu), \quad (\text{J.36})$$

the periodic wave function is written as

$$Q_{w_j}^{i*}(t^*) = Q^* f_j(t^*, Ku), \quad 0 \leq t^* < 4Ku, \quad (\text{J.37})$$

$$Q_{w_j}^{i*}(t^*) = Q_{w_j}^{i*}(t^* - 4Ku), \quad t^* \geq 4Ku, \quad (\text{J.38})$$

where we see that the parameters controlling the governing equations can be reduced to few dimensionless parameters. The Kubo number Ku plays a central role.